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Roman Kuhar, Rok Smrdelj

1. Introduction to the report

This report provides a comprehensive mapping of the main anti-feminist and anti-gender actors in Denmark, France, Greece, Italy, Poland, Slovenia, Spain and Turkey. It identifies the most salient issues at stake and the way these cluster together according to the main themes of the project: (1) labor market, (2) health & reproductive rights, (3) migration, (4) LGBTQ+ rights, and (5) gender-based violence.

The structure of this report is as follows. First, we present the key objectives of the first work strand of the FIERCE project and the working definitions of anti-gender and anti-feminist actors that we used in our research. We then summarize the key findings of a critical analysis of the existing literature on anti-gender and anti-feminist movements in the eight countries. This is followed by the individual national reports. Finally, the methodological manual we used to prepare this report is included. In accordance with this manual, the national reports are organized in several sections covering the following topics:

- the history of the emergence of anti-gender and anti-feminist movements in each country;
- the key actors of the movement and their allies,
- themes and agendas;
- the issues the movement is addressing;
- its strategies and repertoires of actions;
- the key arguments of anti-gender and anti-feminist actors;
- their transnational links;
- the empirical and theoretical explanations to date for the rise and success of anti-gender and anti-feminist movements.

The national reports also include a graphic time-line of key moments in the development of the anti-gender movement in each country, including its major successes and failures, as well as key oppositional events/actions on the part of feminists, LGBTQ+, and similar actors. At the end of the report, we have also added a short analysis of anti-gender and anti-feminist activities at European level.

2. Objectives and working definitions

The main objective of the first work package of the FIERCE project is threefold: (1) to understand the structural and contextual conditions at national and transnational levels explaining the rise and, in particular, the developments and transformations of the anti-feminist and the anti-gender mobilizations in the eight countries and over the period 2010-21; (2) to identify how gender and gender categories are framed, used, disseminated, and widely communicated and which agendas these movements prioritize in their national contexts; and (3) to disclose the complex and expanding web of interactions and connections both within anti-feminist/anti-gender groups, communities, and milieus as well as among these and external actors at local, national, and transnational levels.

This report pursues all three objectives, although our main empirical contribution to understanding and explaining the anti-gender and anti-feminist movements will be made in the next steps of the project, which includes critical frame analysis of anti-feminist and anti-gender campaigns and

interviews with actors on all sides of these campaigns. This report thus presents and elaborates upon a critical review of existing literature in the eight countries participating in the project.

In the project, anti-gender actors are defined as all actors who use "gender ideology", "gender theory", "genderism" or closely related concept as key terms in their rhetoric and actions. Gender ideology is an empty signifier that can stand for anything from marriage equality and sex education in schools, to reproductive and adoption rights and abortion. In everyday usage "gender ideology" (or "gender theory" or even "genderism," as it is called in some languages) is today perceived as a kind of conspiracy by "radical feminists and LGBT activists" and other "leftist elites", who purposely seek to trigger a cultural revolution. The alleged goal of this revolution is the denial of biological explanations about men and women and the "promotion" of gender fluidity. "Gender theory" is thus constructed as a project of social engineering in which feminism and LGBT activism is accused of an attempt at human intervention in something that is fundamentally "divine", i.e. natural and unquestionable: gender and gender relations. Accordingly social constructivist interpretation of gender and gender studies as such are fabricated into a kind of "conspiracy", lurking over unsuspecting people.

Anti-feminist actors, on the other hand, reject some or all forms of feminism, its political struggles for equality and emancipation, and its principles. There are various forms of antifeminism, but generally they are based on the belief that the traditional gender division of labor is natural, or that women's rights and equality negatively affect men's rights and position in society without necessarily making use of conceptual devices such as "gender ideology" or "genderism" and without assuming the above presented features of conspiracy theories. In some cases their approach is not to deny women's rights and equality, but rather an assumption that equality has already been achieved and that current feminism struggles have simply "gone too far".

As shown by our report, many of the anti-feminist actors now overlap with the anti-gender movement or have used the success of the anti-gender movement and its platform to spread their ideas. These actors are usually older initiatives/organizations that existed before the anti-gender movement and their target was an attack on feminism as such.

3. Introduction to anti-gender mobilization

Several countries of Europe, including Turkey, are witnessing new waves of opposition in the shape of the so-called anti-gender movement, following decades of steady development in gender and sexual rights (Kuhar & Paternotte, 2017). The anti-gender movement is a social and political neoconservative movement that developed in Europe at the beginning of the 2010s and has since spread around the world (Corrêa, 2022; Fassin, 2020; Graff & Korolczuk, 2022; Kaoma, 2016; Kováts & Pöim, 2015; Kuhar & Paternotte, 2017; Lavizzari, 2020; Stoeckl, 2020). It contends that gender theory, feminism, and gender equality legislation are detrimental to society. The anti-gender movement's political agenda includes opposition to reproductive rights and abortion, sex education in public schools, LGBT+ rights, sexual liberalism, and the very concept of gender itself. On a structural level, the anti-gender movement contributes to modern authoritarian de-democratization processes that target not just gender and equality, but also the concept and practice of democracy (Lombardo et al., 2021). These mobilizations should not be viewed merely as contemporary reiterations of established forms of opposition to specific understandings of gender and sexuality, nor as a continuation of previous (conservative) forms of opposition to human rights pertaining to intimate and sexual citizenship policy debates; they are new manifestations of resistance, shaped by new forms of organization and mobilization (Paternotte & Kuhar, 2018).

The emergence of the anti-gender movement in Europe coincided with the economic crisis and stringent austerity measures. This further reinforced the widespread discontent with the political and economic status quo, particularly with political and economic elites. The austerity measures were not the primary catalyst for the movement, but they greatly aided it since the movement's leaders successfully constructed the identity of the majority as an oppressed identity in opposition to corrupt elites.

Anti-gender mobilizations are also linked to the current surge of right-wing populism sweeping across Europe. There are a number of connections between right-wing populism and anti-gender initiatives, most notably the former's emphasis on corrupt elites and the latter's desire to give a voice to those who are deemed voiceless (Farris 2017). This is not to imply that anti-gender campaigns are the direct result of the right-wing populist wave, but the shift to the right strengthens these campaigns and provides them with new supporters who have adopted a concept of "gender ideology" that shares some ideological structures with right-wing populist ideology. Europe has experienced a significant shift in the functioning of populist right-wing parties, which has facilitated the collaboration between anti-gender players and radical right-wing populists. They are increasingly rephrasing its radical components and engaging in softer discourse, in which blatant hostility is substituted by a form of coded politics that is nevertheless exclusive and anti-elitist (Sauer, 2020; Wodak, 2015).

The current research has focused on the roots and emergence of the anti-gender movements (Case, 2011, 2016; Kuhar & Paternotte, 2017), its actors and the network of connections between them (Graff & Korolczuk, 2022; Kováts & Pöim, 2015; Kuhar & Paternotte, 2017; Martinsson & Ericson, 2021; Nicholas & Agius, 2018; Obst, 2017); numerous studies looked into the discourse, rhetoric, and the strategies used by the anti-gender actors (Corrêa, 2022; Darakchi, 2019; Datta, 2021; Garbagnoli, 2016; Grzebalska & Pető, 2018; Lavizzari, 2020; Stoeckl, 2020; Valkovičová & Meier, 2022; Zarembek et al., 2021); and finally some studies specifically look into the alliances between anti-gender actors and populist and radical/far right parties, particularly in countries where these parties are in power (Bogaards & Pető, 2022; Graff et al., 2019; Grzebalska & Pető, 2018; Kováts, 2018; Kováts & Zacharenko, 2021; Paternotte & Kuhar, 2018; Pető, 2021). The latter is particularly important as anti-gender actors have already entered public offices and institutions – be it as members of political parties or simply because of their connections to these political actors – and in such a way introduce their agenda into official policies, plans of actions, and resolutions of national governments.

In the remainder of this introduction to the report, we will briefly summarize the key findings of our critical analysis of current studies on anti-gender and anti-feminist movement with focus on the actors and their allies, the themes and agendas raised by anti-gender and anti-feminist movements, the strategies they use, the frames of their argumentation, and how different authors explain the rise and success of anti-gender movements.

3.1. Actors and allies

Over the past decade, numerous anti-feminist and anti-gender actors and organizations have emerged in the countries studied. Their efforts focus primarily on opposing rights related to gender equality, reproductive rights (e.g., abortion, medically assisted reproduction), and LGBTQ+ rights. Except for Denmark, the anti-feminist and anti-gender movements are well-organized, visible, and have substantial support networks and resources. Although anti-feminist and anti-gender actors vary according to their role in the movement (whether they are central actors or allies), their mode of operation, time of emergence and activity or their pre-existence to the rise of anti-gender and anti-feminist movement, the following types of actors can be identified: (1) religious actors, (2) political

parties, (3) old (anti-gender) actors, (4) new anti-gender actors, (5) media, celebrities and public figures, and (6) the manosphere.

3.1.1. Religious actors

The Roman Catholic Church (RCC) plays a significant role in the anti-feminist and anti-gender movements in Spain, Italy, Slovenia, and Poland. Depending on the country, it may come across as one of the main anti-gender actors (as in Italy and Poland) or operate in the background and support its satellite organizations that spread anti-feminist and anti-gender agenda (as in Slovenia and Spain).

The RCC authorities are the most powerful actors in Poland, driving the government's anti-LGBTQ+ and anti-reproductive rights policies. They constantly provide moral and philosophical underpinnings for the state's anti-gender propaganda. Similarly, the RCC in Italy was indispensable for organizing large-scale mass mobilizations. Although in most of European countries the RCC's involvement is viewed as potentially damaging to the scientific credibility of the issues and subsidizing the secular nature of the state, in countries such as Italy the RCC's support has lent at times legitimacy to the anti-feminist and anti-gender campaign, especially in its early stages. In Spain, the historical significance of the RCC in the anti-gender movement is also noteworthy. However, RCC is no longer viewed as an active subject, but rather as a shadow ally within the anti-gender and anti-feminist movement, in favor of other secular organizations and political parties. In the case of Slovenia, the RCC plays a distinctly satellite role within anti-gender and anti-feminist movement, primarily because of the financial scandals of ten years ago that undermined its reputation, and also because RCC has realized that its antiquated biblical discourse cannot appeal to the majority. Instead, numerous actors and organizations - financially and otherwise supported by the RCC, promote its anti-feminist and anti-gender agenda.

In the same way, the Christian Orthodox Church in Greece and Islamic actors in Turkey are important stakeholders in the anti-feminist and anti-gender movements in both countries. Although the Danish Protestant Lutheran Church cannot be fully equated with the work of the RCC, it is a fact that this church is also internally split and that certain actors within it are working against what they call "gender ideology".

3.1.2. Political Parties

Political parties can play a prominent role in the anti-feminist and anti-gender movement, or they can be the movement's allies. Turkey and Poland stand out among the countries studied, because the government political party significantly influences the existence of the anti-feminist and anti-gender movements in both countries. While the Polish governing party PiS is the patron of virtually all anti-feminist and anti-gender campaigns in the country, the 20-year rule of the AKP government played the main role in the rise of conservatism, anti-feminist and anti-gender discourses and policies in Turkey. Moreover, AKP was the sole actor of anti-gender mobilization in the country until 2019. In these political contexts, anti-gender ideology has become the official state ideology in relation to gender, sexuality and reproductive issues. Similarly, in Italy, numerous politicians are members of one or more of the anti-gender and anti-feminist organizations, which provide anti-gender actors with direct access to the political system and government officials. Their simultaneous presence in courts, hospitals and health services, media, government offices, churches, political parties, schools, universities, demonstrations, and public events aids in recruiting supporters, raising funds, and furthering political and ideological goals.

In some other countries, such as Slovenia or Spain, (far) right-wing political parties are movement's allies and actively spread anti-gender and anti-feminist ideology, while at the same time capitalizing politically on the successes of this movement, as anti-gender ideas become part of their political agendas. In Italy, neo-fascist groups of the radical right, such as Forza Nuova and CasaPound Italia, have been notable allies of anti-gender actors, similar to, for example, Greek's neo-nazi party Golden Dawn or Spanish neo-nazi groups España 2000 and Hogar Social de Madrid.

Although there are various organizations in the anti-gender network that are closely linked to political parties, special mention should be made of the phenomenon of the government-organized non-governmental organization (GONGO) in Turkey, specifically *Kadın ve Demokrasi Derneği* (Woman and Democracy Association), a 2013-founded Islamist women's organization with organic ties to the AKP administration that effectively advocated gender equity/justice as a “culturally apt” alternative to gender equality.

In Denmark, political parties are also significant anti-gender actor. For example, Danish Parliament passed a resolution warning against “excessive activism in certain research environments”, such as gender, race, and postcolonial studies.

3.1.3. Old (anti-gender) actors

Old actors are organizations, initiatives, and groups that existed prior to the emergence of the anti-gender mobilizations, but which in the last decade have adopted the strategies and discourses used by the anti-gender movement, particularly the reference to the so-called “gender ideology” or “gender theory” when constructing arguments to advance their agenda. Among old “anti-gender” actors, historical pro-life organizations, traditional religious organizations, and men's rights efforts stand out the most. Such organizations exist in all examined nations.

3.1.4. New anti-gender actors

The new anti-gender groups and networks are the ones that are most often the most visible actors of the anti-gender movement in the public arena. These are often ostensibly grass-roots organizing groups of people who present themselves as “concerned citizens” or “concerned parents”, as the Roman Catholic Church is behind these activities. These groups are formed either in response to various policy proposals related to intimate/sexual citizenship (marriage equality is one of the frequent catalysts of the movement, but not the only one), or as an actor seeking to prevent such proposals (for example by changing the definitions of social institutions such as marriage in the constitution).

Among the new anti-gender actors, it is also worth mentioning organizations and networks that operate transnationally – including anti-gender lobby groups in Brussels, or think tanks such as *Ordo Iuris*, which is setting up its branches across Europe.

3.1.5. Media, celebrities and public figures

The employment of various communication tactics and channels to disseminate anti-feminist and anti-gender messages is one of the most crucial strategies and features of the anti-feminist and anti-gender movement in all of the studied countries. Therefore, media actors are of utmost importance since they play a crucial role in disseminating anti-feminist and anti-gender propaganda. There are primarily conservative and pro-Catholic media outlets among them. In nations where ruling parties completely

back the anti-gender movement (such as Poland), right-wing media are regarded as mainstream due to the government's financial and other support.

Important allies of the anti-feminist and anti-gender movement are typically celebrities, such as actors and musicians. There are also internet influencers, bloggers, columnists, journalists, editors, etc. who promote anti-genderists. Italy and Poland provide evidence that some academics or scholars can also support anti-feminist and anti-gender movements. In 2015, for example, a group of academics in Slovenia signed a declaration against a law that legalized marriage equality.

3.1.6. Manosphere & TERFs

Finally, as a special anti-feminist and anti-gender actor, we should mention the manosphere. In reality, it is an atypical actor, as the manosphere is a loose network of disconnected individuals, initiatives, forums, short-lived groups organizing online harassment etc. What unites them is the fact that they work online and subscribe to the anti-feminist and anti-gender agenda. In our report, we consider them as a specific network of actors and manosphere as their online arena.

Although this network did not play an important role when the anti-gender movement emerged fifteen years ago, the manosphere is gaining importance thanks to the growing influence of online social networks and the emergence of specific groups of mainly young men, such as incels who are members of an online subculture of individuals who self-identify as unable to have a romantic or sexual partner despite wanting one.

The manosphere has also been at least explored in research to date. The Danish case, for example, demonstrates that the manosphere is a significant anti-feminist and anti-gender activity hub in the online digital environment and that in the future more attention will need to be paid specifically to anti-gender activities in virtual space.

Another group that has not received much research attention so far are TERFs (Trans-exclusionary radical feminist). While it has its roots in feminism and can hardly be fully equated with anti-gender activities, there are some similarities between them. This actor, which is more marginal in the countries we are studying, also requires further research.

3.2. Themes and agendas

Based on the literature analysed in the countries we are studying, we can conclude that among the five themes that are part of our research project, issues related to “LGBTQ+ rights” and “health & reproductive rights” and, to a lesser extent, “gender-based violence” are of particular importance to anti-gender and anti-feminist actors. In contrast, “labor market” and “migration” are less developed and established as two areas of anti-feminist and anti-gender actions and mobilizations. The analyses in the countries studied also reveal that anti-feminist and anti-gender actors frequently allude to the area of “education” in their actions and rhetoric.

3.2.1. LGBTQ+ rights

As mentioned earlier, LGBT rights are central to the agenda of the anti-feminist and anti-gender movements in the countries studied. Moreover, LGBT rights are the trigger for the emergence of anti-gender movements in some countries. In Slovenia, for example, attempts to introduce an inclusive and non-heteronormative definition of family and marriage into the Slovenian legal system in 2012

and 2015 were the main trigger for the rise and organized action of the anti-gender movement. The first anti-gender actor in Slovenia arose in 2009, when the first marriage equality law proposal was presented to the public. Moreover, during the first referendum in 2012, the opponents of marriage equality did not yet frame their arguments with references to “gender theory”, but they had already established a discursive substance that was subsequently developed into “gender theory” during the second referendum in 2015. In Italy, LGBTQ+ rights have also been one of the primary targets of anti-gender activities. Since the beginning of the mobilization in 2013, anti-gender activists have been staunch opponents of any of these rights, including the bill on same-sex civil unions in 2016. Similarly, in Greece, the 2015 passage of the “Pact on Cohabitation” law, legalizing same-sex marriage was met with opposition from right-wing political parties, the Orthodox Church and clergy, and a portion of the Greek public. Moreover, despite the legalization of same-sex marriage in Spain in 2006, the LGBT community continues to endure prejudice, particularly in the workplace. Moreover, attacks based on sexual orientation and/or gender identity or expression are the third most prevalent form of hate crime in the country. The situation related to LGBT rights is harshest in Turkey where anti-gender movement has been calling LGBT groups “abnormalities”, “perverts” and constantly reproducing the frame “homosexuality as sin”. In fact, there have been calls for LGBT people to be expelled from the country. In addition, the withdrawal from the Istanbul Convention, which is one of the primary goals of anti-genderists in Turkey, is tied both to the issues of LGBT rights and of gendered violence. Although Poland has no cohabitation statute, several legal acts and Supreme Court judgements recognize unmarried partners and offer rights and obligations. Finally, compared to other countries studied, the wave of anti-gender campaigns and rallies across Europe against “LGBT rights” has appeared to be less vocal in Denmark, where the majority of mainstream political parties have supported LGBT rights.

3.2.2. Health & reproductive rights

Health and reproductive rights, along with LGBTQ+ rights, have been at the centre of the anti-feminist and anti-gender movements. The most significant issues within this domain are the right to abortion and the right to medically assisted reproduction.

Numerous pro-life organizations in Slovenia employ the concept of “gender theory” to oppose abortion rights. In 2018, the “Let Me Live” movement opposed legal abortions in Greece. Abortion and pregnancy termination have also been the topic of numerous activities in Spain. Moreover, Turkish government is increasing efforts to restrict contraception and abortion access. The justification for these changes is to be found in discourses uttered frequently by the government elite emphasizing motherhood as the God-given role of women, how families must have three children to avoid demographic dangers, how family is the backbone of the country, and the societal dangers posed by feminists and LGBT actors.

Of the countries studied, the harshest backlash on gender related issues is present in Poland, where in October 2022 the Constitutional Tribunal, Poland's highest court, declared legislation allowing women to seek abortions for serious foetal impairment unconstitutional after years of attempts to tighten the abortion law. This law restricts abortion in Poland to rape, incest, or life-threatening situations, making it nearly impossible for Polish women to obtain one.

Furthermore, the anti-gender movement in Italy, which sprang from the local pro-life movement, opposes abortion, medically assisted reproduction, and surrogacy. Last but not least, explicit references are made by Danish users on the manosphere to the reproduction inside the nuclear heterosexual family that is viewed as a safeguard against the decline of the fertility rate in the country.

3.2.3. Gender-based violence

Gender-based violence is not one of the key issues addressed by the anti-gender or anti-feminist movement in the eight countries covered by our project. The biggest mobiliser in this area is the protests against the Istanbul Convention, which anti-gender actors consider not to protect women but to perpetrate further violence against them. In Turkey, for instance, anti-feminist and anti-gender efforts against the Istanbul Convention were built on discourses about the dissolution of the family, rising divorce rates, and that men become victims when they are evicted from their homes due to their violence.

Gender-based violence also appears in anti-gender discourse as resistance to the interpretation that women are the main victims of violence. For instance, in Turkey, the more radical discourses blame “evil” women of abusing alimony to divorce husbands, who are the “real victims”. Moreover, in Spain, anti-feminist groups reject gender-based violence laws and specific laws addressing male violence. Also in Italy, the anti-gender movement opposes defining gender-based violence as violence against women.

Finally, the prevalent belief in Denmark is still that gender equality has been achieved, and until the #MeToo global mobilizations in 2017, gender-based violence and sexual harassment got little public or government attention.

3.2.4. Labor market

The existing literature and available sources do not address “labor market” in great detail, yet we can nevertheless draw some conclusions. In Slovenia and Greece, for instance, the anti-feminist and anti-gender movement noted the succession of austerity measures implemented by national governments. Family Initiative questioned the impact of austerity measures implemented during the 2012–2013 economic crisis on family social policy in Slovenia. The austerity policy in Greece contributed to the rise of Golden Dawn. Moreover, in 2012, the arrest and public stigmatization of HIV-positive women who allegedly worked as prostitutes in Greece was a noteworthy event. The public debate about the arrest also raised, at least in part, the issue of precarious employment. Furthermore, anti-gender and anti-feminist movements in Spain have reluctantly accepted, normalized, and naturalized the gender pay disparity, while opposing positive discrimination and maternity leave extensions. In Turkey, the government and GONGOs have predominantly adopted state policies based on the concept that women’s primary responsibility is to care for their families. In Poland, the Labor Code guarantees LGBTQ+ equality, but LGBTQ+ individuals rarely utilize it out of fear of discrimination. Furthermore, transgender individuals in Poland endure regular employment prejudice. They must use employment records providing personal information and gender from before the gender reassignment procedure. Poland also forbids military service of transgender individuals. In Denmark and Italy, existing research indicates that the subject of “labor market” does not significantly engage the anti-feminist and anti-gender movement.

3.2.5. Migration

Migration, like “labor market”, is not a particularly significant concern for anti-feminist and anti-gender actors in the countries studied. Since they mostly oppose LGBTQ+ and reproductive rights, their primary “enemies” are LGBTQ+ activists, abortion rights advocates, “gender theory” ideologists, feminists, “socialists”, etc. Nevertheless, the intersection of migration and LGBTQ+ rights is detected

in the existing literature in Slovenia and Poland. For instance, some anti-gender actors in Slovenia are campaigning against the Marrakesh Declaration¹, which they say threatens the EU and European culture by inviting non-Christian immigrants. Anti-gender actors also see marriage equality and migration policy as part of a radical left political agenda: If we let one in, we open the door to the other. Similarly, in Poland, the 2014–2015 Polish campaign against “genderism” was displaced by the panic over the European migrant “crisis”. The main enemy that the conservative right focused on during their 2015 election campaign was the “Muslim refugee”, bolstered by demonized “gender ideology”. The Law and Justice Party's ability to integrate these two themes prepared the road for its victory in the 2015 election. In Poland, “genderists” and migrants (now called “invaders” and “terrorists”) are seen as national foes, collaborating in a Brussels-led plot against Polish culture and sovereignty. In addition, the anti-immigrant agenda is a feature of the far-right Golden Dawn Party in Greece. Despite Turkey having the most migrants in the world, anti-gender and anti-feminist movements have not focused strongly on this issue. Similarly, according to existing literature and sources, anti-gender and anti-feminist movements in Spain and Italy are not actively concerned with the migrant issue since they priorities LGBTQ+ and reproductive rights.

In the Danish context, a narrative of gender and sexual exceptionalism enables anti-feminist and anti-gender actors to assert that the Danes have fully attained gender equality and LGBTQ+ rights, in contrast to immigrants (particularly Muslims) who are “lagging behind”. This argument is presented in homonationalist (Puar, 2007) and femonationalist (Farris, 2017) fashion.

3.2.6. Education

In addition to the five areas presented above, “education” has also emerged as an important area influencing the agenda and actions of the anti-feminist and anti-gender movement in the countries studied.

In Slovenia, for example, anti-gender actors generate public controversies over certain content in public schools, claiming that it represents “gender theory”. The moral panic that occurred in some schools and among some parents resulted in teachers self-censoring themselves and avoiding issues that were constructed as problematic by such debates, e.g., different family forms, gender equality, homosexuality, etc. Similarly, the anti-gender mobilization in Poland focuses on sex education, which ultraconservatives equate to LGBTQ+ and “genderists”, aiming to sexualize youngsters. In Turkey, secular and Islamic actors have long fought over education. Islamic actors have always wanted the school system and curriculum to reflect their national and Islamic beliefs, but anti-gender components are new to their goal. However, the AKP government has implemented various anti-gender actor demands into the school system, which have changed the national organization and education itself. Moreover, in recent years in Spain there has been opposition to sex education in schools related to “parental PIN” (i.e., a way for parents to decide on certain types of content and teachings given to their children). This issue manages to widely mobilize the moral panics of social conservatism as it touches on issues related to sexuality, feminism, and sexual and gender identity. Italian and Danish anti-feminist and anti-gender actors have also addressed schools and academia. The Italian anti-gender movement has targeted the “alias career”, which allows trans students to use their preferred name in school instead of their first name. Furthermore, gender studies, along with critical race and colonial studies, are increasingly criticized by right-wing commentators and politicians in Denmark.

¹ The Marrakech Declaration proposes the duties and responsibilities of EU member states in managing migration. The declaration has been criticized, particularly by right-wing political parties and actors. See: https://cfnhri.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/Marrakech_Declaration_ENG_2.pdf

The argument is predicated on the notion that “identity politics” and “wokeness” have become the “new normal” in a significant portion of society, and particularly in gender, race, and postcolonial studies in academia.

3.3. Repertoire of actions (strategies)

Anti-feminist and anti-gender activists have used a variety of mobilizing tactics and a rich repertoire of actions and tools, which has been thoroughly described and analyzed in the existing literature. Despite their complexity, they can be grouped into three main categories: (1) public event organization; (2) communication strategies, tactics and channels; and (3) networking and lobbying.

3.3.1. Public event organization

The organization of public events, such as conferences, public meetings, roundtables, protests, rallies, and direct actions, is a notable tactic employed by anti-feminist and anti-gender actors in the countries examined. Pro-life anti-gender actors, for example, organized "Every Life Matters" in Spain and "March for Life" in Slovenia, praying for unborn children in front of gynecological clinics and similar. Mass protests against marriage equality in France, organized by “Manif pour tous”, is another visible example of such mobilizations.

Anti-gender actors also mobilize their supporters by organizing “frontal lectures” by so-called professionals (lawyers, physicians, researchers, journalists, intellectuals) who use quasi-scientific discourse in order to create an impression of debunking “gender ideology” with hard scientific data. Often these lectures take place in church-owned facilities.

3.3.2. Communication strategies, tactics, and channels

Anti-feminist and anti-gender actors utilize many methods to propagate their messages. Online petitions, chain emails, website promotion of anti-gender notions, social media defamation campaigns, press releases, radio and TV appearances, etc., are crucial.

Anti-gender movement websites have been crucial in referenda campaigns, promoting anti-genderism and mobilizing support. Online communication channels were very important in recruiting volunteers and discrediting national press information. Such online communication methods were also used to raise donations, sell merchandise, and broadcast scandalous "life stories" (often from dubious US online media) about the horrific impacts of "gender theory".

Moreover, anti-gender activists utilize social media defamation campaigns (Turkey, Spain, Slovenia). The Danish case demonstrates that the "manosphere" is another prominent anti-feminist and anti-gender arena that promotes anti-feminist and anti-gender agendas. In the case of manosphere it is not about influencing public opinion, but rather developing a community of "brotherhood" and like-minded people.

An important part of their communication strategy is to appropriate liberal discourse on human rights. Anti-feminist and anti-gender actors have adopted tactics and rhetoric from feminist and LGBTQ+ activists. In Turkey, AKP uses policymaking and co-optation to legitimize conservative gender norms. The next important discursive element is the construction of fear against the LGBTQ+ community, primarily in connection to “our children” and the future of “our nation”. In such context children adopted by same-sex couples are seen to be at risk.

Much of the anti-gender rhetoric is motivated by fear and affect. Due to the successful building of the fear that same-sex couples may adopt "innocent" children, "children" have become the most important mobilizing weapon of the anti-gender movement, beginning with their logos, which frequently feature a child silhouette (and natural heterosexual family). Additionally, pictures of fetuses personified as smiling, sucking their thumbs, or bleeding, and dismembered fetuses are used. Stories told by an "unborn daughter" or "unborn son" to her mother before being aborted, as well as accounts of abortion survivors, are among the most powerful and successful means of communicating anti-gender and anti-feminist ideas.

3.3.3. Networking and lobbying

Research shows that anti-gender and anti-feminist movements have adopted networking methods that have proven successful in the feminist and LGBTQ+ movements. Processes of up-loading and cross-loading of agendas and tools are taking place among these actors at a transnational level. They have also adopted successful lobbying tactics and practices. In centers of political power, such as Brussels, international anti-gender lobby organizations and groups are emerging, seeking to ensure that their representatives have the greatest influence on equality and other issues of importance to the anti-gender movement. One of their strategies is to "walk through institutions", which means that they try to position themselves as a "party to the process" in the decision-making and deliberative bodies of governments at national and transnational level. Similarly, they are increasingly active in the field of strategic litigation and attempts to influence the functioning of courts, including the European Court of Human Rights.

3.4. Frames

A number of previous studies on anti-gender movements in national contexts have dealt with the frames of arguments used by anti-gender and anti-feminist actors. Our analysis shows that there is a large overlap between frames in different national contexts, which supports the thesis of intense (global) processes of cross-loading of agendas, strategies and discourses between anti-gender actors. Nevertheless, there are also some specificities and specific national frames.

In a review of the existing literature, we identified 14 major frames that appear as part of anti-gender and anti-feminist rhetoric in the eight countries analyzed. These frames can be divided into four interrelated groups: (1) Children and family frames; (2) Gender-contract frames; (3) Conceptual frames; and (4) Ideological frames.

3.4.1. Children and family frames

These frames are the most basic frames used by the anti-gender and anti-feminist movement. They are based on an understanding of the role of the traditional family in society, as a place of reproduction and childcare. As this is not only about the narrow function of reproduction in the family, the role of the future of the nation is also specifically emphasized. It is through this dimension that nativist and nationalist ideas enter anti-gender frames and anti-gender discourse. Through these frames, all other forms of cohabitation are discredited, primarily same-sex partnerships, but also homosexuality as a non-reproductive practice. Additionally, superimposed on these frames is the contemporary phenomenon of the »protective childhood«, through which parents attempt to control every aspect of their children's lives, including the content of school curricula. The emotive dimension of these

frames is linked to the fact that the focus is placed on the »innocent child«, who - alongside the traditional family and the nation - is supposed to be the primary target and victim of gender ideology.

Among »Children and family frames« are »Natural family and anti-homosexuality frame«, »Best interest of children frame«, »Education frame«, »Demographic winter frame«, and »Abortion frame«.

Natural family and anti-homosexuality frame

One of the key frames that the current research on anti-gender movement outlines is the focus on »natural family«. It is the basis through which the anti-gender actors try to establish a unifying identity among »ordinary people«, those who were »left-behind« or believe that things have simply gone too far. The identity rests on the essentialist ideas about sexuality and gender. As a result, this also leads to »pathologizing and de-humanizing of LGBTQ+ people« (Lavizzari, 2023) or to seeing homosexuality as being »non-natural, a sin and an abnormality« and »as an obstacle for the reproduction of the nation« (Kiouпкиolis & Karydou, 2023).

The "natural family" frame is based on the idea that the nuclear family of a man, a woman and children is the only true form of family, and the only institution that deserves to be called a "family". This form of family is also understood as the only safe environment for raising children. In some contexts, anti-gender actors attack 'domestic violence' laws precisely because they are supposed to cast a bad light on the traditional family. They deny that the family is often a place of violence and that women are the most frequent victims of domestic violence.

The "natural family" frame operates both at an individual level (what is good for the individual, especially the child) and at a collective level. At the latter level, the traditional family is the foundation of the nation, of the nation's future, and also of the nation's authenticity. The traditional family is the beginning and the end of everything, and gender ideology is seen as a direct attack on the traditional family.

Best interest of children frame

Closely related to the definition of the natural family is also a pursuit of the best interests of the child which cannot be determined by the experts (as they are already brainwashed by gender ideology), but rather by the anti-gender actors themselves. In other words: the best interest of the child is "considered self-evident rather than subject to contested social/political definition" (Kiouпкиolis & Karydou, 2023). The best interest of a child – and their human rights – are determined by living in a heterosexual family. More important than family dynamics is who makes up the family and what gender they are.

Children are also often used to set off episodes of moral panic. Here, anti-gender actors use their media and social networks to construct different scenarios about the threat to "our children". In Poland, for example, "right-wing journalists kept repeating that those in favor of LGBTQ+ wanted to teach 4-year-old kids how to masturbate" (Muszel, 2023).

Education frame

Another major frame is linked with education and the rights of parents to raise their children according to their philosophical and religious beliefs. This frame is based on an apparent clash between said right of parents and the duty of the public schools to base the curriculum on scientific knowledge without

ideological admixture. Sex education and transgender issues are common themes raised as problematic.

Demographic winter frame

A classic “nationalistic frame” that is not used only by anti-gender actors, but also by radical right and populist actors, is the idea about the alleged »demographic winter« and the need to increase the birth rate. In such contexts this frame is closely intertwined with anti-islam and anti-immigration discourses.

Abortion frame

The abortion frame is already familiar from the pro-life movements and has only been taken over by the anti-gender movement. It appears in various iterations, but it is fundamentally based on the idea that life begins at conception, not birth, and that people have no right to interfere in the life of the unborn child. Of particular discursive interest is the use of the term 'unborn child', as it attributes human qualities to embryos, often by using images that purport to show the embryo laughing, sucking a finger, and so on.

3.4.2. Gender contract frames

These frames are essentially concerned with the relationship between men and women and are closely related in content to the previous group of frames on the family and children. The gender-contract frames insist on a binary gender system and on the idea of complementarity of the sexes. This means that each gender also has inherently defined social roles. These frames can be called "gender-contract" frames precisely because they seek to re-establish the traditional "contract" between the sexes, according to which men are given an active role in public life and women are given a primarily nurturing role based on their nature. While this does not mean that women should not enter the public sphere, it does mean a denial of the concept of gender equality.

Among »Gender contract frames« are »Back to the kitchen frame«, »Gender-based violence frame«, »Men's groups frame«, and »Gender-binary frame«

Back to the kitchen frame

Closely linked to essentialist ideas about the gender system and essentialized constructions of masculinity and femininity is the frame which, in some of the national cases analyzed, advocates the return of women to the context of the home. The privatization of caring activities is understood as consistent with the 'natural' role of women. This frame appears in various forms, often in the “between the lines” format in religious, neoliberal, and nationalist anti-gender and anti-feminist rhetoric.

Gender-based violence frame

In terms of violence, the frames, used by anti-gender and anti-feminist actors, are clustered around the interpretation that the concept of "gender-based violence" is in fact ideological and causes additional violence against women, while overlooking the violence perpetrated by women against men. This is what is supposed to be enshrined in the Istanbul Convention, which, in the context of

gender-based violence, is one of the main bones of contention and a mobilizing element for many anti-gender movements across Europe. In some countries, the violence frame is constructed around attempts to re-frame “gender-based violence” into “intra-family” or “domestic violence”.

In some other manifestations of the frame related to violence, it is directed against migration. In Spain, for example, Vox leaders use “false data to accuse foreigners of the majority of sexual crimes” (Romanos & Sádaba, 2023).

Men's groups frame

Specific discursive contexts arise in relation to so-called men's groups and men's rights activism, which advocate the establishment of a system whereby children should belong equally to both parents in the event of divorce. These groups are based on the understanding that the judicial system and social services are feminized and that this results in a violation of the human rights of men and children.

In Greece, for example, through the frame of the best interests of the child, they stress that the absence of one parent (i.e., the father) causes the child to develop in a physically and mentally abnormal way. This frame assumes a kind of scientific representation and, at the same time, discredits classical science, which has supposedly already succumbed to feminist ideology.

On the other hand, Turkish men's group use the frame of self-victimization in their anti-alimony campaigns. As they are “financially burdened”, they become frustrated and potentially violent and cannot re-marry.

Specifically in Turkey the frame that men are victims of laws on alimony, child custody, and domestic violence seems to stand out clearly, as there are anti-gender actors which actively demand “masculinist restoration” and even justify and normalize violence in everyday life. Similar frames can be found also in Denmark, where feminist campaigns are interpreted as “smear campaigns where women are ‘ganging up’ innocent men in ‘witch hunts’ and ‘kangaroo courts’” (Beyer Gregersen et al., 2023). The frame that women in Western society are planning to rule over men is specifically present in manosphere.

Gender-binary frame

Gender-binary frame is used mainly in contemporary debates on transgender rights and is based on the idea that biologically there are two sexes, which means that there are also only two gender identities - masculinity and femininity.

3.4.3. Conceptual frames

Conceptual frames are those that are fundamentally based on a reinterpretation of the understanding of certain concepts used by the feminist and LGBTQ+ movements. Frames are based on the principle of conspiracy theory, which is said to underpin the actions of feminist and LGBTQ+ actors and political elites who are pushing for equality policies. With these frames they try to debunk the alleged hidden agendas behind the consumption of concepts such as human rights, equality and the like. They do not deny these concepts, but rather reinterpret them in a way that suits their political and ideological objectives. One could attribute to these frames attempts, based on Gramscian theory, to reshape meanings and establish a new cultural hegemony.

Among »Conceptual frames« are »Human rights frame«, »Natural law frame«, and »Gender fatigue frame«.

Human rights frame

In anti-gender discourse the term “human rights” is not used in its ordinary usage, but rather in a mirroring strategy by which the human rights of the majority (i.e., of anti-gender actors, and more specifically of religious believers, innocent children, etc.) are being taken away by the proponents of feminist and LGBTQ+ movements. The human rights frame therefore reveals how those who usually refer to human rights are in fact covering up the ideology on which they operate and with which they seek to gain further privileges.

Natural law frame

Another frame, which appears predominantly in religious discourse, is related to the argument of natural law or the law of God. Such framing intensifies an essentialist understanding of nature and the gender system, since there is supposed to be a natural order in social relations as well. In this sense, gender ideology is seen as one that goes against the natural order of things.

Gender fatigue frame

In some countries, specifically Denmark, but not limited to that political context, is the frame of gender fatigue. This frame is based on the conclusion that gender equality has already been achieved and there is no need for concepts such as “gender equality”. In this sense, there is also no longer a need for feminism and other similar movements. An alternative version of this frame is the claim that today’s struggles for gender equality are in fact struggles for privileges, since equal rights and equal opportunities have already been achieved.

3.4.4. Ideological frames

The last set of frames is called the ideological frames. Although all frames are based on a particular (anti-gender and anti-feminist) ideology, the specificity of this set of frames is that they place a particular emphasis on the ideologization of gender equality politics. Thus, these frames specifically highlight the alleged colonizing efforts of political elites who are trying to impose Western values on the whole world, while at the same time bringing to absurdity value-based concepts such as political correctness as a sign of proof of the existence and consequences of gender ideology.

Among the »Ideological frames« are »Political correctness and woke culture frame« and »Colonization and Marxism frame«.

Political correctness and woke culture frame

The frame of political correctness and woke culture is one of the supporting frames in anti-gender discourse. It is linked to debates about the freedom of speech, which is said to be restricted by feminist and LGBTQ+ movements in a way that women and sexual minorities cannot be questioned or opposed. The freedom of speech frame is a typical example of how human rights discourse is

appropriated by anti-gender actors in order to socially and politically exclude specific groups of people which they construct as unacceptable, abnormal, against the natural law, etc.

Colonization and Marxism frame

Finally, some reports point out that one of the rhetoric strategies of the anti-gender movement is to refer to »gender« in its original English language in order to send the message that this is an alien construct imposed on unsuspecting innocent people. Gender is constructed as a “Trojan Horse” (Alniaçık & Altan Olcay, 2023). In connection with this framework, ideas of contemporary ideological colonization by political elites and radical feminist and homosexual actors also emerge. Gender ideology is thus presented as a form of ideological colonization – either by the current elites (which is another “empty signifier” in anti-gender discourse) or by former communist elites. In fact, in some countries, such as Slovenia or Poland, gender ideology is presented as an “offshoot of Marxism” and a new “gender struggle” which replaces previous class struggle.

The frame of colonization is specifically situated in the national-historical context in which the anti-gender movement operates. Closely related to colonization frames are also debates about “cultural authenticity”, which brings us back to the “natural family” frame and its derivations in relation to the nation.

3.5. Explanations of the successes of the movement

Existing literature list different combinations of domestic and international political, social, cultural, and economic factors in order to explain the emergence and the success of the anti-gender and anti-feminist movement in the eight selected countries. This includes negative effects of economic crisis and neoliberalism on equality policies, the cultural persistence of traditional gender roles and crisis of masculinity, political authoritarian shifts, and reactivation of the Catholic Church in the context of growing secularization.

Negative effects of economic crisis and neoliberalism on equality policies

Current literature on the anti-gender movement typically explains it as a conservative reaction to the social and economic devastation caused by neoliberalism, in which "every sphere of social life is subject to economization, all institutions are managed according to the logic of profit maximization, and people are primarily defined by their purchasing power" (Muszel, 2023).

Anti-gender and anti-feminist movements are, according to some studies, a "marriage of convenience between neoconservatism and neoliberalism" (Alniaçık & Altan Olcay, 2023). This is exemplified by the way in which neoconservative political leaders profit from the neoliberal disintegration of the welfare system, which is consistent with their ideological interpretation of the gender system, according to which women are innately intended to be caregivers. It is an effort to reestablish the "patriarchal gender contract." In Turkey this is specifically facilitated by the suspension of the EU membership process and Turkey's drift away from EU norms, particularly gender equality.

Cultural persistence of traditional gender roles and crisis of masculinity

Another reason for the growth of the anti-gender and anti-feminist movement is the alleged "crisis of masculinity." Some men are viewed as "victims" and "losers" under the equality policies. In addition,

this interpretation is intensified by social and economic uncertainty and rising unemployment, as conventional masculinity is frequently characterized in terms of work. In Greece, for instance, this type of masculinity crisis has led to an increase in the legitimization and normalization of sexism, violent masculinity, and the "rigidification of gender hierarchies" (Kioupkiolis & Karydou, 2023), especially among radical/far-right political groups.

A slightly more social-psychological approach to explaining the phenomenon of the anti-gender movement also focuses on the "crisis of masculinity". Anti-genderism and anti-feminism are seen as a reaction of young, angry, vulnerable, and dissatisfied men who associate their position of powerlessness to the antagonistic relationship between men and women. The latter are understood as perceiving privileged positions at the expense of men. The crisis of masculinity is thus fostered by the dismantling of former allegedly natural male privileges.

Political authoritarian shifts

A third strand of literature links the successes of the anti-gender and anti-feminist movements to the authoritarian shifts and political success of radical right parties, such as *League* in Italy or *Vox* in Spain. These parties are connected with the processes of deterioration of democracy. "Since democracy is a necessary condition (and prerequisite) of the feminist movement as well as an ally, any problem in the democratic situation affect feminism" (SP). According to some interpretations we are witnessing a "dignity revolution" in which underprivileged groups are trying to restore their dignity by playing on "national pride and collective fantasies about wronged people and treacherous elites" (Muszel, 2023). The latter are represented by feminists, LGBTQ+, and political elites in Brussels that one has to fear and fight against.

From this perspective the anti-gender and current anti-feminist movements are part of a broader backlash politics that instrumentalizes religion and the traditional gender system as tools of resistance. Traditional gender roles and respect for religion are seen as crucial foundations for the existence of the nation. In a broader sense, "gender" is understood as a sign of everything that is wrong with liberal democracy, which needs to be replaced by a strong (authoritarian) leader and politics.

Reactivation of Catholic Church in the context of growing secularization

The fourth interpretive strand of the anti-gender movements links them to the internal dynamics and changes of the Roman Catholic Church and the process of re-evangelization initiated in response to increasing secularization. An important part of re-evangelization is precisely the activation of lay people in newly formed associations, organizations, and movements that spread religious messages through a secularized discourse. What was essentially a Catholic project has expanded to other religions through the anti-gender movement, which has adopted the discourse of threats to the family, masculinity, femininity, and the future of the nation.

The increasing secularization and dismantling of patriarchal culture is seen as a result of the intense and successful feminist and LGBTQ+ movements of the last three decades. From this perspective, the anti-gender movement is also interpreted through action-reaction logic. As international feminist movements have been on the rise in recent years with projects such as #MeToo, this has fueled resistance on the other side that seeks to preserve the traditional gender contract. Moreover, the passage of specific progressive laws related to intimate or sexual citizenship could have similar effects. In Spain, for example, the anti-gender movement emerged from mass protests against the Zapatero

government, which passed several progressive laws on gender-based violence, same-sex marriage, abortion, and sex education in schools in a relatively short period of time (from 2004 to 2010).

4. Conclusion

A comprehensive mapping of key anti-feminist and anti-gender actors, their strategies, and discourse frames in Denmark, France, Greece, Italy, Poland, Slovenia, Spain, and Turkey, presented in this report, shows that after decades of steady development of gender and sexual rights, new waves of opposition have emerged in the form of the so-called anti-gender movement. Moreover, many of the anti-feminist actors that existed before the emergence of the anti-gender movement in the 2010s now overlap with it or have used the success of the anti-gender movement and its platform to spread their (old) ideas.

In the countries studied, there has been a rise in anti-feminist and anti-gender actors and organizations over the past decade. Based on our analysis, we can conclude that among the five thematic areas of our research project, "LGBTQ+ rights," "health and reproductive rights," and, to a lesser extent, "gender-based violence" are of particular interest to anti-gender and anti-feminist actors. In contrast, "labor market" and "migration" are less established as areas of anti-feminist and anti-gender action and mobilization, while "education" emerged as one of the new areas for anti-gender activity identified alongside the above five thematic areas.

The anti-feminist and anti-gender movements are well resourced, well organized, and widely visible, and they have extensive support networks and resources. Although anti-feminist and anti-gender actors differ according to their role in the movement (whether they are central actors or allies), their modus operandi, the timing of their emergence and activity, or their antecedents to the emergence of the anti-gender and anti-feminist movements, we identified six groups of actors: (1) religious actors, (2) political parties, (3) old (anti-gender) actors, (4) new anti-gender actors, (5) media, celebrities, and public figures, and (6) the manosphere, which is an online arena in which a network of very different actors work against the so-called "gender agenda".

Anti-feminist and anti-gender activists have employed a variety of mobilization tactics and a rich repertoire of actions and tools that have been extensively described and analyzed in the existing literature. Despite their complexity, they can be grouped into three main categories: (1) organizing public events; (2) communication strategies, tactics, and channels; and (3) networking and lobbying. Our analysis also shows that anti-gender and anti-feminist actors in different countries use similar argumentation frames. This supports the idea that agendas, strategies, and discourses between anti-gender actors are heavily influenced by each other on a global scale.

In reviewing the existing literature, we identified 14 key frames that appear as part of anti-gender and anti-feminist rhetoric in the eight countries studied. These frames can be divided into four interrelated groups: (1) Children and family frames, which are based on an understanding of the role of the traditional family in society as a site of reproduction and childcare; (2) Gender contract frames, which insist on a binary gender system and the idea of complementarity of the sexes; (3) conceptual frames, which are those that are essentially based on a reinterpretation of the understanding of certain concepts used by the feminist and LGBTQ+ movements, particularly "human rights" and "equality"; and (4) ideological frames that place a particular emphasis on the ideologization of gender equality politics.

In attempting to understand the emergence and success of the anti-gender and anti-feminism movements in the eight selected countries, the existing literature lists various combinations of

national and international political, social, cultural, and economic elements. These include the negative impact of the economic crisis and neoliberalism on gender equality programs, the cultural persistence of traditional gender norms and the crisis of masculinity, political authoritarian movements, and the reactivation of the Catholic Church against a backdrop of increasing secularization.

The literature review has shown that the importance and relevance of studying anti-gender mobilization is not limited to identifying the characteristics, actors, and strategies of this new movement that has developed over the last decade but also touches on broader issues such as the decline of the public sphere and democratic norms (e.g., erosion of democratic argumentative debate, appropriation of public spheres by right-wing populist elites, crisis of trust in science, increasing individualization, etc.). As argued earlier, the anti-gender movement contributes to contemporary authoritarian processes of de-democratization that target not only gender and equality but also the concept and practice of democracy (Lombardo et al., 2021). For this reason, as highlighted by Kováts (2018), the anti-gender movement should not be understood primarily as a mobilization against equality but rather as a symptom of a larger systemic crisis of progressive politics and its complicity with neoliberal ideology.

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*Feminist movements
revitalizing Democracy in Europe.*

DENMARK

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1. Introduction

This literature review maps the antifeminist and anti-gender mobilizations in Denmark by using the already available research. The extant literature and resources provide us with the indispensable knowledge from where to delve further into the density and variety of the Danish antifeminist and anti-gender sphere.

The available literature on antifeminist and anti-gender actors and movements in Denmark is varied, and not limited to a specific research field (such as gender studies). The literature collected here is based on academic as well as non-academic production. Our material and data include: research articles and monographs, reports, investigative journalism data, podcasts on social media use and online antifeminist and anti-gender content, research on the #MeToo counter-mobilizations and on the radical and populist right-wing approach to gender. The material was first gathered by browsing various online research databases by using the keywords “antifeminism” AND/OR “anti-gender” AND/OR “mobilizations”, AND “Denmark”, as well as by applying a broader spectrum of search of relevant articles and reports, and other material available on databases such as [Infomedia](#). Besides, our literature search included the consulting of experts in the field; we have conducted an expert interview with Christian Mogensen, who is a digital consultant widely recognized for his expertise on Danish users in the manosphere. Our literature search activity also disclosed a growing problematic emerging from the [harsh critique](#) of the scientific value and the activism of gender research scholars which endangers the engagement of further research and investigation on these [topics](#). The FIERCE project underlines the need to provide solid and comprehensive background knowledge of the antifeminist and anti-gender actors, on their network, web of alliances and worldviews.

Our first screening of the material available allows us to differentiate between at least two main strands of literature dealing with antifeminism and anti-gender issues. On the one hand, the earlier research on gender and the far right, and, on the other, the more recent focus on the global online and mainstreaming phenomenon of antifeminism and anti-genderism. The growing electoral support and political influence achieved by the far right in Europe and globally during the past decades has triggered a strain of study that investigates how questions of gender and (de-)gendering also enter the political agenda, ideology and discourse of the far right in Denmark. In the Danish case this relates to both parliamentary and extra-parliamentary far right organizations, which have appeared and developed across the past twenty years. Among these, the most researched is The Danish People’s Party (Meret & Nissen, 2021), although a few new far right parties have been launched more recently. A particular subject matter within this area of research is the way in which the Danish far right understands and explains gender, gender roles, family politics, and gendered party leadership (Meret & Siim, 2013, Meret, 2015, Meret et al., 2017). To varying degrees, these gender scholars concur in the notion that far right politics should be inscribed in the material and ideological context of gendered globalization, and of the new gendered and racialized relationships. The focus of these studies is on formal and often institutionalized actors, namely political parties/organizations and their programs, active members, leadership and electorate.

The other strain of literature is of more recent date and less institutionally driven (Lorentzen 2022; Mogensen & Rand 2020a; Marker & Hendricks 2019). It engages with the global and complex phenomenon of antifeminism and anti-genderism. This covers a complex web of alliances, collaborations, direct and indirect networking of broader array of actors and allies with a much less clear and coordinated agenda. Among the definitions used to identify these variegated environments

is the concept of *'manosphere'*. The manosphere is thought of as a loose network of digital communities which share the conviction that feminism is a threat to our society and that there is undeniably an unequal and biologically determined relation between the (only) two sexes. Some Danish mainstream media also play an active role in further disseminating and amplifying antifeminist and anti-gender standpoints and worldviews. In this sense, these media platforms are also active actors that placed antifeminist and anti-gender issues in their own framing about how feminist views and pro-LGBTQ+ attitudes work against a free and equal society.

Antifeminist and anti-gender positions in Denmark therefore come in many different disguises. Skepticism as well as the direct critique of the #MeToo movement are also among the issues we find discussed in the available literature. Another is the association of feminism and LGBTQ+ rights with terms such as 'identity politics,' 'wokeness,' or 'wokeism,' and 'political correctness'. Antifeminist and anti-gender actors critically refer to both global and local triggering-events, which re-ignite discussions, tensions, and disagreements, and want to demonstrate that Denmark is not different than other contexts when it comes to 'how far' feminist and LGBTQ+ demands can go. A case in point here is the fuss stirred by the decision of a bakery chain in Denmark to call the human-shaped birthday cake that they bake a "[cake-person](#)" (*kageperson*), thus avoiding the gender-binary choice between the traditional definitions "cake-man" (*kagemand*) or "cake-wife" (*kagekone*). This local issue was picked up and widely divulged by the media to illustrate the far-reaching results of feminism and LGBTQ+ demands. It became a way to nail global anti-feminist and anti-gender narratives down to Danish everyday life, linking the removal of basic freedoms and natural relations between people of different sex to concrete results, already identifiable at your favorite bakery shop. This notwithstanding the triviality and rather insignificant implication of this event. However, we still lack in-depth research on the effects of such discourses on the Danish media and public opinion.

2. History of the Danish anti-gender/anti-feminist movement

Resistance to women's movement and to women's struggles for emancipation is not new to Denmark and can be traced back to the fierce critique addressed against independent women and feminist forerunners such as Natalie Zahle (1827-1913), Mathilde Fibiger (1830-1872) and Ida Fable-Hansen (1849-1922) by traditional conservative actors. In the 1970s, the second wave of the feminist movement, known as the Redstocking Movement, triggered a heated reaction of traditionalists, conservative and religious milieus. In recent decades it has often been the far right to portray the feminist movement of the second wave as a threat to the core family at the basis of Danish society, in which traditional gender roles with women and mothers responsible for care work and children upbringing and men as breadwinners act as main guarantors of stability, cohesion and reproduction. This approach was for instance formulated by The Danish People's Party in the party 2002 Principle Program, which states that the "family", consisting of husband, wife and children, "is at the core of the Danish society" (DF, 2002, p. v). Scholars point out that The Danish People's Party position towards gender equality, gay rights, and the family are used strategically in public debates to target Muslim minorities' patriarchal views and failure to emancipate from Islam's lack of a gender equality approach (Meret & Siim 2013; 93; Siim and Meret 2016, 126). Arguably The Danish People's Party advocates for femonationalist views (Farris 2017) supporting nationalist Danish gender equality to target and stigmatize the Muslim population.

In his book "Antifeminism: Hate against women in the age of equality" (Thorup 2021, 43), Mikkel Thorup argues that Danish (as well as global) antifeminism cannot be understood without situating it within two main historical tendencies. On the one side, the 2002 rightward turn in politics that

provoked the so-called 2001 ‘system change’ in politics, opening to more than a decade long minority right-wing rule under the Liberals and Conservatives that depended on the support of The Danish People’s Party. This government coalition lasted throughout consecutive governments until 2011 and it gained power again in the years 2015-2019 after the brief center-left wing interregnum. The role of The Danish People’s Party proved influential to radically reform Danish immigration, asylum and citizenship politics (Meret, 2020), but it also contributed to push the threshold of what it is allowed to say on minorities, Islam, and other matters (see e.g., Meret & Gregersen, 2019). On the other side, Thorup also underlines the impact of the global rise of the Internet, and of the widespread use of social media. These provided a completely new arena and new rules for political expression for traditional mainstream media, but also new prairies for extreme subcultural milieus, which could undisturbedly post, exchange and circulate virulent antifeminist and anti-gender content. An extreme case in this regard is the anti-feminist and anti-gender content contained in the infamous 2083 – A European Declaration of Independence, the 1500 pages document manifesto posted on July 11, 2011, by far-right terrorist Anders Behring Breivik on the internet before his killing spree in Oslo and Utøya.

In the Danish context, where gender equality is officially praised as a national value, a third historical tendency adds to the previous two: the escalating concern for men’s status and role in Western society, guided by what is seen as the overruling principle of gender equality and LGBTQ+ rights. The phenomenon (sometimes framed in conspiracy terms) triggered the formation of groups and organizations working for men’s rights, such as the Forum for Men’s Health, established as early as 2004. In 2020, The Danish Men’s Society was also founded as the male feminist counterpart to the well-established The Danish Women’s Society. Another men-based organization, The Men’s Council (*Manderådet*), was launched in 2019 having a more extreme gender vision and outspoken mission, for instance in their view of feminists overpowering men in Western societies. In its most extreme version (bridging over to far right narratives), the fear for men’s future in the West gets conflated by The Great Replacement conspiracy theory: the fear that the Muslim minority eventually will overtake the increasingly feminized, secularized, and demographically shrinking Christian West. These developments need to be understood and contextualized within the much broader canvas, represented by the global emergence of men’s groups and movements with antifeminist and anti-gender worldviews and their relations with the global far right. Among the influential voices to push for a global “Men’s Rights Movement” we find for instance the American activist Paul Elam, who in 2009 started the website *A Voice for Men*, that today continues being updated and it is a source of inspiration for new and consolidating groups in different parts of the world. While we need to be cautious in categorizing all groups and organizations promoting men’s rights as antifeminists and anti-gender, it is however worth noticing their concomitant emergence with the claims that women’s struggles for emancipation and rights have gone too far and now negatively impact men’s role, position and condition in society.

3. Actors and allies in antifeminist and anti-gender milieus

Anti-feminist and anti-gender actors in Denmark have very different backgrounds and reputation and their positions have only recently stirred the public and scholarly interest. Some of them are well-known right-wing politicians, while others belong to less frequented online spaces, and to far right milieus. . Yet their positions, activities, and connections ought not be underestimated, particularly considering the global antifeminist and anti-gender mobilizations of recent years. In this section we have merged anti-feminist and anti-gender actors and allies; we see the distinction between actors and allies as difficult to concretely employ with respect to the networks and connections characterizing the Danish context. Thus, the individuals and groups presented below are often both

agents and supporters of antifeminist or anti-gender positions, for instance, being concurrently user of antifeminist online community and member of antifeminist men's rights group. At the same time, we acknowledge the fact that some actors only limitedly, and often congruently to his/her position and tasks, focus on antifeminist or anti-gender issues.

The Centre for Digital Youth Care (CFDP) in their report on "The angry internet" (2020) estimates that there are about 850 Nordic unnamed users posting antifeminist content online on the four main platforms the report examines (Mogensen & Rand, 2020a, p. 30). The identity of the users is anonymized, and the number refers to the entire Scandinavian region; amongst these there are allegedly also several Danish users. These users belong to the transnational manosphere, which "is a term used to describe online forums opposing feminism, where men gather to discuss gender, equality, and masculinity with a pro-male focus" (Ibid., p. 35). In this section, we refer explicitly to the "Danish users on the manosphere" to underline that we are in fact dealing with a genuine transnational 'community' with English as its main language of communication. At the same time, we are aware of the existence of closed-forums online, where Danish content is posted primarily to a Danish/Scandinavian community. Our mapping below starts with the Danish users on the manosphere and continues widening out the picture including mainstream antifeminist and anti-gender actors, that is, public profiles affiliated to political parties and/or organizations/groups, or otherwise actively engaging publicly with the broader public opinion.

In our interview with Christian Mogensen (Interview 06-12-2022), an expert on the manosphere, he speaks of the manosphere as a forum mainly engaging young men and teenagers trying to find their place in society. Platforms such as YouTube, Facebook, Discord, Telegram, Reddit, Instagram, and Twitter (and we can also add TikTok) are giving young men a place to belong that they don't seem to find outside (Lorentzen, 2022). This longing for belonging is "a fundamental human motivation to engage in meaningful, enduring relationships" (Mogensen & Rand, 2020a, 18). For young men that do not seem to find where to belong, "the digital arenas are many and diverse, they provide the individual with a multitude of possibilities of fitting in, not constrained by physical proximity" (Ibid., p. 18).

Obviously, Danish actors on the manosphere are not easily traceable and identifiable. We only have guesstimate of how many Danish men are part of the manosphere. The actors that we can identify have been actively and recurrently engaging in the online communities. They have posted updates, made statements and comments related to specific Danish events, issues or incidents and for this reason they are more in the public eye. Uncovering how many users on the manosphere are based in Denmark becomes of course more and more difficult, the lesser their interactions with the forums. The paragraphs below start from those individuals with most frequent and contentious activity on the manosphere, moving then to the mainstream actors and allies.

A known antifeminist and anti-gender user on the manosphere is Jack Hou. Hou was active on various Pick-Up Artist platforms for several years. He became notorious for having sedated and raped two women, which he was sent to jail for in 2019 (Lorentzen, 2022). He is also one of the few Danish actors connected to the manosphere that, to our knowledge, has turned to gender-based violence in real life. Another case is an anonymous 27-year-old Danish man who was sentenced in 2022 for having planned school shootings in the Northern Jutland Region. His plans were prevented by police intervention and by the Center for Digital Youth Care monitoring work, which had followed him on various incel forums for several years.

On Youtube, Lars Kragh Andersen is perhaps the most prominent Danish antifeminist. Kragh Andersen harshly attacks feminism and promotes antifeminist views. YouTube is an interesting social media in this respect since the platform is non-anonymous and the content moderated, which provides less extreme content, but at the same time more widely accessible (CFDP, 2020, p. 57). Kragh Andersen's

videos are mainly in Danish, and he speaks predominately to a Danish audience. Yet, the English channels with content from profiles such as Jordan Peterson and Andrew Tate, are still the most widespread, particularly among Danish teens.

Amongst those who advance both antifeminist and anti-gender opinions, we also find Lennart Kiil, who was active particularly in the years 2010-2022. Lennart Kiil is a journalist and known for being the founder of the online newspaper [The People's Newspaper](#) (*Folkets Avis*) where he writes about anti-gender and anti-feminist themes. Kiil was responsible for the Facebook-page MANDFO, which he opened in 2012 as a direct provocation to [KVINFO](#), the Danish Center for Women and Gender Research. The webpage MANDFO, which the Facebook-page links up to, was part of the same project. However, both the web- and the [Facebook page](#) have been inactive since 2020. In 2014 and 2015, Lennart Kiil was also involved with the initiative of organizing political meetings for only men called MENday (*MANDdag*). MENday was founded by Jakob Coff, who was in the editorial board of The People's Newspaper at that time. Coff justified that only men could participate by maintaining that men and women are different "not just biologically and physically, but also in their interests" (Redox, 2014). Many of the participants are known for their antifeminist opinions, some belong to far right milieus.

Several of the active Danish antifeminist and anti-gender profiles are also members of established political parties. A 2014-15 survey-based study among Danish MPs shows that "the interplay between gender and party yields the remarkable result that *none* of the male MPs from the four right-wing parties believe that we still have problems of gender inequality in Danish society" (Dahlerup 2018, p. 197). Contrary to what we may assume, it is not only actors from the far right holding antifeminist and anti-gender positions, but also politicians from the mainstream parties. The paragraphs below introduce those Danish politicians who have been most vocal and influential in advancing an antifeminist and anti-gender agenda. In most cases their positions look as a personal crusade against feminism and gender equality right, while their party of reference officially holds to the reputational shield offered by the conformity to gender equality values and homosexual rights, as in the case of The Danish People's Party and the New Right (Nye Borgerlige). In other cases, it also truly represents an individual standing, going against the party ideological and policy positioning on gender issues.

Henrik Dahl from the party Liberal Alliance is among the most active and engaged profiles within the Danish antifeminist and anti-gender political scene. Dahl is renowned for his attacks against 'gender identity', 'genderism' and his harsh criticism of 'gender studies' and for having voted against the action plan against femicide (Lorentzen, 2022). Together with MP Morten Messerschmidt from The Danish People's Party, Dahl has repeatedly attacked feminists and particularly researchers within gender studies for being activists who conduct 'pseudo-science' on taxpayers' money. Messerschmidt and Dahl were the main promoters of the parliamentary motion calling on universities to avoid the "excessive activism in certain research environments" that was passed in the parliament on June 1, 2021.

Chris Bjerknæs, leader of The Danish People's Party's Youth in the years 2017-2020, also actively promoted and disseminated antifeminist opinions for several years. He authored a letter to the editor published in 2015 by the broadsheet *Politiken*, where he directly urges Danish men "to man themselves up". According to Bjerknæs, Danish men are losing their power, while women are overtaking it by means of their "long educations and loudmouth" (Thorup 2020, p. 54).

Anti-gender and antifeminist agenda is not only a territory for the populist and the far right. For instance, David Munk-Bogballe, a Conservative parliamentary candidate in the 2019 elections, avowed that 'we' should go back to a society where women stay at home and prioritize children and family as "that is natural, that is good, that is the result of biology and has been a cultural pattern for thousands

of years” (Thorup 2020, p. 61). The Social Democratic profile Simon Simonsen, member of the Copenhagen city council, has also on several different occasions voiced his antifeminist viewpoints. Together with Daniel Pinderup, Simonsen founded in 2020 The Men’s Council. Going against his own party, he has voiced critique of the public funding of artificial insemination with respect to single mothers, and in an infamous radio interview from 2019 he further explained his antifeminist position, arguing that “feminism is an antidemocratic movement” (Thorup 2020, p. 31).

In this regard, both The Men’s Council as well as the older and established The Association Dad (*Foreningen Far*) are men’s rights organizations with explicit antifeminist content and objectives. The Association Dad was founded already in 1977, with the aim of giving men more agency in fatherhood, especially after divorce. Today, the association actively supports The Men’s Council in their agenda for men’s rights and shares the belief that women (and mothers) have achieved too much power in today’s Denmark, jeopardizing the role of men but also their relationship with their children.

Within the extra-parliamentary far right we find the initiator of the party Hard Line (*Stram Kurs*), Rasmus Paludan. Besides his notorious and infamous anti-Islam rallies in Denmark and Sweden, Paludan also expresses antifeminist and anti-gender viewpoints and entertains close contact with antifeminist actors. Notably, one of those connections is with Kim Poulsen, formerly the party’s deputy chairman and one of the foreknown far right antifeminists in the Danish manosphere (Redox, 2017). Poulsen is the author of the blog *Polemiken* where he writes under the alias “*Kimpo*” and “*Kimporator*”. In his blogposts, Poulsen gives free wheel to his hatred against women and articulates his position by using statements such as: “Forget about love! All women are sluts”, or: “Can rape save the west? Women are opportunists who, without proper upbringing, do not care for the good of the community, but for their own benefit and needs” (Redox, 2017).

The Danish chapter of the far right organization Generation Identity (*Generation Identitær, GI*) launched in 2022 a campaign with the title: “There are only two sexes” and a direct attack on what they call “LGBT-ideology”. In connection to this campaign, Generation Identity made an action at the headquarter of the NGO Sex and Society (*Sex og Samfund*), where they put up posters and stickers at the entrance capturing “There are only two sexes” and “Stop the insanity” (Redox, 2022).

An organization that focuses on the same issue is the Danish Rainbow Council (*Dansk Regnbueråd*), founded in 2022 as an alternative LGB organization critical of the established LGBTQ+ groups, which is endorsed by The Danish Peoples Party and also avows that there are only two sexes. The latter case prompts mentioning that there is still very little research in Denmark on the risks of some critical radical feminists (or by their critics, TERF, Trans-Exclusionary Radical Feminist) to siding with the far right by legitimizing positions against trans- and non-binary people and the mischievous identity ideology of the “transgender”. Karen M. Larsen and the group Lesbian Feminists (*Lesbiske Feminister*) is among the few examples that can be quoted in this respect.

Finally, the antifeminist and anti-gender actors amongst religious organizations in Denmark needs mentioning. [The Right to Life](#) (*Retten til Liv*) is a group that works for “the right of the born and the unborn” and considers an embryo human from the very moment of conception. Right to Life is closed to Christian anti-abortion milieus, which are not very strong in Denmark but gained attention in 2023 in relation to the 50th year from the approval of the abortion right. Religious groups such as Jehovah’s Witnesses and Hizb ut-Tahrir are also strongly against feminism and gender. One of the most influential profiles within the religious milieus is Hans Ole Bækgaard, who is chairman of the church organization Inner Mission (*Indre Mission*) and has been involved in debates on gender equality and LGBTQ+ rights since at least 2010 where he, on his personal blog, accused women to be without honor and moral (Lorentzen 2022). Notably, Bækgaard and Inner Mission have also cooperated in 2018 with other Evangelical Christian organizations to denounce what they see as the ‘queer ideology’

disseminated by the media (Hansen, 2021, p. 61). This alliance was arranged in response to a speech held by former Liberal prime minister Lars Løkke Rasmussen (2015-2019), who at the 2018 Copenhagen Pride Parade avowed that LGBTQ+ persons ‘are Denmark’ (Hansen, 2021, p. 61) – an event that also related to the Danish government approving in the same year an LGBTQ+ action plan that was accepted by most of the parties across the political spectrum. Overall, the research on the role of religious organizations, and particularly the Evangelical-Lutheran Church of Denmark, in the development of Danish antifeminist and anti-gender positions within faith communities is limited and would need academic consideration. . It is known however that The Church of Denmark encompasses both liberal-progressive and traditional-conservative ministers, holding different positions towards same-sex marriages and female priests as colleagues.

4. Main themes and agenda

To see how concrete themes are exploited in the antifeminist and anti-gender agenda, the FIERCE project focuses on five main subject-driven policy areas. These are: (1) the labor market, (2) health & reproductive rights, (3) migration, (4) LGBTQ+ rights and (5) gender-based violence. The aim is to look closely at the way in which specific topics figure in the literature about anti-gender and antifeminism and whether some specific issues (or their bridging) trigger antifeminist and anti-gender mobilizations and actors’ alliances. The relevance of some issues can be both contextual and time sensitive; the collected sources indicate in fact that not all themes are given the same attention.

4.1. The labor market

There is a lack of research so far on anti-feminist and/or anti-gender actors approaches to the labor market. It remains to be examined further what exact role antifeminists have played so far in the continuous public debate on the equal pay gap that persists between different professions which are dominated by either men or women. This debate was reignited in 2021 with the nurses’ strike in July and August and the related feminist campaigns on the issue. Other studies available examine the reactions prompted by the #MeToo-movement amongst the public opinion and in Danish media and politics. In this regard, the labor market is thematized somehow indirectly, since the #MeToo mobilizations have led to heated discussions about the conditions in particular job sectors, such as news and entertainment, political and public administrations, as well as in higher education (Askanius & Hartley 2019; Skewes et al. 2020). Since #MeToo is a campaign about different forms of gender-based violence, we will outline and discuss the relevance of these studies in the section dealing with this thematic area.

4.2. Health and reproductive rights

Two main reports on the Danish manosphere directly mention reproduction within the nuclear heterosexual family as a life form that is perceived also within the Danish manosphere as a warranty against the decline of the fertility rate in the country and abroad. Relatedly, feminists play a key role in The Great Replacement conspiracy theory, stating that (white) Europeans will be wiped out by (Muslim) immigrants, whose birth-rates are higher than those of the natives (Cybernauterne & DareGender, 2020, p. 15). This conspiracy theory is widely disseminated throughout the manosphere, also by Danish users. One prominent example is far right and Islamophobic activist Rasmus Paludan, who participated in a demonstration against free abortion organized in 2018 by the Christian anti-abortion organization The Right to Life. Overall, it remains under researched how Danish users on the

manosphere approach issues such as health and reproductive rights and how questions like abortion, surrogate maternity, and assisted reproduction are today problematized by antifeminist and anti-gender actors.

4.3. Migration

Lars Hedegaard, the well-known Islam critic and former chairperson of the [Free Press Society](#) (*Trykkefrihedsselskabet*), said during an interview in 2010: “Muslim men rape their own children. You hear it all the time. Girls in Muslim families are raped by their uncles, their cousins, their fathers” (Keskinen 2012, p. 266). His words were widely criticized and Hedegaard was reported for racist speech. Yet, these declarations are far from exceptional in Denmark. Others before him made use of similar understandings of Islam and Muslims, amongst them members of the far right. There is also a rich literature considering the appropriation of gender by the radical and populist right, serving the purpose to stigmatize Islam and the Muslim communities (Siim & Meret, 2016). Since the 2000’s, and throughout the 2010s, Muslims have become the object of intense critique for not living up to Western standards of gender equality. According to Suvi Keskinen (2012), Danish public debate has been influenced by a “racialized politics of gendered violence” that frames Muslim immigrants as the primary cause of concern about not only gender-based violence, but gender inequality as such.

As Marie Leine, Henrik Hvenegaard Mikkelsen & Atreyee Sen underline in their article “Danish women put with less: Gender equality and the politics of denial in Denmark from 2020”, this racialized politics is closely connected to a gender and sexual exceptionalism that posits Denmark as a country that has already achieved gender equality (Leine et al., 2020, p. 191). In this regard, Muslims are perceived as not complying with gender equality norms and values; the more Danish society is posited as being a gender equality model within the European context, the stronger the narrative. Gender and sexual exceptionalism are not necessarily and directly related to the antifeminist and anti-gender agenda, yet the narrative of the supposedly unique Nordic ‘gender regime’ is at times appropriated by antifeminists and by the far right. Their argument builds on feminist emancipation as an accomplished struggle. This creates a point of juncture between different actors, allowing also for frames that bridge gender inequality with non-Western (particularly Muslim) culture (see Christensen & Siim 2010).

In an interview from 2012, scientist and pundit Karin Helweg-Larsen issued a warning to “Danish girls”. According to Helweg-Larsen, they should be careful when they engaged with foreigners from “other cultures”, who interpret their way to behave differently than Danish men. As an example, she mentions that a girl could easily sleep safely on the couch of a Danish male friend, but if she did so with a man from another country, it would be interpreted as an invitation to have sex together (Ibid., p. 190). Additionally, the media coverage of the events in Cologne during New Year’s Eve in 2015-16 was widely reported as a proof of the culturally imported ‘Muslim sex-game’ called *taharrush gamea*, where large groups of men would harass women (e.g., ‘Taharrush gamea’, 2016). This led influential politicians and commentators to question whether Danish women could move around in the night life without being accompanied by a Danish-native male friend protecting her against potential attacks by young Muslim men.

However, there is still little research disclosing the connection between the far right and the antifeminist and the anti-gender milieus, besides the reports on Danish users of the manosphere where it has been shown that migration issues and antifeminism can overlap.

4.4. LGBTQ+ rights

Compared to other countries, the wave of anti-gender campaigns and protests across Europe against 'gender ideology' has seemingly been less vocal in Denmark. Homosexual rights have been accepted by most of the mainstream parties across the political spectrum. Former Prime Minister Lars Løkke Rasmussen publicly [declared](#) at the 2018 Copenhagen Pride Parade that LGBTQ+ persons "are Denmark". Scholars such as Malte Breiding Hansen (Hansen, 2021, p. 65) argue that such a discourse can be considered as an example of what can be characterized as "homonationalism" (Puar, 2013), since advocating for LGBTQ rights and in particular for homosexuals' rights becomes coupled to a nationalist agenda. Thereby the Danish nation is portrayed as a frontrunner of liberal-mindedness, tolerance, trust, and for legislative improvements taken to safeguard LGBTQ+ people, for instance referring to the piece of legislation that in 2017 ended the praxis of diagnosing transgender people as people with a mental illness.

Two main strategies, that may seem to contradict each other, are used by anti-gender actors in Denmark. The first strategy focuses on the interpretation that the growing focus on LGBTQ+ rights is an expression of an excessive individualism that dissolves traditional gender identities, as well as what are considered the "natural" and biologically-determined heterosexual relations between man and woman. This is a strategy that particularly religious associations and conservative-traditionalist debaters follow. For instance, Hans Ole Bækgaard, chairman of the Christian Free Church Inner Mission (*Indre Mission*) criticized what he calls the "queer ideology" for being "norm disintegrating" and "socially disintegrating" (Hansen, 2021, p. 68). The second strategy focuses on the imposition of a new societal order associated with terms such as 'political correctness', 'identity politics' and 'wokeness'/wokeism'. The term 'gender ideology' (*kønsideologi*) is rarely used in public debates, since in Danish there is no word for gender as such. Yet, the 'identity politics' definition is used particularly in relation to LGBTQ+ rights to refer to a perceived movement in society that works to establish a new and problematic 'dictature of the minorities' (also other than gender), where gender is socially constructed. This trickles down to politics, education, and family life.

Religious actors also play a role in Danish anti-gender campaigns. In the article titled "Between Two Ills: Homonationalism, Gender Ideology and the Case of Denmark from 2021" Malte Breiding Hansen reconstructs the anti-gender campaign spearheaded by a network of Christian independent organizations, which was triggered as a reaction to the previously mentioned Lars Løkke Rasmussen's speech. In the second half of 2018, various representatives of three of the Evangelical churches publicly denounced the prime minister's support to the LGBTQ+ community and the way the former PM dismissed the "stock-conservative and outdated views of human nature" (Hansen 2021, p. 61). The religious communities' campaigning consisted of a series of opinion pieces as well as TV and radio appearances. The argument did not only warn against the tolerance and accept of gender identities and sexual orientations that would dissolve the natural difference between men and women. It was also argued that Lars Løkke Rasmussen implicitly excluded religion from being part of the Danish national community by identifying Danish-ness with LGBTQ people. Doing so, these communities represented themselves in opposition to LGBTQ people, and as the new marginalized and threatened minority in the new order.

LGBTQ+ rights and particularly transgender rights are mostly the object of critique, scorn and attacks on the manosphere. The earlier mentioned report "The angry internet: A threat to gender equality, democracy and well-being" estimates there are about 850 Nordic users on Twitter, Reddit and 4chan who publish misogynistic and antifeminist content on these platforms (Mogensen & Rand, 2020a, p. 8). Amongst them there are likely hundreds of Danish users. Part of the ideology that can be said to define the manosphere is gender essentialism, which posits men and women as not only completely

different, but also as the two parts of a binary relation that necessarily exclude third parties such as transgender and queer people. This means that although the focus is primarily on women within online communities such as incel-forums and sites for MGTOWs (“Men Going Their Own Way”), there is often an expressed antipathy, if not hate, against anyone who, at least deliberately, does not follow assigned gender norms.

In the national report titled “Under influence: Paths into extreme digital communities” (2020), the research collective *Cybernauterne* and the NGO DareGender emphasize that both hyperfeminine and hypermasculine ideals of gender expression are used to demonize and ridicule other ways to express gender and sexuality. The report is based on the collection of approximately 12 million comments on Youtube, Discord, Facebook, Instagram, and Telegram and on a series of interviews with young Danish men, who have previously frequented and interacted with the manosphere. According to one of the interview persons, transgender people and queers were the main target of hate in the Facebook-groups that he frequented (*Cybernauterne & DareGender, 2020, p. 16*). In contrast to this, women can in principle fit into their ideal societal order by following stereotypical norms as well as roles such as what is perceived and idealized as a traditional wife, the so-called ‘trad-wife’.

Yet, the relationship between the mainstream public debate about LGBTQ+-rights and the manosphere in the Danish context remains unexplored. An exception is the podcast by *Cybernauterne* titled “Cybernorms” (*Cybernormer*), published in 2020 in connection to the report. Amongst other things, the podcast discusses how the manosphere relates to Danish society in general and mentions at least one example where a critique of LGBTQ+-rights by a Danish politician seems to connect with the Danish manosphere. The background for this is the Danish media coverage in 2021-22 of the young American transgender Lia Thomas, who won a prestigious swim competition. This led several radical and right-wing debaters to denounce it as unfair play and as an expression of a broader and worrisome international trend, where society is giving in to LGBTQ+ demands. Conservative MP Rasmus Jarlov, commented this as an example of “wokeism” driving the world into an “absurd theater”, where men and women were no longer biologically defined anymore. Along the same lines, Liberal MP Mads Fuglede posted a joke on social media as a comment to Lia Thomas’ case stating that “a motorbiker identifying as a biker wins yet another race”. Fuglede acknowledged that this was not his own joke, but he could not recollect where he saw it first. *Cybernauterne* claim that this joke derives from the meme “I sexually identify with an attack helicopter”, which began spreading on the social platform Reddit in 2014. This Meme is often used in the manosphere to ridicule how transgender people identify themselves. That is, even though there is a difference in the vehicle of transportation, the underlying logic and gender-essentialism remains the same. You cannot identify with something completely different from what you are. It is difficult to tell whether and how Danish politicians get influenced by the manosphere and likely the influence goes in both directions, in the sense that Danish users on the manosphere are also influenced by mainstream public debate. Thereby mainstream media and politics provide the manosphere with content on questions regarding LGBTQ+ rights.

4.5. Gender-based violence

Like other countries, the Danish debate was directly affected by the #MeToo international mobilizations that started in 2017. Prior to this the public and political attention towards GBV and sexual harassment was comparatively little and perhaps also influenced by the opinion (and conviction) that gender equality is been achieved in the country (Dahlerup, 2018). This fed the antifeminist mill with a narrative that builds upon a critique of feminist struggles in today’s Denmark for being unwarranted, failing to focus on issues such as the submission of women under Islam (Stormhøj, 2020).

Marie Leine, Henrik Hvenegaard Mikkelsen and Atréyee Senargue for instance that Danish mainstream media in the 2010s and today produce and enforce a “politics of denial” which results in the “invisibilization of Danish male violence” (Leine et al., 2020). The authors focus on the public debate about a controversial report issued by the European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights that ranked Denmark, in 2014, as the country in the European Union with the highest occurrence of male GBV against women. This report was characterized in Danish mainstream media as both “grotesque” and “misguided” (Ibid. p. 182). The article quotes former senior researcher at the Danish National Institute for Social Research, Karin Helweg-Larsen, who explained the overrepresentation of violence reports as the effect of Danish women’s oversensitivity (Ibid., p. 182). This study did not lead to any significant public debate. Ever since the emergence of the #MeToo movement in 2017, and particularly after the tragic and macabre murder of Mia Skadhauge Stevn in 2022, there has been a [renewed mobilization and political focus on violence against women](#), most notably resulting in a new action plan in 2022 on partner violence and partner murder proposed by the Social Democratic-led government with the support of other parties.

Tina Askanus & Jannie Møller Hartley show through a comparative analysis in their article “Framing Gender Justice: A comparative analysis of the media coverage of #metoo in Denmark and Sweden” (2019) that the spreading of #MeToo as a hashtag from 2017 changed Danish society but compared to Sweden, it led to considerable backlash as shown by a 2018 opinion poll (Askanus & Hartley, 2019, p. 20). The media coverage was also much less extensive in Denmark than in Sweden. The total number of Danish newspaper articles on #MeToo was even less than a fifth of Swedish articles when the movement arose in October 2017. In the Danish public debate, the critique of #MeToo has been a trigger to a broader critique of feminism, indulging on explanations that both sexism and feminism have ‘gone too far’. This stands clearly out in the Danish portrayal of Sweden as a worst-case scenario, with the use of rhetorical characterizations of Sweden as a “feminist dictatorship” and “totalitarian feminism” (Ibid., 29). The so-called second (domestic) wave of #MeToo in Denmark that was triggered in 2020 contributed to mitigate the critical gaze, particularly in the mainstream media. Yet the #MeToo account as the “witch-hunt against men” still thrives amongst antifeminist actors.

In the article “Attitudes to Sexism and the #MeToo Movement at a Danish University from 2021”, Lea Skewes, Joshua C. Skewes and Michelle K. Ryan detect several arguments of skepticism against #MeToo in the Danish context (Skewes et al., 2021). These range from the direct questioning of the magnitude of sexual harassment cases reported to insinuations that the phenomenon is overestimated because of the false accusations (Skewes et al. 2021). It is, however, still mainly within the manosphere where GBV is explicitly condoned and at times also encouraged.

The manosphere puts emphasis on the antagonistic relation between men and women, which implies that one sex must necessarily dominate the other. A Danish user on 4chan is reported to have posted: “...women evolved to be controlled by men and to be followers. Allowing them to lead was opening pandoras box” (Mogensen & Rand, 2020b, p. 30). GBV is described as the necessary tool (when not a praiseworthy method) of controlling women; this to avert chaos and instability as a consequence of the unstable relation between the two sexes. Physical violence is not always considered the main measure; men can rely on psychological manipulation, for instance in the form of what is called “negging”, that is, the deliberate attempt to undermine a woman’s confidence. Different forms of psychological manipulation are listed by the so-called Pick-Up Artists, or ‘PUAs’, a part of the manosphere that exchanges skills for seduction (Ibid., p. 50).

Another example of the legitimization of GBV is the misogynistic content on Danish closed Facebook-groups, which the liberal progressive newspaper *Politiken* uncovered in 2021. One of these groups counted more than 10.000 members. Part of the shared content consists of memes that turn GBV into

a humoristic, light topic. For Maia Kahlke Lorentzen from *Cybernauterne*, this content is indicative of a “culture of rape” that condones, at least to some extent, rape, violence, and femicide committed by men. One of these memes shows for example a crying woman along with the capturing: “What do you do after you have raped a deaf-mute? Break her fingers so she does not tell anyone.” Another shows a cartoon with a person making a hole in the ground and the text: “When she says: “choke me daddy” and you get a little carried away”. Although there is no research on the spillover in Denmark from such groups to GBV in society, nonetheless there is an indication of the attempt to belittle discussions about violence against women. Scholar Mira C. Skadegård claims that such groups at the very least contribute to heighten the fear that Danish women have of being sexually assaulted by men (Henningsen, 2021).

There are also examples showing the spillover effect from the manosphere into ‘real life’. In 2020, a 27-year-old Dane was arrested for planning mass shootings at local schools where women would be the main target. The man had for years engaged with and posted content in the manosphere, declaring that his hatred towards women was eating him up and that he particularly disliked seeing young female students. A mapping conducted by The Association of Digital Responsibility (Foreningen Digital Ansvar) and the Danish Broadcasting Corporation, DR, uncovered nearly 6.000 posts made by him.

4.6. Gender and gender studies: The attacks on academic freedom

Gender studies, together with critical race and colonial studies, have become target of more and more intensive criticism by Danish right-wing pundits and politicians. The criticism builds on the belief that ‘identity politics’ and ‘wokeness’ have become the ‘new normal’ in large parts of society and particularly within gender, race, and postcolonial studies in academia. In 2020 a wave of criticism was triggered by the deliberate and public attacks on specific research centers and researchers launched by MP Morten Messerschmidt, now leader of the Danish People’s Party, and MP Henrik Dahl, member of the right-wing party Liberal Alliance. These were picked up and further ignited by right-wing debaters and pundits from the columns of newspapers such as *Jyllands Posten*. A resolution was proposed by the two politicians and passed by the Parliament in May 2021. The resolution warned explicitly of an “excessive activism in certain research environments” (Meret, 2021).

Scholars Mathias Danbolt and Cecilie Ullerup Schmidt argue that this critique against an ‘excessively activist’ gender studies’ milieu in Denmark, articulated also as a scholarly environment characterized by comparatively lower academic standards, such as norms of objectivity connects to a broader antifeminist and anti-gender agenda. The type of “feminist” and “left-wing activism” that gender studies have been accused to encourage is seen, with the words of Morten Messerschmidt, as “hatred to and doubt about our societal structures” that flourishes undercover of research freedom (Danbolt & Schmidt, 2021, p. 57). The logic beneath builds on the Danish gender and sexual exceptionalism that Messerschmidt and others argue for. Most of these attacks against gender and gender ideology started in 2021 and the research on the role played by this topic within the broader antifeminist agendas, as well as the connections of these attacks to other thematic areas, is still insufficiently researched.

5. Repertoires of action (strategies)

The repertoires of action in a Danish context are highly dependent on the position and resources available to the different antifeminist and anti-gender actors. It certainly makes a difference whether it is an activist online or a prominent representative of a party with easier access to media and to

public opinion. For Danish users on the manosphere, the opportunities and strategies are limited to online engagement and to the community of like-minded connected by virtue of antifeminist, misogynistic worldviews. The research available points to these two types of antifeminist repertoires of action, that is: on the one hand, right-wing debaters/pundits and politicians who strive to influence the political agenda (and the public opinion) via mainstream media and, on the other hand, the mobilizations primarily triggered by internet users, who often express and share their antifeminist and anti-gender views in specific fora. In this sense, antifeminism and anti-gender communication in Denmark takes places through both formal and less formal channels.

The type of action that goes through mainstream media has been quite effective in pushing the boundaries of what are conceived as legitimate and ‘tolerable’ opinions in Danish public debate. This is how Suvi Keskinen reads Lars Hedegaard’s infamous statements on how ‘Muslim men rape their girls’ and Mathias Danbolt and Cecilie Ullerup Schmidt’s understand the recent attacks on gender studies (Keskinen, 2012; Danbolt & Schmidt, 2021). Some, like Lars Hedegaard and Rasmus Paludan, have been heavily criticized for their statements, racist views, and confrontational performances. And yet they have contributed to push the threshold of what is perceived as the difference between legitimate critique and hatred towards groups such as women and Muslims. Prominent politicians and public debaters have also been effective in marginalizing the criticism coming from feminists by emphasizing Danish gender and sexual exceptionalism (Leine et. al., 2020, 190-91). This strategy has also been employed in the debate about the #MeToo mobilizations. A case in point was the dismissal of the results evidenced by [the 2014 report of the European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights](#). Antifeminists have worked not only to discredit the report itself, but also to prevent the rise of further critique and debate on GBV and sexual harassment.

The action repertoires that primarily take place online are not so much about engaging in and with the public opinion, but rather to attract supporters and to create a community of “brotherhood” and like-minded people. This strategy can also be effective, particularly among the younger generation of “angry white men” (Kimmel, 2017). The previously mentioned 2020 report on the ‘angry internet’ maintains that it is in fact particularly among students in secondary education, but also among the younger cohorts, that misogynistic phrases, anti-gender, and transphobic positions find a receptive audience (Mogensen & Rand 2020a, p. 18).

Nowadays mainstream public debate increasingly takes place online. In this regard, there is also a grey area between the closed community groups of the manosphere and the open debate unfolding on Facebook, Instagram, Twitter and Tik Tok by political parties, bloggers, and debaters. An algorithmic analysis by the research institute *Analyse & Tal* published in 2021 shows that more than 5 pct. of the 63 million comments they scraped from the Facebook-pages of Danish mainstream media and politicians were “verbal attacks” (Analyse & Tal, 2021, p. 7). Muslims were the most targeted group with 25 pct. of the total number of attacks. Women came in second place with more than 13 pct. while sexual and gender minorities constituted about 2 pct. of the targeted groups (Ibid., p. 58). The period covered is only just above two years (2019-21), which presumably means that several hundred thousand Facebook comments which verbally attack or abuse women and ethnic, sexual and gender minorities are published every year on the Danish Facebook pages of mainstream politicians.

The manosphere also shows that the mobilization of the community of like-minded engages a considerable number of antifeminist and anti-gender actors. As *Cybernauterne* and DareGender highlight in their interviews with former users navigating on the manosphere, their main experience is belonging to a community that resists against ‘political correctness’ as well as against the feminization and thereby the dissolution of the Western societies. But as one of the former users told them, there is ironically also an extensive “social control” of what are acceptable opinions within the

manosphere, particularly against those who raise critique (Cybernauterne & DareGender, 2020, p. 27). This makes these communities particularly resistant towards debates with outsiders if they ever engage with people who do not already share their worldview. In this regard, *Cybernauterne* and DareGender speak metaphorically of the manosphere as a “rabbit hole”, partly detached from the rest of society and from where it is difficult to return.

6. Frames of arguments

Based on the literature, it is possible to distinguish between four dominant frames of arguments amongst Danish antifeminist and anti-gender actors. These can be characterized as follows:

6.1. ‘We already have gender equality’

One of the main reasons why feminism as a concept has almost disappeared from mainstream political lingo is that gender equality is framed as an already achieved goal through politics and the welfare state. There are equal opportunities on the Danish labour market, and now also two female prime ministers for the history record. Even care and domestic work have become gender equal domains, and LGBTQ+ rights as well. If we doubt any of this, as Karin Helweg-Larsen puts it (Leine et al., 2020, p. 187), we risk losing “the great trust that is the foundation for our society”. Since gender equality is perceived as an accomplished goal, the feminist critique is considered a hidden agenda that takes attention away from major problems such as immigration, Islam, and the refugees.

6.2. ‘There are only two sexes’

LGBT+ rights are by many cherished as a component defining Danish gender and sexual exceptionalism, and yet they are also criticized for contributing to the ‘false’ belief that gender identity is not just the same as belonging to one of two sexes. In mainstream public debate, the advancement of such gender essentialism addresses questions of transgender and gender fluidity. However, the Danish users on the manosphere as well as far right groups such as Generation Identity still ascribe to norms of hypermasculinity, which imply that ‘real’ men only desire women, as well as to the distinction between heterosexual women and lesbians or bisexuals.

6.3. ‘Feminists want women in power’

In the Danish backlash against the #MeToo movement, #MeToo is described as a continuing series of smear campaigns where women are “ganging up” innocent men in ‘witch hunts’ and ‘kangaroo courts’ (Askanius & Hartley, 2019, p. 29). In the manosphere, as previously mentioned, this relates to conspiracy theories about women in Western society planning to rule over men. In a milder version, a similar narrative is found at times on mainstream media, delivered in the version of the career women, who with their high educational level and well-paid jobs have ‘feminized’ society. Chris Bjerknæs, a member of the Danish People’s Party Youth, wrote in 2015 that Danish men today risk becoming a “whole generation of men who are sperm donors and goes to single parties in the province” (Thorup, 2021, p. 54). From this perspective, there is an ongoing struggle for power between men and women and the only way out for men is to take back control.

6.4. 'Feminism is identity politics'

Feminism and LGBTQ+ rights are increasingly associated with 'identity politics' and 'political correctness'. These terms connote a new order in society that is changing the natural and biologically determined relationship between men and women. Political correctness is limiting freedom of speech and expression, setting limits to what can be said, for instance on gender minorities. According to Marker and Hendricks (2019) the amplified reactions towards trivial events and episodes such as [the "gender-neutral traffic lights" proposal that was allegedly being proposed by council members of two of the largest municipalities](#), are part of a repeating pattern that firstly sees the reaction of outraged MPs and next the mainstream media picking up such stories uncritically. The story of the gender-neutral traffic-lights also went viral and was exclusively used to show the "madness of identity politics." (Marker & Hendricks, 2019, p. 133).

7. Transnational connections

The transnational connections, network and funding sources of the Danish antifeminist and anti-gender actors are still an under researched field. Yet, there are several ideological and discursive overlaps between the Danish and the international anti-feminist and anti-gender mobilizations. Malte Breiding Hansen compares for instance the 2018 Evangelical Christian campaign against 'queer ideology' with the right-wing discourse against 'gender ideology' originally launched by the Vatican, which became widespread across Europe and beyond (Hansen, 2021, p. 61). But the Danish gender regime is often analyzed in contrast rather than in connection to other countries; this also within the Nordic region. The Danish gender regime has been framed in terms of gender exceptionalism, and as such rarely compared to other contexts, or investigated in the light of the possible influence exerted by transnational connections and influence.

An exception to this is perhaps the Danish anti-abortion association The Right to Life (*Retten til Liv*), which is part of the "One of Us Federation" that counts about 40 members in countries across Europe. The overall influence and the financial funding of One of Us is described in the report "The Tip of the Iceberg: Religious Extremist Funders against Human Rights for Sexuality and Reproductive Health in Europe, 2009-2018" published by the European Parliamentary Forum for Sexual and Reproductive Rights (Datta, 2021, p. 34), but not with a specific focus on the Danish association. However, the anti-abortion cause plays a marginal role in the Danish political and public debate about abortion rights, recently rekindled by the proposal to [increase the deadline for legal abortion](#) from 12 to 18 weeks .

Transnational connections are in many respects inherent to the online antifeminist and anti-gender mobilization and propaganda and the Danish users on the manosphere are known to interact online with users outside Denmark. Maia Kahlke Lorentzen from the collective Cybernauterne in the podcast Cybernormer ("Cybernorms") argues that antifeminists such as Jordan Peterson and Andrew Tate although speaking from another context also reach out to users in Denmark and instill the conviction that issues are global rather than only local or national. Additionally, users in Denmark interact on platforms such as 4chan, 8chan and Reddit without specifically and actively reaching out for other Danish users. There are exceptions to this, such as the Danish influencer Lars Kragh Andersen, who mainly communicates in Danish about a Danish context.

8. Explanations of the anti-gender and antifeminist backlash

The available literature provides mainly three types of explanations for the anti-gender and antifeminist backlash in Denmark; socio-psychological, cultural and political explanations. Regarding

the first type of explanation, the reports on the Danish manosphere and its users suggest a socio-psychological framework of interpretation in which the hatred against women and the misogynist as well as antifeminist opinions are the product of “vulnerable” and “angry” young men who find an answer to their unhappiness in the idea of an inherently agonistic relationship between men and women, within a society that increasingly privileges the latter. Additionally, perceived, or real exclusion from the community of peers and of acknowledgement within the communities at school, at home or on the working place are considered among the individual triggers (Mogensen & Rand, 2020b, p. 6). Within this framework, the popularity of the manosphere is connected to widespread social and identity problems of some of the Danish young (white) males. Digital anonymity is also interpreted to some degree as a form of incentive for online socialization, it being “less risky and vulnerable” than offline contexts, where rejections are most often clearly visible (Mogensen & Rand, 2020a, p. 18). Thorup complements this explanatory framework by claiming that we cannot understand modern hatred of women and minorities without considering the role that education and unemployment play as fuels that can trigger such hatred. Also, the widespread opinion that women are performing better than men and are now outpacing them in the educational and working sectors provide these networks of online men’s communities with discursive ammunitions against women and with antifeminist and sexist beliefs.

As to the second type of explanation that focuses more broadly on Danish political culture and history, gender and sexual exceptionalism are also among the mentioned explanatory factors to antifeminist and anti-gender backlash. Somehow paradoxically, the tendency to emphasize the Scandinavian welfare and gender regimes and praise the Nordic region as an international frontrunner, not only on gender equality policy but also, for instance, in the green transition, has backlashed on the effectiveness of the feminist critique and on further achievements through the representation of gender equality as an accomplished goal in the country. In this regard, Denmark is also characterized as the “libertarian of the north” by Tina Askanus and Janni Møller Hartley, in the sense that individual freedoms are stressed as highly important in public debates, which partly explains why #MeToo has been widely perceived as an infringement on individual freedom amongst Danes (Askanus & Hartley, 2019, p. 31). This relates to the recurring critique of feminism as ‘identity politics’, which is framed as an illegitimate imposition of new regulations and restrictions on behavior.

Regarding the third type of explanation focused on politics and the turn, towards the populist right witnessed in Danish politics since 2001 has had an influence on how the mainstream public debate today relates to issues such as gender, ethnicity, identity, race, and religion. The recent attacks on gender studies are also paradigmatic of the shift towards specific areas of research and towards what is (negatively) understood as the activist engagement in academia. Also, the defense of the traditional family and the conservative emphasis on a biologically based gender essentialism that radical right-wing populist politicians, public debaters and bloggers stand for can better be understood within the context of the so-called “system shift” that took place in the 2000s, when the Danish People’s Party became an important player in Danish politics. However, in a Danish context the arguments provided for gender essentialism, that there are only two sexes as a biological fact, are most often scientifically rather than religiously framed. Views on gender and family make traction also among religious organizations, for example the Evangelical church and some of its chapters.

Mainstream media have also played a significant role in contributing to these developments in Danish politics. Intense criticism of feminist views and ‘queer ideology’ is often instigated by media platforms, with the coverage of local events and cases and their amplification. According to Marker and Hendricks (2019), this is inherently connected to the “attention economy” cycle of society, in which the mainstream media remains at the center. This means that “identity-politics bubbles” are often created

with the deliberate purpose of attracting and engaging the limited attention of media consumers today (Ibid., 128). In this sense, Danish media do not just cover such events. They actively generate, amplify, and circulate them, influencing the public opinion.

9. Counter-movements

Antifeminist and anti-gender mobilizations are quite clearly not given as much attention amongst feminist actors in Denmark as the other way around. Based on the available literature, the counter-reactions to anti-feminist and anti-gender mobilizations in Denmark are still fragmented and rather unstructured. However, there are some reactions to antifeminism and anti-gender mobilizations that might develop into countermovement activity. Most noticeable, associations such as the Center for Digital Youth Care, Cybernauterne and DareGender have put substantial and targeted critical focus on developments within the manosphere, for example, with report publications, research and media engagement. The aim of these groups and communities is to highlight, publicly discuss and expose what happens within the more or less closed antifeminist sites and platforms on the internet. The Center for Digital Youth Care works, for instance, on education and dialogue with male teenagers who are at higher risk of being appealed to via online antifeminist content. The Centre cooperates with municipalities and relevant educational institutions on different projects. It also seeks to inform parents about sites and platforms where antifeminist content and extremist views are disseminated.

Amongst civil society actors, men's organizations with an outwardly feminist profile such as The Danish Men's Society have now been launched. These organizations maintain that their purpose is to safeguard men's rights even though they have a different approach to this than antifeminist organizations such as The Men's Council. The Danish Men's Society argues explicitly that it is both possible and meaningful to work for men's rights and still maintain a feminist approach. Yet, there is a lack of knowledge about the organizations, interrelations, and the tensions between men's rights groups in Denmark, likely so because these groups have only become active in recent years. Similarly for the counter reactions from LGBTQ+ communities and organizations in Denmark, which have not been so visible in their responses to anti-gender activism.

Finally, it is possible that some of the recent feminist mobilizations have arisen as a reaction to antifeminist and anti-gender positions and developments in Danish society. The so-called 'second wave' of the #MeToo mobilizations started in 2020. One reason for the sudden increase in attention towards sexual harassment, as well as other forms of gender-based violence, might have been triggered by the harsh critique and the strategy of dismissal pursued by some influential debaters and politicians in the years 2017 to 2020. Similarly, minority women's organizations' critical focus on the ways in which minority women are portrayed in Danish media and in the public debate is presumably also a reaction to the racialization of gender issues, represented as a problem within the Muslim communities. However, it is difficult to draw a direct causality chain between the recent feminist mobilization and the developments within the Danish antifeminist and anti-gender sphere.

10. Conclusion

The main findings of this mapping of the anti-feminist and anti-gender literature in Denmark contribute to disclose the role played by three main areas: 1) The manosphere, 2) the public debate and 3) the mainstream media. The studies on Danish users in the manosphere show, for instance, that users are influenced by and contribute to generate as well as disseminate extreme antifeminist and anti-gender worldviews on sites such as Twitter, Reddit, 4chan and Facebook. However, whether the

numbers of Danish users and their role in the manosphere have increased throughout the period from 2010 to 2022 has not yet been sufficiently researched. The public debate has been strongly influenced by politicians, public opinion makers and debaters who argue that feminism 'goes too far,' since Denmark already achieved gender equality by means of equal opportunities. This position also relates to the backlash on #MeToo and the attacks against 'identity politics' that are further fueled by the media coverage and have become part of the mainstream media agenda.

The debates about particularly LGBTQ+ rights, but also gender studies, men's rights and gender-based violence, have become more and more intense since the late 2010s and seem to have escalated in recent years, also prompted partly by discussions in other parts of Europe (Meret, 2021) and beyond. The implications of these developments on the debates about gender inequality within Islam remain to be seen. Similarly, there is a lack of research on the positions characterizing the various religious denominations, whether Christian or Muslim. This also reflects the widespread opinion that religious organizations and groups are generally less influential in Danish politics and society, particularly with respect to gender equality and compared to other European countries. Fact is that we know still very little about the networks and activity between Christian free churches and religious organizations and antifeminist milieus. Finally, some thematic areas are still only superficially covered by the literature, for instance the labor market as well as health and reproductive rights. Whether this at least partly reflects that there has not been as much mobilization related to these thematic areas remains to be studied.

All in all, the available literature on the antifeminist and anti-gender movement in Denmark is not yet able to provide a comprehensive overview that allows to clearly map the web of connections, interrelations and influences among the different actors. In this sense, it remains to be explored how specific antifeminist and anti-gender actors such as men's rights groups, populist and far right politicians, bloggers and pundits interact organizationally, ideologically, and discursively. Just as there is a variety of actors, there must also be several bridging strategies and frames amongst these. Some of these frames have been the object of analysis within the extant literature; yet the ways in which strategies and frames overlap, actors interact and resources support and strengthen these milieus remain to be more carefully investigated.

11. Appendix A - Antifeminism and anti-gender timeline (Denmark)

12. Appendix B - List of anti-gender and antifeminist organizations and initiatives

Name of the organization (original)	Name of the organization (English)	Antigender or antifeminist ?	Logo of the organization	Head of the organization (in the period 2010-2021)	Web-page (social media)	Size of the organization (if available)	Comment (brief description)
Manderådet	The Men's Council	Antifeminist		Simon Simonsen	Web: http://manderaadet.dk FB: https://facebook.com/manderaadet Twitter: https://twitter.com/manderaadet Instagram: https://instagram.com/manderaadet Youtube: https://youtube.com/channel/UCRO2Uc_RZW9iJGgW5wBILp_w	n/a	Organization established in 2020 with a focus on "men's and boys' gender equality" and a critical position on feminism.
Ligestillingsdebat	Gender Equality Debate	Antifeminist		Daniel Holst Pinderup	Facebook: Ligestillingsdebat Facebook	n/a	Association founded in 2020 by Rikke Helene Nielsen and Daniel Holst Pinderup but mainly driven by Pinderup who has also been active in Manderådet and is now active in the political party New Right (<i>Nye Borgelige</i>). The association mainly runs a

							podcast on issues relating to gender equality.
Foreningen Far	The Association Father	Antifeminist		Claes Ludvigsen (2010-11), Jesper Lohse (2011-)	Web: Forside (foreningenfar.dk) Facebook: Foreningen Far Facebook Twitter: @ForeningenFar / Twitter	n/a	A sort of interest organization for fathers and their relations to their own children. They are often accused of being too aggressive in their involvement with divorce cases and their criticism of women's organizations.
Dansk Ligestilling	Danish Gender Equality	Both antifeminist and anti-gender		Karen West	Web: https://danskligestilling.dk/ Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/danskligestilling	n/a	Organization established in 2020 based on the claim that we already have gender equality in Denmark and that feminists as well as 'identity politics' are

							working against this.
Reelligestilling.dk	Realequality.dk	Antifeminist	No logo	Tobias Petersen	Web: https://reelligestilling.dk/ Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/reelligestilling	n/a	Personal blog established in 2014 as an "alternative to the feminist approach to gender and equality" and highly critical of feminism today. Presumably widely read – at least it is updated regularly.
MANFO	MANFO	Antifeminist		Lennart Kiil	Web: https://manfo.dk (not available any longer) Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/www.manfo.dk/	n/a	Initiative created in 2012 as a public platform almost exclusively run by Lennart Kiil to espouse criticism of contemporary feminism. Its main 'enemy' was KVINFO (hence the name). The platform is no longer active (FB-posts)

							stopped in 2020). Instead, Lennart Kiil posts regular content on his website "Folkets Avis" (folkets.dk) with occasionally antifeminist claims.
Manddag	Menday ("Men" + "Monday")	Antifeminist		Jakob Coff	Web: https://manddag.dk (not available any longer) Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/MANDDAG/	n/a	Initiative founded by Jakob Coff in 2014 with only men meeting together to discuss political issues "rationally" and with a community about being men. The political issues have most often not been about gender or feminism, but Coff has made public antifeminist statements. The meetings (at least the

							public ones) ended in 2015.
Dansk Regnbueråd	Danish Rainbow Council	Anti-gender		Marcus Dib Jensen	Web: https://danskregnbueraad.dk Facebook: Dansk Regnbueråd - Startside Facebook	n/a	Newly founded LGBT-association from 2022 that claims to be a reaction to the Danish LGBT-community's "extremism" and "wokeness" with regard to gender and identity politics. One of their slogans is "there are only two sexes" (<i>der er kun to køn</i>).
Generation Identitær	Generation Identity	Anti-gender		None (they only have spokespersons)	Web: https://identitaer.dk Youtube: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCi71jjq2pv3Txs1KnSAwA9Q Odysee: https://odysee.com/@generationidentitaer:6 Telegram: https://t.me/s/generationidentitaer Snapchat: https://www.snapchat.com/add/gidanmark	n/a	Danish section of the European "patriotic" youth movement that began in France. It was established in 2018 with immigration policy as their primary focus. In

							2022 they also began to campaign against what they call "LGBT ideology" in Denmark.
Den Nordiske Modstandsbevægelse	Nordic Resistance Movement	Mostly antigender		Klaus Lund and then Simon Lindberg from 2015	Web: https://nordfront.dk	n/a	Scandinavian Nazi movement established in 2009 with a Danish branch that regularly makes public actions. In recent years, they have focused more and more on what they call the "gay lobby". They might cooperate with Generation Identity in their anti-gender campaigning.
Indre Mission	Inner Mission	Anti-gender		Hans-Ole Bækgaard	Web: Hovedbestyrelsen - indremission.dk Facebook: Indre Mission Fredericia Facebook Instagram: Indre Missions Hus (@indremissionshus) • Instagram-billeder og -videoer Twitter: Indre Mission i DK (@indremission) / Twitter	n/a	An independent Lutheran revival movement who is widespread with small churches and

							influence, but they have made some spectacular happenings over the years, particularly one where they set up 13.000 crosses on a field in 2013.
Jehovas Vidner	Jehovah's Witnesses	Antifeminist and antigender		The Governing Body (no single leader, it seems)	Web: Jehovas Vidners officielle hjemmeside: jw.org Dansk	Approximately 14.500 followers in Denmark	Global millennial movement that also in Denmark advocates, for instance, that homosexuality is a sin, that there are only two sexes, and that abortion is murder.

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FRANCE

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1. Introduction

In her study of conservative women's movement Les Antigones, sociologist Marie Labussière notices that ethnographic studies of conservative movements are still rare in France. She highlights that up until then, the sociology of social movement has heavily focused on left-wing mobilizations (Bereni & Revillard, 2012), and ethnographic studies of the far-right concentrated on the Front National (Bizeul, 2003). However, La Manif Pour Tous (LMPT) has been heavily studied and five years after Labussière's ethnography, more social science work focussed on anti-gender and anti-feminism is being published. In 2019, twenty years after the publication of her landmark study of anti-feminism, historian Christine Bard (Bard, 1999) writes in the introduction to her latest edited volume *Antiféminismes et masculinismes d'hier et d'aujourd'hui* ("Antifeminisms and masculinisms of yesterday and today").

Twenty years after *Un Siècle d'antiféminisme*, an intellectual mobilization is organizing itself (...) it is deepening the history of French antifeminisms, exploring its links with the extreme right, pro-family conservatives and natalists, religions. It shows how antifeminism has been redeployed faced with contemporary issues such as co-education, gender, the opening of marriage to homosexual couples, in a word, with "sexual democracy". (Bard et al., 2019, p4) (our translation)

Bard's edited volume and others show, even though anti-feminist movements are more of a nebula than a single group (Devreux & Lamoureux, 2012), gender is becoming an organizing concept for many of them. In fact, a Google-Ngram search shows a sudden increase in academic and non-academic books published in French and mentioning "anti-gender" starting in 2013¹. This year corresponds to the massive, national protests against civil marriage for people of the same sex ("Le mariage pour tous") (AFP, 2013). The conservative, anti-gender and homophobic movement "La Manif pour tous" (LMPT) is often taken as the beginning of a new epoch of anti-gender movements in France, and also to some extent across Europe (Paternotte & Kuhar, 2020).

The LMPT protests also marked the moment when gender as such became a contested term for mass publics in France. Explicitly linked with American academia by its opponents to strategically position it as a suspect "foreign import" from the global superpower France most often compares itself with, "gender theory" became the theme around which a numerous diverse groups opposed to legislative initiatives of the Hollande government could organize and renew a conservative and largely catholic opposition to female and LGBTQ+ emancipation and equality (Fassin, 2001). Whilst notable engaged academics such as Eric Fassin – who himself bridges the United States of America and France and lead important research units such as the Laboratory of Studies of gender and sexuality (LEGS) at Paris VIII University – openly oppose the existence of a "gender theory", the diversity of groups that are opposed to the very idea of gender, and to gender related rights and emancipation, has tended to be studied discreetly: as far-right, nationalists or fascists, as anti-feminists, as masculinists, as anti-homosexual etc and not necessarily as "anti-gender".

¹ https://books.google.com/ngrams/graph?content=antigenre&year_start=1990&year_end=2019&corpus=fr-2019&smoothing=1 The 2006 bell-shape coincides with the publication of the French translation of Judith Butler's *Gender Trouble* (Butler, 2006) and Eric Fassin's *L'inversion de la question homosexuelle* (E.Fassin, 2005).

The major part of studies on anti-gender and antifeminism concentrates on LMPT, sometimes from the same academics researching on the Front National (for example, Brustier, 2014). On the open-archives HAL, 32 work mention it in their summary in the 2013-2022² period (book sections, journal articles, dictionary entries, conference papers, theses). On Cairn.info, hundreds of papers mention LMPT, mostly in Political Science (202 items) and Sociology (190 items). On both platforms, LMPT is also the topic of foreign-language publications (Geva, 2019; Gunther, 2019).

Seen from the vantagepoint of post-LMPT, an “intransigent Catholic minority”, which was able with LMPT to form alliances beyond Catholic activists, opposed to multiple ways in which French society is changing, appears to be key. These catholic movements were already studied as such prior to the period under consideration here. In the post-LMPT academic world, investigating the links between Catholic movements and anti-gender activism is at the core of many research agendas (Prearo & Garbagnoli, 2018). The return on the political scene of religions in general over the past decade has also led to study of the anti-gender, masculinist and violent attitudes and practices in some interpretations of Islam and Judaism, again a highly delicate set of subjects in France where the figure of the Arab man (“garçon arabe”) can be used to tone down the Western domination of women by white men and simultaneously burnish a “sexual nationalism” (Bard et al., 2019) and femonationalism (Farris, 2017).

Other publications related to antifeminism and/or anti-gender since 2010 are scarce. They include the special issue of Cahiers du Genre on antifeminisms (Devreux & Lamoureux, 2012), research on misogyny (Daumas & Mékouar-Hertzberg, 2017) and the controversy around inclusive language in another special issue of Cahiers du Genre, which the editors refer to as a “French specificity” (Loison et al., 2020). Few recent studies focus on what Bard coins “cyberantifeminism” (Bard et al., 2019) that often take the form of cyber harassment and cyberattacks orchestrated by the far-right and masculinist groups (Gallot & Pasquier, 2018; Julliard, 2018; turchi & Mésangeau, 2022). Masculinist groups are also the topic of a limited number of studies (Gourarier, 2017; Grannis, 2019; Kunert, 2017; Morin, 2021).

The lack of research on this topic is probably what led to the creation of specific research groups, such as the GEDI (Gender and homophobic and sexist discriminations) research programme at the university of Angers (2014-2017) (Bard et al., 2019). In 2022-2023, the CEDREF (Teaching, Documentation and Research Center for Feminist Studies) organizes a monthly seminar on “Antifeminisms from here and elsewhere”³.

During the 2010-2022 period, key policies related to gender and LGBT rights in France were:

- 2011: “parity law” on equal representation of men and women within boards and professional equality committees
- 2012: “Mademoiselle” banned from public administration forms
- 2013: Taubira law on the Marriage for All
- 2013-2014: failure to implement ABCD of equality in schools
- 2021: Law authorizing AMP for single and female same-sex couples

²https://hal.science/search/index?q=%22manif+pour+tous%22&rows=30&docType_s=COMM+OR+ART+OR+COUV+OR+OUV+OR+THESE+OR+NOTICE

³<https://citedugendre.fr/fr/2022/09/16/seminaire-du-cedref-2022-2023-anti-feminismes-dici-et-dailleurs/>

- January 2022: “conversion therapies” which intended to change one’s sexual orientation and/or gender identity are officially banned
- March 2022: extension of abortion period from 12 to 14 weeks

None have sparked such massive anti-gender movements than the Marriage for all, followed by the ABCD of equality, and in a smaller proportion AMP for all. We detail those moments in the next section.

2. The History of the anti-gender/anti-feminist movement and its context

2.1. Anti-gender movements

Before LMPT, and arguably as a condition of the possibility of such a large mobilization, various more or less dormant networks of Catholic and anti-feminist activism should be mentioned, and specifically in their relation with schooling, health and state institutions. These networks existed in the parishes of the Catholic church, in confessional schools, in the Scouts Unitaires de France which rejected co-educational school in the 1970s (today has around 33000 active members) and in the Catholic Family Associations amongst others (Avanza & Sudda, 2017; Cheynel, 2022).

The Centre de Liaison des Équipes de Recherche sur l’amour et la famille (Liaison Center of Research Teams on Love and Families - CLER) established in 1962 is a medical research organization which promotes a method of family planning based on self-observation of periods and temperature, which has become the main institution providing sex education to students at private schools in France (Fradois, 2017). It involves 400 educators, 170 councilors of couples and families and 75 monitors of family planning in 75 centers across France. Its method of family planning - developed in the 1940s in the Equipes Notre Dames based on a technique used by l’abbé Caffarel in 1938, and presented as successful on the island of Mauritius in the 1960s as a way of limiting overpopulation - was strategically of interest to the Catholic church at a moment in history when the place of the clergy in family life was being challenged by contraception and the medical profession. Partly as a result, this method and several French clergy promoting it were influential in the preparation of Vatican II and in the orientation of the encyclical *Humanae Vitae* (1968). This encyclical led to the foundation and funding of the Human Life association in the USA and later in 1974 the International Federation for Family Life Promotion in which influential French Catholics such as Francois Guy had senior positions, promoting ‘natural methods’ of family planning, which have worked to influence the World Health Authority with Catholic doctrine in competition with the International Planned Parenthood Federation. The CLER was able to create numerous structures and institutes across France, and notably work in coordination with clergy preparing couples for weddings, and both through its work and through the influence of individuals in it developed campaigns and structures working against both contraception and abortion. In addition to paid staff, these structures benefit principally from female volunteers, to give sex education classes in schools or to accompany future mothers, often from upper class traditionally Catholic families, thereby perpetuating and giving an opportunity to a philanthropic tradition of the Catholic elite (Fradois, 2017).

A more direct form of activism marked the period from 1987 – 1995 in the anti-abortion ‘commandos’ which would attempt to disrupt abortions from taking place, principally organized by two groups, SOS Tout-Petits and Treve de Dieu. In 1993 the Neiertz law of the socialist government specifically outlawed this kind of action, leading to prison sentences for activists involved from 1994. An attempt to grant amnesties to these activists by Jacques Chirac on being elected president of France in 1995 was voted down by the parliamentary assembly, leading to the end of this kind of activism. In its place the Marche Pour La Vie (March for Life) developed from January 1995, then called ‘Union for Life’ on the anniversary of the Loi Veil of 1975, and became an annual march from 2005, led by a collective of associations including SOS Tout-Petits and Treve de Dieu, but supported by the Confederation of Catholic Family Associations and powerful associations such as Alliance pour les droits de la vie (renamed Alliance Vita in 2011). This March for Life can be seen as a direct precursor to LMPT, and its relatively small impact and mobilization of under 10,000 people each year can be a comparison to the success of Manif pour tous which mobilized between 70,000 and 300,000 (up until 1,4 billion according to organizers (AFP, 2013)).

In 1998, protests against the civil solidarity pact (PACS, the French name of legal civil partnership), are organized by the Générations anti-Pacs collective, with support from the far-right but also a dozen of organizations, including AFC and Alliance pour les droits de la vie (Hugonnier, 2021). Within the medical profession, particularly of psychoanalysts, there was strong opposition to PACS in the 1990s, based on the idea that recognition of homosexuality would undermine the symbolic order based on sex (É. Fassin, 2005), which is the basis of filiation. Even the conference of priests referred to psychoanalysis to justify their opposition to PACS (rather than to the Bible). Psychoanalyst Michel Tort made the link in 1999, the year the PACS was approved, in *Le Monde*, condemning the “psychoanalytical homophobia” in the following terms:

The analysis of the interventions of psychoanalysts in the debate about PACS confirms (with rare exceptions) that ‘symbolic’ horizon remains, amongst them, the positions of the catholic church adapted by the Lacanian symbolic order (Fassin, 2005, p270).

In 2012, presidential candidate François Hollande promised to make marriage possible for all (Mariage pour tous), without sex-based discrimination. Christiane Taubira, named Minister of Justice, is in charge of preparing the law. Even before the parliamentary debates, a strong movement of opponents emerged, around the Catholic Church, right-wing politicians and like-minded media (Hugonnier, 2021).

The unexpected size of these protests came as a surprise to the government, in particular due to the relative public invisibility of many of the actors involved over the prior decade in which anti-abortion and anti-contraception activism had largely disappeared from public attention. Obviously, a condition of LMPT becoming as big as it did was precisely that conservative and Catholic movements were still existing, even if they were not mobilizing in the streets. It is important to take into account that not all activism is publicly visible to understand the ongoing influence of LMPT and its successor organizations and initiatives, and also to bring out transnational connections and influence, in particular to the Vatican and to the United States of America. As scholars have pointed out,

“mobilizations against “Le mariage pour tous” are first and foremost presented as a new French exception, ignoring the striking similarities with similar resistances elsewhere, as well as their precedence in countries like Spain, Italie, Croatia or Slovenia” (Paternotte & Kuhar, 2020).

Despite months of intense mobilization, the Mariage pour tous was voted in spring 2013. The scope of the movement led some to coin it the “Conservative May 68” (Brustier, 2014).

It is in this context that in September 2013, the government launched les ABCD de l'égalité (ABCD of equality) an experimental programme in 600 schools across the country to raise awareness on gender stereotypes. This programme was in line with the 2010 article in the Education code on equality between men and women and the fight against sexism and violence against women⁴ (Blézat, 2022). The project was spearheaded by the Ministry of Education (Vincent Peillon) and the Ministry of Women's Rights (Najat Vallaud-Belkacem). As soon as the project was announced, LMPT and their allies (including right-wing muslim parents and public personalities (Gallot et Pasquier 2018)) formed a huge campaign which included street protests, rumor bombs and targeted cyber-attacks on participants in the project. They claimed it to be teaching explicit sexual content to children (Picq, 2014) and “gender theory” Gallot & Pasquier, 2018; Harsin, 2018; Paternotte & Kuhar, 2020; Stambolis-Ruhstorfer & Tricou, 2018, Harsin, 2018) ven though the first results were encouraging among participating classes, the project was canceled after a teacher received death threats (Blézat, 2022). In addition to the cancellation of the project, one of the consequences of the LMPT battle against the ABCD of Equality was the erasure of the word gender from some educational content (Gallot & Pasquier, 2018).

LMPT and their allies' actions included the development “Vigi-gender”, a network of Catholic parents screening educational content and acting against any mention of “gender theory”, as well as a “Boycott school day” (“Journées de retrait de l'école” JRE) campaign, initiated by Farida Belghoul, an antiracist activist of the 1980s who was then a teacher (Blézat, 2022; Khemilat, 2018). The initiative was supported by far-right figure Alain Soral. The success of the JRE is difficult to measure, however their communication strategy contributed to the abandonment of the ABCD of Equality. There was an interest in suggesting that these JRE have been widely followed, both by Muslim anti-gender actors – in order to have leverage in negotiations with public authorities. Regarding online attacks for the ABCD of Equality, racism and anti-gender collided, specifically targeting Najat Vallaud-Belkacem, then Minister for Women's rights and main promoter of the programme, and allowed the movement to gain wider support (Julliard, 2018).

The trajectory of anti-ABCD of Equality movement has been different outside of mainland France: in her study in Martinique, Nadia Chonville shows that the “gender theory” framework was less impacting in this oversea department, due to the perception that patriarchy and sexism were European issues rather than Martinican ones. The project was nevertheless toned down despite the

⁴ Article L312-17-1 of the Education Code “Information devoted to equality between men and women, the fight against sexist prejudice and the fight against violence against women and violence committed within the couple is provided at all stages of schooling. Educational establishments, including French educational establishments abroad, may join forces for this purpose with associations for the defense of women's rights and promoting equality between men and women and personnel contributing to prevention and repression of such violence.”

lack of organized movement in Martinique, based on the fear of actions such as the one organized by LMPT in mainland France (Chonville, 2018).

Following LMPT, “The collective has (...) developed its lobbying activities and has taken advantage of all electoral deadlines to challenge candidates and invite them to speak out on its demands.” (Réguer-Petit & Morabito, 2015). In 2017, presidential candidate Emmanuel Macron took on the promise made by François Hollande but which the latter gave up during the *Mariage pour tous* debates: opening Medically Assisted Procreation (MAP) to “all women”, arguing that the current difference between heterosexual and homosexual women was indeed a discrimination. In 2019, the first protest against “MAP for all women” happened, through the newly formed collective “*Marchons enfants!*”⁵. The collective formed against what they call “MAP without father and GPA (surrogacy)” and include many former members of LMPT (Béraud, 2021; Hugonnier, 2021). Between 2019 and 2021, protests of both pro and anti-MAP for all took place, but the anti-MAP for all movement was never able to mobilize as strongly as in the previous years.

The different groups within LMPT continued their activities with more or less success. For example, the “French Spring” (*Le Printemps français*) “emancipated from LMPT by adopting a more radical line of populist contestation of the government” (Raison du Cleuziou, p138, 2017). Some actors from LMPT continued their activities in the political sphere through lobbying at the local and European level (de Boissieu, 2016). LMPT also led to the creation of the masculinist movement *Hommen* (see next section). Finally, the early LMPT spokesperson Frigide Barjot distanced herself and created “*L’Avenir pour tous*” (Future for All), which focuses on the recognition of biological filiation exclusively.

2.2. Anti-feminist movements

Even though anti-gender and anti-feminist discourse are often intertwined, revolving around the figure of the heterosexual nuclear family, some movements revolve around anti-feminism, notably targeting in the public space “neo-feminism”. This report classifies notably right-wing women’s movements that articulate a conservative “feminist” discourse, as well as some masculinist movements, as clearly anti-feminists. It is to notice that at least two such movements (*Antigones*, *Hommen*) have appeared directly as a response to the feminist group *FEMEN*, most visible in the 2010’s with street actions of women, writing slogans on their naked breast. *FEMEN* sometimes acted directly in gatherings of the *Front National* (2015⁶). At first, these movements often articulated a “femonationalism” (Farris, 2017) which interlinked with islamophobia. These movements use the same repertory of action as the anti-gender but differ from them in that their main endeavour is to articulate a conservative understanding of “feminism”, which we wanted to highlight. Such anti-

⁵ Member organisations are mentioned on their website and include: La Manif Pour Tous, Agence Européenne des Adoptés – European Agency for Adoptees, Centre européen pour le droit et la justice (ECLJ), Collectif pour le respect de la médecine, Comité Protestant évangélique pour la Dignité Humaine (CPDH), Éveilleurs d’espérance, Les Associations Familiales Catholiques, Fédération Nationale de la Médaille de la Famille Française, Générations Avenir, Institut Famille & République, Juristes Pour l’Enfance, La Voix des Sans Père, Les Familles Plumées, Alliance VITA, Les Gavroches, Les Poissons Roses, Les Sentinelles, Les Veilleurs, Maires pour l’Enfance, Trace ta route, Vigî Gender. See <https://www.marchonsenfants.fr>, consulted February 2023

⁶ https://www.francetvinfo.fr/societe/femen/le-discours-de-marine-le-pen-coupe-par-les-femen_892535.html

feminism is often led by public figures, sometimes issued from the feminist movement, or by small collectives, which act to attract media attention.

There have been several key moments in the period related to an attack on women's rights, and especially Muslim women, in which anti-feminism and islamophobia meet, in what scholar Sara Farris has coined "femonationalism". Specifically, we refer to the French laws of 2004, 2010 and 2021 law prohibiting religious signs at school, the dissimulation of one's face in public space (burka and niqab) and religious signs (hijab) for parents accompanying their children during school trips, respectively.

To these laws, we add the summer 2016 public debate on "burkini" during which about thirty municipalities in France passed a decree to forbid burkini on their beaches. The State Council (Conseil d'Etat) later canceled these rulings. Conversations about the burkini came back in the public debate in 2022, after the City of Grenoble authorized burkini in public swimming pools - which the State Council canceled.

The racist trope of antifeminism was also visible following the 2016 New Year Eve sexual assault in Cologne, Germany. Prominent French feminist organizations such as Osez le féminisme and the National Collective for Women's Rights (Cndf) warned against the racist treatment of the event⁷. However it was also interpreted in a "femonationalist" trend (Farris, 2017) and led a couple of years later to the creation of the "identitary feminist" group Nemesis, which claims "We are the Cologne generation"⁸.

A second set of anti-feminist movements appear in the post-#Metoo period. Many anti-feminists, who use terms such as "alterfeminists" or "femalists" to describe themselves, and masculinist movements have appeared on the public scene since 2017. Their discourses are well represented in conservative media and spill over in mainstream media as well. Such groups include previously mentioned Les Antigones and Nemesis, as well as even smaller groups whose discourse focus on anti-abortion. Anti-abortion movements do not act at a legal level (for example against the right to abortion) but rather use a moral discourse to promote conservative views about women's bodies and abortion – a repertoire of action which echoes US "pro-life" movements. One such example is "Les survivants", whose public figures are young, white and upper-class men and women.

3. Actors

Traditional catholic and nationalist movements gained in representation and strength during LMPT, many of them managed to collaborate within the banner of LMPT and even the movements that developed on the side regained momentum. Della Sudda (2017) highlights that "despite the fact that catholic and nationalists movements are diverse and diverge in terms of socio-economic and education background and age of their members and structure and belong to distinct political culture, sometimes antagonistic ones, these protagonists met in the streets during the demonstrations of 2012 and 2013 and then more sporadically after 2014." She explains how opposition against Taubira law

⁷ <https://www.leparisien.fr/faits-divers/cologne-les-feministes-francaises-mettent-en-garde-contre-le-racisme-12-01-2016-5444531.php>

⁸ <https://www.collectif-nemesis.com/manifeste>

“cemented” a coming together. “Sexual questions” become central and offer points of commonalities in defense of heterosexual families and of children”.

The main actors of anti-gender and anti-feminist movements can be broadly classified in the following sections:

- Movements linked to Catholicism and the Vatican
- Other religious movements
- Far right movements
- Anti or Alterfeminists
- Masculinists movements

Movements linked to the Catholic Church include La Manif pour Tous, and several sub-mouvements, which were present or not in LMPT, such as:

Alliance Vita is an anti-abortion, anti-LGBT rights organisation. The organization was created in 1993 by Christine Boutin. It provides information on the internet about abortion (www.ivg.net) and organizes actions such as lobbying, petitions, conferences, and meetings with political decision makers (Le Point, 2013). It was one of the funders of LMPT (Rauglaudre, 2020).

The Associations Familiales Catholiques (Catholic Family Associations (AFC)) were created in 1905 as the Catholic Heads of Family Association (Associations catholiques des chefs de famille (ACCF)) but became the AFC in 1955, have around 26,000 members and uses strategic entryism with other associations and in state structures to promote a vision of the French family founded on marriage between a man and a woman, to support homeschooling, to legally contest education books contents, and to remove mention of contraception or abortion from sex education in schools, amongst other causes promoting a conservative Catholic vision of gender relations. The members of AFC are strategically part of student-parent associations in schools, and the AFC is a member of the Haut Conseil de la Famille, de l'Enfance et de l'Âge, part of the National Union of Family Associations, and hold the presidency of a large number of regional family unions. Through this presence in various bodies recognized by the State, the AFC manages to place members strategically in power circles (Cheynel, 2022) and has for example influenced over questions such as adoption agreements (Rétif, 2017).

Les Veilleurs: The Watchers “was formed in opposition to police repression and adopted a strategy of nonviolent conscientious objection to defend the rights of children.” (Reason of Cleuziou, 2017). Its main public figure is Marianne Durano, philosopher and member of the review “Limit”. The modus operandi of the watchers is to demonstrate by reading texts of literature and philosophy, listening to music and singing, sitting in a group, on the ground. This movement, which wants to be apolitical and non-confessional, announces to defend a "calm revolution of consciences through art and culture" (Le Figaro, 2013).

Civitas: homophobic organisation, founded in 1998. Since 2011, Civitas actions have attracted media attention, notably when Civitas demonstrated in opposition to theatre plays by throwing eggs on the actors. Civitas also attacked Femen (feminist collective doing media oriented flashmobs, usually with messages written on naked breast) in 2012, in the margins of a demonstration called “non à

l'homofolie" (Ackerman, 2013). In 2013 Civitas was banned from La Manif Pour Tous (Cervulle, 2013). Alain Escada has been its president since 2012. Alain Escada is close to Alain Soral. Civitas became a political party in 2016, "La Coalition pour la vie et la famille", describing itself as a "traditionalist catholic lobby". The movement was present in the mobilisation against the "sanitary pass" in the covid period (Le Monde, 2021). According to Le Monde (2017) "La Coalition pour la vie et la famille" was supported by the Front National and has links with members of neonazi parties in Greece and Slovakia, which supported it to become a recognised European Political Party to access funding from the European Parliament.

Institut Ichtus: Le Monde (2013) recently highlighted the role of the Ichtus network, a traditionalist Catholic institute, whose objective is to penetrate secular spheres in order to transmit the message of the Church there.

3.1. Religious movements

The Union des Organisations Islamiques de France (UOIF) is publicly hostile to 'gender theory' and 'marriage for all' as Khemilat (2018) highlights. Its members were also invited to speak during certain events organized by the 'Manif pour tous', such as that of March 24, 2013, where Rachid Laamarti, administrator of the UOIF, called to the podium his "Muslim co-religionists" to mobilize. At the Annual Meeting of French muslims (Réunion Annuelle des Musulmans de France) in 2014, Ludovine de la Rochère, then president of the 'Manif pour tous' was invited to highlight an interreligious alliance in favour of "family".

JRE (Journée de Retrait) de l'École (2014) initiated by Farida Belghoul was also presented as a movement of muslim parents joining mobilisation against ABCD de l'égalité, although the mobilisation of French Muslims on this topic is less strong than suggested by the movements trying to claim a union of religions in this fight (Khemilat, 2018).

3.2. Far/right movements

The Rassemblement National is the successor of the Front National. It develops a rhetoric linked to alterfeminism in the sense that two of its main figures in the period considered, Marine le Pen and her niece Marion Maréchal le Pen have used the fact that they are women to give a face of "acceptability" to the party, which thereby pretends to leave equal space to women within its governance structure. It develops an islamophobic approach that uses women's rights against migrants and muslims.

Sens Commun is an offspring of LMPT. It was created in 2013 "with the stated aim of weighing from within the UMP and influencing the line of the pretender to the Elysée in 2017" (Le Monde, 2017). The UMP was already providing tacit support to La Manif pour tous, despite the apolitical label claimed by its president, Ludovine de la Rochère. In 2014, Le Monde revealed that "several logistical meetings organized on the eve of major parades had taken place at the headquarters of the UMP. Similarly, dozens of buses had been chartered by the party federations to allow movement demonstrators to join the Paris processions. The Sens Commun association undertakes to donate to the Republicans, in the form of a subsidy, a share of the subscriptions collected".

Le Printemps Français was a nebulous organization. Gathered behind a common label, "French Spring", activists close to traditionalist Catholic networks against Same Sex Marriage. Associated with the movement is Beatrice Bourges. A diverse right-wing candidate in the legislative elections of 2002 and 2012, this 50-year-old woman from Versailles has long been involved in anti-gay marriage movements. Spokesperson for the Collective for the child, she exercised the same functions within the collective of LMPT, before being pushed towards the exit. "Asked by several young people", she agrees to become the muse of French Spring" (Mouillard & Livolsi, 2013). The website of Le printemps français makes explicit references to 1968, Tiananmen and Solidarnosc and the "Arab Springs". "This lexical retortion is an old method of the French far right", analyzes Nicolas Lebourg, specialist in this political family. "This is a symbolic counter-subversion that allows these movements to look subversive while being perfectly responsive."

Génération Identitaire was a far-right action oriented group. Its spokesperson was a young woman, Thaïs d'Escufon (born 1999). Dissolved by the government in 2021 it has now revived in the group "Les Natifs", which mode of actions include direct action against feminism, notably against theater plays, such as within the recent action (2021) in "response" to the "Coquettes", a feminist humorist music group⁹. There is also Les Remparts, another group born out of Génération identitaire in Lyon.

Eric Zemmour as a public figure, as well as its political movement "Reconquête!" are clearly anti-feminists. For Zemmour, the world is undertaking an anthropological mutation, leading to feminisation of men. His discourse also criticises texts against sexual harassment at work, which according to him "criminalise masculine desire", and thereby supports forms of sexual violence. Eric Zemmour (2022) happily claims "I hold a counter-feminist discourse, I think that feminists are wrong"¹⁰. One of his first books was "the first sex" (Zemmour, 2006), presented as "an essay on virile manners for the use of young feminized generations". Eric Zemmour did get 7% of the votes in the first round of the Presidential elections in 2022.

Essayist Alain Soral is together with Zemmour a misogynistic author, who contributed to diffuse masculinist thought in France. According to him the feminisation of society is a complot organized by international imperialism. Alain Soral creates videos "Soral a (presque toujours) raison"¹¹ with very offensive and abrasive language.

3.3. Anti-feminists

The anti-feminists also call themselves "féministes intégrales" (Delaporte, 2018) or Alterféministes (Causeur.fr, 2016) or "femelliste" (L'hospital, 2023) or "féministes identitaires"¹². Some would fall in the category defined by analysts as "femonationalists" (Farris, 2017). Some are opposed to all forms of feminisms, some on the contrary recognised the legacy of some of the historic feminists movements, and some have defined their own version of feminism, i.e. and are femonationalists in

⁹ https://actu.fr/ile-de-france/paris_75056/des-anciens-de-generation-identitaire-creent-un-nouveau-groupe-d-extreme-droite-a-paris_46640974.html

¹⁰ <https://www.dailymotion.com/video/x844fhy>

¹¹ Website of Egalité and Reconciliation: <https://www.egaliteetreconciliation.fr/Soral-a-presque-toujours-raison-Episode-21-70087.html>

¹² https://www.lexpress.fr/politique/enquete-sur-le-feminisme-identitaire_1496325.html

that they oppose western white feminism to threats coming according to them mostly from immigrants and other cultures. The most visible movements are the following:

Les Antigones is a women's movement - a collective initially - formed in 2013 in the wake of mobilizations against the legalization of marriage for same-sex couples. Its President is Anne Trewby. According to Labussière (2017, online resource on cairn.fr): "Antigones relied on a shock action to stand out: the infiltration of the Femen for several weeks, followed by a publicized confrontation in their premises, at the Lavoisier Moderne in Paris." Within the movement is at play a "Secularization of slogans and demands, in accordance with the strategy of the Church and other movements of the radical right, and on the other hand by the formulation of a new way of defining the cause of women, called "alter-feminist", aimed at countering egalitarian and liberal feminism." The two initial founders of the movement, Iseul and Mathilde, present their project as a reaction to the hegemonic visibility of the Femen and intend to fight back on the same ground, that of the media and social networks." The movement started when Iseul, then 21 years old and a law student, set out to create a blog called Antigones. An activist for several years within the far-right political organization Dextra, she has benefited from training that she can use to give scope to her project. Wishing to make "a media stunt" in response to those who "really occupied the screens, the TV, all the time, permanently".¹³

Nemesis was created in 2019 by a group of friends according to its website. Its Manifesto mentions "We are the cologne generation" in an open reference to the rape in Cologne in which a migrant was the raper. We are "The island where the shipwrecked of feminism can take refuge". It is created openly in reaction to feminism. It claims that "The Nemesis Collective has therefore decided to take up the fight concerning the fulfillment of Western women." Nemesis is using street actions as one of its major forms of action. For instance, it penetrated Nous Toutes demonstrations as a group of women wearing hijab, with the purpose of discrediting Nous Toutes. The website announces that the movement intends to become European.

3.4. Masculinists

Boosted by the movement coming from the US, a masculinist movement has developed in France. Masculinist movements are not all similar. Some of them, which provide "coaching" can, according to the governmental agency observing sects¹⁴, Miviludes, may be considered as sects¹⁵.

Mouvement Zeromacho introduces itself as a movement of "men against prostitution and for equality". It was founded by the Chiennes de Garde, initially a feminist movement, now openly anti-gender. Florence Montreynaud from Les Chiennes de Garde openly said: "We must resist against transactivists, pro-prostitution and pro-veil" (Charlie Hebdo, 2022). The network "Encore féministes!" is part of the same coalition.

¹³ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Xxpwa1jKSw&list=PLPby4TVpvzMvn7GGt1BUwAu6E6UFXH_VZ

¹⁴ <https://www.interieur.gouv.fr/actualites/communiqués/rapport-annuel-de-miviludes-gouvernement-se-mobilise-face-a-hausse>

¹⁵ <https://www.leparisien.fr/faits-divers/pseudo-guerisseurs-masculinistes-ultra-feministes-ces-nouveaux-gourous-20-qui-inquietent-la-miviludes-02-11-2022-DVDILMEORBCU5KNHYU45KNL5E.php>

Hommen¹⁶ is a group created as a counterpoint to the Femen. It was active around 2013 with street actions, asking Femen to get dressed, or vandalizing the locals of Act Up. They claim international links, notably with Italy.

The Hominisme is a French-speaking current of masculinism that is gaining in popularity, in particular because it dissociates itself from other anti-feminist discourses. See notably the website of Patrick Guillot La cause des hommes which claims to be defending both the right of women and men. Kunert (2017) quotes for instance how the Hoministes support the feminisation and homonisation of names of professions, in order, for instance, to open access symbolically to jobs linked with care for young children to men as well.

Mankind Project¹⁷: “The Mankind Project (MKP), an American masculinist association created in 1984, has been exported to Europe and in particular to France where it offers weekends of “initiatory adventure for new warriors”. Miviludes identified 10 reports on this group in 2021¹⁸.

Mgtow is a branch of a movement born in the US. The French Speaking Facebook had 3200 subscribers on FB in 2020 and the YouTube channel had accumulated nearly 5 million views on YouTube. In France, the first groups were formed in 2015.

Associations of Fathers such as SOS Papa, Allô Papa, Allô Maman, SVP Papa, Fédération des mouvements de la condition paternelle, briefly united in 2023 within a Collective La Grue Jaune (in reference to two men who had climbed up cranes to call for their rights as regards to their children in Nantes), are using the rhetoric of the rights of father to discredit fights against gender-based violence.

4. Allies

The allies of the anti-gender and anti-feminist movements are numerous. Here we have classified in the following categories: Institutions, the media, publishing houses, social media, political parties, medical institutions and others.

4.1. Institutions

4.1.1. Municipalities

In 2016, about 30 French municipalities issued local regulations to forbid women to wear burkinis. The local regulations were largely cancelled by a judgment of the French “Conseil d’Etat” (the highest jurisdiction when it comes to administrative law)¹⁹.

¹⁶ https://www.huffingtonpost.fr/actualites/article/qui-sont-les-hommen_21742.html

¹⁷ <https://www.unadfi.org/actualites/groupe-et-mouvances/des-signalements-en-hausse-apres-des-stages-masculinistes-du-mankind-project/#more-19038>

¹⁸ <https://www.unadfi.org/actualites/groupe-et-mouvances/des-signalements-en-hausse-apres-des-stages-masculinistes-du-mankind-project/#more-19038>

¹⁹ https://www.lemonde.fr/societe/article/2016/08/26/le-conseil-d-etat-suspend-l-arrete-anti-burkini-de-villeneuve-loubet_4988472_3224.html?random=1586741712

To be noted that a certain number of mayors have also refused to celebrate same sex marriages. They even took the request to the European Court of Human Rights. In 2018, The European Court of Human Rights ruled inadmissible the request filed by 146 mayors in France, who claimed their freedom of conscience to refuse to celebrate marriage between people of the same sex.

4.1.2. The State

In many ways the anti-veil legislation pushed forward by the French government nourished islamophobic discourses and favoured the consolidation of femonationalism, i.e. using women's rights defense in opposition to a perceived threat coming from migrants.

State Institutions such as the justice system also clearly play a role in discrediting feminist claims, notably by issuing a lot of rejections of complaints for sexual violence and harrasment because of a lack of conclusive proofs (non-lieux, classements sans-suite) and by giving the opportunity to men sued for sexual harassment to sue the complainers for defamation. A recent report by the Haut Conseil à l'Égalité entre les femmes et les hommes states : "As such, 2022 was a period rich in defamation lawsuits against the accusers of powerful men: in April, Patrick POIVRE D'ARVOR accused 16 women of slanderous denunciation; in May, the Court of Cassation gave right to the accusers of Pierre JOXE and Éric BRION Alexandra BESSON and Sandra MULLER, initially convicted of defamation" (Pierre-Brossolette et al., 2023).

4.1.3. Police

The Police is known for not being adequately trained to receive the deposition of women victims of sexual violence, leading, according to feminist groups to undertaking "rape culture". Such practices have been denounced online using several keywords such as #Paye ta Police (slang word meaning "Take that in your face because of the Police") #Paye ta Plainte (2018) ("Take that in your face when you put file a police complaint") and #DoublePeine (2021) (#Double Sentence) as related on France Info (2019). A 2021 Study by CEVIPOF (Centre for Political Research at Sciences-Po) shows that the police and the military is the group of public servant that has the highest "partisan's proximity" (39% of interviewees) with Rassemblement National and shows that 60% of this group (police and military public servants) announce their intention to vote for Marine le Pen at the second round of the Presidential elections (CEVIPOF, 2021, p 4)²⁰. Direct attacks of police officers against feminists have also been relayed in the media recently. For instance, in 2020, police violence was recorded against a feminist manifestation (Le Monde, 2020) or hiding feminists' statements from a window of a library without any legal basis (Le Monde, 2022). To counter this, in 2021, the Ministry of Interior started a campaign "You are Feminist, become a police officer", which objective is in part to "create new vocations among young people who have the feminist cause at heart" (website, Ministry of Interior²¹).

4.2. The Media

First, right wing and extreme right wing media have relayed and given a platform to anti-gender thinkers and activists. Cervulle (2013) writes that "the press occupies a central position in defining the controversy" around "marriage for all".

²⁰https://www.sciencespo.fr/cevipof/sites/sciencespo.fr.cevipof/files/NoteEP2022V24_LR_votefonctionnaires_mai2021_VF.pdf

²¹ <https://www.interieur.gouv.fr/actualites/actu-du-ministere/campagne-nationale-vous-etes-feministe>

Causeur is one of the key antifeminist publications (Labussière, 2017; Lévy, 2021), for instance in 2015, featured in number 26, on the front page “The feminist terror. Sexism, inequality, harassment... They have their eye on you”, with the image of a fifties-looking woman holding a chainsaw in her hands (Pahud, 2018). The magazine’s website homepage proposes “feminism” as one of the topics tags one can choose, out of 9 themes (website, homepage). Other media include Le Figaro, which employs Eugénie Bastié, author of “Adieu Mademoiselle” (2016), to cover issues linked to gender and feminism; Marianne, souverainist magazine, which has Natacha Polony as editor in chief, provides a regular tribune to individuals such as blogger and influencer Dora Moutot and activist Marguerite Stern (ex-member of the feminist group FEMEN and initiator of “collages féministes”); Minute, the extreme right wing newspaper (now weekly), issued a racist cover in 2013 against then Minister of Justice Christiane Taubira and condemned for this in 2015 (Le Monde & AFP, 2015); Valeurs Actuelles, another extreme right wing journal, which titled in 2020 “feminists have become crazy” (Etancelin, 2020). The magazine also conveyed a misogynistic and racist attack on deputy Danièle Obono (Damerdji, 2020). Other media outlets include: Radio Courtoisie, Conservateur, L’Incorrect and Réseau d’Égalité & réconciliation (E&R), an “alternative” media launched and presided by essayist Alain Soral since 2007.

Second, more mainstream media, less associated with right- and extreme right wing politics also relay largely anti-gender discourses. As Fondation Jean Jaures Backlash report (2023) mentions “Masculinist and anti-rights discourses are widely echoed in a number of media, including in France. The mere fact of using the terminology of these movements – “gender theory”, “wokism” – contributes to legitimizing their discourse and discrediting the emancipation movements as a whole. The media’s treatment of gender-based and sexual violence, in particular, is too often constructed against women’s voices and still largely tends to perpetuate the culture of rape, brushing aside the aspirations stemming from the #MeToo movement. Describing domestic violence as “passionate dramas” is an operation to exonerate the perpetrators of violence... The fact of having given wide media coverage to men accused of violence, such as Nicolas Hulot, Patrick Poivre d’Arvor or Adrien Quatennens, for example, feeds backlash dynamics.”

4.3. Publishing houses

Several publishing houses give a platform to anti-gender writers, such as éditions du Rocher (Monaco), which published, after Plon’s refusal, Oriana Fallaci’s Islamophobic trilogy (Damerdji, 2021) under the cover of “Literary dressing” (Al-Matary & Damerdji, 2022). Labussière (2017) highlights that “during 2016, no less than three essays, with evocative titles, were published on this subject: Adieu Mademoiselle. The defeat of women, A sexually liberated youth (or almost), or Adieu Simone. The last hours of feminism”.

4.4. Forums and social media

Citizens’ led journals or forums have been strategically developed and used by anti-gender movements such as jeuxvideos.com which provide a space to build cyberharassment strategies. Another such forum is “fdesouche”.

Social Media: It is well documented that behind a computer, more violent and radical comments and actions have become common. If Social Media channels have been occupied as a space of freedom and denunciations by feminists, it has also become a space of harassment, extreme violence leading to burn out and a space for building and spreading counter-narratives to feminism (turchi &

Mésangeau, 2022). Encrypted communication groups, such as telegram, have also been widely used tools by anti-gender and feminist groups. Fisha accounts have developed during covid times, harassing women and cyberattacking them.

4.5. Political Parties

Political parties seem to have difficulties dealing with change and reacting to sexual harassment cases in their ranks. Political figures have been nominated to high positions in the Government as Ministers, while on trial under accusation of rape (G. Darmanin as Interior Minister) or despite having held sexist discourses (E. Dupond Moretti as Minister of Justice). In 2022, two cases of domestic violence have been revealed within the political parties which nominally include “feminism” in their programme, involving men which were at the head of those parties, Julien Bayou for Europe Ecologie les Verts and Adrien Quatennens for La France Insoumise. The reactions to these cases, within the parties, such as the one of JL. Mélenchon, LFI leader, have been diminishing the feminist agenda of fighting against sexist and sexual violence.

4.6. The medical institution

The French medical institution has been an important actor of the medicalization and psychiatrization of trans health. A long-term conflict exists between trans organizations and the French Professional Association for Transgender Health (previously SOFECT) regarding their approach to trans health, and the role of psychiatrists within the organization (Beaubatie, 2021; Giami & Nayak, 2019). Until 2022, trans people had to provide a psychiatric certificate in order to be able to transition and be reimbursed²².

Prominent figures of the medical profession also co-founded in 2021 the Observatory of the Little Mermaid (Observatoire de la petite sirène (see section 5)) to lobby against the gender transitions of minors.

Regarding anti-feminist allies within the medical profession, the French law has a specific conscience clause regarding abortion, which some medical professionals use to refuse performing abortions.

Several Public Figures have also been allies of anti-gender and anti-feminist discourses such as Elisabeth Badinter, Christine Angot or writer Michel Houellebecq to name a few.

²² <https://www.neonmag.fr/assurance-maladie-met-fin-a-lobligation-dun-certificat-psychiatrique-pour-la-prise-en-charge-des-personnes-trans-559869.html>

5. Themes and agendas

Several thematic have attracted the mobilization of the anti-genders and anti-feminists.

5.1. Labor market

The “right” of women to choose to stay at home is one of the choice defended by the alterfeminists, such as Eugénie Bastier (2016).

Another element of the argument is that quotas, such as the ones in companies and administrations are counterproductive and arbitrary. This is based on universalists arguments, insisting on the fact that women have the rights as men legally by now and should not have more rights.

The right of men to work in positions that are often occupied by women, such as the masculinist activist group Hoministes highlights on its website in the employment section²³.

Finally, a discourse has developed against regulations targeting sexual harassment as essayist and political figure Eric Zemmour writes in “The First Sex”, as Marcuss (Mediapart Blog, 2022)²⁴ quotes “For Zemmour, laws against sexual harassment in the workplace criminalize male desire through “judicial surveillance of desire”. Men no longer have the right to desire, to hustle, to attract, since “in our feminine society, all seduction is likened to the unbearable violence of the infamous macho”. » (translated by authors)

Anticapitalism is quite present in the movements such as Les Antigones, which identify the violence against women and the inequality of salaries to the methods of the big capital. This is close to the arguments developed by the ecologists following the theoretical line developed by the Vatican (Carnac & Bertina, 2013).

When it comes to the rights of sex workers, several movements are anti-prostitution.

5.2. Health & reproductive rights

The main topic that galvanized the anti-gender movement in France is linked to health and reproductive rights. It is LMPT (2013) which created a link between same sex marriage and issues linked to raising children and Medically Assisted Procreation. The major threat was that Same Sex Marriage was conceived as the first step to the apparition of non-heterosexual families.

On the side of family planning, the anti-feminism and anti-gender movements attack on several fronts:

When it comes to Family planning and abortion, a movement such as the Centre de Liaison des Équipes de Recherche sur l’amour et la famille (CLER), born around the willingness to inform about “natural” methods of family planning, i.e observation of menstrual cycles and temperature curves and public figures such as Eugénie Bastié who relayed this preference for natural forms of family planning in opposition to contraceptives have developed anticontraception and anti-abortion discourses. The movements behind LMPT were anti-abortion. For instance “The Survivors” (Les Survivants) a

²³ <https://www.hoministe.com> (consulted, January 2023)

²⁴ <https://blogs.mediapart.fr/marcuss/blog/120122/la-violence-masculine-une-norme-du-masculinisme-11-12>

movement created in 2016 conceptualizes the “syndrom of the survivor”²⁵. “A survivor is a survivor of the terrible lottery which has been exerted for several years on the future born children.” “Abortion survivor syndrome was discovered a few years ago in the United States by psychiatrists Philip G. Ney and Marie A. Peeters.” (website, Les Survivants, consulted in 2022). This Anti-abortion movement by young, white people is analyzed by sociologist Anne-Sophie Crosetti in “the movements Les Survivants and La Marche pour la vie” (2022)”. Its militants use actions in public space and online (Eyries, 2021; Fleury & Walter, 2020). They are linked with far-right and royalist parties²⁶.

To be noted is that the antivax movements, linked to some souverainists, nationalist and complotists movements, have also addressed the question of reproduction, when they considered that one of the risks of the vaccine was to sterilise the population.

Education to Sexuality has been a topic highly invested by anti-gender and anti-feminist movements. The law plans for 3 compulsory sessions of education to sexuality per year from highschool on. This has been largely invested and recuperated by anti-abortion organizations, since other organizations (Planning Familial, Centre d’Information sur le Droit des Femmes) cannot catch up with the amount of requests. The CLER notably has the State Agreement to provide sexual education sessions and operates mostly in private education highschools.

5.3. Migration

Most of the movements identified in this report are openly anti-migration and do develop a line of thought that identifies violence against women and patriarchal culture to the countries of origins and religion of migrants. Nemesis organised an action in front of the “Museum of Immigration” to, as they claim, “honour victims of sexual violence perpetrated by migrants who have been under a repatriation order, but not yet expelled”.

5.4. LGBTQI+ rights

Anti-gender movements have largely mobilized against what they call “gender theory” and have been successful in this battle. If the movements have lost the battle against Same Sex Marriage (2013), they won a symbolic one against the ABCD de l’égalité (2014) and manage to diffuse ideas against “gender theory” broadly in the public discourse.

More recently, the anti-gender movements have mobilized against medically supported gender transition. For instance, the Observatory of the Little Mermaid, a group led in particular by psychoanalysts Céline Masson and Caroline Eliacheff, raised their points against “the possible excesses of too rapid medicalization that can lead to irreversible bodily changes” of trans minors”, according to its founders.

5.5. Gender-Based Violence

Hanitra Andriamandroso (2019) highlights how the topic of Domestic Violence is invested as a battlefield by anti-feminist movements. According to her the discourses on domestic violence are partly diffused thanks to the interventions of public intellectuals. She also identifies the publication of the first national survey on violence against women (Enveff, 2021) as the point of departure of anti-

²⁵ <https://lessurvivants.com/le-syndrome-du-survivant/>

²⁶ <https://www.marieclaire.fr/les-survivants-nouveau-mouvement-de-jeunes-anti-avortement,824118.asp>

feminist discourse and mobilisations on that topic. She highlights that “the topic, its mediatic impact, the status of authors and references to Enveff have been criteri used in the articles published against it by M. Iacub (2003), E. Badinter (2005), D. Welzer Lang (2009) in the press and the publication of books by Badinter (2003), Coutanceau (2006) and Bastard (2013) on such topics.” According to her study these authors argued against taking into account psychological violence as a form of sexual violence, they highlight the co-responsibility of women in creating cases of violence, and cases of violence against men, also operating a language slip from “domestic violence” to “domestic war” or “violent couple”.

Among the discourses and strategies developed in this domain are notably the regular reference to false denunciations. Despite the actual very exceptional occurrence of false denunciations, the anti-feminists managed to raise doubts in the institutions. She explains that from the end of 2000, the discourses on domestic violence insist on the character of the beaten man and of the father, bringing children at the core of the debate.

The right of fathers is often mounted as an argument against women’s rights, both in case of violence against women, but also in case of violence against children. Andriamandroso (2019) shows the theory of the so-called “Syndrome of Parental Alienation” which would deny fathers from their rights, following a manipulation of children by the mothers is used by anti-feminist actors, such as for instance validated juridical psychologist experts operating in Courts, such as Roland Coutanceau and Paul Bensoussan. Organizations such as “SOS Papa” (Devreux, 2009; Fillod-Chabaud, 2017) have contributed to this rhetoric.

5.6. Education

The mobilisation against ABCD de l’égalité has shown how anti-gender movements have invested the terrain of education. The mobilisation managed to claim in public debate the existence of a “gender theory” that would be detrimental if taught at school. As mentioned earlier in the report, the anti-gender movement have also heavily invested the sector of sexual education in high schools. Essayist and Political figure Eric Zemmour also continues to use the language of “indoctrination” of children at school (La Croix, 2021).

6. Repertoires of Action

Anti-gender and anti-feminist movements have a heavy online presence. They own well-referenced anti-abortion websites, which led to the vote in 2016 to the law condemning illegal online interference to abortion right²⁷. During the anti-MAP for all protests, the Marchons Enfants ! collective launched a petition (29k signatures).

Masculinists share their messages through blogs and websites (MGTOW website, artdeseduire.com etc.). The 18-25 forum of the website jeuxvideos.com is also a place where masculinists share anti-feminist content. In 2017, journalist Nadia Daam dedicated her daily radio chronicle to a critique of

²⁷ https://www.lemonde.fr/les-decodeurs/article/2016/12/07/ivg-net-sosbebe-org-ecouteivg-org-les-sites-faux-nez-des-anti-ivg_5044556_4355770.html

the forum, and was immediately cyber-harassed. Two of the perpetrators were condemned in court in 2020²⁸.

Cyberattacks on feminist content take place on all platforms : Youtube, Twitter (Gallot & Pasquier, 2018), Zoom²⁹. The strategies are similar from case to case, as analyzed in the documentary #SalePute (Hainaut & Leroy, 2021). They organize on Telegram or Discord platforms and target feminist accounts or events³⁰.

In the public speeches, the anti-feminist movement aim at discrediting feminist struggles by using depreciative vocabulary such as “ayatolette” (from ayatollah), “néoféministe”, “feminazi” etc. They also position themselves within key institutions such as private High Schools³¹ and use lobbying to push their agenda forward (Rétif, 2017).

Anti-gender movements have also taken the streets and organized massive protests, as well as happenings in front of the National Assembly (“Opération Mariannes”). Other actions in the public space include billposting of anti-abortion posters (Les Survivants in the Paris metro in 2017)³², Street graffiti³³...). Antifeminsit fathers’ movements have organized events that have marked the public opinion (Fillod-Chabaud, 2017; Leport, 2020), such as climbing on top of a crane and refusing to come down³⁴.

Regarding the funding of such moments, a survey conducted by Mediapart suggests that La Manif pour tous was financed in particular by the Lejeune Foundation and Alliance Vita, Catholic organizations campaigning against abortion. Bosses of large companies have also participated actively in this financing.

Blais and Dupuis-Deri (2019) highlight how masculinist movements managed to propose conferences, activities and events in the frame of weeks for equality of women and men, notably to public administrations. They describe how the service dedicated to fighting discriminations of the municipality of Grenoble for instance, co-organised events with “Réseau Hommes”, a masculinist Quebec based organisation. This is a detailed micro-example describing how masculinist movements walk through institutions and lobby unnoticed. The influence of masculinists and antigender groups

²⁸<https://www.numerama.com/politique/609236-menaces-contre-nadia-daam-la-justice-confirme-la-condamnation-dun-membre-du-forum-18-25.html>

²⁹<https://france3-regions.francetvinfo.fr/occitanie/haute-garonne/toulouse/extreme-droite-attaque-colloque-feministe-ligne-universite-toulouse-jean-jaures-depose-plainte-1893608.html>

³⁰https://actu.fr/ile-de-france/paris_75056/des-anciens-de-generation-identitaire-creent-un-nouveau-groupe-d-extreme-droite-a-paris_46640974.html

³¹ In 2022, *L’Express* magazine revealed anti-abortion and anti-feminist teaching in the elite private High School Stanislas in Paris https://www.lexpress.fr/societe/stanislas-le-college-d-elite-qui-prone-la-pudeur-feminine-face-aux-pulsions-des-garcons_2174704.html

³²<https://www.leparisien.fr/info-paris-ile-de-france-oise/transports/affiches-anti-avortement-la-ratp-porte-plainte-26-04-2017-6893235.php>

³³<https://www.neonmag.fr/pochoirs-pour-tous-ils-recouvrent-de-coeurs-les-messages-homophobes-haineux-racistes-ou-sexistes-525187.html>

³⁴<https://www.elle.fr/Societe/News/Pere-sur-une-grue-les-associations-feministes-montent-au-creneau-2345474>

in international institutions (UN for instance) and national groups working on violence against women for instance is also well documented in Bard and al. (2019).

7. Frames of Arguments

7.1. "Gender Theory"

The main discursive element used by anti-gender activists is an opposition to what is presented as "Gender theory" (Levet, 2014). In France, the reference to a "gender theory" was initiated before La Manif pour Tous but became used recurrently in mainstream media at this occasion (La Manif pour tous, 2013). According to Garbagnoli & Prearo (2017) the genesis of the discourse of "theory of gender" (théorie du genre) has been orchestrated by the Vatican. In France, it appeared in the public sphere in 2011 following a public question to the ministry of Education by deputy Philippe Gosselin in 2011 (Stambolis-Ruhstorfer & Tricou, 2018).

The "gender theory" is presented as a socio-cultural construction coming from abroad (with much reference to Judith Butler's work) to "feminize" (and thereby diminish) men and abolish heterosexuality (and therefore the family). It is presented as a theory that denies the existence of differences between women and men, disregarding the fact that there are several approaches to gender in research. Rochefort (2016) states that the status of gender theory and of the different disciplines of scientific knowledge itself in public has been a key theme in French national debate, with education and the educative system as a key contested terrain. Gender theory would lead to dangerous blurring of identity construction for children and to dangerous and anticipated conversion operations. "Gender theory" was a major argument against the ABCD of Equality (Pachoud, 2018).

While Gender Theory has been prominent in LMPT and anti-ABCD of Equality protests, it is less visible in the anti-MAP movement (Béraud, 2021). In the following years, anti-feminist attacks have focused on islamophobia (with the use of "islamogauchiste" (Raynaud, 2021)) and, in a similar mechanism than for Gender Theory, on the danger of US-imported ideas such as "intersectionality" (Lépinard & Mazouz, 2021) and "wokisme" (Policar, 2022).

7.2. Rights of the child/Filiation/Family

Rights of the children have been a major argument used by both anti-gender and anti-feminist movements. One element of discourse of the LMPT against Same Sex Marriage, and later on against GAP and MAP is the right of children to have a mother and a father. LMPT argument foregrounded the model of the heterosexual, married, couple as the basis of family - even though in France at , 20% of families were single mother (Cervulle, 2013).The right of the child was also advanced in the fights against the ABCD of Equality, accusing gender theory of blurring the identity definition process of children and of indoctrinating the children.

When it comes to separation of couples in cases of domestic violence, masculinist movements have managed to include the Syndrome of Parental Alienation into jurisdictional habits, notably using the provision 373-2 of the civil code in 2002 that says "Each of mother and father has to maintain personal relationship with the child and respect the links the child has with the other parent". This legislation has, as Pringent and Sueur (2019) mention, "been elaborated without any provisions to limit it, taking

into account essentially the proposals of separated fathers, the legislators have not asked the opinion of mothers, nor taken into considerations the recommendations of feminist organizations”. Their legislative proposals include “the imposition of alternate residency of the child in both parents’ houses by default, condemnation of parents not presenting their child to the court, and recognition of the syndrome of Parental Alienation. Pringent and Sueur (in Bard et al., 2019) highlight that those concepts notably made their way to the law in 2013, in its version adopted by the Senate, before the National Assembly voted them out, after organizations fighting for women’s rights mobilized. Beyond the victimization of men, among their strategies are legislative proposals and forcing their ways to take part to working groups about issues they are interested in, being numerically more important than mother’s representatives, monopolization of speaking time, intimidation and isolation, and calling into question the credibility of their opponents and the use of false theories.

7.3. Islamophobia

Between 2004 (Law forbidding wearing of religious symbols in schools) and 2010 (interdiction to wear burqa and niqab in public space) and up to this day (debate on interdiction of islamic veil wearing in sports) much of the Islamophobic rhetoric in political speeches revolved around women. The prevailing narrative pictures muslim women as unaware victims of islam. A public narrative, recuperated by both the left and the right was formed that gender based violence and women's issues in France were inherently anti-French. This was paired with an increasingly toxic climate towards non-white and predominantly muslim people in France since Sarkozy’s Presidency (Mballo and Bourget, 2018). Dalibert (2021) expands on this through their quantitative and qualitative analysis of all available online articles from seven main news sources in France on the subject of feminist movements in the 2000s and 2010s, consisting of 5336 articles, and finds that both the perpetrators and victims of female oppression are predominantly portrayed as muslim. A public narrative, recuperated by both the left and the right was formed that gender based violence and women's issues in France were inherently anti-French.

7.4. Environment/Ecology

Anti-gender movements have built their discourse around a “human ecology” which shares a certain vision of “nature”, to promote their homophobic agenda on the importance of “the father” and of “biological” families (Béraud, 2021; de Boissieu, 2016). The timing of LMPT coincided with an increased public awareness and discussion of the effects of climate change and environmental limits, and the discourse of the ‘naturalness’ of the sexes linked explicitly with themes around respect for nature in general, following a discursive path prepared by the third Encyclical of Pope Benedict XVI ‘Caritas in veritate’ in 2009 (Stambolis-Ruhstorfer & Tricou, 2018).

Right after LMPT, the term of “integral ecology”, coined by the co-founder of Le Veilleurs (Bès et al., 2014) gained popularity and was later mentioned in Pope Francis’ *Laudato si’* (2015) (de Boissieu, 2016) . According to La Croix journalist Laurent de Boissieu, in addition to criticizing an “overuse” of technology and thus MAP, integral ecology aims at recruiting supporters among the left through a discourse that calls to take into account environmental limits and nudges at degrowth theories.

On its end, “integral feminism” relies on an ecological discourse to highlight the “naturalness” of gender roles and heterosexuality and glorify the role of stay at home mothers (Pavard et al., 2020).

Historians Bibia Pavard, Florence Rochefort and Michelle Zancarini-Fournelle highlight how the critique of contraception, and the pill in particular, is a recurring theme among these antifeminists who claim that “real feminism” needs to respect the laws of nature. The authors conclude,

“The theories of this group of “integral feminists” on degrowth can attract a new public at a time where the ecological awareness becomes necessary, even if this integral ecology reveal themselves to be traditionalist and moralizing in the end” (Pavard et al., 2020, p. 452)

7.5. Alterfeminism

According to della Sudda, the term “alterfeminism” was “created in the 1990’s in contest to the neoliberal globalization, has been reappropriated by Sabine Hérold-Fillias, President of Alternative Libérale (2008-2009). At the time she used it in a way that is hostile to redistribution policies and to policy promoting equality between women and men, notably regarding income. It is also used parallelly in France from 2007 on in a group that is opposed to abortion, Le collectif Alterféministe (created in Paris in 2007)”. The collectif Alterféministe (2007-2010) argument is that there is no rivalry between women and men but complementarity. Then “forgotten” until 2017, the term is reinvested by a militant generation born from the opposition to the Same-Sex Marriage Legislation in France (loi Taubira). Essayist and Philosopher Marianne Durano uses it, so do Les Antigones, linking their action to the feminists of the first wave of feminism, while disconnecting themselves from the contemporary “neofeminism” (della Sudda, 2022)

The concept of “féminisme intégral” developed by Philosopher Marianne Durano wants to “defend women integrally, without negating their specificity and specific vulnerability”. She frames this in reference to the integral ecology as defined by the Vatican in *Laudato Si* (2015).

The concept of “neofeminism” was defined by Eugénie Bastié (2016) as a pejorative way to refer to the current feminist waves, as groups that mobilise counter-temporally (since equality is supposed to have been mostly achieved) on issues that would be peripheral and useless such as inclusive writing or gender-biased toys. Neofeminists are also described as inquisitorial when they use movements such as “#balancetonporc”. Neofeminism is also presented as an accomplice of islamism and mass migration from 2017 on in clear opposition to intersectionalism.

8. Transnational Connections

Transnational connections seem to be at play in several ways in the anti-gender and anti-feminism movements. The embedding of anti-gender activism in a wider conservative moment across the world has also seemed an evidence in the years of the Trump presidency and the emergence of a nationalist, nativist and natalist international that meets on occasions such as the annual Budapest Demographic summit.

The links between the French and Italian extreme right-wing movements is well documented, but further links with other European and International extreme right-wing movements has been notably highlighted by a recent study by the European Parliamentary Forum for Sexual and Reproductive

Rights (EPF)³⁵. The report notably states: “In Europe, the ECLJ, led by Grégor Puppink, has been active in anti-gender advocacy at national and European levels, as well as around the Council of Europe and United Nations bodies in Geneva, notably during the homophobic protests of La Manif Pour Tous (LMPT) in France in 2013, serving as a legal focal point for the anti-abortion ICE “One of us” and playing a leading role in Agenda Europe summits.”

The report also mentions the support of Fondation Saint-André le Premier, i.e. founded by Russian Oligarch Vladimir Yakounine - to French European Parliamentarian Aymeric Chauprade, and Fabrice Sorlin, representative of the World Congress of Family. Medias also report on the deep links between the movements (Turchi, 2015).

Other influential networks include the European Center for Law and Justice (ECLJ), the international conservative Christian NGO founded in 1998 in Strasbourg by two American lawyers, which is active with European bodies and the UN. The ECLJ declares to act mainly for the defense of human life from conception, against euthanasia, for traditional marriage, for the right to conscientious objection and freedom of belief, as well as the defense of Christians from the East. According to Le Monde, the ECLJ is a lobby “which relays at European level many of the fights of La Manif pour tous”.

The “Backlash” report (Clavaud et al., 2023), from the Jean Jaures Foundation and the NGO Equipop highlights European links between anti-gender and anti-feminist movements, notably through “the Agenda Europe20 coordination. Its approach is analyzed in the report of the European Parliamentary Forum for Sexual and Reproductive Rights (EPF) entitled “Restoring the natural order”. The coordination brings together more than 100 associations from more than 30 European countries. This movement is based on the concept of “natural law”, which forms the normative framework for the fight against sexual and reproductive health and rights (SRHR). Members are Catholic activists and conservatives.”

The “Backlash” report also argues that “anti-rights movements all over the world, which very closely imitate the strategies of feminist organizations in order to weaken them better: clearly established lines of conduct in reaction to feminist discourse, funding via foundations and governments, signing of joint declarations...It states that “The political program of anti-rights on a European scale can be summed up as follows: “To change the legal and societal status quo in a way that is totally contrary to fundamental European rights. They are in an expansionist approach, that is to say that they want to impose their reactionary vision, for a rollback of sexual and reproductive rights. Their attacks also target the rights of LGBTQIA+ people.” (Clavaud et al., 2023).

When it comes to the Catholic movements, the role of the Vatican is framing and supporting the debate has been highlighted by several studies, including by Prearo & Garbagnoli, (2018). In section 3 we also mentioned the instrumentalisation of the legislation on European parties to access funds by the European Parliament by the offspring political party of Civitas.

The masculinist movement is an offspring of movements born in the US and in Quebec.

³⁵ https://www.epfweb.org/sites/default/files/2022-03/EPF_EN_TOTI_9SEP%20DEF%20-%20FR.pdf

9. Explanations of the anti-gender/anti-feminist backlash

The political turn that brought to the French presidency a political alternance more favourable to gender and women's rights in 2012 (Election of President F. Hollande in 2012 and then election of President E. Macron in 2017) opened a new political opportunity for gender and women's rights activists. The willingness of those governments to advance on key legislations and issues such as same-sex marriage, medically assisted procreation for all, fight against sexual and sexist stereotypes (ABCD de l'Égalité) has provided a synergetic move for conservative movements, which were operating in the backend and less in the forefront until La Manif Pour Tous. These gained momentum and a strong access to public debate from 2013 on, building on the ground of State-led legislations attacking such of the muslim women's religious outfits and islamophobia. The strength of La Manif Pour Tous took the government by surprise, the length of the mobilisation provided experience and access to the media to many of the most conservative groups and discourses.

The declination of #MeToo in France, with the slightly more verbally violent version with #BalanceTonPorc (#NameYourPig) provided the ground for the development of an articulated discourse against the practices of "neo-feminist" and for alternative discourses that were recognising no or only some parts of the feminism legacy. Amandine Clavaud (2022) also presents the Covid period as a period of Backlash for women's rights as cases of domestic violence increased, access to birth planning associations became more difficult, the charge on women increased and work-life balance suffered and as women paid the toll of being more present in the care industry and at the same time more touched by unemployment.

Recent publications document the backlash, such as the report report of the Haut Conseil à l'Égalité entre les femmes et les hommes (High Council for Equality between Women and Men, HCE, Pierre-Brossolette et al., 2023), traces international backlash since the me too movement and compares it to a backlash post 70s feminism, insisting on the role of the internet in the growth of masculinist movements and cyberharassment, a tendency also documented by Le Monde³⁶.

10. Counter-movements

Reactions to the backlash include: creation of new targeted movements, against cyberharassment for instance, or as a safeguard against sexist and sexual violence in politics or against discourses framing muslim women, counter demonstrations, creative, media attracting actions such as kissing and institutional reactions such as the proposal to constitutionalise the right to abortion or institutional campaigns such as "Sans oui, c'est interdit" (on consent) or creation of coalition movements such as "Ensemble contre le sexisme" (Together against sexism).

Some movements have sprung in response to new forms of anti-gender attacks, this is specifically the case of movements against cyberattacks such as Féministes contre le cyberharcèlement and "StopFisha", feminist groups created to help victims of cyber-attacks. Féministes contre le cyberharcèlement started the viral hashtag #TwitterAgainstWomen (2016).

³⁶https://www.lemonde.fr/pixels/article/2022/10/12/cinq-ans-apres-metoo-l-antifeminisme-prospere-sur-les-reseaux-sociaux_6145406_4408996.html

At the height of LMPT (2013), countermovements reacted by creative actions such as massive kissings³⁷ dedicated to providing counter news to the media. In the Streets feminist and LGBTQI+ rights activists have also reacted to demonstrations against Medically Assisted Procreation, by organizing counter demonstrations, sometimes leading to violent interactions³⁸ (2020, 2021).

Movements such as the feminist movement Lallab were created in reaction against anti-feminist/anti-gender views of muslim women.

When it comes to the political sphere, a movement such as the “Observatoire des violences sexistes et sexuelles en politiques” was created in reaction to a specific violence affair.

A feminist response to masculinists has been the development of research/ programs on masculinities, for example the podcast *Les couilles sur la table* by Victoire Tuillon (which later became a book (Tuillon, 2019)). Blais and Dupuis-Deri (2019) highlight that in France two anti-masculinist collectives, have managed to operate over long periods of time, although they do not operate anymore: the Collective “Stop Masculinisme” created in Grenoble in 2011, which published a book entitled “Against Masculinism: Guide of Intellectual Self-Defense”. The collective is mix and organizes protests and alerts against masculinist activities and events notably by calling to media and local political actors. The second collective mentioned is Collectif Mixte antimasculinist Ile-de-France-Paris, created in 2013, after a mobilization of divorced and separated fathers. Both groups were close to anarchists networks. The collective organizes “counter-meetings, projections of films and debates” and “written and publish texts such as *The Myth of Beaten Men* and “*Imposed Paternalities : A False Problem*” as well as “popular education workshops”. There is also emerging research looking at individual initiatives and men’s reflection on anti-masculinist (Grannis, 2019).

Creation of coalitions of actors is another strategy used, such as Ensemble contre le sexisme is a coalition of 40 movements to fight against sexism and gender discrimination in France. The recent HCE report mentions for instance that “Since 2017, Ensemble Contre Le Sexisme has been organizing an event to raise awareness of the issue of sexism in all its forms and consequences.” (Pierre-Brossolette et al., 2023)

Finally, identifying and reporting about the Backlash has been realized by organizations that have been pinpointed in this study as allies of feminism, such as HCE or by political foundations (Clavaud et al., 2023) or by state agencies such as the Arcom (ex-CSA) report on the representation of women in videos watched on YouTube (2018) or its follow-up study edited by the Fondation des femmes “Digital: sexism on the loose, Representation of women in the most viewed videos on YouTube, August 2021”.

³⁷ <https://tetu.com/2016/09/06/kiss-in-contre-manif-pour-tous/>

³⁸ <https://www.francebleu.fr/infos/societe/projet-de-loi-bioethique-quelques-milliers-de-manifestants-s-opposent-dans-la-rue-1612038583>

11. Other Important Issues

Another important issue in France includes mobilizations for and against changing the use of “Mademoiselle” in administrative forms (Bastié, 2016) and debates around “Inclusive language” (Della Sudda & Paoletti, 2022).

12. Conclusion

Research on Anti-gender and anti-feminist movements remains little developed in France and limited to a few key academics. In National and International Research, La Manif Pour Tous (2013) concentrates most of the attention. This movement represents a galvanizing momentum for anti-gender and anti-feminists activists in France and beyond, signaling the renewal and transformation of the nebula of Christian, Nationalist, Souveranist, Identitarian Movements. It is also the point of departure of a penetration of public discourse in France of the vocabulary and argumentations developed in great parts by the Vatican in reaction to “theory du genre”. This happened on the fertile ground of islamophobia in France leading to mainstreaming of femonationalism to a large public.

Sexual and Reproductive Rights are at the core of the battles of anti-gender movements, which in the latter period concentrated their efforts on issues related to transgender transitions as an evil example of the perverse effects of “gender theory”.

Antifeminist movements consolidated during the 2011-2021 period. First, some movements were created directly as a response to mediatic actions of FEMEN, and as the development of a women’s led discourse at the right and extreme right, which accepts some elements of the first waves of feminism, while attacking vehemently what they call “neofeminism”. A growing nebula of right wing women and women collectives develops new words to position themselves in relation to the heritage of feminism and current feminist movements, such as femellism, alterfeminism, integral feminism.

#MeToo and the Covid period mark another point of rupture in the development of antifeminism and masculism in France, which reaches out one step further, and manages to perpetuate public discourse, thanks to the undertaking of elements of the discourse by various public figures and intellectuals, including some known as feminists.

Both anti-gender and anti-feminists movements continue to use a wide array of strategies to defend their ideas, from influence of legislation and policy makers, to staged street actions shaped to attract media attention and extensive use of technology to both diffuse their ideas and attack their opponents.

A phenomena of backlash on women’s rights has been observed by feminists groups, State organizations and Media alike and documented in recent reports, testimony of the strength of anti-gender and anti-feminists discourses and practices. The French policy makers have continued to slowly advance the legislation in favour of LGBTQIA+ rights, and have claimed to act more in the area of women’s rights, while letting some of the movements define the terms of the debates, notably when it comes to the relation of the movements with islam, thereby often validating femonationalism.

13. Timeline

14. List of the anti-gender and anti-feminist organizations and initiatives

Name of the organization (original)	Name of the organization (English)	Anti-gender or anti-feminist?	Logo of the organization	Head of the organization (in the period 2010-2021)	Web-page (social media)	Size of the organization (if available)	Comment (brief description)
La Manif Pour Tous	The protest for all	Anti-gender		Ludovine de la Rochère	https://www.lamanifpourtous.fr/	not available but estimated at least 100,000+ people in France at one of their protests.	Created in 2012 in opposition to gay marriage (nicknamed le mariage pour tous). Regalvanised against ABCD de l'égalité in 2013-14 (most 'successful' movement) and then against the proposed change in IVF laws (to allow lesbian couples & single mothers access) in 2019-21.
Les Antigones	The Antigones	Anti-feminist		Anne Trewby	https://lesantigones.fr/	unknown, likely small.	"alter-feminism", created in opposition to new waves of feminism and legalisation of gay marriage. First actions were directly against FEMEN. Links to far right and the church.

Nemesis	Nemesis	Anti-feminist		Alice Cordier	https://www.collectif-nemesis.com/	100>	Anti-immigration / racist “feminist” collective. Often infiltrate feminist protests with islamophobic signs / public performances.
Alliance Vita	Alliance Vita	Anti-feminist & anti-gender		Xavier Mirabel 2010-14, Francois-Xavier Peres 2014-2022, Anne-Charlotte Rimaud 2022+	https://www.alliancevita.org/en/	Claims on site to have over 37,000 supporters and 1000 volunteers in France.	anti-abortion, anti-gay marriage and adoption, anti-PMA
Civitas	Civitas	Anti-gender		Alain Escada	https://www.civitas-institut.com/	165,000 supporters.	For the rechristianisation of France & Europe. opposed mariage pour tous separate to LMPT, supported <i>jours de retrait de l'école</i>

Observatoire de la Petite Sirène	Observatory of the Little Mermaid	Anti-gender		Céline Masson and Caroline Eliacheff	https://www.observatoirepetitesirene.org/	<p>Collective supposedly for the rights of children. Created against rise of gender dysphoria diagnostics. Claims children do not have the maturity to consent to having a trans identity and is against autodetermination. Shared pro-conversion therapy media, and spreads disinformation such as claiming that all medication for gender dysphoria is irreversible.</p>
Les Survivants	The Survivors	Anti-feminist			https://lessurvivants.com/	<p>Anti-abortion in all forms, members are exclusively born post 1975 abortion legalization. Raise awareness of 'survivor syndrome' - mental health affected by the fact they could have been aborted. Arguing abortion is not just a women's issue as 'we all have a 1 in 5 chance of not living'.</p>

MGTOW - Men Going Their Own Way	Men Going Their Own Way	Anti-feminist			https://mgtow-france.fr/		<p>French branch of international mainly online community MGTOW. Believe feminism is destroying society, outwardly anti-feminist, masculinist and spreads women-hating messages. Used as a tag online, one example in France is a youtuber with a large following 'l'Observateur'.</p>
Reconquête!	Recapture / win back	Anti-feminist and anti-gender.		Eric Zemmour	https://www.parti-reconquete.fr/	127,000 claimed members as of June 2022	<p>Political group created in late 2021 by Eric Zemmour and gained 7% of the national vote. Misogynistic and homophobic messages / ideals.</p>

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GREECE

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1. Introduction

Research and publications on antifeminist and antigender politics in 2010-2021 are scant and rarefied in the Greek context. The attempted reconstruction in the following draws on few excerpts from literature on the feminist and LGBTQI+ movement in this period and limited first-hand research undertaken for the purposes of this project, which provides important indications related to key events and will be further pursued in depth in the coming months. The less than ten publications on anti-gender and anti-feminist politics and discourse were identified through a web search using these terms (and the Greek words for them), as well as the terms ‘Golden Dawn-women,’ femicide (in Greek and English), ‘same-sex cohabitation pact/civil partnership’ (in Greek and English) and ‘shared custody’ (in Greek). The latter terms refer to recent legislation which sparked intense debate and opposition. The excerpts from publications on feminist and LGBTQI+ movements were discovered through the search carried out for such movements (for WP2). Finally, there was also targeted research in Greek alt-right sources (blogs, websites) based on our prior knowledge of the actors.

According to Αθανασίου (2017: 25-26) aversion to feminism in the 2010s is inextricably tied up with the agenda of social and racial racism and constitutes a pivotal dimension of the discourse against ‘Metapolitefsi’ and post-democracy.¹ The incrimination of feminism has been a core motif of social conservatism in Greece. During the dictatorship (1967-1974), the notorious slogan «Πατρίς-Θρησκεία-Οικογένεια» [‘Fatherland-Religion-Family’] summed up the conditions that a ‘law-abiding’ subject must fulfil according to the nationalist ideology of the post-war right. The logic of the ‘plaster’ was deployed under the junta to circumscribe the national body and exclude all kinds of ‘foreign bodies.’ In the same vein, the norm of the ‘ethno-racial’ purity, which is underpinned by military masculinity and subdued femininity, is the fundamental presumption informing contemporary neo-Nazi discourse and politics in Greece. This calls for a reflection on persisting and resilient patriarchal, nationalist, homophobic and sexist norms underlying modern Greek society in the ‘Metapolitefsi’ era. At the same time, there is in Greece and internationally a leftist incrimination of feminism on the grounds that the feminist turn in left-wing politics occurred at the price of disregarding the everyday material experiences of working class people. This logic, according to which the left should be primarily concerned with the plight of the working class, conceived as male and white, instead of ‘secondary issues’ accords with the contemporary spirit of a generalized conservative shift.

However, in the period 2015-19, several laws and policies promoting gender equality and LGBTQI+ rights have been enacted. Key examples include (Remoundou, 2022; Anastasiadou, 2020):

- anti-discrimination laws in the workplace, which were put in place in 2005, consider now other spheres such as gender identity, sexual orientation, and sex characteristics;
- the Law 4356/2015, known as the ‘cohabitation pact’, civil partnership contract, legalized civil unions for same-sex couples;
- an amendment of Law 4285/2014, ‘Law Against Racism and Xenophobia,’ introduced important reforms regarding hate speech and violence against LGBTI+ individuals or groups in Greece. This

¹ ‘Metapolitefsi’ is a Greek term historically established since 1974 to refer to the process of restoring constitutional democracy in Greece and the new phase of political history in the country after the military dictatorship in 1967-1974. An equivalent term used in Spain is ‘Transition.’

was further reinforced in 2016 with the extension of strong anti-discrimination protections based on sexual orientation, gender, and religion in the workplace;

- the legal gender recognition Law 4491/2017 simplified the procedures for transgender people to change their legal gender identity;
- the Law 4538/2018 gave to same-sex couples the right to child fostering to same-sex.
- in 2018, the Greek parliament ratified the Istanbul Convention on violence against women (4531/2018), integrating it in national legislation;
- the Law 4604/2019 on 'Promoting Substantive Gender Equality, Preventing and Combating Gender-Based Violence-Provisions for Granting Citizenship -Provisions for Elections of Local Authorities Other Provisions' lays down the content of Equality Plans, and the private and public bodies liable to produce them. This law also increased the gender quota on election candidate lists from 30% to 40%. However, after the government change in July 2019 and the consequent political shift to the right, several of the above measures were repealed (e.g. primary and secondary school classes on Gender Identities planned by the former government and the 40% gender quota in elections have been abolished), and new conservative gender policies have been promoted in the country, such as the new 4800/2021 law on 'shared parental responsibility;'
- the Law 4589/2019, passed under the left-leaning SYRIZA government, includes an article that provides for the establishment of Committees for Gender Equality (CGE) in all Greek universities, as advisory bodies to assist the university administration to advance gender equality;
- in 2019, the Greek Criminal Code was amended by the same government to recognize officially that all sex without consent constitutes rape and is therefore punishable by law;
- the law 4706/2020 mandates Greek listed companies to meet a 25% quota of the underrepresented gender on their boards from July 2021 onwards;
- Last but not least, in response to the European Commission's first-ever implemented strategy to enshrine the rights of LGBTQI+ people in the European Union, a Greek committee was set up in March 2021 to draft a National Strategy for the Equality of LGBTQI+ people.

2. The history of the anti-gender/anti-feminist movement and its context

Given the deeply engrained patriarchal culture of Greek society, antifeminist and anti-LGBTQI+ rights actors have been always present in recent decades, featuring mainly the Greek Orthodox Church, the political and cultural right and the far right, but also members of other political parties and sectors of civil society infused with this culture.

In the period of reference, a number of events and legislative reforms triggered the resurgence of older antifeminist/anti-LGBTQI+ actors, chiefly from the Church and the traditional right, and the appearance of new actors.

1. To begin with, a first grave incident of antifeminist politics and discourse was the arrest and public stigmatization of HIV-positive women who were drug addicts and worked reputedly as prostitutes in 2012. In what can be described as the worst violation of human rights in Greece in recent years, police arrested more than 2000 women from prostitution houses and the streets. They forcibly tested for HIV by the Hellenic Center of Disease Control and Prevention (HCDCP), which detected HIV-positive sex workers. 32 HIV-positive women were imprisoned in April 2012, and their identities, photos and personal health condition were publicly disclosed by order of the attorney of the Athens First Instance Court with a view to 'protecting the community from contagious diseases.' The personal data of HIV-positive women have been published in newspapers, the media, social media and the Internet, in a

major violation of the right to protect personal data enshrined in the Greek Constitution in Art 9.1. In this witch-hunt, the discourse of mass media, police, justice and healthcare agencies stigmatized these persons as a 'hygienic bomb' which purposefully transmitted the HIV virus to ignorant Greek family leaders. Uncovered photos of these women were published in press in order to 'protect the Greek family.' The Health Minister at the time, Andreas Loverdos, associated the rise in HIV incidence with migrants and prostitution. Prostitutes potentially infected with virus were considered as a 'threat to society at large' (Καναβέλη, 2016: 41-42).

2. The extension to same-sex couple of the 'cohabitation pact,' or civil partnership contract, that was legislated for heterosexual couples in 2008 was a second major point of contention and anti-gender discourse and practice in the 2010s. In the public and parliamentary debate on the issue in 2013, the bishop of Piraeus Serafeim objected in a press release that such a legal reform will bring about the subversion and eventual ruin of the institution of the family and Greek society at large, as it would institutionalize the 'reversal of human ontology and physiology and the enshrinement of the psychopathological diversion of homosexuality.' He went on to argue that the institutionalization of homosexuality would lead to the institutionalization of paedophilia and bestiality. The statement of the archbishop Hieronymus was more moderate, noting that the union of two human beings through marriage is a grave Mystery for the Church and anything outside this Mystery is alien to church's life (Καραμάνου, 2021: 338-339).

Greece was condemned in December 2013 by the Strasbourg Court which ruled that the lack of legal protection for same-sex couples contravenes the European Convention of Human Rights. Thereafter, the extension of the 'cohabitation pact' -civil partnership- to same-sex couples became one of the most burning issues in the Greek parliament. In November 2015 the Ministry of Justice of the coalition government led by the left-wing and former anti-austerity SYRIZA party announced certain key points of the new bill. This would enable same-sex couples to make a 'cohabitation contract' and would grant certain inheritance rights. Citizens were invited to a public debate on the bill 'Cohabitation pact and other decrees' which took place on-line on the site of the Ministry of Justice in 9-23 November 2015 (Μίχος, 2017: 8-9).

An avalanche of reactions by the Greek Orthodox Church followed suit. The archbishop of Athens stated that this contract is a 'deviation from life,' while the bishop of Kalavruta and Aigialia Amvrosios argued on his personal blog that this law corrupts the institution of the family and constitutes a menace for Orthodoxy and Greek identity. The bishop of Piraeus Serafeim announced that his bishopric would terminate any relationship with MPs who would vote in favour of the bill. After the passage of the bill on 23 December 2015, he made a public statement arguing that the bill is at odds with the cultural identity of Greek, whose core elements consist in religious marriage and a family made up by a man and a woman. The law turns 'a tragic vulgarity into a lawful good deserving legal protection' (Μίχος, 2017: 10-11).

However, the reaction to the law involved broader sectors of civil society who were tellingly represented in the official on-line public deliberation on the bill before it was brought to the parliament (Μίχος, 2017).

3. The issue and terminology of femicide/feminicide («γυναικοκτονία» in Greek) has been another hot issue which attracted antifeminist discourse in late years. According to Γκασούκα (2020: 58) and Μιχαλακέλη (2020: 90-93), the term has been dismissed by the new and old right as abusive, coined by weird leftists. Blogs, webpages, authors in the mainstream 'bourgeois' press, opinion leaders and media personalities are at the forefront of this 'battle of words.' Key (alt-) right politicians and vectors of anti-feminist discourse, disseminated through Twitter, blogs and other digital media, have

participated in this public opposition to the use of ‘femicide,’ such as Thanos Tzimeros (Θάνος Τζήμερος@Thanos Tzimeros), Konstantinos Bogdanos (Constantinosbogdanos@bogdanosk) and Yannis Loverdos (Γιάννης Λοβέρδος@YiannisLoverdos; see Μιχαλακέλη, 2020). Even apparently more moderate and ‘liberal’ media personalities on the right, such as Paschos Mandravelis, have questioned the terms and the arguments not only of femicide but of gender-based violence, as well, countering that the expression of aversion should be due to violence rather than the genders of victim and perpetrator (Μιχαλακέλη, 2020: 93). This rejection is arguably the effect of a collective endorsement of a macho culture in which man is entitled to impose his will, even through corporal or psychological violence. Plenty of studies establish that this culture, calling on men to ‘hit as a man’ is deeply ingrained in Greek society.

4. Diverse and nuanced strands of anti-feminist discourse and politics were also elaborated recently around the new 4800/2021 law on ‘shared parental responsibility’ which was laid down by the right-wing New Democracy government. In the Greek context, patriarchal relations still assign disproportionately to women the task of bringing up children and caring for dependent family members. A radical legal reform could problematize this naturalized inequality, deconstructing an understanding of women as self-evidently apt caregivers, challenging relations of blood and the proprietary logic informing Greek family law, and pluralizing the positions included in the concept of family (Παπαναγιώτου, 2021: 128-130).

In the former family law, parental responsibility/custody in the case of divorce is decided by courts, unless the divorce were consensual. According to the new law, in the case of divorce or the dissolution of a civil partnership, both parents maintain together and equally their parental responsibility/custody, unless they themselves agree to make a different arrangement. If the agreement is not kept or if shared responsibility harms children’s interests, they can take recourse to mediation and, ultimately, courts may decide (Παπαναγιώτου, 2021: 131). In effect, shared responsibility would entail an ongoing common decision-making about the children’s everyday life which is very difficult to implement. It presupposes collaboration and equal power which is lacking in unequal gender relations. Shared custody as the default option or agreement or mediation are fields in which gendered, class and other social differences can subvert real equality, often exposing women to gender violence and harassment by their former partners (Παπαναγιώτου, 2021: 133).

Purportedly, gender biases presided from the outset over the new legislation, as groups of ‘organized fathers’ admitted that they were the sole interlocutors of the Ministry of Justice in the process of framing the law, excluding other agencies and organizations.

The controversy around ‘shared parental responsibility’ mobilized right-wing antifeminist politicians in the parliament, such as Yannis Loverdos of New Democracy, but significantly it sparked the creation of a ‘male movement’ in Greece by groups such as «Ενεργοί μπαμπάδες» (‘Active daddies’). These actors do not only advocate for shared custody but make also a case for gender-based violence against men which is allegedly higher in Greece than violence affecting women (<https://www.energoimpampades.gr/i-via-den-echei-fylo/>) and call for the inclusion of ‘parental alienation’ in the law against domestic violence which is now under reform (<https://www.energoimpampades.gr/goniki-apoxenosi-sto-ypo-anamorfosi-thesmiko-plaisio-gia-tin-antimetopisi-tis-endooikogeneiakis-vias/>). The foregoing group, along with the cognate «Σύλλογος Συνεπιμέλεια» (Shared Custody Association, <https://www.synepimelia.gr/>) are arguably new actors in antifeminist and antigender discourse who have international links (such as the ‘International Council of Shared Parenting’) and have not been studied yet from this perspective. Hence, they should become the focus of first-hand research in the context of the present research project in Greece.

5. A related late event which sparked heated debate was the organization of the ‘1st Panhellenic Conference of Fertility and Reproductive Autonomy. Limits and options’ that would be held in the city of Ioannina in North-western Greece at the initiative of a group of male Gynaecologists at the Universities of Ioannina, Thrace and Thessaly, along with the ‘Greek Association of Reproductive Medicine of Athens.’ This would be held in 2-4 July 2021 with the participation of university professors from medical, law, political science and other schools, as well as representatives of the Orthodox Church (bishops). Its aim would be to foreground the issue of low fertility, to propose remedies, to convey the message that childbearing and the creation of families is the ‘joy of life,’ and to help restore the model of the nuclear family. The conference would be placed under the auspices of state institutions including the Region of Epirus, the Ministry of Development and the General Secretariat of Family Policy and Gender Equality.² As a result of fierce reaction by feminist groups and the opposition, state support was withheld, and the conference was cancelled. Still, the group of actors brought together around this event, including male professors of medicine and the ‘Greek Association of Reproductive Medicine,’ as well as the discourse and the public debate that erupted on the occasion, are worth exploring as antifeminist actors, practices and frames of reasoning.

6. Another major antifeminist and anti-gender actor during these years is the far-right and particularly the neo-Nazi Golden Dawn party, whose rise was occasioned by the number of immigrants that Greece started receiving in the 1990s from Balkan and eastern Mediterranean countries, Central and South Asia, and Africa (Carastathis, 2015). Immigrants were characterized as criminals that threaten the Greek society (Carastathis, 2015). This is one of the reasons that explains the rise of xenophobic discourses and the Golden Dawn, whose leadership is now convicted and imprisoned, and constituted a standing source and agency of antifeminist and anti-gender politics and discourse in the decade 2010-2020 on the streets and in parliament.

A telling illustration of such far-right activism occurred in the aftermath of Zack Kostopoulos transphobic murder. On the 25th of September 2018, a group of far-right wing people staged a demonstration on the street where the murder took place, repeating the slogan ‘Πρεζάκια και γκέι δεν είστε αναγκαίοι’ [‘Druggies and gays you are not needed’] (Αθανασίου & Παπανικολάου, 2020: 11; <https://www.documentonews.gr/article/paralrhma-misoys-exw-apoto-kosmhmatopwleio-poy-exase-th-zwh-toy-o-zak-kwstopoylos-prezakia-kai-gkei-deneisteanagkaioi-video-photos>).

7. Finally, it worth pointing out that traditional leftist ‘communist’ parties such as KKE [Communist Party of Greece] are sceptical or even dismissive when it comes to LGBTQI+ rights and politics. Hence, KKE voted against extending to same-sex couples the right to form civil partnerships when the law was passed in December 2015 and the Legal Recognition of Gender Identity in October 2017, on the grounds that ‘sexual orientation, sexual relationships and sexual satisfaction are private matters and, accordingly, cannot produce social rights’ (Κοσσυφολόγου, 2018: 46).

² <https://www.isioanninon.gr/info/conferences/2000-1%CE%BF-%CF%80%CE%B1%CE%BD%CE%B5%CE%BB%CE%BB%CE%AE%CE%BD%CE%B9%CE%BF-%CF%83%CF%85%CE%BD%CE%AD%CE%B4%CF%81%CE%B9%CE%BF-%CE%B3%CE%BF%CE%BD%CE%B9%CE%BC%CF%8C%CF%84%CE%B7%CF%84%CE%B1%CF%82-%CE%BA%CE%B1%CE%B9-%CE%B1%CE%BD%CE%B1%CF%80%CE%B1%CF%81%CE%B1%CE%B3%CF%89%CE%B3%CE%B9%CE%BA%CE%AE%CF%82-%CE%B1%CF%85%CF%84%CE%BF%CE%BD%CE%BF%CE%BC%CE%AF%CE%B1%CF%82-%CF%8C%CF%81%CE%B9%CE%B1-%CE%BA%CE%B1%CE%B9-%CE%B5%CF%80%CE%B9%CE%BB%CE%BF%CE%B3%CE%AD%CF%82-2-4-7-202>

3. Actors

3.1. Golden Dawn

Golden Dawn, the main anti-feminist and anti-gender Neo-Nazi political party in Greece, which has been normalized and legitimized as such when it entered the parliament in 2012 (Carastathis, 2015; Petrogiannis & Freidenvall, 2022) and has been convicted as a criminal organization because its members assassinated Pavlos Fyssas in Athens, 2013 (Remoundou, 2022), became a cardinal space for expression of heteronormative, sexist, homophobic, anti-leftist, xenophobic, racist and authoritarian discourse focused on anti-immigrant and anti-Islamic scapegoating (Dagkouly-Kyriakoglou, 2021; Koronaïou & Sakellariou, 2017). Golden Dawn's dominant discourse promoted traditional values, identifying motherhood as essential to women's lives, defining gender in biological terms and dismissing feminism as leftist politics linked to a 'new world order' that endangers the national community (Kamenou, 2023).

The agency of women in Golden Dawn has received particular attention in recent research. Koronaïou & Sakellariou, (2017) analyse the role of Golden Dawn women drawing on online material retrieved from the website of the women's organisation of the party, Women's Front (<http://whitewomenfront.blogspot.gr/>) – which not active any more- in Golden's Dawn previous official webpage (<http://www.xryshaygh.com/>) – replaced by (ΧΡΥΣΗ ΑΥΓΗ – xrisi avgi site) and the website of the party's youth division (Antepithesi/Counterattack) (<http://www.antepithesi.gr/>). After reviewing diverse online material, they mention examples of the women's participation in the activity of the political party such as the distribution of food to the poor and homeless or to families, including also clothes or toys for children, and dissemination of Golden Dawn's ideology through the distribution of leaflets and the party's official newspaper and in demonstrations against immigrants.

They suggest that the activities in which women were involved reproduced 'the stereotype that women are more sensitive and suited to work on issues related to disabled people, children, older people etc.' (Koronaïou & Sakellariou, 2017:13)

With regard to the visibility of Golden Dawn's women in the parliament, one out of twenty-one MPs of the party after the elections of May 2012 was a woman: the leader's wife. One out of seventeen was a woman (again the leader's wife) after the elections of June 2012. And in the elections of January 2015 two of seventeen were women, including the leader's wife. However, all three European Parliament members elected in 2014 are men (Koronaïou & Sakellariou, 2017). The authors argue that the above-mentioned findings indicate that Golden's Dawn women should be active but within the confines of their gender and sex, and that still the major role that need to fulfil is that of the mother and child-bearer.

On the other hand, a recent study of Golden Dawn's women activists and their counterparts in Cyprus (Kamenou, 2023) brings out a more nuanced and complex variant of anti-feminist politics and discourse. In the last fifteen years in Greece, far-right women contest feminism while drawing on some of feminism's main themes and positions, appealing thus among women with diverse positions on gender, politics and feminism. Hence, GD women opposed feminism on the grounds that it calls on women to focus on their career, but they claimed both that having a family places women 'at the highest pedestal' in society and that 'we' [i.e GD] do not want women to stay at home (Kamenou, 2023: 8-9). They explicitly affirm the ability of men and women to do 'the same things,' while attacking feminism by arguing that it 'inferiorises' women because it wants them not to be different from men and to adopt an 'androgynous' style (Kamenou, 2023: 10). Far-right women articulated thus a strong form of female political militancy and agency, presenting themselves as 'political soldiers' and even

prioritizing their political militancy over personal family life in ways that challenge perceptions of gender roles within the far right. They reconstructed their party's discourse as implying no distinction between male and female political agency, while requiring the preservation of gendered modes of manifesting this agency (Kamenou, 2023: 11, 13).

3.2. Christian Orthodox Church

Another prominent anti-feminist actor in Greece is the Christian Orthodox Church, the official religion of the state, whose key figures and typical discourse are illustrated in the foregoing account of the debate around the 'cohabitation pact' of same-sex couples (Anastasiadou, 2000).

3.3. Afiste me na ziso (Αφήστε με να ζήσω)

In 2018, the movement Afiste me na ziso ('Let me live') made its first public appearance, advocating against legal abortions.

3.4. Right-wing and alt-right politicians and media personalities

Key old and alt-right politicians and vectors of anti-feminist discourse, disseminated through Twitter, blogs and other digital media include Thanos Tzimeros (Θάνος Τζήμερος@Thanos Tzimeros), Konstantinos Bogdanos (Constantinosbogdanos@bogdanosk) and Yannis Loverdos (Γιάννης Λοβέρδος@YiannisLoverdos; see Μιχαλακέλη, 2020). The list should be expanded through further first-hand research by looking into the cases of right-wing politicians and media personalities such as Rachil Makri, president of the political formation 'Victory Front' (<https://www.facebook.com/rachel.makri>), and Afrodit Latinopoulou who is vice president of the new right-wing party 'Fatherland' and has vocally and aggressively sided with 'fathers' against mothers and women on the issue of the 'shared parental responsibility law' (<https://latinopoulou.gr/synepimeleia/>)

3.5. Male movement for shared custody and against 'women's violence'

Occasioned by the debate around the new 4800/2021 law on 'shared parental responsibility' drawn up by the right-wing New Democracy government, a 'male movement' of groups such as «Ενεργοί μπαμπάδες» ('Active daddies') has arisen, mainly through on-line campaigns and lobbying with the government. These actors do not only advocate for shared custody but make also a case for gender-based violence against men, (<https://www.energoimpampades.gr/i-via-den-echei-fylo/>) demanding the inclusion of 'parental alienation' in the law against domestic violence which is now under reform (<https://www.energoimpampades.gr/goniki-apoxenosi-sto-ypo-anamorfosi-thesmiko-plaisio-gia-tin-antimetopisi-tis-endooikogeneiakis-vias/>). This group along with the cognate «Σύλλογος Συνεπιμέλεια» (Shared Custody Association, <https://www.synepimelia.gr/>) are new actors in antifeminist and antigender mobilization discourse with international links (such as the 'International Council of Shared Parenting').

3.6. Media outlets

Diverse right-wing journals (such as ‘Makeleio,’ ‘Eleftheri Ora’ etc.), blogs and twitter addresses (e.g. <https://twitter.com/bogdanosk?lang=el>, <https://latinopoulou.gr/>), news websites (e.g. pronews.gr, energoimpampades.gr,), and radio stations (such as the one belonging to the nationalist right-wing party ‘Hellenic Solution’) disseminate antifeminist and antigender discourse but have not been systematically studied in existing literature. They should become the object of further research in the context of the project (see e.g. https://www.pronews.gr/elliniki-politiki/binteo-sok-i-drug-queen-pou-diavase-paramythia-sta-paidia-paradexetai-oti-pidei-15xrona/?fbclid=IwAR0teHZstMAiJeceij6i_wD7iWL5j3MvgD05owkb0WiRPBBJsFXdW4YDkK4).

3.7. Civil society

Several non-organized citizens and groups in civil society who articulate antifeminist and antigender positions in relevant debates, such as the public debate on the bill ‘Cohabitation pact and other decrees’ which was conducted on-line on the site of the Ministry of Justice in 9-23 November 2015 (Μίχος, 2017).

4. Allies

The Greek police and right-wing political parties can be considered frequent allies of anti-gender and anti-feminist actors. For example, Carastathis (2015) argues that there are significant links between Greek Police and Golden Dawn. Drawing from Amnesty International, Carastathis (2015: 78) notes that over 50 per cent of police and armed forces voted for the party in 2012 and in the 2014 European elections; police officers have actively participated in, passively allowed and refused to investigate attacks on migrants and LGBTQ people by members of Golden Dawn.

5. Themes and agendas

5.1. Labor market

The outbreak of the global financial crisis in 2008 has severely affected the political and social life in Greece (Koronaïou & Sakellariou, 2017). Since 2010, the country has been subject to a series of austerity measures imposed by IMF-EU-ECB ‘troika’ (Arampatzi, Kouki & Pettas 2022; Kouki & Chatzidakis, 2020).

In 2011-2019, the austerity regime contributed to the rise of Golden Dawn and its antifeminist and antigender politics. Golden Dawn performed several ‘acts of solidarity’ such as the distribution of food to the poor and homeless or visiting families or organised blood donations to exclusively ethnic Greeks (Koronaïou & Sakellariou 2017; Carastathis 2015; Athanasiou 2014).

An important incident of antifeminist discourse and action in this period loosely associated with labor is the arrest and public stigmatization of HIV-positive women who were drug addicts and worked reputedly as prostitutes in 2012. What can be described as the worst violation of human rights in Greece in recent years was in effect a new witch hunt targeting vulnerable women (Βωβού, 2020: 201). Police arrested more than 2000 women from prostitution houses and the streets. They forcibly tested for HIV by the Hellenic Center of Disease Control and Prevention (HCDCP), which detected HIV-positive sex workers. 32 HIV-positive women were imprisoned in April 2012, and their identities,

photos and personal health condition were publicly disclosed by order of the attorney of the Athens First Instance Court with a view to 'protecting the community from contagious diseases.' The personal data of HIV-positive women have been published in newspapers, the media, social media and the Internet, in a major violation of the right to protect personal data enshrined in the Greek Constitution in Art 9.1.

5.2. Health & reproductive rights

In 2018 the movement 'Let me live' appeared on stage, advocating against legal abortions.

As mentioned above, a related late event which sparked heated debate was the organization of the '1st Panhellenic Conference of Fertility and Reproductive Autonomy. Limits and options' that would be held in the city of Ioannina in North-western Greece at the initiative of a group of male Gynaecologists at the Universities of Ioannina, Thrace and Thessaly, along with the 'Greek Association of Reproductive Medicine of Athens.' This would be held in 2-4 July 2021. Its aim would be to foreground the issue of low fertility, to propose remedies, to convey the message that childbearing and the creation of families is the 'joy of life,' and to help restore the model of the nuclear family.

Relatedly, the 'male movement' of groups such as «Ενεργοί μπαμπάδες» ('Active daddies') engages in on-line campaigns and lobbying with the government to advocate for shared custody but also to make a case for gender-based violence against men, (<https://www.energoimpampades.gr/i-via-den-echei-fylo/>) demanding the inclusion of 'parental alienation' in the law against domestic violence which is now under reform (<https://www.energoimpampades.gr/goniki-apoxenosi-sto-ypo-anamorfosi-thesmiko-plaisio-gia-tin-antimetopisi-tis-endooikogeneiakis-vias/>).

5.3. LGBTQ+ rights

5.3.1. Same sex-marriage

2015 is marked by the passage of Law 4356/2015 known as the 'cohabitation pact' which legalized civil unions for same-sex couples amid a climate of conservative opposition from right-wing political parties, the Orthodox Church and clergy, and a portion of the Greek public (Remoundou, 2022; Kantsa, 2014). For example, long before the bill was drafted members of the Church hierarchy threatened to excommunicate members of Parliament who would vote to amend the civil union law to include same-gender couples (Carastasthis, 2018).

Same-sex civil partnership was denounced in the discourse of the Greek Church as a 'deviation from life' that corrupts the institution of the family and constitutes a menace for Orthodoxy and Greek identity. In the words of the bishop of Piraeus Serafeim, the bill is at odds with the cultural identity of Greek, whose core elements consist in religious marriage and a family made up by a man and a woman. The law turns 'a tragic vulgarity into a lawful good deserving legal protection' (Μίχος, 2017: 10-11).

5.4. Gender-based violence

The several incidents of sexual harassment, femicide and other instances of gender-based violence which gave rise to feminist and LGBTQI+ reactions and campaigns -the #MeToo movement, which in Greece unfolded mainly on the Internet and mass media from 2011 onwards, femicides including the emblematic tragic cases of Eleni Topaloudi in Rhodes, in November 2018, and Suzanne Eaton in Crete,

in July 2019, who were raped and killed by macho men on the two islands, the transphobic murder of Zack Kostopoulos on the 21st of September 2018 in Athens- instigated also antifeminist and antigender discourse and action which has not been studied systematically in existing research and publications. To illustrate, on the 25th of September 2018, a group of far-right wing people staged a demonstration on the street where Zack's murder took place, repeating the slogan 'Πρεζάκια και γκέι δεν είστε αναγκαίοι' ['Druggies and gays you are not needed'] (Αθανασίου & Παπανικολάου 2020: 11; <https://www.documentonews.gr/article/paralhrhma-misoys-exw-apoto-kosmhmatopwleio-poy-exase-th-zwh-toy-o-zak-kwstopoylos-prezakia-kai-gkei-deneisteanagkaioi-video-photos>).

5.5. Migration

As noted above, the aggravated socio-economic crisis that started in 2010 contributed to the rise of the anti-immigrant Far Right, mainly of the neo-Nazi Golden Dawn, and the alt-right from 2015 onwards (Βαΐου, 2021: 185-187; Καραμεσίνη, 2015: 239-278). Golden Dawn carried out physical and verbal assaults against immigrants, employing paramilitary battalions («τάγματα εφόδου») that patrolled neighborhoods and attacked immigrants, leftists and and queer (LGBTQ) people (Carastathis, 2015). Moreover, Golden Dawn performed nationalist 'acts of solidarity' such as the distribution of food to the poor and homeless or visits to poor Greek families or blood donations to exclusively ethnic Greeks (Koronaίου & Sakellariou, 2017; Carastathis, 2015; Athanasiou, 2014). Notably, in their discourse and practice, attacks on immigration intersected with assaults on homosexuality. Homosexuality is construed as an obstacle to the reproduction of the nation, and the 'danger' it constitutes is identified with the danger for the nation raised by immigration. Hence, Golden Dawn leaflets distributed in a 'gay' urban neighborhood warned 'homosexuals': 'after the immigrants, you are next' (Carastathis, 2015).

3. Repertoires of action (strategies)

The foregoing actors have deployed a diverse repertoire of actions to make their case against feminism and LGBTI+ rights.

In the case of the Golden Dawn, physical and verbal assaults come on the top of their list. One of the main strategies employed were the paramilitary battalions («τάγματα εφόδου») that patrol neighborhoods and carry out attacks on migrants, leftists and lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender and queer (LGBTQ) people (Carastathis, 2015).

In addition, a Golden Dawn group, headed by members of Parliament and accompanied by angry para-religious crowds, assailed the theatrical company and the audience at the drama play 'Corpus Christi' (which dramatised themes of queer sexuality in Christianity by depicting Jesus and the Apostles as gay men living in contemporary Texas) shouting antigay and anti-immigrant slurs, chanting religious psalms, tearing down the posters of the show etc. (Carastathis, 2015; Athanasiou, 2014).

The Church has used press releases, radio and TV shows and the pulpit itself to articulate their opposition to LGBTQI+ rights.

The 'Let me live' campaign tried to diffuse its messages through advertisements in public transport (mainly, underground stations). The new 'Active Daddies' and cognate groups agitating for 'shared custody' and against 'women's violence' undertake on-line campaigns on Facebook and their sites, and lobby the (friendly) right-wing government. Finally, the organization of a conference and on-line

communication campaign was chosen by the multitude of actors who converged in the initiative for the '1st Panhellenic Conference of Fertility and Reproductive Autonomy.'

4. Frames of arguments

In general terms, Athanasiou (2014) argues that religious, neoliberal, nationalist, and Far Right discourses informed by privatized conceptions of care actively promote women's return to their 'natural domestic place' and to their maternal duty, providing caring labor for those who are ill or for the young and elderly. The Far Right construes its gender politics as antagonistic to mainstream emancipation discourses and advocates heteronormative family values in the name of familial cohesion in insecure times (Athanasiou, 2014: 5). According to the essentialized and normative constructions of masculinities and femininities which lie at the core of Far Right and neo-Nazi politics, women who opt for abortion, feminists, LGBTQI+ people, HIV-positive people, and immigrants are all considered social abnormalities, biological deviations, and national enemies. They are designated thus as dangerous and disposable bodies in ways which carry multiple implications for the daily life of LGBTQI+ individuals, immigrants and women in Greece (Athanasiou, 2014; Dagkouly-Kyriakoglou, 2021).

Existing literature on anti-feminist and anti-gender politics does not note the dissemination of critiques of 'gender theory.' Rare uses of the term can be found in original sources in recent 'grey literature' such as the essay of archimandrite Lemontzis who argues that the 'theory of social gender' is a revival of an ancient Gnostic theory (Λεμοντζής, 2018).

In the staunch antifeminist and antigender discourse and action of Golden Dawn, racism and militarism merges with more traditional conservative and patriarchal stances. Hence, protecting the white 'race' by giving birth to children is one of the main motifs of Golden Dawn discourse. Koronaiou & Sakellariou (2017: 6) argue that through its discourse on the role of women as mothers, motherhood becomes not only a private issue and a role played out in the private sphere, but also a matter for the public sphere since it is tied up with the protection and reproduction of the white 'race' in general and the Greek nation in particular.

Homosexuality is construed as an obstacle to the reproduction of the nation, and at the same time the 'danger' it poses is identified with the danger for the nation raised by immigration. Golden Dawn leaflets distributed in a 'gay' urban neighborhood warned 'homosexuals': 'after the immigrants, you are next' (Carastathis, 2015). In 2012, Ilias Panagiotaros, Golden Dawn's parliamentary member, protesting the abovementioned Corpus Christi drama play was been recorded on video uttering: 'fags with ripped assholes, fucking Albanian assholes' («αδερφές ξεσκισμένες, γαμημένες αλβανικές κωλοτρυπίδες»; Carastathis, 2015). Furthermore, Golden Dawn put a new militaristic twist on traditional attitudes by positioning women as the reproductive matrices of the Greek nation but more specifically of Greek soldiers (Koronaiou & Sakellariou, 2017; Athanasiou, 2014).

More specifically, novel and nuanced frames of antifeminist and antigender argument arose in the context of salient debates around gender identities and rights.

To begin with, the issue and terminology of femicide/femicide («γυναίκοκτονία» in Greek) has become a focus of antifeminist discourse in late years. According to Γκασούκα (2020: 58) and Μιχαλακέλη (2020: 90-93), the term has been dismissed by the new and old right as abusive, coined by weird leftists. Blogs, webpages, authors in the mainstream 'bourgeois' press, opinion leaders and media personalities are at the forefront of this 'battle of words,' taking issue with this 'racism against

women' 'discursive dehumanization of woman' which is engendered by 'political correctness and the neomarxist/feminist lingo' (Yannis Loverdos & Kostas Bogdanos, associated in the past or the present with the right-wing New Democracy party, alt-right politicians, quoted in Μιχαλακέλη, 2020: 92). Key (alt-) right politicians and vectors of anti-feminist discourse, disseminated through Twitter, blogs and other digital media, have participated in this public opposition to the use of 'femicide,' including Thanos Tzimeros (Θάνος Τζήμερος@Thanos Tzimeros), Konstantinos Bogdanos (Constantinosbogdanos@bogdanosk) and Yannis Loverdos (Γιάννης Λοβέρδος@YiannisLoverdos). Even apparently more moderate and 'liberal' media personalities on the right, such as Paschos Mandravelis, have questioned the terms and the arguments not only of femicide but of gender-based violence, as well, countering that the expression of aversion should be due to violence rather than the genders of victim and perpetrator (Μιχαλακέλη, 2020: 93). This rejection is arguably the effect of a collective endorsement of a macho culture in which man is entitled to impose his will, even through corporal or psychological violence. Plenty of studies establish that this culture, calling on men to 'hit as a man' is deeply ingrained in Greek society.

Second, in the on-line public debate on the 2015 bill 'Cohabitation pact and other decrees,' Μίχος (2017) identifies the following central themes in the discourse of citizens who opposed the bill:

- there is a unified and compact Greek Orthodox identity in which 'nation' and (Orthodox Christian) 'religion' presuppose and supplement each other in a homogeneous Greek Orthodox nation/community. In this context, Greece is a purely Orthodox country and homosexuality is constructed as 'non-natural, a sin and an abnormality' (Μίχος 2017: 73). The champions of the bill are constructed thus as the dangerous 'other,' a dimension of otherness that constitutes an enemy of the Orthodox tradition and, by extension, of the Greek nation (Μίχος, 2017: 108).
- the bill is perceived as a 'Western European product' which is not only incompatible with Greece but constitutes an important menace for it. Greece is constructed as a singular/other country which is not fully 'European,' while Europe and, more broadly, the West are constructed as a counterexample to avoid. Certain commentators called also into question the notions of progress and liberal values often associated with the latter (Μίχος, 2017: 90).
- the evocation of the law of God serves to underpin the assumption of a natural order assigned to humanity by God and to essentialize heterosexuality as the sole natural and normal sexual identity sanctioned by God and the reproductive needs of the species. Accordingly, homosexuality is not recognized as a 'natural' sexual identity but is castigated as a sinful act that contravenes nature and the 'divine law' (Μίχος, 2017: 106).

It should be noted that this public consultation took place a few months after the 'battle' of the new SYRIZA-led government with the EU, the July 2015 referendum called by the Prime Minister Alexis Tsipras over the acceptance of a new 'Memorandum' enforcing further austerity measures in return for new loans, the rejection of the deal by 61% of the voters and the eventual 'capitulation' to an austerity Memorandum in August by the same government. The deep political crisis and turbulence sparked by these events were experienced as an existential threat to the nation and the state, raising anew issues bearing on Greek national identity and its enemies.

On this occasion, and beyond the on-line controversy itself, the Greek Orthodox Church foregrounded the heterosexual family as the core structure of society, while other modalities of family life which escape the heteronormative model were construed as threats to society (Dagkouly-Kyriakoglou, 2021). Homosexuality was condemned again as a moral sin and a natural defect (Remoundou, 2022). Archbishop Ieronymos dismissed the bill as 'satanic,' sustaining amoral deviation from the traditional

white, heteronormative, national orthodoxy: ‘anything outside this is a diversion,’ he protested. In a counter-protest, two queer activists dressed up in clergy garments and performed a kiss-in act outside the Athens Orthodox Metropolitan Church (Remoundou, 2022).

Finally, new argumentative themes emerged in the context of the new bill on ‘shared parental responsibility’ in 2021. The Minister of Justice and the official report of the consequences of the new regulations accompanying the bill evoked the contested concept of ‘parental alienation’ which is attributed to resentful women intent on alienating children from their parents. The same report contends that child’s lack of communication with the parent with whom it does not live leads to a non-normal psychic and spiritual development of the child and impedes the formation of a well-rounded personality (Παπαναγιώτου, 2021: 136, 147). Discourses diffused on the Internet are cast in a supposedly scientific style and argue that communication with both parents is very beneficial for children, but it is often blocked by ‘resentful’ mothers (Παπαναγιώτου, 2021: 136). In this vein, the ‘famous’ antifeminist MP of the right-wing New Democracy party, Ioannis Loverdos, exculpated gender violence arguing in the parliamentary debate that even if the husband is violent and used to ‘beat his wife’ he is still entitled to have a relationship with the child, because ‘the child needs both parents’ (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=IrjnOqibPLA>, quoted in Παπαναγιώτου, 2021: 149). The campaign in favour of the bill and the accompanying report present and praise it as ‘children-centered,’ evoking the ‘interest of the child’ which supposedly guides this legal reform. Insofar as this ‘interest’ is considered self-evident rather than subject to contested social/political definition, the purported ‘focus on the child’ tends to naturalize gendered relations in the family and the house (Παπαναγιώτου, 2021: 139, 144).

On the other hand, it should be noted that there is hardly any Greek activism and discourse related to ‘femonationalism’ and ‘homonationalism.’ This is explained by a specific set of conditions defining the ‘Greek particularity’ which did not favour the development of these phenomena in Greece until very recently: the hegemony of the Left in feminist and LGBTQI+ movements, the role of the church and its strong bonds with the right, and the abiding influence of the second wave feminism which weds gender to class. Only recently did the right-wing government of Kyriakos Mitsotakis appropriate certain elements of an ‘equality discourse’ on women’s sexual harassment and LGBTQI+, including a gay politician in his government, but this was widely denounced as ‘pink washing’ (Βουγιούκα et al., 2022: 39, 44, 55-59).

5. Transnational connections

No existing study in the secondary literature explores this issue.

6. Explanations of the anti-gender/anti-feminist backlash

The antifeminist and antigender backlash in 2010-2021 unfolded under the dire circumstances of the socio-economic downturn and the political crisis which has affected Greece from 2010 onwards. Insecurity caused by unemployment and poverty challenged established masculinities constructed around work. The ensuing crisis of aggressive masculinity brought about a rigidification of gender hierarchies, deeper conservatism and a further normalization of sexism which was amplified by the rise of the Far Right, mainly of the neo-Nazi Golden Dawn, and the alt-right from 2015 onwards (Βαϊου, 2021: 185-187; Καραμεσίνη, 2015: 239-278).

The themes of antifeminist and antigender discourse cohered around a unified and compact Greek Orthodox identity in which 'nation' and (Orthodox Christian) 'religion' presuppose and supplement each other in a homogeneous Greek Orthodox nation/community. In this context, Greece is considered a purely Orthodox country and homosexuality is constructed as 'non-natural, a sin and an abnormality;' 'parental alienation' which is attributed to resentful women intent on alienating children from their parents. Related discourses diffused on the Internet are cast in a supposedly scientific style and argue that communication with both parents; the issue of low fertility and the argument that childbearing and the creation of families is the 'joy of life,' and to help restore the model of the nuclear family; racism and militarism merged with more traditional conservative and patriarchal stances in the discourse of neo-Nazi Golden Dawn and elsewhere (Μίχος, 2017; Carastathis. 2015).

7. Conclusion

The antifeminist and antigender reaction in 2010-2021 broke out under the dire circumstances of the socio-economic downturn and the political crisis which has beset Greece from 2010 onwards. The general social dislocation under the austerity regime generated a broader 'gender trouble' which unsettled the traditional gendered division. The destabilization of dominant identities gave rise to gender violence manifested and legitimized by its agents as a performance of masculinity in an endangered patriarchal context which was also experienced a lethal threat to the 'nation,' hence the reaffirmation of nationalism through the reaffirmation of male power, the traditional family structure and the Greek Orthodox Church, the key pillars of historical Greek nationalism (Κοσσυφολόγου, 2018: 40-42).

In addition to gender equality and LGBTQI+ advances which provoked conservative reactions, a number of distinct events constituted the focus of antifeminist and antigender action and discourse: the persecution and stigmatization of HIV positive women in 2012; the 'cohabitation pact' extended to same-sex couples in 2015; campaigns against legal abortion in 2018 onwards; the issue and terminology of femicide/feminicide since 2018; the new 4800/2021 law on 'shared parental responsibility;' the organization of the '1st Panhellenic Conference of Fertility and Reproductive Autonomy. Limits and options' in 2021.

Traditional agents of antigender and antifeminism -the conservative Right and the Greek Orthodox Church- were reinforced by newcomers, including crucially the neo-Nazi Golden Dawn, alt-right politicians and media personalities disseminating anti-feminist discourse in the parliament but also through Twitter, blogs and other digital media, the male 'movement' for shared custody and against 'women's violence,' the 'Let me live' campaign, a diverse chorus which coalesced around the '1st Panhellenic Conference of Fertility and Reproductive Autonomy,' diverse right-wing journals, blogs, news websites, newspapers and radio stations, along with non-organized groups and individuals from civil society.

Their repertoire of action involves old and novel patterns: physical and verbal assaults, press releases, radio and TV shows and the pulpit, advertisements in public transportation means, on-line campaigns on Facebook and specific sites, lobbying right-wing politicians and the organization of conferences.

All the foregoing topics, and antifeminist/antigender politics and discourse in 2010-2021 in general need to be studied systematically as existing research is very poor and fragmentary.

8. List of the anti-gender and anti-feminist organizations and initiatives

Name of the organization (original)	Name of the organization (English)	Anti-gender or anti-feminist?	Logo of the organization	Head of the organization (in the period 2010-2021)	Web-page (social media)	Size of the organization (if available)	Comment (brief description)
Αφήστε με να ζήσω	Let me Live	Anti-gender		N/A	Web: afistemenaziso.gr FB and twitter: @afistemenaziso	n/a	Pro-life movement against abortion rights
Μέτωπο Νεολαίας	Youth front	Anti-gender/Anti-feminist		n/a	Web: antepithesi.gr	n/a	Golden Dawn's youth section
Χρυσή Αυγή	Golden Dawn	Anti-gender/Anti-feminist		Nikos Michaloliakos	Web: xrisiavgi.com	n/a	Ex-political extreme right political party. Now criminal organisation
Μέτωπο Νίκης	Victory Front	Anti-gender/Anti-feminist		Rachil Makri (https://www.facebook.com/rachel.makri)	Youtube: MetopoNikis Twitter: metoponikis Web: metoponikis.gr FB: https://www.facebook.com/metoponikis/	n/a	Nationalist Political party

ΠΑΤΡΙ.Δ.Α.	Fatherland	Anti-gender/Anti-feminist		President Konstantinos Bogdanos (Constantinosbogdanos@bogdanosk) Vice president: Afroditi Latinopoulou: https://latinopoulou.gr/synepimeleia/	Web: https://patrida.net/	n/a	New right-wing party
Ενεργοί μπαμπάδες	Active daddies	Anti-gender		n/a	Web: https://www.energoimpampades.gr FB: https://www.facebook.com/EnergoIMpampades.gr	n/a	New actor in antifeminist and antigender mobilization discourse
Σύλλογος Συνεπιμέλεια	Shared Custody Association	Anti-gender		n/a	Web: https://www.synepimelia.gr	n/a	New actor in antifeminist and antigender mobilization discourse with international links (such as the 'International Council of Shared Parenting').
Ελληνική Λύση	Hellenic Solution	Anti-gender/Anti-feminist		Kyriakos Velopoulos: https://www.facebook.com/filoivelopoulou.velopoulos	Web: https://elliniki-lisi.gr/	n/a	Nationalist right-wing party

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ITALY

Anna Lavizzari

1. Introduction

The mobilization against “gender ideology” attracted the interest of few Italian scholars, mostly in the field of sociology and political science.¹ Since 2010 studies analyzing anti-gender campaigns in Italy have concentrated on three main lines of inquiry. The first focuses on the content of the anti-gender discourse and rhetoric, rooted in the Vatican’s “gender ideology” rhetoric developed during the 1990s and subsequently adopted and adapted to the Italian national context by conservative religious organizations, as well as right-wing social and political actors (Garbagnoli, 2016; Garbagnoli & Prearo 2018; Spallaccia, 2020; Colella, 2021). A second line of investigation has focused on the emergence and establishment of an anti-gender movement that sociologists Anna Lavizzari and Massimo Prearo define as “the expression of a network of individuals, already existing organizations, and newly-formed groups concerned with the political and ideological threat centered around the notions of gender ideology and gender theory” (2019, p. 425). These analyses include empirical findings on the main actors, their relation to the state and religious institutions, their repertoires of action and claim-making strategies (Lavizzari and Prearo 2019; Lavizzari 2020; Prearo 2020; Lavizzari and Siročić 2022; Trappolin 2022). Finally, later studies have paid increased attention to the alliance between anti-gender actors and Italian populist radical right parties, most notably the League and Brothers of Italy, focusing on the appropriation or instrumentalization of the anti-gender discourse by the parties’ leaders and exponents in their attempt to qualify themselves as the political representatives of Italian Catholics (Bellé and Poggio 2018; Lavizzari and Prearo 2019; Prearo 2020; Serughetti 2021; Giorgi 2022; Trappolin 2022).

Research conducted on this phenomenon in the Italian case reflects the evolution of anti-gender actors and discourses as they adapted to the political and institutional context. In fact, looking at the period 2010-2022 we can point to several key political and policy developments targeted by anti-gender campaigns (see also Lavizzari and Siročić 2022 for an analysis of selected critical events that led to the consolidation of the anti-gender movement along the years). Indeed, the establishment of the anti-gender movement in the Italian landscape since the early 2010s has been favored by certain political circumstances, or political opportunities. In this sense, we can consider the onset of the anti-gender mobilization as part of a political and public debate that has developed around a series of bills aimed at strengthening the institutional recognition of LGBTQ+ subjectivities, also improving the legislation on family and the national school system. In particular, three bills, emerging in the context of the increasing post-secularization of Italian society vis-à-vis sexual citizenship rights, constitute the *casus belli* for the reaffirmation and radicalization of a religious, identitarian and conservative collective identity centered on a conservative discourse to “gender theory and ideology”, and the defense of the traditional and natural family (Lavizzari 2020, 5): “The draft bill Scalfarotto² (2013) proposes the introduction of the crime of homophobia in the penal code; the bill Cirinnà (2013-2016), the recognition of civil unions; and the draft bill Fedeli³ (2014, later merged into the reform of the so-called “Good School”), the inclusion of gender-oriented educational programs in school”. From a legal perspective, a first bill on domestic partnerships was proposed in 2002, almost contemporary to the approval of the European Parliament’s resolution against discrimination on grounds of sexual

¹ A search through the string [“anti-gender” AND/OR “anti-feminism” AND “Italy”] for the period 2010–2022 on Web of Knowledge produced less than 15 entries in total.

² <https://www.senato.it/leg/17/BGT/Schede/Ddliter/41977.htm>

³ <https://www.senato.it/leg/17/BGT/Schede/Ddliter/45005.htm>

orientations (2003), and subsequently replaced by the so-called Dico (the equivalent of PACs in other European countries) in 2007. The two bills provided the starting point for political and legal negotiations on same-sex unions, which have been subject to countless revisions and deadlocks, until 2013, when the Italian Parliament started to examine a new proposal to legally recognize same-sex unions, including the right to adopt the partner's children (Lavizzari 2020; Trappolin 2022). The bill was finally approved in 2016, after the removal of the stepchild adoption provision, in response to the objections from right-wing and Catholic parties. Several bills discussing the inclusion of the crime of homotransphobia were presented and never discussed since 2007, until the Parliament started to debate a single bill against hate-crime and hate-speech in 2013 (Scalfarotto bill). In 2021, a new bill, proposed by the Democratic Party MP Alessandro Zan (Zan bill) and "aiming at penalizing discrimination, violence and hate speech on grounds of sex, gender, sexual orientation, gender identity and disability, equating these offences with racist crimes already included in the penal code" (Feo 2022, 1), was rejected by the Italian Senate after a heated debate within and outside the institutional arena.

Alongside these legal provisions, the anti-gender movement has been acting and/or reacting to a set of additional political developments that are worth considering in order to understand its strategies and development, and notably its institutionalization in the electoral and political arenas (cf. section 2, 3, 4 and 6 below for details). Among these, the political elections of 2018 won by Matteo Salvini's League in coalition with Luigi Di Maio's Five Star Movement and of 2022, won by Giorgia Meloni's Brothers of Italy in coalition with the League and Forza Italia, brought in office members of the anti-gender movement enlisted in the populist radical right parties of the League and Brothers of Italy. As we will see in section 4 and 6, it constitutes an established strategy by the movement to enter public offices and institutions, thus embedding their agenda in formal and administrative bodies (Lavizzari and Prearo 2019; Lavizzari and Siročić 2022). The changes within the political and party system since 2018 certainly push Italian scholars to renew and sharpen their attention to the actions of populist radical right parties currently in power and their relations with the anti-gender movement, threatening fundamental rights such as reproductive rights, bodily integrity, gender and sexual education in school, while promoting a staunchly conservative understanding of the natural family and heteronormative society.

2. The history of the anti-gender movement and its context

As mentioned in the previous section, a set of policy proposals to regulate LGBTQ+ rights and promote gender and sexual education in school created a political opportunity for the Italian anti-gender movement to emerge. However, in order to describe the roots of the movement and, to some extent, its success in the Italian context, we need to understand some critical features of Italian Catholicism, most notably its relation to politics, in the past three decades. Indeed, the relative success of the movement can only to a certain degree be attributed to the proximity of the Vatican to Italian institutions and the public sphere. Certainly, in the Italian context, historically, religious authorities and the presence of the Vatican have had a significant role in deploying their power through Catholic morality and doctrine, intervening in the public debate at multiple levels, and determining a complex dialectic among social and political actors along the spectrum (Lavizzari 2020, 56). The positioning of the Church in the Italian socio-political context has opened up structural opportunities and repertoires of action that appeal not only to the public opinion at large, but also to decision-makers, as a result of powerful lobbying activities (*ibid.*). More specifically, a distinctive trait of the Italian landscape is the direct influence of the Catholic Church in the political activities of right-wing, conservative and center-left parties; all major political parties belonging to the center-left have historically maintained a strong

basis of Christian members, preventing a real secularization process from occurring (Ozzano and Giorgi 2015). This can be seen as the legacy of Christian Democracy (DC), a post-war Christian democratic political party that played a leading role in the first phase of the Italian Republic for fifty years, until its dissolution in 1994 in the midst of corruption scandals. After the party's dissolution, a significant proportion of religious voters felt orphaned without a powerful Catholic party to support. Since then, politically committed Catholics have engaged in a policy of presence defined as 'Catholic diaspora' (Apruzzese 2012; Lavizzari and Prearo 2019). This model describes the involvement of Catholics (as both electorate and candidates) in defending and promoting religious values in government policies not as a single Catholic party (as it was until the dissolution of the Christian Democracy), but dispersed throughout most of the parties along the political spectrum (Lavizzari and Prearo 2019).

In this context, as a consequence of the waning of conventional political influence through a single, hegemonic party, religious issues became highly politicized by different political entrepreneurs, including Catholic movements. During this evolution, "[a] huge internal pluralism exploded, with the establishment of major differences that can still be recognized in contemporary Church. Among Catholic associations, political cleaves emerged more sharply and gave birth to different kinds of spiritual, social, and political engagement" (Ozzano and Giorgi 2015, 22).

Taking everything into consideration, we can accurately say that the Italian religious context is a fractured one – in which the "life line" of Italian Catholicism has been kept alive through the numerous Catholic schools, associations, groups, cultural centers and specialized press active all over the Italian territory (Lavizzari 2020, 58). In particular, the so-called "new religious movements" or, adapted to the Italian context, the ecclesial movement organizations – such as Communion and Liberation, The New Catechumenal Way, Opus Dei, Renewal in the Spirit and The Focolarists – have been the primary forms of Catholic activism, responsible for the diffusion and expression of Christian values and Catholic morality throughout the Italian society (*ibid.*).

The case study of the anti-gender movement and its evolution in Italy allows to highlight, on the one hand, the occupation of a renewed and hybrid Catholic political space through the reactivation of a collective identity based on the "non-negotiable values" of the anti-gender cause and, on the other hand, the strategies and dilemmas that underlie its collective action. This analysis allows to (re)think the (dis)continuity of Catholic representation in the Italian public debate and political space. However, the creation of a Catholic hybrid political space must not be interpreted as a coming back of Catholics into politics, which had never left, but rather as a re-composition of Catholic political projects founded on the hybrid forms of collective presence and intersecting strategies (Lavizzari and Prearo 2019). In this sense, the anti-gender cause – understood as the result of a mobilization discourse that would allow the creation of a community and of a movement identity – represented a political opportunity to "solve" the problem posed by the Catholic diaspora, raising tensions and criticism with respect to the modes of action within the arenas of political parties and social movements.

Despite the internal fragmentation and increased detachment of the Catholic base from the ecclesiastic elites, the strategic alliance between the Church and the Catholic movements has also guaranteed a higher degree of conservatism in every area of ecclesial life and in bioethical debates, including the assertion of an anthropological drift of human nature caused by "gender ideology" (Lavizzari 2020). As we will see in the next sections, much of the repertoire of actions employed by anti-gender activists is also shaped by the political and institutional knowledge already acquired through their legacy in the DC party and the political arena (*ibid.*).

However, it is above all on the side of the radical Catholic movement, rather than of the majority Catholic movement closer to ecclesiastical elites, that we need to turn if we want to understand the anti-gender movement that emerged from 2013 (Prearo 2020). The activism of this movement consists precisely in picking up the lines of the discourse elaborated by the Vatican on the “gender theory” in order to make it an extra-ecclesiastical discourse mobilized in the streets and public squares, a discourse that responds to the desire for mobilization of the minoritarian and radical components of that Catholic people, even against the Catholic elites (Prearo 2020, 116):

“On the one hand, it is a question of establishing and promoting a more radical Catholic action with respect to the mainstream movement close to ecclesiastical institutions. On the other hand, this operation of intra-Catholic contestation is accompanied by a project for the establishment of a competitive front, an alternative pole, which allows the development of a model of action of the movement type, detached from ecclesiastical leadership.”

This process reflects a “dynamic of externalization of Catholic political work” (Prearo 2020, 17), through which a new form of Catholic militancy has emerged in Italy. This activism is characterized by being “extra-ecclesiastic”, that is, it is increasingly autonomous with regard to ecclesiastical structures and organization and inscribed in a secular discursive framework (Prearo 2020, 22). Since the success of the first national March for Life organized by the pro-life movement in 2011 and 2012, the radical Catholics have progressively coalesced around the anti-gender cause. The emergence of this new militant field unfolds also via the NGO-ization (Vaggione, 2005) of the new Catholic movement, which, since 2013 established new, satellite organizations (Lavizzari and Siročić 2022, cf. section 3). A clear display of this dynamic is reflected by the creation of La Manif Pour Tous Italia, imported from the homonymous French organization through transnationally linked French and Italian anti-gender actors (cf. section 8). Italian anti-gender activists, such as Filippo Savarese and Jacopo Coghe, personally attended some of the French La Manif Pour Tous initiatives in Paris, and started a real franchising model to export the organization to Italy, as Prearo (2020, 208) writes: “The same Ludovine de la Rochère [President of the Manif Pour Tous in France], during the press conference on July 23, 2013 in Paris, announces the ‘second season’ of the Manif Pour Tous, and announces that she wants to ‘consolidate our partnerships: Europe, Italy, Croatia’. It is the creation of a real Italian franchise, [...]”. Certainly, different and multiple, and complex are the encounters between key figures bridging between the two national realities (see Prearo 2020 for a reconstruction), but importantly, the overlapping of similar “challenges” (notably, in this case, same-sex marriage) across different countries helped the creation and diffusion of a new militant model, characterized by factors as explained in the previous paragraphs.

In retracing the trajectory of the anti-gender movement, we can point to a series of (selected) critical events from which it emerged and developed. The first critical event, as mentioned, is the submission of a draft bill on homotransphobia in Parliament in March 2013. A few months later, the newly-created La Manif Pour Tous Italia (LMPTI) – Family Generation mobilized against the introduction of the draft bill in defense of (Catholic) freedom of opinion. Following this, and mirroring argumentation patterns and tactics traditionally employed by progressive movements, between 2013 and 2016, other newly created organizations, such as the Committee to Defend Our Children (CDNF), Lawyers for Life and ProLife Onlus, initiated an intense phase of protest mobilization. In this phase, the Family Day rallies that took place in 2015 and 2016 were critical events for the newly established organizations. By proposing the Family Day as the major platform and megaphone through which to display collective worthiness, unity, numbers and commitment (so-called ‘WUNC’, Tilly 2004), the anti-gender

movement became a visible and credible actor (Lavizzari and Siročić 2022). For the first time, representatives of the anti-gender movement were repeatedly present at public protests such as sit-ins in front of the Government in Rome. In sum, the phase between 2013 to 2016 is defined by the assembling of the anti-gender campaign and the organization and coordination of the movement's strategies in the public sphere until their consolidation.

In May 2016, the Democratic Party, the center-left party in government at the time, approved the Law on Civil Partnership, which legally recognized and regulated same-sex civil unions. This critical event sparked public confrontations between anti-gender groups and the progressive civil society, including feminist and LGBTQ+ groups. In the context of a contentious politics of gender in Italy at the time, the approval of the Law on Civil Partnership was a major political opportunity shift for both conflicting sides (Lavizzari and Siročić 2022). Although it represented a political victory for a part of the LGBTQ+ movement, at this point the anti-gender movement recognized a need for a strategic turn toward the institutional arena (*ibid.*). After the phase of intense public demonstrations, which nonetheless did not bring to the desired outcome of avoiding the Law on Civil Partnership from being passed, Italy's anti-gender movement politicized its cause through institutional lobbying, facilitated by the Catholic diaspora model of political representation previously mentioned (Lavizzari and Prearo 2019). To this end, the anti-gender movement extended the frame of a "struggle against gender ideology" to include a broader range of issues, such as same-sex marriage, adoption, "uterus for rent", abortion, and women's rights, and linked these issues to a "decline in family values" and changes in gender roles.

The referendum on the Renzi–Boschi constitutional reform (2016) was another political opportunity for the anti-gender movement (Lavizzari and Prearo 2019). Prime Minister Matteo Renzi launched a referendum to reform the constitution, including the composition and powers of the Parliament and the Senate – most notably to end the so-called "perfect bicameralism" between Parliament and Senate, characteristic of the Italian government. In May 2016, the promoters of the Family Day formed an ad hoc committee with the name of Families Against the Referendum. Discursively, this initiative aimed at discrediting the government in office (led by the center-left Democratic Party) by presenting the constitutional reform and the approval of the civil unions bill as an attempt to scratch the Italian constitution, with consequences for the disparage the traditional family, and thus the foundations of Italian society. In this context, the anti-gender movement's rhetoric shifted more clearly from an "anti-gender" to a "pro-family" stance (Prearo 2020). This initiative can also be interpreted as a strategic attempt at alliance-building, aligning the anti-gender movement's position to right-wing parties, notably Matteo Salvini's League, Silvio Berlusconi's *Forza Italia*, and Giorgia Meloni's Brothers of Italy. Simultaneously, the referendum represented a discursive opportunity for the right-wing parties to reinforce their own position on these issues through the instrumentalization of religion in their political rhetoric and by supporting anti-gender movement members in their electoral lists. Eventually, the 59% of the electorate voted against the constitutional reform, after which Matteo Renzi resigned.

While gaining ground in schools, public services, and the government, Italy's anti-gender movement also diversified its strategy by embedding its claims in a revitalized pro-family and anti-feminist stance on women's reproductive rights. Prior to the Italian 4 March 2018 elections, Massimo Gandolfini, the founder and leader of the CDFN and the major promoter of the Family Day, explicitly invited Italian citizens to vote for center-right parties on the basis of their commitment to the anti-gender movement's values and goals – pro-life, pro-family and freedom of education. The subsequent political success of the center-right coalition led by the League, along with the populist Five Star

Movement, allowed the anti-gender movement to enhance its power of agenda-setting by allying with the League, notably through the double membership of some of its activists. In fact, the latter occupied several important offices, including Lorenzo Fontana as Minister of Family and Disability, and Simone Pillon as vice-president of the Commission for Children and Adolescents in the Senate. With the support of center and radical right allies in the government, the anti-gender movement gained a privileged position from which to attack women's and LGBTQ+ rights. Some of the coalition's first legal proposals were in line with the opposition to gender and sexual equality. The elected senator from the League, Simone Pillon, who was the creator of the controversial "Pillon bill"⁴ championed a radical and revitalized theo-conservative stance within the government.

Finally, we should mention two other critical events in the evolution of the movement. The World Congress of Families, held in Verona in March 2019, can be seen as the culmination of the coalition government's dedication to the promotion of anti-gender and anti-feminist claims and the direct outcome of the processes described above. The Minister of the Interior and leader of the League Matteo Salvini participated in the event, along with other international party leaders who shared the same ideological beliefs and whose presence gave the appearance of governmental support. The WCF is "an international network of NGOs and intellectuals established at the end of the 1990s by a coalition of US groups of the Christian right such as the *Howard Center for Family, Religion and Society*, the Mormon *World Family Policy Center* and the *Family Research Council*" (Buss and Herman 2003 cited in Trappolin 2022, 134). The event thus demonstrates the importance of the transnational networks linking the anti-gender movement in Italy with other European, US and Russian right-wing political forces (Trappolin 2022, cf. also section 8). Alongside international actors and Italian radical right parties, all the major organizations campaigning against gender ideology since 2013 were present at the event, as co-organizers, sanctioning the alliance between the actors involved and the definite institutionalization of the movement. Eventually, the political elections of September 2022, won by Giorgia Meloni's Brothers of Italy, can be seen as a clear display of the processes of movement's institutionalization and embedding of the anti-gender agenda in the parties' political programs. In fact, we find several actors that entered office on the back of the League and Brothers of Italy and that are directly traceable to the anti-gender and pro-life movement (cf. section 3 and section 13 for a periodization).

⁴ The proposal included new rules for couples intending to divorce, such as mediation, counselling and equal access to children's custody as a way to promote both parental figures, including the father figure and demands that both parents are obliged to provide for minors' direct maintenance.

Table 1. Draft bills and bills from 2010–2021

Name	Aim	Year	Proponent	Outcome
Draft bill Scalfarotto	Homotransphobia	2013	Ivan Scalfarotto (Democratic Party)	Merged into draft bill Zan ⁵
Draft bill Fedeli ⁶	Gender education in schools	2014	Valeria Fedeli (Democratic Party)	Stalled; merged into Law 107/2015 “Good School” ⁷
Bill Cirinnà	Civil unions	2014–2016	Monica Cirinnà (Democratic Party)	Passed into Law 76/2016 ⁸
Referendum on Renzi-Boschi constitutional reform	Reform of the constitution, bicameralism	2016	Maria Elena Boschi, Matteo Renzi (Democratic Party)	Rejected
Draft bill Zan ⁹	Homotransphobia	2020–2021	Alessandro Zan (Democratic Party)	Passed (Parliament, 2020) ¹⁰ ; rejected (Senate, 2021)

3. Actors and allies¹¹

In Italy, the anti-gender movement encompasses a diversified subset of religious and politically conservative players (cf. section 14 for details on the organizations’ background, section 4 for allies, and section 8 for transnational connections). The few Italian scholars that have focused on it have proposed various classifications of the actors involved in the anti-gender mobilization since 2013, taking into consideration their social and political nature, the type of values they put forward, their main targets as well as their repertoires of action (Garbagnoli and Prearo 2017; Lavizzari 2020; Prearo 2020; Trappolin 2022). Similarly, different scholars employ different definitions for the same movement, often refraining from calling it anti-gender, and preferring instead other labels, depending on the focus and approach of their conceptualization. For instance, Massimo Prearo (2020) refers to a Neo-Catholic movement which is relative autonomous from the Church. A major criterion of classification in this case is the distance from the ecclesiastical hierarchies along with the radicalism proposed by the organizations’ messages and actions. Anna Lavizzari (2020) instead, speaks about a traditionalist movement, formed by single and compound players of different nature, linked by multiple social, political, economic and ideological connections around a collective identity centered on a conservative, oppositional discourse to “gender theory and ideology”, the defense of traditional and natural family, and heteropatriarchal society. For the purpose of this analysis, we follow the classification proposed by Lavizzari (2020, 85-88). Relevant to understand the composition of the anti-gender movement are also the concepts of de-privatization of religion in the context of the Vatican’s New Evangelization Project, that is, advocating for a public role of religion (Kuhar and Paternotte 2017), along with the NGO-ization of the Catholic Church, meaning the Church’s efforts to revitalized itself through the action of civil society organizations in defense of religious precepts (Vaggione 2005; Lavizzari and Siročić 2022).

⁵ <https://www.camera.it/leg18/126?tab=1&leg=18&idDocumento=868&sede=&tipo=>

⁶ <https://www.senato.it/service/PDF/PDFServer/BGT/00845618.pdf>

⁷ <https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/id/2015/07/15/15G00122/sg>

⁸ <https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/id/2016/05/21/16G00082/sg>

⁹

https://www.camera.it/leg18/995?sezione=documenti&tipoDoc=lavori_testo_pdl&idLegislatura=18&codice=leg.18.pdl.camera.569.18PDL0012340&back_to=https://www.camera.it/leg18/126?tab=2-e-leg=18-e-idDocumento=569-e-sede=-e-tipo=

¹⁰ <https://www.camera.it/leg18/126?idDocumento=0569&leg=18&tab=>

¹¹ I am keeping these two sections together as it better allows for a coherent narrative.

3.1. Identity Catholic groups and organizations

Identity-based Catholics can be defined as the backbone of the Catholic doctrine and include groups, associations and organizations that are active and publicly involved in identity-based Catholic activism, namely the promotion of Catholic morality as expressed in the position of the Vatican. They are critically opposed to liberalism and modernity, championing and raising awareness of issues such as the role of family, right to life, religious freedom, bioethics and regulation of sexual and family policies in the public sphere, with specific reference to natural law. Among the most involved in the anti-gender campaign in Italy we find promoters of pro-life and pro-family values, particularly: the *Forum delle Famiglie* (Families Forum) linked to the *Movimento per la Vita* (Movement for Life); Catholic lawyers, such as the association *Unione Giuristi Cattolici Italiani* (Union of Italian Catholic Lawyers) and so-called expert engaged in different fields, from neurology to psychology, sociology and pedagogy, especially university professors linked to institutions with a Catholic tradition (for instance, the Catholic University of the Sacred Heart in Milan). In addition, among the most active and politicized organizations are: Association *Scienza&Vita* (Science&Life), *Azione Cattolica* (Catholic Action) and *Alleanza Cattolica* (Catholic Alliance). These associations have direct access to the political system and state's agents, either through links with members of Parliament – as many politicians in office are actually members of one or more of these associations – or as institutional partners called in as experts to discuss issues considered to be of their competence. Their simultaneous presence in multiple arenas – courts, hospitals and health services, media, government offices, churches, political parties, schools, universities, as well as during demonstrations and public events – is key for the recruitment of allies, the accumulation of material resources (funding) and the advancement of political and ideological goals. Finally, in this category, religious authorities such as Opus Dei and the Italian Episcopal Conference (CEI) are important players in terms of resources, as both economic and ideological supporters. The latter, in particular, constitutes an important source of legitimization for the actions sustained by these players. They function as *political entrepreneurs* of the Catholic church.

3.2. Ecclesial movements

This subset of players includes organizations known for their commitment to socially conservative policies on sexual and family issues, whose public visibility is more veiled but whose role as ideological, political and economic supporters is also critical to the anti-gender cause. Among the most influential are members of Communion and Liberation, the Neocatechumenal Way, the Focolare movement and the Renewal in the Spirit. These movements constitute the backbone of the activists' base, being at the core of grassroots strategies, and provide arenas and platforms for the organization of public events and meetings: church halls, theaters and other associated facilities. They differ, however, in the ways they have entered (and/or exited) specific arenas, particularly during demonstrations in street and public squares. One of their key features is the extent to which they participate as single or compound players, reflecting different degrees of radicalization around the cause.

3.3. "Ad-hoc" anti-gender groups and NGOs

These players include associations and committees that have been newly formed in response to the increased political relevance and visibility of LGBTQ+ rights and subjects, and to the reforms proposed by the government in the field of education to address affectivity and sexuality in school's curricula. Within this typology we find groups such as *ProVita Onlus* (ProLife Onlus), *La Manif pour Tous Italia* (LMPTI) – *Generazione Famiglia* (Family Generation) – later merged in 2019 into the umbrella *ProVita & Famiglia Onlus* (ProLife & Family Onlus), the *Sentinelle in Piedi* (Standing Sentinels), *Famiglia Domani* (Tomorrow's Family), the *Comitato "Sì alla famiglia"* ("Yes to Family" Committee), *Giuristi per la Vita*

(Lawyers for Life), and the *Comitato Difendiamo I Nostri Figli – CDNF* (Committee to Defend Our Children), primary organizer of the Family Day demonstrations. These groups operate mostly on the level of disclosure, communication, dissemination and presence on the streets at events such as Family Day or the Sentinels' vigils. They represent the "face" and the entrepreneurs of the campaign, having direct access to the media and to government's offices, where they are also able to influence policies and decision-making processes. Although active as a transnational "community of citizens", the ultra-conservative organization *CitizenGo* – born in Spain in 2013 as a spin-off of *HazteOir* – maintains an Italian branch with many overlapping members of the Family Day committee. This latter has been involved in different campaigns against abortion and same-sex marriage, and gay prides, most notably through the *Bus della libertà* (Freedom Bus) campaign in 2017 and 2018, bringing anti-gender messages through major Italian cities.

3.4. Conservative and populist radical right political forces, neo-fascist and radical right groups

In order to qualify the extent to which gender and sexual issues have been increasingly politicized in the Italian context, it is crucial to consider how spillover influences have occurred around anti-gender campaigns in relation to populist and radical right forces. These latter, have not only become key players, but are also fundamental to a political strategy that has allowed religious players, on the one hand, to infiltrate the political, electoral and institutional arenas through their support – forging coalitions with right-wing movement organizations and groups and politicians within political parties along the spectrum – and, on the other hand, benefited from the anti-gender cause to reshape the political context. In particular, we have witnessed the rise of populist and radical right parties – above all Matteo Salvini's League and Giorgia Meloni's Brothers of Italy –, in which the anti-gender cause and the sustained interactions with the anti-gender movement – in terms of frames, relations with authorities, political and discursive opportunity – has been instrumental for their political success in recent years.

These actors, function both as members of the movement and as allies, depending on the circumstances. Several scholars have analyzed the connections between the two parties and the anti-gender movement, especially with respect to the content of their political manifestos, the role of the movement's activists elected in the parties, and their influence on the country's institutions (i.e. Bellé and Poggio 2018; Donà 2020; Ben-Porat et al. 2021; Giorgi 2021). More broadly, this line of research refers to the entanglements between populism, religion, and gender politics (cf. section 9 for an explanation). For instance, Alessia Donà (2020, 162-163) explains how,

Since Matteo Salvini became its leader in 2013, Lega has undergone a deep ideological transformation in order to adapt the party's agenda and discourse according to the changing circumstances of Italian (and European) politics. This led to a shift from the ethno-regionalism of the early years to the current right-wing nationalism based on the defence of the Italian nation, Christian identity and the traditional family. ... Italy is governed by a typical populist radical-right party, with Christianity deployed as an identity marker. The party's radicalisation has been visible in many ways: first, Salvini's use of religious symbols (that is, swearing on the Gospel and kissing a rosary) to reinforce the community's identity; second, the definition of a policy agenda that focuses on the traditional family and the promotion of natality; and, third, the adoption of populist positions designed to defend 'us, the good common people', against 'them, the others', who are accused of damaging the country's 'ethnic pureness' and 'natural morality'.

Already with the political elections in 2018, therefore, the League provides access to government's bodies to a number of anti-gender activists, such as ultraconservative, homophobic, antiabortionist Senator Simone Pillon – promoter of the Family Day, member of the Neocatechumenal Way, former member of the Forum of the Families, promoter of the infamous Pillon Bill on shared custody; and ultraconservative, homophobic, pro-life Lorenzo Fontana, former Minister of Family and Disability (2018-2019) and since October 2022 President of the Chamber of Deputies. In concomitance to the League's support and role in paving the way to anti-gender activists, during the WCF in 2019, Giorgia Meloni publicly sanctions her party's alliance with the movement, by expressing her full support to the cause under the slogan *Dio, Patria, Famiglia (God, Fatherland, Family)*. Indeed, the election of Brothers of Italy in September 2022 opens (further) the way to anti-gender activists in the government.

In addition, we can count neo-fascist groups of the radical right, such as *Forza Nuova* and *CasaPound Italia*, which are closely linked to other associations listed above, in particular *ProVita Onlus* and the Standing Sentinels. These groups were mainly present, or at least visible, in public arenas such as streets and squares, engaging in direct contestation and confrontation actions at LGBTQ+ demonstrations and marches. They support the campaign by making platforms available, organizing informative sit-ins, and by disseminating anti-gender propaganda, appropriating the gender issue to renew their traditionalist position, broaden their electoral/ militant constituencies and boost their visibility in the media, both at local and national levels. These actors attended several national public events supporting the anti-gender cause, such as the 2015 and 2016 Family Days in Rome, and the 2019 World Congress of Families in Verona. *Forza Nuova* and *CasaPound* also organized their own initiatives or took action on their own, in particular around anti-abortionist and anti-gay stances.

Source: Anna Lavizzari, Modena, 2016

Poster by extreme right Forza Nuova hanged in the city of Modena: “Manuel and Marco, together with family and citizenship announce the end of civilization, of our traditions, of the natural family, the only pillar of our society, and of children’s right to grow up with a mom and a dad, that took place Sunday September 25, 2016. Gay Marriage, Funerals of Italy. Italy needs children, not homosexuals”.

Source: Anna Lavizzari, Rome, 2016

In the Italian context, the Church is indispensable for the organization of large mass mobilizations, and, unlike in some other European countries where the involvement of the Church is seen as potentially damaging to the scientific credibility of the issues at stake and the secular nature of the state, the support of the Catholic Church has given legitimacy to the anti-gender campaign, particularly in its initial phase. Although some organizations strategically emphasize their non-religious nature and highlight the scientific character of their arguments to overshadow the religious dimension, the latter appears overwhelmingly prevalent in a more careful analysis of the social and political background of the personalities who are part of the campaign (Lavizzari 2020, 89-90).

The transformation of churches and parishes into platforms for political mobilization requires great efforts from below and sustained support from above. Most of the anti-gender activists are, in a significant way, personally rooted in religious communities and in particular in ecclesial movements. As Mario Adinolfi, director and founder of the specialized Catholic newspaper *The Cross*, himself declares in the *Appeal to the Italian Bishops* on April 19, 2015, the aim is to promote “a real parish by parish mobilization, to prevent the deception at the people’s expense, of the Cirinnà bill” (cited in Lavizzari 2020, 90).

Among other “alliances”, we should mention some strands of feminist movements, in particular radical gender critical feminists but also former activists of feminist groups, endorsing positions resonant with anti-gender claims vis-à-vis specific issues, among which a general aversion to consider gender as fluid identity and most notably against surrogate maternity, sex work and policies that protect trans rights, in particular in so-called trans-exclusionary feminists.

In addition to anti-gender activists as explained so far, in Italy – though to a lesser extent – we also find other actors involved in anti-feminist discourses, represented especially by clusters of men’s rights groups (Shvanyukova 2022). In a study conducted by Farci and Righetti (2019, cited in Shvanyukova 2022) on the Italian Men’s Rights Activists, the authors identify a masculinist backlash taking place especially in the digital environments (the so-called “manosphere”, see Cannito et al. 2021). As the authors explain “this revival, however, is rather ambivalent, since it oscillates between a narrative explicitly hostile to feminism and a more subtle (albeit still problematic) postfeminist

discourse that considers feminism anachronistic and lacking legitimacy because it has seemingly already been largely successful” (2019, 765). Within this framework, we find first a fierce anti-feminist rhetoric that mobilizes “oppressed” men against women as a privileged group and the feminist movement in particular. This type of narrative considers gender inequalities as still existing, but affecting primarily men rather than women. Consequently, for instance, it reinterprets domestic violence against men and divorced or separated fathers (and their children), perpetrated by women and feminists having the “power that monopolises the legal and politics systems” (Farci and Righetti 2019, 772). On this issue, there is clear convergence with anti-gender organizations, which promotes fathers’ rights (see Pillon draft bill, for instance), shared custody of children, is opposed to same-sex civil unions and gender education in schools. Indeed, in 2012 the Manifesto of the Italian Male Movement was signed by MRA organizations and the Movement for Life, paving the way to the rise of the MRA movement in Italy (*ibid.*). As evidenced in the study, these years see the birth of several social media pages denouncing violence against men, such as A Voice for Men Italia, No to Violence Against Men (*No alla violenza sugli uomini*).

Another type of antifeminism emerges from other groups such as Men’s rights – Equity and Humanity (Diritti Maschili – Equità e Umanità) that use victimization and reverse discrimination to “discredit any feminist analysis of structural and political inequalities as unnecessary and unreasonable” in which “despotic and chronically dissatisfied” feminists are promoting a feminist revision of history in which men are depicted as oppressors. (*ibid.*, 773). In this case, the overlapping with anti-gender stances is less obvious, since these groups also endorse – like feminism – a social construction theory of gender that challenges biological determinism into pre-assigned gender roles. Yet, the rejection of traditional gender roles is based on the assumption that women oppress men, and for this, men are paying the costs of the masculine role.

4. Themes and agendas

As mentioned in previous sections, anti-gender campaigns in Italy have been triggered by a series of policy proposals in the areas of LGBTQ+ rights and reproductive rights, along with education (cf. section 1 and 2). It is fair to assume that these are the areas in which the movement has been mostly vocal and based on which it sought the backing of populist radical right parties. Concerning the other policy areas, notably the labor market, migration and gender-based violence (except in the case of hate crimes and homotransphobia), the movement’s agenda has been less developed – in fact, in these areas we would need to look more closely at the political manifestos and proposals put forward by the League and Brothers of Italy, rather than the anti-gender organizations (Lavizzari and Pirro, forthcoming).

4.1. Labor market

To illustrate the anti-gender movement’s agenda on this issue, the “Verona Declaration” adopted by the WCF highlights a need for anti-discrimination initiatives for women in the labor market. Within the framework of women’s rights, the movement supports policies that promote a life-work balance for women set on their primary role as mothers and care-givers: “be able to reconcile work and motherhood by favoring long-term parental leave and – for those who so freely decide – flexible, part-time, or telecommuting work; Choose to dedicate themselves exclusively to children and the family,

with adequate remuneration for home work where the spouse's salary is not sufficient for a free and dignified existence".¹²

4.2. Health and reproductive rights

Together with LGBTQ+ rights, reproductive rights have been and continue to be at the center of the anti-gender movement's agenda. Considering its historical roots, the anti-gender movement rises from a portion of the Italian pro-life movement, which in the early 2010s took distance from the "mainstream" and traditional pro-life movement, accusing it of being "too soft" on these issues (see Prearo 2020 for a careful reconstruction of this phase). As testified by the numerous names given to the newly formed anti-gender organizations, such as ProLife Onlus, Lawyers for Life or ProLife & Family, the protection of biological life rests at the very heart of their claims. Even by just having a quick look at the websites of these organizations it is possible to discern how much of their agenda is focused on anti-abortionist politics. Besides opposing abortion, in the Italian context meaning being against the Law 194 (1978), which gives access to abortion, anti-gender activists fiercely oppose Law 40 (2004) on assisted medical procreation as well as surrogacy (Ammaturo 2020). These two topics are often linked to other issues, such as surrogate motherhood used by same-sex couples to have children, as well as, in line with the Catholic doctrine promoting a culture of life from conception to death, euthanasia.

Another health issue that is perhaps less visible but continuously present in the projects and campaigns of the movement concerns drug consumption by youth and adolescents, and particularly the opposition to any legalization measure.

Recently, the pandemic also brought about a focus on vaccination with the spreading of skeptical view of vaccination by several leaders of the anti-gender movement. The strong protection by international allies such as the then US President Donald Trump and the Brazilian President Jair Bolsonaro—both of which had promoted Covid 19 denialist and anti-vax positions—positioned anti-gender groupings in the anti-vax camp, contributing organizational resources (e.g. through organizations like the *Popolo delle Mamme*, the People of the Mothers), discursive frames (pointing at the emergence of a dictatorship, the victimization of the good people, the urgency to fight an absolute evil) as well as slogans, like "Hands off from Children" (della Porta 2023; Ayoub and Stoeckl 2023). Fake news about the presence of aborted fetuses in vaccination were bridged with adaptation of the QAnon conspiracies to promote anti-gender positions.¹³

4.3. Migration

In this realm, anti-gender actors essentially adhere to the arguments put forward by the radical right, in the classical entanglement between religion, populism and gender (Giorgi 2022). Still, much less emphasis is put on the issue of "migrants" as a threat to the national or Christian/Catholic identity by anti-gender organizations: the "real outsiders" threatening the existence of the traditional, natural family remain the gender ideologists, above all LGBTQ+ people and feminists. However, connections to the demographic winter are present in the Italian anti-gender discourse too, especially when coming from exponents of the League and Brothers of Italy, which call for the moral duty for a strong pro-natality politics (pro-life) in order to face the current demographic crisis: "Everyone agreed on the fact that the policy of relaunching the birth rate in Italy, and against the demographic winter, is one

¹² <https://www.profam.org/verona-declaration-adopted-at-wcf-xiii-on-31-march-2019/>

¹³ <https://ilmanifesto.it/trump-dio-e-putin-viaggio-nella-tana-di-qanon-in-italia>

of the most serious moral duties of the present historical moment. According to the Honorable Procaccini [Brothers of Italy], the demographic crisis cannot be resolved with mass immigration, which on the contrary 'must be governed and qualitative'. Without reaching the 'replacement of Europeans with other populations of the world'. The message of continuing to have few children because there are migrants who arrive at the door is wrong and irresponsible.

Favoring the Italian birth rate is 'on the other hand the way to carry forward the witness of our civilization, of our history to those who will come after us'¹⁴. This type of messages are part of a radical right-wing discourse supporting nativism and connecting natality with exclusive nationalism, resonant with the fascist past.

4.4. LGBTQ+ rights

LGBTQ+ rights, enshrined in the framework of gender ideology colonization, have been one of the main targets of anti-gender campaigns in Italy (cf. section 1 and 2). Since the start of the mobilization in 2013, anti-gender activists have been resolute opponents of any of such rights, beginning with the bill on same-sex civil unions (Cirinnà bill, Law 76/2016¹⁵), which has been nonetheless passed into law; the stepchild adoption procedure, eventually scratched from the civil unions bill; the various bills to include specific punishments for crimes committed against homosexual and trans people in the penal code (draft bill Scalfarotto, 2013 and draft bill Zan 2020, 2021), none of them has been approved by both the Parliament and the Senate, leaving Italy de facto without a law against homotransphobia. Blamed as the main gender ideologists, LGBTQ+ people along with the LGBTQ+ lobby are responsible for the imposition and spreading of gender ideology in the society: the active and fierce opposition to any advancement in terms of LGBTQ+ rights is the cornerstone – together with pro-life stances – of anti-gender campaigns in Italy.

4.5. Gender-based violence

Besides being opposed to introducing homotransphobic crimes in the penal code, as well as any school program educating and raising awareness around these issues, the movement condemns gender-based violence as violence against women in two major ways. First, abortion is interpreted as violence against women, which anti-gender activists label as the "primary cause of femicide in the world". Second, the anti-gender groups denounce the exploitation and commodification of women's bodies, above all through prostitution, the "uterus for rent" practice – namely, surrogate motherhood – and the hypersexualisation of society, notably young girls.

Another cause of concern in this area is represented by pornography and in particular access to pornographic material by minors, which is supposed to favor abusive and violent behaviors against women on behalf of youngster, as well as being source of pedophilia – although no mention is made about pedophilia within the Church.

In the context of the broader anti-gender backlash happening in Italy, we should also consider how the issue of gender-based violence is often linked to anti-migrant stances, depicting othered men

¹⁴ Translated by the author from: <https://www.provitaefamiglia.it/blog/inverno-demografico-il-convegno-dei-conservatori-e-riformisti-europei>

¹⁵ <https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/id/2016/05/21/16G00082/sg>

(migrant, non-white men) as the perpetrators of violence against women (representatives of the Motherland, reproducers of the nation, its culture and identity) (Colella 2021).

4.6. Education

The topic of gender education in schools is one of the major issues around which anti-gender actors have mobilized. The question of modifying the educational programs so that the school curricula are in line with gender equality principles and the fight against discrimination has been object, over time, of various bills. It should be noted, among others, the presentation of two different bills on the subject: the bill on the introduction of gender education, in the Senate, and the bill on affective education, presented in the Parliament. The first is the already mentioned draft bill Fedeli (2014), which aimed at introducing a “clear gender perspective in all educational processes” at school and university levels – so, in this case, it is not meant as the introduction of new courses on gender education, but rather as a didactical approach to existing ones. The second, also known as draft bill Costantino¹⁶ (2013), is similar to the first but it adds a new course on “affectivity” (one hour per week) in schools, and, at the university level, with the introduction of courses on gender studies.

Finally, with the approval of the Law 107/2015 reforming the school system – known as “Good School” reform – a regulatory provision was inserted on the subject of “education for gender equality”, which should represent the implementation of very general principles about gender equality. It is a compromise provision on the subject of gender education, which does not allow for the introduction of effective gender and affective education instead.

The debate on the introduction of gender and/or affective education in schools provoked since the beginning the reaction of the Catholic world, more broadly (through Catholic parents’ associations, for instance), even at the institutional level of the Church. Cardinal Bagnasco, former President of the Italian Episcopal Conference, claimed in 2015 that the diffusion of school books promoting gender diversity aims at “colonizing the minds of children and youth, with an anthropological vision that is wrong and without the authorization of parents”¹⁷. In this field, therefore, accusations by anti-gender actors have been particularly vocal, mostly based on a series of fake news – according to which, among others, masturbation techniques would be taught to children in schools, or homosexuality as a way of living (whatever that means). Discursively, from anti-gender perspective, education is indeed one of the three main channels through which gender theories and ideologies are spread, and possibly the most dangerous one since it targets young people and it aims at bypassing parents’ control. For instance, the anti-gender organization ProLife & Family has a constantly updated file¹⁸, in which they report a “selection of the main projects and initiatives applied in Italian schools, inspired by gender theory – a product of ‘gender studies’ (in English in the original) – or/and by homosexualist theories of LGBT associations.” (2023, 8).

More recently, the anti-gender movement has identified a “new” target in the realm of education policies, although it concerns transphobic crimes more broadly. This concerns the so-called “alias career”, according to which trans students in schools can use their preferred name instead of the given name (Gender Lens 2022). As Massimo Prearo (2022) explains “New realities and new instances have lined up, giving shape to a campaign, speeches and actions whose goal is to oppose, hinder, prevent

¹⁶ <https://www.camera.it/leg17/126?tab=2&leg=17&idDocumento=1510&sede=&tipo>

¹⁷ https://www.ansa.it/sito/notizie/politica/2015/01/26/bagnasco-no-manuali-gender-a-scuola_77d240cf-f778-4320-a20c-d4e9bc9b1607.html

¹⁸ <https://www.provitaefamiglia.it/media/userfiles/files/dossier-gender-21-gennaio-2023.pdf>

the recognition of the trans experience, especially when this concerns young people and adolescents. The debate on and against the DDL Zan constituted a political opportunity for the media coverage of this new mobilization campaign and therefore for the constitution of an anti-trans front [...] In this sense, the recent establishment of the Italian group *Genitori De Gender* [Parents De Gender] has facilitated the introduction in Italy of these pseudo-scientific models which have easily been appropriated – on apparently divergent fronts – by both the anti-gender movements and groups of that radical gender critical feminism, managing to obtain media visibility on television and in the press.” The pseudo-scientific models are based on a “reparatory” assumption that functions as a counter-discourse to the affirmative model, and according to which – among other hypotheses – trans youth would identify as such because of external social pressures such as getting along with other trans youth, information disseminated through the social media and networks, and affirmative policies promoted in schools that would push young people to identify as trans (so-called Rapid-Onset Gender Dysphoria, see Prearo 2022).¹⁹

5. Repertoires of action

The most commonly used repertoires during the anti-gender campaign in Italy are: conferences and public meetings, demonstrations and direct actions, lobbying activities and online activism and social media campaigns (Lavizzari 2020, 70-73).

The first, *conferences and public meetings* on “gender theory” and “gender ideology” had a strong influence in diffusing imaginaries and visions about the reality and values proposed and endorsed by the movement. During the period of time between 2013 and 2016, events of this type were scheduled on a weekly basis, everywhere in Italy, from the smallest province to the biggest metropolitan areas. This type of action was notably significant in terms of numbers. Some of the conferences, or public meetings, were also specifically directed toward sensitization campaigns in favor of the monitoring of educational activities around gender equality issues. Such conferences and meetings take the form of “frontal lectures” in which ad-hoc experts (lawyers, doctors, scholars, journalists, intellectuals) carefully detail the movement’s position on gender and sexuality issues. The large-scale diffusion of these events was contingent on the availability of physical spaces – for the most part, they took place in churches’ properties, municipal halls and schools. The strong connections with public institutions, at the local and regional levels, granted significant support to the organizers, not only in terms of economic resources, but also in terms of public legitimacy.

The second major type of collective action employed were *demonstrations and direct actions*. In particular, the wave of demonstrations in the form of symbolic protest that the Standing Sentinels organized in hundreds of Italian public squares, and, this time in the form of national events, the Family Day and Marches for Life. As already stated, the Family Day constituted the major event which unites activists and associations of the movement, as well as their sympathizers, in a single public demonstration. These events have been strategically used by the main organizations involved, such as LMPTI and CDNF, as a prime stage to show the *unity and worthiness* of the movement through the display of coordinated behavior – such as shared signs, colors, symbols, dress and chants – and the participation of political figures, namely members of the Parliament. In these events, symbols and codes reflecting traditional gender binaries (“pink and blue”, “mom and dad”) were used to transmit the ideological stance of the movement. Public display of posters, often with anti-gay messages, was also very common. One such example happened before a major convention of LMPTI in Rome, in

¹⁹ <https://www.valigiablu.it/carriera-alias-scuola/>

October 2015, when the city was covered with abusive posters displaying slogans such as “No More Gay!”, “Stop gay marriage and adoption”, followed by further episodes of anti-abortion posters with pictures of fetuses. It is in this repertoire that we find clear evidence of imitation dynamics across the opposing movements, and particularly in the adoption of specific practices such as *flashmobbing* and public performances in symbolic arenas, such as in front of the seat of the Italian government and cities’ major squares.

The third main category of actions employed included *lobbying activities* of various kinds. The movement was granted access to multiple arenas in the political and institutional field, such as attendance at parliamentary hearings, and through direct connections to political parties, members of the Parliament and the Senate. These affiliations helped the movement to gain the support of public administrations on a range of “anti-gender measures”, including the removal of books on sexual and gender education from public libraries and schools, the cancellation of courses in schools and even the enactment of “special measures” to assist parents in monitoring the spreading of gender ideology. In general, anti-gender actors maintain a capacity – also because of the religious networks in which they are embedded, which in turn in Italy traditionally have extensive power and influence inside public administrations and the third sector more broadly – to infiltrate multiple public services that deal with women’s health issues (and choices) and reproductive rights. This aspect is also connected to the capacity to attract public resources, i.e. funding, at the local and regional level.

A fourth type of action was centered on *social media campaigns* and *information*. Contemporary examples of these channels are increasingly online-centered: organizations’ websites, forums, blogs, social networks and most recently emailing lists. These channels stood out from others for two reasons: first, they have been exploited to discredit information transmitted by the national press and to provide an alternative means of communication; and second, they were of primary importance in the recruitment of volunteers. The organic dissemination of relevant information through websites, blogs and especially social networks advertised by associations, or shared between the followers themselves, has been instrumental in the spread of ideas and information.

Finally, other types of actions include social assistance to families as well as legal actions, at every level of jurisdiction, “to defend the fundamental rights and prerogatives of the family”.²⁰

6. Frames of arguments

In Italy, one of the first attempts to propose a theoretical and political translation of the Vatican’s position on “gender ideology” was realized in 2007 by the association *Scienza & Vita* (Science & Life) in the series *Notebooks Science & Life* on “Identity and Gender” (Lavizzari and Prearo 2016). The publication is a collection of contributions from a number of Italian and French authors which addresses the problems posed by the concept of gender in its theoretical and ideological form, tying it to the questions of feminism and marriage, and more generally to homosexuality. The anti-gender narrative thus develops through the spread of an intrinsically Catholic knowledge and culture: a double dynamic of *translation* and *importation* of the anti-gender debate born in the international arena, built on a strong, “collective identity”, namely the (traditional, natural, heterosexual) “family”. In synthesis, the anti-gender movement has articulated an interpretative scheme for sexual morality based on three main pillars: identity, values and tradition (Lavizzari 2020).

²⁰ See also: <https://www.provitaefamiglia.it/chi-siamo>

The anti-gender movement reacts to discourses belonging to feminist and LGBTQ+ movements' repertoires. This reaction is based on the opposition to political claims and theoretical concepts that these movements have helped to produce. In this, the anti-gender movement is not only opposed to the claims of feminist and LGBTQ+ struggles, but also to the epistemic project, negating the legitimacy of the theories underlying these struggles (Garbagnoli and Prearo 2017; Lavizzari 2020). This reaction has been iterated through a discursive field that uses the references and stylistic grammar of feminist and LGBTQ+ movements – that is, in particular, through mirroring strategies – in order to pull them apart, transform their meaning and delegitimize them (Lavizzari 2020; Lavizzari and Siročić 2022). Relying on the opposition between science, nature and ideology, the movement presents itself as a project of truth, opposed to the manipulation of knowledge, legal order and educational systems, enacted by “Gender”. The term is strictly reported in English and capitalized, to evoke an unknown entity that threatens our culture as Catholic and Italian. The “Gender”, in fact, is a theoretical paradigm (or an ideology, a theory, etc.) diffused by the Anglo-Saxon world to colonize our culture (Lavizzari 2020). In terms of framing strategies, the movement appropriated the discourse of human rights, particularly in the realm of sexual citizenship and so-called human anthropology, including references to a child’s right to be raised by a mother and a father, and the right of parents to educate their children on subjects related to gender and sexuality, as written in the Italian constitution. This type of framing bridges the protection of the ‘traditional heterosexual family’ and the integrity of the Italian identity and nation, while denying equal rights to LGBTI subjects – interpreted by the anti-gender movement’s actors as ‘special’ rights or individual rights, as opposed to the universality of human rights. Again, we observe the adoption of pseudoscientific language on gender, in terms not only of appeals to law and rights, but also of the use of medical terminology (Lavizzari and Siročić 2022).

Among the most recurring arguments we find the pathologizing and de-humanizing of LGBTQ+ people. During public conferences, homosexuals’ affectivity and sexuality is degraded as sub-human behavior in a strategy for vilification (Lavizzari 2020). The first victims of the “pathology of gender” and “homosexuality”, therefore, are children, defenseless by definition, and exposed to the risk that their growth and natural development may run into the ideological denial of the need to be born and raised in a heterosexual family. The reference to “the supreme interest of the child” is the central *topos* of sexual panic (Robinson 2008). The defense of children’s innocence from corruption is a powerful discursive device, which produces a profound emotional and moral shock. On the one hand, children represent the idea of “nature par excellence”, as they are not yet contaminated by the corruption of man (or gender). The same idea of violated innocence is framed in terms of severe surveillance of children’s sexuality at the exclusive right of parents (not of the educational system). This trend reflects a major frame found in the discourse against gender education in schools along with the medicalization of discourses around young people sexuality. The medicalization of discourses implicitly relates to the possibility of recovering and recodifying a deviant behavior (Lavizzari 2020).

The labeling of LGBTIQ+ people as led by irrational instincts and individualistic interests that are not oriented to the project (natural and/or divine) of procreation suggests that subjective arbitrariness flows into arbitrariness in the law, recalling the frame of the totalitarian state and the “dictatorship of gender”. The transition from the manipulation of reality to the totalitarian state is a constant in the movement narrative, and reflects the alignment with the idea of colonization. Underlying this argument is the assimilation of homosexual subjects with rich, European, white, male, liberal characters who can afford to satisfy their whims. The reference to neocolonialism, slavery and the exploitation of women’s bodies is a key theme that pervades all interventions on the draft bill on civil

unions and in particular on the regulation of *stepchild adoption* and artificial reproduction technologies.

Moreover, the anti-gender discourse develops a populist rhetoric, which concentrates its content on the welfare of families. Such rhetoric opposes universalist rights to the claims of LGBTQ+ movement. The LGBTQ+ movement's opinions on sexual citizenship are re-appropriated and represented as a set of selfish privileges, as the commodification of the person that divert the few available economic resources from ordinary people and their families to their own cause. Extreme right *CasaPound Italia*, for instance, subscribed to this kind of argument when it decided to join the anti-gender campaign back in 2014. International institutions also play an important role in this "ideological colonization", a project spearheaded by the European Union and the World Health Organization. Anti-gender actors denounce a form of social change imposed by external players pressuring Italy to align its sexual and gender policies with other Western countries in order to denounce such institutions as foreign agents and promoters of values that are antithetical to Italian identity.

For example, Elisa Bellé and Barbara Poggio (2018) looked at the websites and documents produced by the ProLife and La Manif pour tous Italia organizations. Their analysis shows the idea of a "silent" social majority that shares Catholic values being "under attack", threatened by powerful global networks of "organized minorities" including LGBTQ+ activists and radical feminists. Similarly, the *League* party and neo-fascist movements and parties exploit the "anti-gender" discourse to claim they are defending Italian culture and identity against globalization (Garbagnoli and Prearo 2018; Pavan 2019): "[t]heir political aim is to attribute the crisis of Italian "tradition" (in terms of the country's identity and socio-economic structures) to outside enemies—be they migrants, globalized financial forces, international networks of LGBT and feminist activists, or supranational institutions supporting the globalization of sexual minorities' rights" (Trappolin 2022).

7. Transnational connections

The double transnational and national dimension of the anti-gender mobilization is an aspect widely discussed in the literature (see Paternotte and Kuhar 2018). It has already been highlighted how such movements are part of a "global" phenomenon characteristic of the neoliberal era and its populist (radical right) moment. For instance, there is ample evidence of the diffusion of the "Manif pour tous" format, including slogans, symbols and repertoires of action across different European contexts – including Italy. Mechanisms of "localization" from the transnational to the national within the context of movement diffusion have been also identified in the literature (Lavizzari and Siročić 2022).

Looking at the emergence of anti-gender organizations in the early 2010s in Italy along with major international events such as the WCF in Verona, clearly shows the transnational connections among multiple actors around few key figures acting as brokers or "connectors". For instance, it is evidenced how Italian Catholic politician Luca Volonté – chairman of the parliamentary group European People's Party at the Council of Europe from 2010 and 2013 – had a key role in connecting the President of Manif Pour Tous in France (Ludovine de la Rochère) and key actors in the anti-gender mobilization in Italy, namely Filippo Savarese (former spokesperson of LMPTI – Family Generation, then member of Prolife & Family and later responsible for the Italian section of the transnational platform Citizen Go), Maria Rachele Ruiu (LMPTI – Family Generation and candidate in the lists of Brothers of Italy) and Jacopo Coghe (vice-president of ProLife & Family and vice-president of the WCF) (Prearo 2020).

These entanglements are also clearly observable during the WCF in 2019, attended by representatives of international organizations, such as Brian Brown from the International Organization for Family, Ignacio Arsuaga founder of Citizen Go, alongside national representatives and “connecting” figures such as Toni Brandi, founder of ProLife Onlus (former ProLife News) which had a crucial role in importing “anti-gender” texts and “knowledge” from France (Prearo 2020). Moreover, as explained by Luca Trappolin (2022), “[t]he *League* used the WCF also to strengthen its links with European, US and Russian right-wing political forces. The *International Organization for the Family* (IOF) co-organized the event, and right-wing leaders from other countries were invited to give talks. The speakers included Igor Dodon (President of the Moldovan Republic), and Katalin Novák (Vice President of the Hungarian *Fidesz* party and State Secretary for Family, Youth and International Affairs).”

8. Explanations of the anti-gender backlash

Scholars explaining the emergence and relative success of the anti-gender backlash in Italy resort to two main sets of explanations. The first, similar to the anti-gender backlash in other European countries, ascribes it to the emergence of a broader backlash politics (Della Porta et al. 2022; Serughetti 2021). In particular, authors point to a crucial topic that is gaining attention in the literature on gender and politics as well as among scholars of populism – that is, the *instrumentation of religion* by populist parties, most notably from the radical right (but see Giorgi 2022 for a discussion). In Italy, the renewal of the League party under the leadership of Matteo Salvini has been based in a “mixed appeal for defending traditional values—such as gender roles, the (heterosexual and mononuclear) family, the Catholic religion—with an authoritarian “law and order” conception of the State and an emphasis on the need to preserve Western traditions as embedded in the Italian nation (Della Porta et al 2022, 10). As Giorgia Serughetti explains (2020, 121) “[t]he “gender” favors the alliance between conservative forces also for its ability to bring together under a single label a plurality of controversial issues referable to the opposing camp of progressive forces. As an umbrella term, “gender” is used with a semantic scope that goes beyond the strict reference to the family and sexual order, evoking a wider threat to the life of individuals and communities, for which responsibility is attributed to democratic-liberal thinking.”

The second, refers to the internal dynamics and transformation of the Italian Catholicism in the past decade. Prearo (2020) carefully reconstructs the “origins of the evil” by proposing a reading of the gender public policies emerged in the European and international arena, such as within the context of UN conferences during the 1990s (the 1994 conference on population and development in Cairo and the 1995 conference on women in Beijing). Importantly, while tracing the birth of the anti-gender cause, the author distinguishes between events happening at the international level – including their progressive translation into the national context – and the *theological and doctrinal developments* around the increasing politicization of the concepts of gender, sexuality and family. In fact, the author argues that the battle over concepts, language and terminology used in the realm of gender politics, is effectively enshrined in the broader contestation of a *democratic paradigm* based on “the political and institutional realization of the secularization process of European societies through the implementation of public policies in the matters of gender, sexuality and family” (p. 55). This contestation is at once *ideological*, carried out by representatives of the Church and the Vatican against the adoption of gender sensitive and gender mainstreaming policies within international agencies, as well as *political*, in the streets and the squares of European cities at the hands of activists and groups belonging to a minoritarian, radical, and contentious form of Catholic activism.

These internal dynamics reflect a deeper crisis that has been growing within the Church's institutions in the post-DC era, in the absence of a political party able to voice and defend Catholic concerns and positions in the electoral and political arenas, and effectively siding the Church outside these realms. At the same time, they represent the internal fracture between a majoritarian (mainstream) ecclesiastic Catholic movement and a minoritarian contentious Catholic movement, relatively autonomous from the Church ("extra-ecclesiastical"). The activism of this new Catholic movement is therefore twofold: it radicalizes the discourses, strategies and repertoires of action of the mainstream, ecclesiastic movement around the anti-gender cause through their actualization "from below", while simultaneously and symbolically distancing itself from the "Catholic élites". In order to do so, the exchange between the new Catholic movement and far-right parties activates three major functions: it contaminates the political agenda of political parties (*contaminating function*), it provides a road map of programmatic points to be followed in accordance with the anti-gender/pro-family stances (*programmatic function*), and it functions as an ideological glue that brings together conservative parties vis-à-vis progressive, leftist ones (*identitarian function*).

9. Counter-movements

Feminist and LGBTQ+ movements in Italy reacted to the rise of anti-gender movement and campaign at multiple levels. Indeed, opposing movements dynamics are central to understand the evolution of the anti-gender movement and, more broadly, the contentious politics of gender happening in the Italian context. Summarizing the response of (counter)movements to the anti-gender campaign, we can point to two major phases: the first took place during the public demonstrations organized by anti-gender actors from 2013 to 2016 especially. In this case, we witnessed to several protest events which involved both movements, reacting against each-others. Notable cases in this sense were the Standing Sentinels vigils (see picture below).

Source: Anna Lavizzari, Forlì, 2016

The second phase reacted not only to the anti-gender movement but to the rise of populist radical right parties in Italy, especially Matteo Salvini’s League in 2018, and especially the formalization of its alliance to the movement. A case in point here is the massive counterprotest organized by the *Non Una di Meno* transfeminist movement against the WCF, in 2019 (see Pavan 2020 for an analysis of that specific protest event).

10. Conclusion

Anti-gender organizations in Italy can be considered at once a forerunning case of this type of mobilizations in Europe and a relatively successful one. Born within the context of a crisis of Italian Catholicism, the movement has been able to affirm itself in the public and political sphere, defining the borders, content, and forms of a new and radical type of activism involving different actors – SMOs, political parties and groups, religious and secular actors, individuals (i.e. parents) – taking place at the national and transnational levels. Italian scholars have paid and continue to pay attention to anti-gender discourses and actions, although some areas remain less studied. For instance, in light of the recent political elections and the successful process of institutionalization undertaken by the movement since the 2015/16, we need to acquire more knowledge concerning the policy outcomes of the alliances between anti-gender actors and populist radical right parties. For instance, on December 6, 2022, newly elected Giorgia Meloni created a new national committee on bioethics, of which the new members for the most part come from different Catholic associations, are against abortion and endorse anti-gender claims. More can be said also on the transnational connections of the movement, especially in international arenas such as the European Parliament, religious fundamentalist lobbies working in the field of law and justice, as well as with other actors such as the Russian Orthodox Church, among others. Further research should also focus on the evolution of anti-gender rhetoric in recent years, expanding into a broader anti-elitist frame centered around the opposition to scientific and academic knowledge, not only concerning gender and gender studies but also including the recent no-vax positions.

11. Timeline

12. List of anti-gender/anti-feminist organizations²¹

Name of the organization (original)	Name of the organization (English)	Anti-gender or anti-feminist?	Logo of the organization	Head of the organization (in the period 2010-2021)	Web-page (social media)	Size of the organization (if available)	Comment (brief description)
La Manif Pour Tous Italia (2013) Generazione Famiglia	La Manif Pour Tous Italy Family Generation	Anti-gender		Jacopo Coghe	http://www.generazionefamiglia.it	n/a	Leading Italian anti-gender organization active in protecting “natural traditional family” of a father, a mother and children, against same-sex marriage/civil unions, surrogate motherhood, gender and sexual education
Comitato Difendiamo i Nostri Figli Associazione Family Day – Difendiamo i nostri figli	Committee to defend our children Association Family Day – Defend our children	Anti-gender Pro-life		Massimo Gandolini	https://familyday.info	n/a	Leading anti-gender organization active in protecting “natural traditional family” of a father, a mother and children, organizers of the Family Day, against gender and sexual education in school, LGBTQ+ rights
ProVita Onlus – Notizie ProVita (2012-2018)	ProLife Onlus – ProLife News	Anti-gender Pro-life		Toni Brandi	n/a	n/a	Predecessor of ProLife & Family, with same purposes and members. The former ProLife Onlus was attached to the specialized magazine ProLife News

²¹ I list here the most visible, vocal “ad-hoc” anti-gender organizations (cf. section 3).

ProVita & Famiglia (2019)	ProLife & Family	Anti-gender Pro-life		Toni Brandi	https://www.provitaefamiglia.it	110 territorial circles as reported in the website	<p>Non-profit association that works in favor of children, of mothers and fathers, defends the right to life from conception to natural death, promotes the family founded on marriage between a man and a woman, and supports the freedom and educational priority of parents.</p> <p>Founded through the merging of LMPTI-Family Generation and ProLife Onlus</p>
Giuristi per la vita (2012)	Lawyers for life	Anti-gender Pro-life		Gianfranco Amato	http://www.giuristiperlavita.org	n/a	<p>Born in 2012 after the second national March for Life, organized by the European Movement in Defense of Life (Movimento Europeo Difesa Vita – MEVD). The association intends «to promote, defend and protect the right to life of every human being from conception to natural death - says the Statute - as the foundation of all other rights. The concept of life includes the natural structure of the family, understood as a union between a man and a woman based on marriage, the right of parents to educate their children and the freedom to publicly profess their religious faith</p>

Citizen Go		Anti-gender		Ignacio Arsuaga; Filippo Savarese head of the Italian satellite	https://www.citizen-go.org/it	17.431.628 active citizens as reported in the website	Transnational platform involved in petitions and social media campaigns against gender, organizer of the Bus delle Libertà (Freedom Bus) displaying anti-gender messages in Italian and European cities
Sentinelle in Piedi	Standing Sentinels	Anti-gender	n/a	n/a	http://sentinelleinpiedi.it/chi-siamo/	n/a	Born after the French Veilleurs Debut, it is an informal network of concerned citizens and members of Catholic associations that started protesting in 2013 against the Scalfarotto bill and the civil unions bill

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POLAND

Magdalena Muszel

1. Introduction

Over the years there were numerous campaigns initiated by the anti-gender and anti-feminist groups in Poland. In the studied period of 2010-2021 few of these campaigns however played a more important role than others, focusing on different groups and creating different 'others' - enemies that could gather supporters around. These campaigns - described in details in the following sections - revolved around: reproductive rights, the so-called 'gender ideology' and LGBT+ community.

The first campaigns - connected to reproductive rights - were undertaken already in the early 1990s. In 1993: The Act on Family Planning, Protection of the Human Foetus and the Conditions for the Permissibility of Abortion. The Act permitted abortion when:

- the pregnancy poses a risk to the life or health of the pregnant woman;
- prenatal tests or other medical indications point to a high probability of severe and irreversible impairment of the foetus or an incurable life-threatening illness;
- there is a justified suspicion that the pregnancy has resulted from a prohibited act (up to 12 weeks from conception);

On 30 August 1996, the Sejm amended the 1993 law, moderating it by adding the premise of a woman's difficult personal situation as permitting legal termination of pregnancy. The law lasted less than a year. On 27 May 1997, the Constitutional Tribunal in its full 12-member body - with three dissenting opinions - ruled that the provision introducing this premise was incompatible with the constitutional provisions in force under the so-called Little Constitution of 1992.

This created a legal blueprint and for many years pro- and anti-choice groups tried to push forward their agenda to liberalize or further restrict the abortion law in Poland. But with the political victory of the conservative Law and Justice (Prawo i Sprawiedliwość, PiS) in 2015, when the party secured full political power, having a majority in both chambers of the parliament and the presidential office, the situation has changed. PiS has become an important ally for the anti-choice movements, funneling money into anti-choice (and other, also anti-gender) organizations, becoming a political ally in position of power and with many activists from the far right receiving high positions within state institutions. The first critical juncture was 2016 when a proposal to restrict the abortion law and make it impossible to terminate pregnancy. This was met with a huge grassroots response later known as the Black Monday or Black Protest. The scale of backlash against women participating in this campaign provides evidence of the anti-gender and anti-feminist nature of the environment behind the proposed amendment of the law.

The second part of this process could have been observed in 2020, when abortion in Poland was nearly banned by the decision of the Constitutional Court that has further restricted the so-called 'abortion compromise' of 1993. The protest wave of 2020 was the biggest protest cycle in Poland after 1989, involving hundreds of thousands of people on the streets and many others supporting the claims of the feminist movements. This protest cycle also triggered an anti-feminist backlash that tried to push forward the conservative agenda. In a rather unforeseen perspective, the participation in these protests have significantly changed the attitudes of Poles, mostly of the youngest generation, towards

the perception of, for example, the role of the Catholic Church as a moral and ethical leader, which had hitherto rarely been questioned in Poland, and the means of expression used during the protest (Muszel and Piotrowski 2022).

Another key debate used by the anti-gender movement was the so-called crusade against gender ideology that was initiated around 2012 and then the topic has been refreshed to be used before elections. It was particularly visible during discussions on adopting and later withdrawing from the Istanbul convention that calls for a stop of violence against women, especially when it is culturally motivated. In this case one of the key elements of criticism by the organizers of the campaigns was the reference to culturally motivated violence that was supposed to also include religious beliefs. The term gender ideology as well as gender invasion or gender crusade were used interchangeably and were often accompanied by terms such as Cultural Marxism. The use of the original word gender in the Polish name of the campaign has proven to be useful as only few people understood its meaning, and the term was not translated into Polish (that also not that many people understood).

Similarly, with gender ideology, another scarecrow used by the anti-gender and conservative movements was the threat theoretically posed by the LGBT community. As direct attacks on the community itself sparked a much more heated reaction, a term LGBT ideology was coined and later used with some small amendments, such as rainbow ideology and alike. The main threats coming from the supposed LGBT ideology were the subversion of the traditional and conservative model of family, gender roles, and often a threat post for children. The last one included not only linking homosexuality with paedophilia, as it was done by numerous anti-gender activists, right wing journalist and even mainstream politicians associated with the ruling party, but it was also pointed out to that talking about sexual minorities and in general offering sexual education might lead to a state of gender fluidity and unnecessary sexualization of children.

All of the above mentioned campaigns were used to maintain the state of alert within the society, or at least among voters of Law and Justice, the readiness of the electoral constituents to defend traditional values impersonated by the party itself, to maintain the state of mobilization and finally to remain in the state of stronghold under siege. According to populism scholars all of the above points sum up to a definition of populist politics.

2. Who is writing about it?

The topic of gender has made a noticeable appearance in the Polish scientific discourse among others through Inga Iwasiów (1999). However, one of the turning points in systemic gender research in Poland was 2003, when the Institute of Sociology at the Jagiellonian University, based on the previously developed empirical research and institutionalized didactic activity, created a new specialization: Socio-Cultural Identity of Gender and postgraduate studies under the same name, realized with the support of Norwegian funds in 2009-2011. The established unit, popularly known as gender studies, has become one of the most important not only in Poland, but also worldwide, which is reflected in numerous research projects, conferences (e.g. Gender in Polish Society, Gender-Economics-Migration, Academic Feminist Congress, Women's Utopias in Action) and cooperation with international institutions and universities in Europe and the USA. Currently, gender research at the Jagiellonian University continues in the Department of Population Studies, headed by Professor

Krystyna Slany¹. Certainly, the slowly emerging anti-gender discourse in ultra-conservative and right-wing circles was also an additional impulse that made gender studies of greater interest to Polish researchers than before.

In 2011, two important publications appeared: *Kalejdoskop genderowy: w drodze do poznania płci społeczno-kulturowej w Polsce* (Gender Kaleidoscope: on the way to understanding gender in Poland) (Slany et.al. 2011a) and *Gender w społeczeństwie polskim* (Gender in Polish society) (Slany et.al.2011b). As Krystyna Slany, who sat on the editorial board of both publications, emphasized, the primary aim of the books "is to provide Polish readers with a complex, multidimensional and intersectional knowledge of gender, deeply embedded in the context of Polish problems, while relating this issue to the findings of international research. Such a comparative approach shows on the one hand the current state of development of gender studies in Poland, their achievements, the topics taken up, their specificity, on the one hand, and the cross-cultural and cross-cultural similarity of gender issues on the other."(Slany et al. 2011b:14).

With the beginning of the anti-gender and anti-LGBT mobilisation in Poland around 2012 (Duda, 2016), we can also observe a mobilisation of scientific research not only on gender itself but also on the anti-gender and anti-LGBT movement and actors describing and analyzing the accompanying discourse and its sources, reflecting on and suggesting their motives and goals (Desperak, 2013; Desperak 2014; Odrowąż-Coates 2014; Majorek et al. 2014; Borkowski 2015; Jawor 2016; Szwed 2015; Man 2015; Chmura-Rutkowska et al. 2016a; Chmura-Rutkowska et al. 2016b; Chmura-Rutkowska et al. 2016c; Graff and Korolczuk 2017). The topic of anti-gender has been frequently addressed also in *Krytyka Polityczna*, a left-wing socio-political magazine that publishes articles and interviews with researchers working on anti-gender issues (Korolczyk and Graff 2016; Rzewska-Skłódowska 2016; Morska 2014; Ryś 2014; Graff 2014, Szczerbiak 2014; Sutowski 2014; Graff 2013, Stawiszyński 2013a, 2013b.)

Particularly noteworthy among the academic publications that appeared in the first years of the anti-gender mobilization is *Dogmat płci. Polska wojna z gender* (Gender dogma. The Polish war on gender) written by Marcin Duda (2016). The author has carefully followed the disputes around the gender category initiated by the misinterpretation of it presented by the Catholic Church. Duda succeeded in identifying the sources of anti-gender language, such as the 'figure of enquiry' (Duda 2016: 56) or the rhetoric of war (Duda 2016:73) and many others in the discourse conducted by the hierarchy of the Polish Catholic Church on gender. The topic of the Polish Catholic Church's discourse on gender was later also continued by, among others, Anna Szwed (2019).

The events of 2016 and the related women's protests across Poland have turned the interest of socio-political observers even more towards both feminist social movements as well as anti-gender movements and the actors they represent (Muszel and Piotrowski 2018, Muszel and Piotrowski 2019, Korolczuk et al. ed. 2019; Grzebalska and Pető 2018; Desperak 2019; Grochalska 2020, Muszel and Piotrowski 2020).

In 2020, there is a famous publication by Klementyna Suchanow entitled *To jest wojna. Kobiety, fundamentaliści i nowe średniowiecze* (This is War. Women, Fundamentalists and the New Middle Ages), in which the researcher presents the results of her systematic investigation, writing down in

¹ Department of Population Studies, Instytut of Sociology of the Jagiellonian University, https://sociologia.uj.edu.pl/en_GB/department-of-population-studies

meticulous detail the history of the development and international connections of the anti-gender movement in Poland and around the world, with the particular attention on the Ordo Iuris organization. At the same time, the author presents the recent history of Polish feminism through an ongoing written diary of women's protests starting from the turn of 2018/2019. The publication is also important because of another aspect: THIS IS WAR - became the slogan of the women's protests in Poland in 2020, but this rhetoric comes precisely from the people described by Suchanow, associated with ultra-right organizations², however in 2016 Marcin Duda (2016) also points to the war in the title of his book, and in 2019 then the Law and Justice MP (now Constitutional Tribunal judge) Krystyna Pawłowicz announced the start of the war on her Twitter account.

The last two years of research have focused, among other things, on topics such as the strategies of feminist/anti-gender movements, the organizational model of these mobilizations and what is novel about them in terms of patterns and actors, the place of social class in the movement and the political framework of the protest and mobilizations (Rozwadowski 2021; Graff and Korolczuk 2021; Grzebalska 2022; Gaweda Barbara 2022; Muszel and Piotrowski 2022; Muszel and Piotrowski 2022b).

The most recent and widely promoted and commented on publication is Agnieszka Graff and Elżbieta Korolczuk's book *Kto się boi gender (Who is afraid of gender?)* (2022), which was also published in English under the title "Anti-Gender Politics in the Populist Moment" (2022). The English title seems to be more in keeping with the content of the book. Korolczuk and Graff have not only provided a detailed calendar of the anti-gender movements, but by analysing the discursive practices of the anti-gender movements, reading anti-gender magazines, looking at the activities conferences and protest marches "anti-genderists" organize, they have also presented the nuanced motivations behind these ultra-conservative groups and the values they promote. One of the most important conclusions in the book is that anti-genderism is not a movement detached from political and social reality, but a response to the multiple crises of neoliberal policy-oriented countries, and that the contemporary feminist movement is identified with it by ultra-conservatives rather than seen as one of its critics, i.e. the opposite of how feminists themselves would like to be perceived. The authors point to the complex interdependence of feminism, neoliberalism and anti-genderism, for example, by referring to feminist attitudes - such as extreme individualism and moralism - as contributing factors to the radicalisation of conservative ideas. The term "welfare chauvinism" also appears in the book, which is a term for social benefits targeted at selected groups of citizens and excluding others (LGBTQ+ community, non-traditional families, refugees). Paradoxically, it also turns out that the social benefits introduced by the ultra-conservatives in Poland, which are targeted at selected groups of citizens and exclude others (the LGBTQ+ community, non-traditional families, refugees), which the authors describe as 'welfare chauvinism', are for women an important source of their financial stability and thus an indispensable means on the path to their emancipation. Finally, looking at mass feminist mobilizations in Poland and around the world, the authors argue that an effective response of progressive movements to the war on gender is populist feminism - intersectional, grassroots, entering into alliances with other marginalized groups.

² "Finally in our conversation the word 'war' falls. It is Komov who uses it, although I also have it in my head all the time.

- *This is war. An ideological war* -

- *So you are talking about war?*

- *Yes, it is a war. And we are now an oppressed minority.*" (Suchanow 2020:228-229)

3. The history of the anti-gender/anti-feminist movement, its context (strategies and arguments)

Despite the fact that Poland has had one of the strictest abortion laws in Europe since 1993, numerous political parties have often used the issue of abortion as a smokescreen, invoking it whenever they wanted to highlight other issues or controversies. In addition, the Catholic Church opposed even the smallest measures to liberalize reproductive rights in Poland and supported any action that might restrict women's rights. In the twenty-first century, they gained another strong supporter in the form of fundamentalist groups in particular, who adopted contemporary tactics to combat what they called 'gender ideology'.

Scholars often point to specific stages in the development of discourse on the topic of gender and LBGTQ+ rights in Poland, most often triggered by specific events or political decisions and clearly correlated with the election calendar (Grochalska, 2020; Korolczuk and Graff, 2022; Duda, 2016). As pointed out by Korolczuk and Graff, three major phases can be distinguished:

“The early one, 2012– 2015, was focused on sex education and opposition to the ratification of the Istanbul Convention, both accused of deceitfully introducing “gender ideology” into Polish culture. (...) The second phase unfolded in 2016– 2018, around the time when Law and Justice came to power. It was focused first on vilifying refugees as rapists and – after PiS won the elections – on abortion rights (...). The third phase has consisted mainly of attacks on LGBT minorities; it began in the spring of 2019 (...) the end of Poland’s anti- gender campaigns is nowhere in sight. (Korolczuk and Graff, 2022:71)

As observed by Monika Grochalska (2020) between 2011 and 2012 the term gender rarely appeared in public discourse in its literal sense and wording. And although issues that are intrinsic to gender for gender scholars emerged during this period, the term itself appeared quite rarely. In Polish politics the topic of gender identity has become present mainly due to the only transsexual member of the Polish parliament so far – Anna Grodzka (2011-2015). In this area of discourse, there have been verbal constructions clearly indicating that gender should be understood as a social construct. Anna Grodzka has pointed out in her public statements that transsexuals are people who "feel themselves to be of the opposite sex to the one they have been assigned in documents". On the other side of the political scene that time The Council of Europe Convention on Preventing and Combating Violence Against Women and Domestic Violence (the Istanbul Convention), civil partnerships and abortion have been explicitly labelled by right-wing politicians and publicists as “promoting feminism, abortion, homosexuality and other deviant behaviour” (Piłka, 2011). Marian Piłka (right-wing politician, publicist and historian) also saw "deviants" as a threat to spiritual and moral strength. During this period (2010) there was the first civic initiative project in the history of Poland establishing a total ban on abortion “Stop Abortion”, which was supported by several hundred thousand citizens³. It failed to obtain a majority in the Sejm and was rejected in 2011⁴.

³ Obywatelski projekt ustawy o zmianie ustawy o planowaniu rodziny, ochronie płodu ludzkiego i warunkach dopuszczalności przerywania ciąży oraz niektórych innych ustaw. Druk nr. 4222, [https://orka.sejm.gov.pl/Druki6ka.nsf/0/23E6F9AA70A2F2DFC125789B004349F5/\\$file/4222.pdf](https://orka.sejm.gov.pl/Druki6ka.nsf/0/23E6F9AA70A2F2DFC125789B004349F5/$file/4222.pdf)

⁴ Kalendarium zmian w prawie o warunkach przerywania ciąży, 04.11.2022, Sylwia Szotucha, Róża Rzepilińska, Mam Prawo Wiedzieć.pl, <https://mamprawowiedziec.pl/czytelnia/arttykul/kalendarium-zmian-w-prawie-o-warunkach-przerywania-ciazy> (10.01.2023)

Although it is difficult for researchers to pinpoint exactly when the anti-gender and anti-LGBTQ+ mobilisation in Poland began, April 2012 and the public expression of opposition to 'gender ideology' and the ratification of the Istanbul Convention by the then Minister of Justice Jarosław Gowin's are cited as one of the major starting points of the Polish anti-gender campaign (Graff and Korolczuk, 2022). Minister Gowin's main argument was that the Istanbul Convention is a hidden Trojan horse whose real aim is the destruction of traditional family. The narrative, according to which Polish feminists and politicians supporting the Istanbul Convention, civil partnerships and women's rights to abortion are traitors and part of an international conspiracy against the traditional gender order has also begun to be constructed and further supported by the Polish hierarchs of the Catholic Church. (Graff and Korolczuk, 2022).

The whole of 2013 has been a phase of escalating conflict in the discourse between liberal-left and conservative-Catholic circles. Another citizens' legislative initiative 'Stop Abortion' has appeared in the parliament. The Pro - Right to Life Foundation (Fundacja Pro-Prawo do Życia) collected more than 400,000 signatures⁵ of Poles who supported a ban on abortion in cases where "prenatal tests or other medical indications point to a high probability of severe and irreversible foetal impairment or an incurable life-threatening the disease" (Musiał, 2013). The representative of the Legislative Initiative Committee was Kaja Godek. The Sejm rejected the proposed bill at first reading⁶.

2013 was a year in which the word gender began to appear extremely frequently in public discourse and was discussed from various approaches. It was even chosen as the word of the year by a committee of linguists and cultural studies experts (Newsweek Polska 2014).

This "popularity" is reflected in the numerous articles and publications in popular media: (weekly and daily press, internet portals) published during this period, which in the titles reflect not only a vivid interest in the subject, but also a varied approach to it.

It means who? The third gender is coming⁷; Priest Oko's homoobsessions⁸; Gender ideology, after kindergartens, is pushing its way into primary schools. We parents have to oppose it somehow!⁹; Gender like Marxism¹⁰; Dispute over definition, war of conviction¹¹; Does the brain have gender?¹²;

⁵400 tys. podpisów pod projektem ws. zakazu tzw. aborcji eugenicznej, 02.07.2013, Prawo.pl: <https://www.prawo.pl/zdrowie/400-tys-podpisow-pod-projektem-ws-zakazu-tzw-aborcji-eugenicznej,239356.html> (03.01.2023)

⁶ Podsumowanie roku 2013, 07.01.2014, <https://stronazycia.pl/podsumowanie-roku-2013/> (03.01.2023)

⁷Ono czyli kto? Nadchodzi trzecia płeć, 30.07.2012, Beatriz Preciado, kultura.onet.pl <https://kultura.onet.pl/wiadomosci/ono-czyli-kto-nadchodzi-trzecia-plec/8295yk6>, (04.01.2023)

⁸Homoobsesje księdza Oko, 30.07.2013, Krzysztof Burnetko, Tygodnik Polityka, <https://www.polityka.pl/tygodnikpolityka/kraj/1550515,1,homoobsesje-ksiedza-oko.read>,

⁹Ideologia gender, po przedszkolach, wciska się do szkół podstawowych. My, rodzice, musimy się jakoś temu przeciwstawić!, 23.09.2013, W Polityce,

<https://wpolityce.pl/polityka/167024-ideologia-gender-po-przedszkolach-wciska-sie-do-szkol-podstawowych-my-rodzice-musimy-sie-jakos-temu-przeciwstawic>

¹⁰ Gender jak marksizm, Bogumił Łoziński, Tygodnik Gość Niedzielny 30/2013,

<https://www.gosc.pl/doc/1638197.Gender-jak-marksizm/2>

¹¹ Spór o definicje, wojna o przekonania, Izabela Łukomska-Pyżalska, 31.01.2013, Na Temat, <https://natemat.pl/blogi/izabellalukomska/49063,spor-o-definicje-wojna-o-przekonania>

¹² Cieśla J. (2013), Czy mózg ma płeć?, Polityka, numer specjalny, nr 4. https://www.polityka.pl/niezbednik/1540651,1,czy-mozg-ma-plec.read?gclid=Cj0KCQiA5NSdBhDfARIsALzs2EB8WeLUZgnJ-p_5gwrQYqpTddQ_LZULVSzpP2S3xzK06ivQ-aWLV3YaAqc3EALw_wcB (04.01.2023)

Gender: between ideology and science, or what it actually is.¹³; We are all a bit homo¹⁴; Gender - totalitarian ideology¹⁵; Gender - more dangerous than Marxism¹⁶; Trapped in a foreign body¹⁷; Homo out of the norm?¹⁸

Since 2013 public gender discourse has been building in eight senses (Grochalska, 2020:353-354):

- as a set of roles - in this view, socio-cultural gender is seen as the influence of cultural factors on the individual, which is felt in the form of social pressure to play social roles assigned to the individual on the basis of biological sex, with a perceived subordinate role for women and a dominant role for men.
- as an ideology - is an offshoot of Marxism, a new way of class struggle and harming women by masculinising them;
- as propaganda - involves the 'affirmation' of transvestites and homosexuals;
- as a derivative of mental sex - an understanding rooted in science - a medical fact;
- as an argument against discrimination - socio-cultural gender is seen as an expression of the struggle between the individual and the collective; in this sense, it is recognised that everyone has the right to shape their lives as they wish, regardless of gender, gender concepts are seen as a path to liberation from the dictates of other people's opinions;
- as a social fact - there is abundant evidence of the importance of cultural patterns in the formation of social roles; what is biological is related to nature, everything else is a cultural "superstructure"; to change limiting roles, it is necessary to use education through "living examples" (ex. female soldiers, female farmers, etc.);
- as scientific fact - in this discourse, scientific knowledge of gender is contrasted with backwardness, often referring to facts and myths about the differences between men and women;
- as a consequence of relativism - relativism as a 'sign of our times', a negative phenomenon, the abandonment of traditional values; the abandonment of collectivism in favor of individualism.

2013 was also the year when the voice of representatives of the Catholic Church became particularly visible in the discussion on gender, and as in the global context, also in the Polish context, the Catholic Church became the main force behind anti-gender and anti-feminist campaigns.

¹³ Gender: między ideologią a nauką, czyli co to właściwie jest, 18.12.2013, Paweł Rzewuski, Portal Histmag, <https://histmag.org/Gender-miedzy-ideologia-a-nauka-czyli-co-to-wlasciwie-jest-8845>

¹⁴ Bratkowska M. (2013), Wszyscy jesteście trochę homo, Wprost, nr 29., <https://www.wprost.pl/tygodnik/408252/wszyscy-jestesmy-troche-homo.html> (05.01.2023)

¹⁵ Cichobłazińska A. (2013), Gender – ideologia totalitarna. Wywiad z ks. Dariuszem Oko, Niedziela, <http://www.niedziela.pl/artukul/106423/nd/>, (05.01.2023)

¹⁶ Jędrzejczyk M. (2013), Gender groźniejsze od marksizmu. Wywiad z ks. abp. Henrykiem Hoserem, przewodniczącym Zespołu Ekspertów ds. Bioetycznych Konferencji Episkopatu Polski, ordynariuszem warszawsko-praskim, Nasz Dziennik, <https://naszdziennik.pl/wiara-kosciol-w-%20polsce/24344,gender-grozniejsze-od-marksizmu.html> (05.01.2023)

¹⁷ Smolińska I., Bratkowska M. (2013), Uwięzieni w obcym ciele, Wprost, nr 7. <https://www.wprost.pl/tylko-u-nas/387988/uwizieni-w-obcym-ciele.html> (05.01.2023)

¹⁸ Środa Magdalena (2013), Homo poza normą? Wprost, nr. 7, <https://www.wprost.pl/tygodnik/387506/homo-pozza-norma.html> (05.01.2013)

For the hierarchy of the Catholic Church, one of the most important sources of knowledge about gender and, at the same time, an inspiration for the construction of an anti-gender discourse in Poland, are also books of Gabriele Kuby (2007) (to the Polish edition of which the foreword was written by Cardinal Hoser), Marguerite A. Peeters (2010) or the publication *Idea gender jako wyzwanie dla teologii* (The idea of gender as a challenge for theology) (Jucewicz & Machinek, 2009). Gabriele Kuby seems to be a particularly valuable inspiration, most often cited by Polish priests and representatives of the ultra-right environment. In Kuby's book we can find constantly repeated by Polish Catholic Church representatives: "gender ideology", "genderists", sexualisation in kindergartens, takeover of international organisations (EU, UN, WHO) by "gender-ideologists", abolition of sex undercover of equality, gender groups aiming to legalise paedophilia, zoophilia, incest (Ryś 2014).

During the mass on 16 October 2013 at Wrocław Cathedral, Archbishop Józef Michalik suggested a link between pedophilia and the promotion of "gender ideology": "Abuse of children by adults is reprehensible. However, no one pays attention to the causes of this behaviour. Pornography and the false love shown in it, the lack of love of divorcing parents and the promotion of gender ideology"¹⁹. In his opinion, the blame for child abuse by adults also lies with feminist environments, especially "the most aggressive Polish feminists", who "for years have mocked the Church and traditional ethics, promoted abortion and fought against the traditional model of family and marital fidelity."²⁰

The Catholic Church gender discourse was described by professor Magdalena Środa, who in late 2013 (November) - on behalf of Women's Congress - wrote a letter to the Pope, explaining that the Catholic Church in Poland is taking unfair advantage of gender ideology and giving examples: "Over the past month, many of the archbishops, bishops, cardinals, Catholic academics and whole numbers of priests and catechists have denounced 'gender ideology', proclaiming that it is 'worse than Nazism, Maoism and Marxism', 'leads to the death of a given civilisation', 'to crimes against humanity', to the 'sexualisation of children', to 'great sexual depravity' including 'paedophilia', 'gender elimination', 'breaks up families', that it is 'the voice of Satan', 'a source of demoralisation' and that its effect will be 'the disappearance of the white race'. The leaders of this crusade even proclaim that in the fight against gender ideology 'one must be prepared to die'²¹.

The Catholic Church's stance on gender was officially sanctioned by the pastoral letter of the Polish Episcopate, which was read out in all churches in Poland on 29 December 2013, where church authorities emphasise the destructive impact of gender on traditional values and the family. The Polish Episcopate wrote²²: "In view of the increasing attacks of this ideology, we feel urged to speak out strongly in defence of the Christian family, the fundamental values that protect it, to warn against the dangers of promoting a new type of family life." Of particular concern to the bishops was the fact that,

¹⁹ O co chodzi z ideologią gender? Echa wypowiedzi abpa Michalika, 17.10.2013, Janusz Schwertner, Portal Onet.pl, <https://wiadomosci.onet.pl/tylko-w-onecie/o-co-chodzi-z-ideologia-gender/pmw64> (05.01.2023)

²⁰ Ks. Kloch o pedofilii: Pewne czynniki zwiększają ryzyko nadużyć, 17.10.2013, Radio RMF.FM, https://www.rmf24.pl/fakty/polska/news-ks-kloch-o-pedofilii-pewne-czynniki-zwiekszaja-ryzyko-naduzy,nld,1043714#crp_state=1 (05.01.2023)

²¹ Prof. Środa pisze list do papieża: "Kościół w Polsce nieuczciwie wykorzystuje ideologię gender", 28.11.2013, Dziennik Gazeta Prawna, <https://www.gazetaprawna.pl/wiadomosci/artykuly/748948,prof-sroda-pisze-list-do-papieza-kosciol-w-polsce-nieuczciwie-wykorzystuje-ideologie-gender.html> (04.01.2023)

²² List Pastorski Episkopatu Polski do duszpasterskiego wykorzystania w Niedzielę Świętej Rodziny 2013 roku, https://www.archidiecezja.wroc.pl/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=2059:dokumenty-episkopatu-polski&catid=70:dokumenty-do-pobrania&Itemid=78 (06.01.2023)

according to “gender ideology”/“genderism”, a person would be free to determine his or her sex. They warn that this is to lead to - society accepting the right to form new types of families, for example those built on homosexual relationships. The bishops stressed also that gender is the result of a decades-long ideological and cultural transformation, firmly rooted in Marxism and neo-Marxism, promoted by certain feminist movements and the sexual revolution. “Genderism promotes principles that are totally contrary to reality and to an integral understanding of human nature.” The Episcopate alarmed that genderism has been introduced for months, without the knowledge of society, in the Polish education system, health care, the activities of cultural and educational institutions and non-governmental organisations. As Paweł Ryś (2014) noted, the most part this letter is based on or even copied from Gabriele Kuby's book.

Although the rights of homosexuals were not mentioned in this letter, it became obvious that the main threat to Polish children is, in the opinion of the Catholic Church, homosexuality, described as "LGBT propaganda" and in 2019 as "LGBT ideology". In the Church's discourse on gender, a fairly consistent narrative model can be discerned. The primary protagonist here is the Church, which defends the family, society. The enemy is named ('gender ideology'), although not fully defined. Such definitional fluidity and a certain undefinition of “gender ideology” and its supporters - "genderists" - is functional in the sense that it allows a common label to be given to phenomena and subjects negatively evaluated by the Church (e.g. feminists, representatives of sexual minorities, supporters of in vitro, people who advocate the right to abortion, etc.). "Gender ideology" is presented as something external, alien (starting with the name itself), as an enemy that, through manipulation and deception, tries to infiltrate the ranks of the opponent (Szwed, 2015).

The appeal of the church hierarchy on 29 of December 2013 was met with a very quick response from right-wing politicians. On 8 January 2014 The Parliamentary Group "Stop gender ideology!" was established. The chairwoman of this group (Beata Kempa, later PiS's MEP) in January 2014 justified the need for the group in this way: I am thinking, for example, of the ideas of genderism, which are damaging, especially insofar as they talk about the upbringing of children up to the age of four - that the child is yet to find his or her gender. For me this is ideology, not science, and it is damaging and discriminatory. At this level, let's not make it the norm. And all the signs are that this is quietly becoming the norm, so we say: stop it. At the same time, a member of the far-right Solidarna Polska party asserted that "I do not discriminate against gender ideology".²³ Nevertheless, only a month later, at a meeting with her supporters, she declared: Why do we need gender? (...) I will not give up. I will destroy gender!²⁴ The purpose of setting up the Group Stop gender ideology was to work towards introducing legislative changes to defend the rights of the traditional family and support family-friendly policies. During its one-year activity, the Group debated the Large Family Card, the establishment of a Family Rights Day and issued an appeal "Stop the sexualisation of children and adolescents at school" (15 January 2015). Its last meeting was held on 5 February 2015, when it debated the ratification of The Council of Europe Convention on preventing and combating violence against women and domestic violence (Istanbul Convention) and issued an appeal to withdraw from the ratification of it. The establishing of The Parliamentary Group "Stop gender ideology!" is one of the turning points in the campaign against gender in Poland - a moment of its politicization, although some researchers (Korolczuk and Graff, 2022) point to the lecture given on 31 January 2014 in the

²³ Kania Stanisław (2014), Kempa: Nie dyskryminuję ideologii gender, 14 stycznia, Wprost, <https://www.wprost.pl/tylko-u-nas/432321/kempa-nie-dyskryminuje-ideologii-gender.html>

²⁴ Kempa: Nie poddam się. Zniszczę gender! 19.02.2014, Tygodnik Wprost, <https://www.wprost.pl/kraj/436782/kempa-nie-poddam-sie-zniszcze-gender.html> (05.01.2023)

Polish Sejm by Father Oko as such a point during which the speaker presented gender as “a dire threat to civilization,” “a great evil that must be spoken about,” informing the public that “genderists propagate incest, pedophilia and homosexuality”(Oko, 2014).

Nevertheless, The Istanbul Convention was ratified by Poland in May 2015, and it was signed by President Bronislaw Komorowski just before the end of his presidency.

As many social scientists and commentators on social and political processes in Poland (ex. Gieroł-Klimaszewska, 2017; Ścigaj, 2018; Cywiński et al., 2019; Kłosińska and Rusinek, 2020; Tomal 2019; Kotras, 2018; Harper, 2020; Krzemiński, 2021; Graff and Korolczuk, 2022) point out the 2015 election year was dominated by PiS mobilization against refugees. Above all, Jarosław Kaczyński's statements at that time indicating that they have a 'full moral right' not to accept refugees²⁵ were commented on repeatedly. These statements were not only characterised by a high degree of hostility, but were also intended to create a feeling of fear and anxiety about security; Kaczyński stated that refugees carry diseases and parasites, and contribute to a decrease in security, including terrorism²⁶.

Immediately after the victory of PiS in autumn 2015, anti-gender mobilization intensified with President Duda's first veto, which was against the Gender Accordance Act. The Act would have made the legal recognition procedure of gender change easier and more accessible. In the following years, the dominant topic was mainly abortion, influenced by the Catholic Church, and women's reproductive rights, against which the government took legal actions.

Also as recently as autumn of 2015 the anti-choice network “STOP abortion” led by the Ordo Iuris Institute Foundation launched a massive campaign in favor of a total ban on abortions. In the spring of 2016 Stop Abortion Committee started to gather signatures supporting citizen's law proposal, which included a total ban on abortion and the threat of criminal prosecution for both doctors and women²⁷.

The main politicians of the ruling party (PiS) have declared their support for the proposed law (The Prime Minister Beata Szydło and Jarosław Kaczyński, the leader of PiS). However, due to the mass protests of Polish women (the Black Protests and the Polish Women's Strike) in the autumn, on 6 of October 2016 PiS voted to refer the initiative to the parliamentary committees, thereby withdrawing the proposal (Graff, 2019; Korolczuk, 2016; Majewska, 2017; Muszel and Piotrowski, 2018; Kowalska et al., 2019). Further waves of protests in 2017, 2018 and much smaller in 2019 followed, and the networks of feminist activists consolidated, crystalized, and matured.

In 2017, access to morning-after pills was restricted, and in 2020, a state funded in vitro fertilisation (IVF) programme was terminated. At the same time on the pretext of protecting traditional families Polish right-wing populists continued to attack the Istanbul Convention. In June 2018, the former

²⁵ Kaczyński o imigrantach: Mamy pełne moralne prawo powiedzieć „nie”, 01.07.2017, Portal Niezależna.pl, <https://niezalezna.pl/101460-j-kaczynski-o-imigrantach-mamy-pelne-moralne-prawo-powiedziec-nie> (10.01.2023).

²⁶ Pacewicz Piotr, 02.07.2017, „Tu chodzi o zwykłe, codzienne bezpieczeństwo Polaków”. Kaczyński mówi o „uchodźcach”, ale narusza bezpieczeństwo „obcych”, którzy już w Polsce są, Portal OKO.press, <https://oko.press/chodzi-o-zwykle-codzienne-bezpieczenstwo-polakow-kaczynski-mowi-o-uchodzcach-narusza-bezpieczenstwo-obcych-ktorzy-juz-polsce-sa> (10.01.2023)

²⁷ Obywatelski projekt ustawy o zmianie ustawy z dnia 7 stycznia 1993 r. o planowaniu rodziny, ochronie płodu ludzkiego i warunkach dopuszczalności przerywania ciąży oraz ustawy z dnia 6 czerwca 1997 r. - Kodeks karny

Prime Minister Beata Szydło applauded the authorities of Zakopane for their refusal to establish a multi-agency team for combating domestic violence, as required per the national domestic violence act.

In 2019, when the Law and Justice party was gearing up for European Parliament elections, the systemic mobilisation against LGBTQ+ people entered a new phase. This time it is the LGBTQ+ community and anti-gender discourse that is being used to mobilise conservative voters feeling fear of cultural change and socio-economic marginalisation.

On 18 February 2019, the Mayor of Warsaw signed the “Warsaw Municipal Policy for the LGBT+ community”, commonly referred to as the “LGBT+ Declaration” (“Deklaracja LGBT+”). The document, which was drawn up in cooperation with civil society organisations representing the LGBTQ+ community, comprised a set of measures designed to make the city more inclusive and safer for LGBTI people. The document named areas which, according to the LGBTQ+ community, required action. The most important of these included: safety, anti-discrimination and anti-violence education at schools, artistic freedom and establishing an interventional hostel for people in crisis.

This decision was met with an immediate and hostile reaction, introducing an almost warlike atmosphere, as was MP Krystyna Pawłowicz's tweet, beginning: "Well, it's war! For Polish children, for Polish families, for the Polish countryside and cities, for Poland and Europe"²⁸

Populist right-wing actors, supported by the Catholic Church and ultra-conservative organizations, focused their attention on one of the points of the document, namely on the introduction of “antidiscrimination and sex education in every school, which will factor in the notions of psychosexual and gender identity in line with the standards and guidelines of the World Health Organization (WHO)”. The Ombudsperson for children Mikołaj Pawlak addressed questions on the declaration to the Mayor of Warsaw and stated that the WHO standards carry statements that are questionable for many parents²⁹. The fact that in a document on the LGBTQ+ community education of children was mentioned enabled PiS to combine the two topics in a new fear and hate campaign. The main narrative used against LGBTQ+ people was built on the message about the ‘sexualization of children’ and ‘protection of traditional families’. In Jarosław Kaczyński’s words, this was “an attack on the family” and “an attack on children.” He called “LGBT ideology” an imported “threat to Polish identity, to our nation, to its existence and thus to the Polish state.”³⁰ Until the October parliamentary elections, anti-LGBT+ attacks became the dominant thread of the pre-election political battle.

It is significant, and probably not coincidental, that shortly after the LGBT+ Declaration was signed by the Mayor of Warsaw, the anti-gender mobilization has also taken on a more local character. Since March some regional and local self-government units - mainly from the historically conservative south-east of Poland - started declaring themselves “LGBT-free zones.” A key role in this local

²⁸ <https://twitter.com/krystpawlowicz/status/1104637481138483201> (10.01.2023)

²⁹ Masturbacja czterolatek? Oto co zawiera dokument WHO, który budzi w Polsce takie kontrowersje, 11.03.2019, Dziennik.pl, <https://edukacja.dziennik.pl/aktualnosci/artykuly/593273,masturbacja-edukacja-seksualna-who-szkola-karta-lgbt-trzaskowski-kontrowersje.html> (10.01.2023)

³⁰ Polish towns advocate ‘LGBT-free’ zones while the ruling party cheers them on, Rick Noack, 21.07.2019, The Washington Post, https://www.washingtonpost.com/world/europe/polands-right-wing-ruling-party-has-found-a-new-target-lgbt-ideology/2019/07/19/775f25c6-a4ad-11e9-a767-d7ab84aef3e9_story.html (10.01.2023)

mobilisation was played by the Ordo Iuris Foundation, which also reacted quickly to the Mayor of Warsaw's actions and prepared the text of The Local Government Charter of Family Rights, encouraging local governments to adopt it (Korolczuk and Graff, 2022). The Charter's propagators describe themselves as a "coalition of pro-family organisations" and warn on the website dedicated to the initiative that "some local governments today are trying to undermine the constitutional rights of families and parents, without whose permission they are implementing permissive sex education classes in schools", therefore it is necessary to take a stand "on the side of the constitutional values under threat - the family, marriage as a union between a man and a woman, motherhood and parenthood" and urgently adopt the "Local Government Charter on the Rights of Families", reaffirming the constitutional guarantees of the rights of families and the rights of parents and creating real guarantees for their observance."³¹ In response to these actions, the Atlas of Hate was created on which by 30 March 2020 more than 80 local governments, including five voivodships were marked as being declared as 'free zones' from 'LGBT ideology' or/and accepted the Local Government Charter on the Rights of Families (Karolczuk and Graff, 2022).

However, international pressure and, above all, the vision of losing funding from the European Union³² have resulted that shortly thereafter most of the local authorities decided to withdraw from their anti-LGBT declarations³³. (On 7.01. 2023 on the Atlas of Hate were still marked one voivodeship (łódzkie), 30 counties and 39 municipalities³⁴).

Meanwhile, in April a much-publicized incident took place: three activists spread stickers with an image of the Virgin Mary in a rainbow halo in front of one of the churches in Płock. For this, they were charged with insulting religious feelings under Article 196 of the Penal Code. The reaction of those supporting the activists was the "Rainbow Does Not Offend" ("Tęcza nie obraża") Campaign. The case reverberated also around the world. A number of human rights organisations have spoken out on this issue: Amnesty International, Freemuse, Front Line Defenders, Human Rights Watch, ILGA-Europe, Helsinki Foundation for Human Rights, Campaign Against Homophobia publishing a joint appeal and petitions. The trial ended on 2 March 2021 with a verdict acquitting all the defendants. In its reasoning, the court emphasised that the activists did not mean to offend anyone's religious feelings or insult the image of the Virgin Mary. Their aim was to publicise issues affecting LGBT people and to show their support. After an appeal by the prosecuting side, the case ended on 12 January 2022 and Elżbieta Podleśna, Anna Prus and Joanna Gzyra-Iskandar were legally acquitted by the court).³⁵

The tense atmosphere of the summer 2019 election campaign was also heated up by the Pro-Life Foundation's campaign, which culminated in August in the submission to the Sejm of a bill "Stop

³¹Local Government Charter on the Rights of Families, <https://kartarodzin.pl/> (7.01.2023)

³² The European Commission withheld funding to five local authorities, calling for the repeal of anti-LGBT declarations, which resulted in the resignation of these declarations in four regions.

³³ Councillor of the Town of Kraśnik Paweł Kurek: *"It is possible to receive PLN 39 million. It seems that in the situation when this resolution is in legal circulation, it will be doubtful. We rely not only on statements made by members of the Norwegian government, but also on actions such as those directed against the project implemented by the Podkarpackie Voivodeship. These are well-known facts and we should take them into account."*, <https://oko.press/krasnik-uchyla-uchwale-anty-lgbt-prawicowi-radni-straszyla-sadem-ostatecznym-na-prozno> (7.01.2023)

³⁴ Atlas Nienawiści (Atlas of Hate), <https://atlasnienawisci.pl/> (7.01.2023)

³⁵ Sąd: Tęczowa Maryjka nie obraża uczuć religijnych - prawomocny wyrok, 10.01.2022, Monika Sewastianowicz, Portal Prawo.pl, <https://www.prawo.pl/prawnicy-sady/teczowa-maryja-a-obraza-uczuc-religijnych-wyrok-sadu,506808.html> (7.01.2023)

pedophilia”, which provided for increased penalties for paedophile acts, but also to criminalise sex education. At the vote on 16.04.2020, the draft was referred to a parliamentary committee for further work.

The Catholic Church has not remained neutral in the anti-LGBTQ+ campaign of 2019 either. The statement from the side of the Catholic Church that caused perhaps the greatest outrage at the time was that of Archbishop Marek Jędraszewski about the 'rainbow plague'. “Fortunately, the red plague is no longer on our land, but this does not mean that there is not a new plague that wants to take over our souls, hearts and minds. Not Marxist, Bolshevik, but born of the same spirit, neo-Marxist. Not red, but rainbow.” said Archbishop Marek Jędraszewski, the Metropolitan Archbishop of Krakow, on 1 August 2019 (so two months before the parliamentary elections) during a Mass commemorating the 75th anniversary of the outbreak of the Warsaw Uprising³⁶.

Both during the 2019 parliamentary campaign and the 2020 presidential campaign ‘gender’ and ‘LGBTQ’ terms have been dehumanised and depersonalised and were called a hostile ideology. PiS described LGBTQI as something Western and destructive, a factor that is alien to Polish tradition and culture. For example, President Duda in June 2020 during his second presidential campaign said at a rally: “Ladies and gentlemen, they’re trying to make us believe that these are people. But it’s just an ideology.” He also argued for the need to oppose it, as it is more descriptive of children than communist ideology that Poles have fought against in the past. “It was not for this my parents' generation fought for 40 years to expel communist ideology from schools (...) so that we now accept that another ideology should come along, an ideology that is even more destructive to humanity, an ideology which, beneath the platitudes of respect and tolerance, conceals profound intolerance and elimination, the exclusion of all those who do not wish to submit to it.”³⁷

While in June 2020 the future education minister Przemysław Czarnek said in a TV studio: “Let’s end the discussion about these disgusting LGBT things, homosexuality, bisexuality, pride parades. [...] Let’s protect families from this kind of corruption, depravity, and absolutely immoral conduct, let’s protect ourselves from LGBT ideology and let’s stop listening to this idiocy about some human rights or some equality. These people aren’t equal with normal people, and let’s end this discussion.”³⁸

Definitely a turning point for both sides of the political spectrum speaking out on gender issues and above all on women's reproductive rights was the Constitutional Court verdict of 22 October 2020 declaring the rationale allowing the termination of pregnancy in the case of severe foetal abnormalities unconstitutional. This has sparked nationwide and international protests that lasted throughout the winter until the spring of 2021.

³⁶ Arcybiskup Jędraszewski o "tęczowej zarazie", 2.08.2019, TVN24, <https://tvn24.pl/polska/arcybiskup-marek-jedraszewski-teczowa-zaraza-zamiast-czerwonej-ra957818-2308295> (7.01.2023)

³⁷ Gwiazda Urszula (2020), Andrzej Duda o LGBT: Próbuje się nam wmówić, że to ludzie, a to po prostu ideologia, 13.06.2020, https://www.rmf24.pl/raporty/raport-wybory-prezydenckie2020/najnowsze-fakty/news-andrzej-duda-o-lgbt-probuje-sie-nam-wmowic-ze-to-ludzie-a-to,nld,4551951#crp_state=1 (06.01.2023)

³⁸ Słowa Czarnka o LGBT "ci ludzie nie są równi ludziom normalnym" wyrwane z kontekstu? Akurat, 05.10.2020, Dominika Sitnicka, Portal OKO.press, <https://oko.press/czarnek-o-lgbt-studio-polska> (06.01.2023)

The year 2021 brought further legislative initiatives, from the anti-gender and anti-LGBTQ+ environment, such as the "Yes to family, no to gender" project of Ordo Iuris on 30 March 2021. The project has been referred to by the Sejm for further work in committees.

The main aim of the Ordo Iuris proposition is to denounce by Poland the Istanbul Convention ratified in 2015. Instead of the Istanbul Convention, the project proposes a Convention on Family Rights. The authors argue that their Convention will strengthen women's protection against violence, and it is the Istanbul Convention that fails to protect women: "Based on erroneous, ideologised premises, the Convention does not contribute to improving the situation of women victims of violence. The authors argue that the Istanbul Convention introduces "the category of gender, 'socio-cultural sex', into Polish law, assuming the contractual nature of gender differences. This stands in radical contradiction to the foundations of the Polish Constitution. Article 12 of the Convention obliges states to 'eradicate' customs and traditions 'based on a stereotypical model of the role of women and men'. Moreover, these actions are not only to be negative in nature, but states are to agree contra: 'promote changes in social and cultural patterns regarding the behaviour of women and men'."³⁹ On the project's website, its authors also cite the statement of the Episcopate of Poland on the Istanbul Convention, in which the Church hierarchs recalled that a consensus position on the issue had already been adopted by the Central European Bishops' Assembly, which called for the rejection of the document.⁴⁰ During the debate on the draft on 17 March Marek Jurek a representative of the legislative initiative and former MP said: "We do not want our children and grandchildren to be subjected to experimental induction into so-called atypical gender roles, as Article 14 of this Convention says, so that our education or cultural policy is a terrain for the eradication of traditions or customs."⁴¹,

In August 2021, another homophobic citizens' initiative "Stop LGBT" signed by 140,000 people was submitted to the Sejm, this time by activist Kaja Godek and her Family and Life Foundation. The draft proposes a ban on: organizing Equality Parades; questioning marriage as a union between a man and a woman; promoting same-sex unions and the adoption of children by same-sex couples; extending the definition of marriage to include same-sex couples, -promoting the definition of gender as a phenomenon independent of biological conditions. Presenting the bill in the parliament, a representative of the Family and Life Foundation (Fundacja Życie i Rodzina) Krzysztof Kasprzak argued that the 'goal of the LGBT lobby' is the destruction of marriage and 'any natural social order', and equality parades are organised "to recruit Polish children into the homosexual movement" where they "get into the hands of the oppressors of the LGBT movement."⁴² On 29 October 2021, the Sejm rejected the bill and referred it for further work in parliamentary committees.

The most recent citizens' bill is called "Abortion is Murder" and it is also prepared by Kaja Godek and Life and Family Foundation (Fundacja Życie i Rodzina). The bill was submitted to the Sejm on 28 December 2022. The proposal of Kaja Godek was a clear response to the reaction of feminist activists to the decision of the Constitutional Court in October 2020, which was followed by a number of initiatives in Poland and abroad that help Polish women to access safe abortion. Among other things,

³⁹ Project website: Yes to family, no to gender., <https://takdlarodziny.ordoiuris.pl/>

⁴⁰ Project website: Yes to family, no to gender., <https://takdlarodziny.ordoiuris.pl/>

⁴¹ Marek Jurek, Sprawozdanie Stenograficzne z 27. posiedzenia Sejmu w dniu 17 marca 2021 r, s.235, http://orka2.sejm.gov.pl/StenoInter9.nsf/0/D529AA18D9598E08C125869B007CFD45/%24File/27_b_ksiazka_bis.pdf

⁴² Krzysztof Kasprzak, Sprawozdanie stenograficzne z 40. posiedzenia Sejmu w dn. 28 października 2021 s. 140, http://orka2.sejm.gov.pl/StenoInter9.nsf/0/A5147BDA3C09B46DC125877D000A3742/%24File/40_a_ksiazka_bis.pdf

the bill provides for a ban on public advocacy of any action regarding the possibility of aborting a pregnancy inside and outside the country and provides for imprisonment for such actions. The ban also applies to public information on the possibility to terminate a pregnancy inside and outside the country. However, PiS politicians announced that they would not support a bill that would further tighten abortion laws in Poland.⁴³

2023 is the year in which the next parliamentary elections in Poland are scheduled (probably for autumn). The ruling party, ultra-conservative environments and the Catholic Church will probably continue their crusade against 'gender ideology' and LGBTQ+. The question that has yet to be answered is who or what the Law and Justice Party will put on the 'electoral sacrificial altar' this time. The presentation of the 'enemy' to the Poles will officially start the election campaign.

4. Actors, organizations and organizational models

The anti-gender backlash in Poland has to be replaced in the broader framework of a growing transnational movement made of numerous actors, including governments, right-wing think tanks, the Catholic Church, and other far-right groups (Suchanow 2020, Korolczuk and Graff, 2022). There are three different types of actors: the old, the new, and the allies. The old actors group comprises the Catholic Church. The new actors emerged in the last decade, specifically in opposition to 'gender ideology,' and include politicians and political parties, government-backed NGOs, and right-wing think tanks which have established strong international ties. The last category, allies, are primarily media outlets, journalists and academics. By attacking gender equality, these actors undermine women's rights, LGBT communities, and civil society itself.

4.1. Political parties and government associated actors

The Polish governing party is the patron of virtually all anti-LGBTQ+ campaigns in the country. Therefore, there has been less space for other significant players on the field since 2015. The PiS camp is not homogeneous in general and in regards to attitudes towards LGBTQ+ people. The so-called United Right, a conservative political alliance created by Jarosław Kaczyński, is composed of the PiS party and junior coalition partners, such as Solidary Poland, which is the most radical one in relation to LGBTQ+. Within PiS and the government, the main actors are President Andrzej Duda, Minister of Education (since 2020) Przemysław Czarnek, the Minister of Justice (2005-2007, 2015-now), leader of Solidary Poland - Zbigniew Ziobro, Commissioner for Children's Rights (since 2018) Mikołaj Pawlak.

Since 2018 PiS has competed with Confederation (Konfederacja), a block of radical right, nationalistic and ultraconservative parties and organizations. Some of its leaders (eg. Robert Bąkiewicz) are directly connected with neo-fascist organisations known for organising events, such as the Independence March (Marsz Niepodległości). It is the largest far-right event organised every year on November 11th,

⁴³ "The proposed solutions are a simple argument for extreme left-wing circles to push for the liberalisation of abortion law in Poland in the future, and even to introduce abortion on demand without any restrictions. For this reason, for us the subject of this law is closed and we do not deal with it at all as a party" – explained one of the PiS part politicians (Rafał Bochenek).

<https://www.gazetaprawna.pl/wiadomosci/kraj/artykuly/8621542,zaostrenie-prawa-aborcynego-godek-pis.html>

on Poland's Independence Day. It attracts nationalist groups from all over Europe and is known for violence and anti-Semitism. For many years participants of the march were burning down an installation of a rainbow on Warsaw's Saviour square. Another far-right actor is the National Guard (Straż Narodowa), with the nickname "PiS militia", a nationalistic organisation known for its violent actions against, for example, women protesting during Black Protests.

4.2. NGOs and think tanks

In the category of NGOs and think tanks mainly anti-abortion organisations are present:

The Pro - Right to Life Foundation (Fundacja Pro-Prawo do Życia)⁴⁴ is a pro-life foundation that started its activity in 2005. Its founder is Mariusz Dzierżawski. The Foundation is the organiser of the anti-abortion exhibition *Wybierz życie* (Choose life), the nationwide campaign *Szpitala bez aborterów* (Hospitals without aborters), as well as the campaign *Stop paedophilia* (Stop pedofilia). The Foundation has, on several occasions, submitted signatures in the Sejm to draft civic legislative initiatives aimed at limiting or banning the practice of abortion in Poland, as well as preventing the introduction of sexual education in Polish schools according to WHO standards. In its activities, the Foundation also points to the existence of post-abortion syndrome.

Life and Family Foundation⁴⁵ (Fundacja Życie i Rodzina, Kaja Godek, Krzysztof Kasprzak). The foundation was established in November 2015. In presenting its activities, the Foundation writes on its website: 'The action of the Life and Family Foundation is simple - we tell it like it is and show it like it is: abortion kills babies and LGBT is an ideology that threatens life, health and society. We take to the streets of cities and outside hospitals to show the truth about abortion'.

Fundacja „Centrum Wspierania Inicjatyw dla Życia i Rodziny”⁴⁶ (The Foundation "Centre for Supporting Initiatives for Life and Family" (leaders: Paweł Ozdoba, Kamil Zwierz) was established in 2012. The main form of activity is the Marches for the Family, which take place in around 120 towns and cities each year. Unlike Pro Life, Marches for the Family do not focus on shock and media effect, but on a friendly, family atmosphere. At the same time, the Marches are an opportunity to collect signatures and distribute support to local politicians (handing out titles of 'Family Friendly Local Government'), and other organisations involved in changing abortion laws. The head of the Foundation, Paweł Ozdoba, became famous in May 2022 for stating that the TV series 'Friends' and 'Bold and Beautiful' are to blame for the divorce of Poles, because Poles follow their characters⁴⁷.

Stowarzyszenie Ruch 4 Marca (March 4th Movement Association)⁴⁸. As written on the website of the organization it was formed in response to the 'Standards for Sexuality Education in Europe - Basic recommendations for policy makers and education and health professionals' published by the World Health Organisation (WHO). The immediate impulse for the creation of the organisation was the fact

⁴⁴ Organization's website: <https://stronazycia.pl/stop-pedofilii/poradnik/>

⁴⁵ Organization's website: <https://www.zycierodzina.pl/o-nas/>

⁴⁶ Organization's website: <https://czir.org/o-nas/>

⁴⁷ „Polacy się rozwodzą, bo naoglądali się »Przyjaciół« i »Mody na sukces«”. Brednie Szefa Centrum Życia i Rodziny, 24.05.2022, Dominika Długosz, Tygodnik Newsweek, <https://www.newsweek.pl/opinie/pawel-ozdoba-o-przyczynach-rozwodow-w-polsce-winna-moda-na-sukces/ejeh1vh>

⁴⁸ Organization's website: <http://lodz.ruch4marca.pl/>

that the Warsaw authorities signed in February 2019 the LGBTQ+ Charter. The Association's main aim is to work towards the city's withdrawal of this declaration and to block analogous initiatives in other Polish cities. The 4 Marca Movement also wants to inform parents and teachers how to "react to attempts by gay organisations to enter schools" and to respond to any attempts at "worldview indoctrination". The founders of the movement come from the Mum and Dad Foundation.

The Ordo Iuris Institute for Legal Culture Foundation (hereafter Ordo Iuris) was founded in Warsaw, Poland, in mid-2013. It gained notoriety in the autumn of 2016, when the draft of the restrictive "Stop Abortion" bill was submitted to the Polish parliament. The bill was to introduce, among other things, prison sentences for women who undergo abortions. It was rejected by the Sejm shortly after the women's strike on 3 October 2016. Initially, the president of Ordo Iuris was Aleksander Stępkowski, the vice-president was Joanna Banasiuk and the treasurer was Jerzy Kwaśniewski. Currently, the president is Jerzy Kwaśniewski. The organisation's activities are aimed, as the statute states, at 'researching the legal and spiritual culture of the heritage in which Polish culture is rooted and promoting them in public life and the legal system'. Probably for this reason, the foundation is registered as subordinate to the Ministry of Culture. Ordo Iuris conducts conferences, writes expert opinions and reports, organises training courses, and invites students for legal internships. Its main field of activity is (as stated on its website)⁴⁹ "the protection (...) of human and civil rights", resulting from the "inherent and inalienable dignity of the human being". It also participates in legal proceedings, domestic and international, as the foundation operates in Poland but has international ambitions. As co-author of the Agenda Europe' manifesto titled Restoring the Natural Order emphasised that the main objective is to change the language and created their own dictionary/vocabulary, according to which instead of the word "homosexuality" the word "sodomy" is to be used; no mention should be made of health care or pregnancy prevention because pregnancy is not a disease; instead of "patchwork families" it should say: "broken families", instead of "equal treatment of homosexuals" - 'privileges for homosexuals'; instead of 'reproductive rights', 'free access to abortion'.(Suchanow 2020). Therefore, in the way how the Ordo Iuris communicates, similarly to other anti-gender and anti-feminist organizations, manipulation and ideologically oriented language is evident: "abortion is killing", "sex education is the sexualisation of children", LGBTQ+ persons are linked to paedophilia and deviancy.

The organisation also carries out extensive lobbying activities in parliament. Ordo Iuris lawyers have commented on almost every draft law or regulation that concerned reproductive rights, family life, children's rights, non-heterosexuals, the conscience clause or broad worldview issues. Ordo Iuris also participates in social consultations laws prepared by the government (Suchanow 2020). Ordo Iuris has fenced itself with a network of other organisations, such as PCh24.pl, an online right-wing news and opinion portal.

As the example of The Local Government Charter of Family Rights shows⁵⁰, the organisation is in the position to mobilise to a number of other ultra conservative organisations more or less commonly known from their anti-gender and anti-LGBT approaches activities: Fundacja Życie i Rodzina; Ruch 4 Marca Łódź Association, Ordo Caritatis Institute, Stowarzyszenie Rodzin Wielodzietnych Warszawy i Mazowsza, Stowarzyszenie Pedagogów Natan, Związek Podhalan w Polsce, Instytut Ona i On,

⁴⁹ Organization's website: <https://ordoiuris.pl/>

⁵⁰ Samorządowa Karta Praw Rodzin (The Local Government Charter of Family Rights), <https://kartarodzin.pl/>

Konfederacja Kobiet RP, Fundacja Mamy i Taty, Centrum Życia i Rodziny, Stowarzyszenie Rodzice Chronią Dzieci.

Polish Non-Governmental Initiatives Confederacy (Konfederacja Organizacji Pozarządowych RP, Fundacja Edukacja do Wartości) a platform of conservative and ultra-conservative organisations focused on promoting nationalism, sovereignty and traditional values.

4.3. The Catholic Church

In Poland, religious actors play a major role in the mobilisation. The Catholic Church authorities are the most influential actors that inspires the anti-LGBTQ+ measures of the government in Poland. The church constantly delivers moral/philosophical underpinnings for the anti-LGBTQ+ state propaganda. One of the most conservative actors of Poland's episcopate are archbishop Marek Jędraszewski, self-appointed opponents of "gender ideology" have included Father Dariusz Oko, Archbishops Henryk Hoser and Marek Jędraszewski.

The main promoter of the thesis of the totalitarian character of 'gender ideology', Father Dariusz Oko (2013:40-43). "Gender is a classic example of ideology, as it becomes a tool of ruthless struggle to benefit the atheist gender and homolobby." "Gender ideology", according to Father Oko is supported above all by: „Fighting gays, who want to promote their distorted way of life as the best one, attaching a justifying theory to their behaviour. There are also feminists - often lesbians - who, under the guise of slogans about women's liberation, want to "liberate" them from marriage, motherhood, the family, and men." According to Dariusz Oko in order to oppose genderism it is necessary to: "participate in marches and other forms of protest, write and send letters to the Minister of National Education and other members of the government, publicise the scandals in the media and seek legal help, do not be afraid of a court battle. It is also necessary to control what happens in school, such as the introduction of new classes." (2013:40-43)

A key actor within the Church has been also the Redemptorist priest Father Tadeusz Rydzyk, whose media empire includes the Radio Maryja radio station, as well as television station (TV Trwam), a daily newspaper (Nasz Dziennik), a university complex (Academy of Social and Media Culture), and a foundation (Lux Veritatis) involved in research, education, cultural production, as well as a number of various large- scale investments.

5. Allies

The anti-gender and anti-feminist actors in Poland are supported by media and higher education institutions associated with them, whose official aim is to educate in subjects such as law (Collegium Intermarium- ultra-conservative law school focused to promote Christian values and the idea of the Intermarium and Poland's leading role in Central and Eastern Europe;) or media communication (Academy of Social and Media Culture: the academy's mission is 'service to man' and its motto is: Faith, Reason and Homeland. Admission to the university requires a recommendation from a representative of the Church authority), so they do not officially consider themselves as part of the

anti-gender/anti-feminist movement. However, the founding organisations, educational programmes and people employed at these institutions make the aims of these institutions clear.

In Poland, right-wing media outlets were a niche before 2015, but with PiS coming to power, they became mainstream, or at least they are treated like that by the government and state-owned media. They are all personally, politically, and financially connected to PiS. They can be divided into two groups:

1) Conservative outlets, like: W Sieci, Gazeta Polska Codziennie, and Gazeta Polska, which is known for producing 'LGBT-free Zone' stickers; Tygodnik Solidarność, DoRzeczy, Telewizja Republika, Fronda.pl

2) Religious outlets, like the media empire of Tadeusz Rydzyk, a priest, who manages, among others, Radio Maryja, TV TRWAM, Nasz Dziennik, which are known for homophobic and anti-Semitic views, besides these also: Gość Niedzielny, Tygodnik Katolicki Niedziela.

The Piotr Skarga Foundation/Association is the main financial and media engine of the campaign "Stop Abortion" in 2016. The Polonia Christiana portal (medium and press agency of the Piotr Skarga Foundation/Association) was the media partner for most of the actions carried out by the allies. Articles from this source are often reprinted in other right-wing media (e.g. Fronda.pl) (Rzewska-Słodowska, 2016).

6. Themes and agendas

6.1. Labor market

The actions of the anti-gender and anti-feminist organizations regarding the labour market are not that visible as it is in other cases. The most visible actions are located in the discursive area, where the studied groups promote their conservative agenda based on patriarchal gender role division, often discouraging (discursively) women from making careers. Most visible actions are in particular cases where - according to these groups – discrimination occurred on the basis of beliefs. That was the case of an IKEA worker, who posted quotes from the bible in reaction to company's newsletter about pride month. These quotes (from the old testament) were perceived as homophobic (they were about punishing homosexual people with death) and the worker was fired. In his defence Ordo Iuris became very active, together with the Minister of Justice (and at the same time the head of PiS coalition party and prosecutor general) Zbigniew Ziobro defended this person (also in public debates). As a result the labour court reinstated him in his work because of formalities, but the superior of the worker was acquitted of discrimination charges by another court.

Equal treatment of LGBTQ+ people is regulated by the Labour Code. Article 18 states that all employees are entitled to the same rights and that for discriminating against them on the basis of their sexual orientation, the company must face consequences such as paying them financial compensation.

However, the practice of the application of the law shows that it is rarely used to assert their rights by LGBT persons. Only two court cases have been brought to the Ombudsman's attention concerning

violations of the principle of equal treatment in employment on the basis of sexual orientation and only one ruling on discrimination against a transgender person in this area⁵¹.

However, discrimination in the area of employment is a daily reality for many transgender people in Poland. One form of it, and at the same time a possible cause of stigmatisation and discrimination in the work environment, is the need for transgender persons to use employment certificates issued with personal data and gender from before the gender reassignment procedure⁵².

Transgender people also have difficult access to military service in Poland. In the Ordinance of the Minister of National Defence of 24 January 2018 on the adjudication of capability for active military service and the procedure of military medical commissions in these matters, 'transsexualism' is listed as a disease that is the basis for the 'E' category meaning permanent and total incapacity for active military service⁵³.

Research indicates that 25% of all LGBTQ+ people surveyed (9052 respondents) who were in paid work were afraid to disclose their sexual orientation at work for fear of discrimination, and only 28% of respondents reported that they could talk about their private life as freely as heterosexual or cisgender people. In the case of 70% of transgender people surveyed, none of the co-workers knew about their gender identity. The percentage is even higher when it comes to direct superiors (82%).⁵⁴

Discrimination on the Polish labour market also affects women. Research of Hays Poland „Kobiety na rynku pracy 2022” (Women on the labour market 2022) indicates that 53 % of women and 28% of men have encountered obstacles based on their gender in the course of their career. Female professionals and managers are more likely than their male colleagues to experience situations in which their career opportunities are determined by stereotypes, unconscious biases or discriminatory practices. They are most often confronted with cases of favouritism towards men (55%), stereotyping in hiring and promotion decisions (53%), assumption of their lower availability (48%) and lack of confidence in their qualifications (42%). Female respondents in managerial roles, on the other hand, indicated as an obstacle the negative and hurtful opinions about the so-called 'female management style', stereotypically perceived as too emotional, with an excessive tendency to compromise and a lack of obedience among subordinates.

There is still perception of women in the labour market through the prism of – even theoretical – motherhood. Parenthood and family responsibilities are still mainly identified with women, which, in the perspective of some employers, puts the hiring of female candidates at additional risk. Some decision-makers in companies still assume that, as mothers, they will take sick leave for their children

⁵¹ Raport RPO: Sytuacja prawna osób nieheteroseksualnych i transpłciowych w Polsce. Międzynarodowy standard ochrony praw człowieka osób LGBT i stan jego przestrzegania z perspektywy Rzecznika Praw Obywatelskich (2019),

<https://bip.brpo.gov.pl/sites/default/files/Raport%20RPO%20Sytuacja%20prawna%20os%C3%B3b%20LGBT%20w%20Polsce.pdf>

⁵² Równe traktowanie w zatrudnieniu bez względu na tożsamość płciową. Analiza i zalecenia, raport z serii Zasada równego traktowania - prawo i praktyka nr 19, Biuletyn Rzecznika Praw Obywatelskich 2016, nr 6, Warszawa 2016.

⁵³ Załącznik nr 2 do Rozporządzenia, Dz.U. z 2018 r., poz. 268.

⁵⁴ Sytuacja społeczna osób LGBT w Polsce. Raport za lata 2019–2020. Przegląd najważniejszych danych. (2021), red. Mirosława Makuchowska, Kampania Przeciw Homofobii i Stowarzyszenie Lambda Warszawa. <https://kph.org.pl/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/raport-maly-2019-2020.pdf>

or soon become pregnant and disappear from the company for a year. This is therefore a manifestation of inequality that affects both working mothers and childless women.

The scientists argue that gender differentiates both the causes and consequences of unemployment. In the case of women, the following problems are indicated: the exit from the labor market due to childbirth or child care, concomitant with the pressure for the care period prolongation, depreciation of housework, gendered ascription of the responsibility of care for the dependent, and the unequal economic resources. Caring responsibilities still largely fall on women. The belief that it is the job of mothers to take care of children is a stereotype deeply rooted in culture. In the professional space, there is often a perception that it is working mothers who take care of children when they are sick and use all the parental leave available to parents (Hryciuk&Korolczuk 2015, Mikołajczyk&Stankowska 2021, Karwacki&Suwada 2020, Wojciechowska 2012).

The ultra-conservative opinions on women's involvement in the labour market, especially in view of the demographic crisis in Poland, are heard also from politicians. Przemysław Czarnek (currently Minister of Education and Science), giving the lecture at the Catholic University of Lublin in 2019 during the election campaign, argued⁵⁵: "Go and work, ride a tractor, ride a combine, study, make a career. Career first and maybe a child later. This leads to tragic consequences. The first child is born not at the age of 20-25, but at the age of 30. If you have your first child at 30, how many of these children can you have? These are the consequences of explaining to a woman that she does not have to do what God has called her to do."

6.2. Health and reproductive rights

Successive years of attempts to tighten the abortion law eventually resulted in October 2022, when the Poland's Constitutional Tribunal, the country's highest court, ruled legislation allowing women to seek an abortion on the grounds of severe foetal impairment as incompatible with the Polish Constitution. Through this ruling, abortion in Poland is now only authorized in the case of rape, incest, or threats to the mother's life, making it practically impossible for Polish women to seek an abortion.

Another important health topic around which anti-gender mobilisation centres is sex education, which is identified by ultraconservatives with the desire to sexualise children by LGBTQ+ and 'genderists'. A remedial action against this would be, among other things, to denounce the Istanbul Convention.

Important topics in the discourse on health and reproductive rights in Poland also remain:

In vitro fertilization (IVF): Until 2016, IVF treatment was reimbursed in Poland under a government programme; after the change of government since 2016, the programme is no longer continued.

⁵⁵ "Uderzenie w rodzinę idzie zawsze przez uderzenie w kobietę. Od tego jest feminizm" (<https://tvn24.pl>), <https://fakty.tvn24.pl/ogladaj-online,60/przemyslaw-czarnek-o-kobietach-rodzinie-i-koscie-poglady-przyszlego-ministra-edukacji-i-nauki,1032333.html>

Argumenting their opposition to in-vitro, the extreme Polish conservatives often demonstrate an extreme lack of knowledge on the subject and their opinions are in line with the Catholic Church, which has equated the IVF procedure with eugenics⁵⁶, so they refer to⁵⁷:

religious arguments: "It really is a sin. I am a Catholic. According to Church teaching, human life is given a supernatural character. Life begins at conception and ends at natural death. This is not something to be afraid of in a Catholic country." (Senator Stanisław Kogut – PiS), "The Church takes an extremely harsh view of such a method of conception, pointing out that it goes against nature." (ultraconservative publicist Tomasz Terlikowski)

human dignity and ethics: "There is such a thing as conceiving a human being in unethical ways. Such methods can include rape, and such methods can also include the in vitro method." (Kaja Godek, Life and Family Foundation), "humiliating to human love procedure", (senator Dorota Czudowska-PiS),

biology, health risks: "A child with Prader-Willi syndrome may have, for example, delayed speech development, microcephaly, distinctive facial morphological features. There are some doctors who know from the first look at the baby's face that it was conceived in vitro." (Prof. Franciszek Longchamps de Bérier)

or even children's rights: "This violates children's rights", "It sort of dehumanises the child by killing it." (senator Stanisław Kogut-PiS).

The burden of reimbursing in-vitro treatment has been taken over by some local governments of Poland's largest cities.

There are also ongoing disputes around the so-called Poland's "conscience clause" under article 39 of the Doctor and Dentist Professions Act, according to which medical personnel may decline to perform medical treatment on the grounds that it conflicts with their personal values or beliefs. The law states that personnel must refer a woman to an alternate doctor where she has a real possibility of obtaining services, however such referrals are often not made⁵⁸.

Also important in this theme is the discrimination faced by transgender people receiving health care in Poland, as up to 48% of trans people whose gender identity was known to doctors faced worse treatment.⁵⁹

⁵⁶ „In vitro to młodsza siostra eugeniki”. Duchowni piszą do posłów, 18.10.2010, Tygodnik Newsweek, <https://www.newsweek.pl/polska/ekskomunika-za-in-vitro-abp-hoser-wspolautorem-listu-do-poslow/c6wbzqk>

⁵⁷ Co politycy wiedzą na temat in vitro. 30 najbardziej absurdalnych wypowiedzi, 02.10. 2016, Paulina Ryglowska-Stopka, plodnosc.pl, <https://plodnosc.pl/co-politycy-wiedza-na-temat-in-vitro-30-najbardziej-absurdalnych-wypowiedzi/>

⁵⁸ Dispatches: Abortion and the 'Conscience Clause' in Poland, 22.10.2014, Hillary Margolis, Human Rights Watch, <https://www.hrw.org/news/2014/10/22/dispatches-abortion-and-conscience-clause-poland>

⁵⁹ Sytuacja społeczna osób LGBT+ w Polsce. Raport za lata 2019–2020. Przegląd najważniejszych danych. (2021), red. Mirosława Makuchowska, Kampania Przeciw Homofobii i Stowarzyszenie Lambda Warszawa. <https://kph.org.pl/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/raport-maly-2019-2020.pdf>

6.3. Migration

In 2015, the refugee crisis in Europe coincided with the parliamentary election campaign in Poland, which Polish right-wing politicians scrupulously made use of.

Although the European Social Survey 2002-2007 shows that before the migration crisis of 2015, Poles even compared to other countries were characterised by relatively good attitudes towards foreigners and Poles' experience with refugees was marginal[110], 'similarly to Western contexts, the 2014–2015 Polish campaign against "genderism" was partly displaced by and partly merged with panic over Europe's refugee crisis.' (Korolczuk and Graff 2022:89) and the main enemy around which conservative right-wingers focused their 2015 election campaign was the "Muslim refugee." Reinforced by demonised 'gender ideology'. 'Arguably, it was the ability to combine the two themes that paved the way to the Law and Justice party electoral victory in 2015. However, the logic of this combination is significantly different from the nationalist grammar of sexual democracy vs macho-Islam. In Poland, "genderists" along with refugees (now referred to as "invaders" and "terrorists") were demonized as enemies of the nation, both groups partaking in a conspiracy engineered by Brussels elites aimed against Polish culture and sovereignty.'(Korolczuk and Graff 2022:88-89)

Since mid-2015, the approval of accepting refugees in Poland has been gradually decreasing. Surveys by CBOS argued that this was related to the dominance of negative content about refugees in media and political messages. Already in August 2015, support for accepting refugees from countries of armed conflict fell to 50% (from 58% in May), while opposition rose to 38% (from 21% in May). In autumn 2017, a record 63% of Poles expressed their opposition, and only 29% wanted to help refugees. Between 2018 and 2021, overall attitudes towards the idea of helping refugees improved, although this may have been due to a 'muting' of the topic of the migration crisis in the media and public debate.

Russia's invasion of Ukraine in February 2022 has resulted in 5,8 million refugees⁶⁰ coming from Ukraine, 3,5 millions of whom have stayed in Poland for a longer time period, mostly women and children. The reaction of the Polish society was very supportive. The situation provoked the mobilisation of both feminist and anti-abortion organisations. For example, the OSK used its regional network to help refugee women across Poland, while Kaja Godek's Life and Family Foundation 'welcomed' refugee women at the Polish-Ukrainian border with anti-abortion leaflets in Ukrainian, including the slogan 'abortion is death', informing them of the possible legal consequences associated with illegal abortion in Poland.

⁶⁰ Central Statistical Office's (GUS) data show, that by the end of 2019, there were over 2 million foreigners living in Poland, with the majority of Ukrainians (over 1.3 million). Around the same time (end of 2019) the official numbers indicate 12 673 refugees, 4791 asylum seekers and 1328 persons under UNHCR's statelessness mandate living in Poland. Within the last two decades Chechens were the biggest group of asylum seekers that have been coming to Poland. Although in official statistics this group is considered as Russian citizens, it is estimated that between 2003 and 2016 about 90 thousands of asylum seekers of Chechen origin claimed asylum in Poland (Anacka, 2015), but only 3-5% of them were given a positive decision to grant some form of international protection (Alieva & Jaworska, 2018).

6.4. LGBTQ+ rights

The actions of anti-gender groups in regards of LGBTQ+ people are on one hand discursive. Some groups – like Pro Prawo do Życia – bought vans that were covered with homophobic pictures and slogans equating homosexuality with paedophilia and alike. These vans were soon dubbed ‘pogromobus’ and began to be targeted by queer, LGBTQ+ and other activists. Other groups initiated campaigns against the NGOs offering sex education and in particular organising ‘Rainbow Fridays’. These initiatives received support from local councils, MPs and the Minister for Education, who tried to incorporate such limitations in the new law on education in Poland. These attempts, called Lex Czarnek and Lex Czarnek 2.0 (that were the same proposals) were both vetoed by president Duda, but had a ‘chilling effect’ on progressive NGOs and teachers. Another well-known case was the ‘printer from Łódź’, who refused to print leaflets for a LGBTQ+ club, whose owners sued him for discrimination. After winning in three instances (including the Supreme Court) the Minister for Justice stepped in and used legal analysis made by Ordo Iuris, sent the case to the politicised Constitutional Court, who decided that the refusal of provision of services justified by ones beliefs as constitutional, technically legalising discrimination justified by religion. The court case is now reopened and ongoing.

The Polish Constitution guarantees equality in accordance with the law and prohibits discrimination based on "any reason". The proposal to include a prohibition of discrimination on the grounds of sexual orientation in the Constitution was rejected in 1995, after strong Catholic Church objections (Duda 2016). Same-sex marriage is not recognized, and Article 18 of the Constitution of Poland states that "Marriage, being a union of a man and a woman, as well as the family, motherhood and parenthood, shall be placed under the protection and care of the Republic of Poland."⁶¹

Although there is no legal recognition of same-sex couples in Poland, cohabiting same-sex couples do enjoy certain limited benefits (in the tenancy of a shared household, the right not to testify against the partner and residency rights under EU law). While Poland possesses no specific law on cohabitation, it does have a few provisions in different legal acts or Supreme Court rulings that recognize relations between unmarried partners and provides said partners specific rights and obligations⁶². For example, Article 115(11) of the Penal Code uses the term "the closest person", which covers romantic relations that are not legally formalised. The status of "the closest person" gives the right of refusal to testify against the partner. The term "partner" includes same-sex couples. Same-sex couples are unable to legally adopt in Poland. Furthermore, lesbian couples do not have access to IVF.

In terms of hate crime laws, as of 2019, a bill is pending in Parliament to provide penalty enhancements if a crime is motivated by the victim's gender, gender identity, age, disability or sexual orientation⁶³. In 2020, there was an official government statement on the bill which expressed doubts about the introduction of additional preconditions, due to - in the government's view - sufficient protection in existing legislation.⁶⁴

⁶¹ "The Constitution of the Republic of Poland". Sejm. 2 April 1997. (13.01.2023)

⁶² Sygnatura akt I KZP 20/15, uchwała 7 sędziów SN z 25 lutego 2016 r.

⁶³ Projekt ustawy (the bill)

<http://orka.sejm.gov.pl/Druki9ka.nsf/0/2D20C923537FBBB0C12584E9003F26EA/%24File/138.pdf>

⁶⁴ Stanowisko Rządu do druku nr.138.

<https://www.sejm.gov.pl/Sejm9.nsf/druk.xsp?documentId=E924B09453C654DFC125857000430679>

6.5. Gender based violence

Politicians of the ruling party assure that Poland is a safe country for LGBT people. As evidence, they cite lower hate crime statistics compiled by the Organization for Security and Co-operation in Europe (OSCE) than in other countries.

The OSCE report gives data based on official statistics from The Ministry of Internal Affairs and Administration. This in turn reports exceptionally few cases of hate crimes against LGBT people to the OSCE. However, the low statistics do not reflect the true scale of the problem. Rather, they reflect the holes in the law and the inability (or unwillingness) of the state to detect this type of crime⁶⁵. According to the Polish Criminal Code, hate speech against LGBT people is not prohibited in Poland. Since 2015, the ruling party (Law and Justice) has been changing the system for anti-discrimination and violence by, among other things, abolishing the Human Rights Protection Team in 2016. In fact, as research shows, the level of violence against LGBT people in Poland is high, but the reporting of such incidents is low. According to the European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights survey results (2020), in the past five years 59% of LGBTQ+ people in Poland have experienced harassment because of being LGBTQ+, while 15% reported having suffered physical or sexual violence⁶⁶. In addition to experiencing discrimination in everyday life, aggressive attitudes towards the LGBTQ+ community are also manifested at events such as Equality Parades, for example in Białystok and Lublin in 2018 and 2019.

Negative effects of the aforementioned lack of legal efforts to prevent violence against LGBTQ+ people are amplified by the aggressive statements of key Law and Justice politicians, including Education Minister Przemysław Czarnek, who has openly called for taking action against LGBTQ+ people, claiming that "these people are not equal to normal people. (...) Let's defend us from LGBT ideology and stop listening to these idiocies about some human rights or some equality."⁶⁷

Such statements are perceived as encouraging overt aggression against LGBTQ+ people. As the Ombudsman pointed out there is also no doubt that local government resolutions against LGBT 'ideology' discriminate against concrete people and create a hostile and intimidating atmosphere around them, which can create the risk of violence against these people.⁶⁸

⁶⁵ Piotr Godzisz, 17.03. 2021, Czy u nas jest mniej przemocy wobec osób LGBTI niż na Zachodzie? Ekspert sprawdza słowa polityków PiS, Portal OKO.press, <https://oko.press/przemoc-wobec-lgbti-statystyki-obwe> (13.01.2023)

⁶⁶ European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights (2020) A long way to go for LGBTI equality. Research report. <https://fra.europa.eu/en/publication/2020/eu-lgbti-survey-results>

⁶⁷ Słowa Czarneka o LGBT "ci ludzie nie są równi ludziom normalnym" wyrwane z kontekstu? Akurat. 05.10.2020, Dominika Sitnicka, Portal OKO.press, <https://oko.press/czarnek-o-lgbt-studio-polska>

⁶⁸ Komunikat Rzecznika Praw Obywatelskich z dnia 17 maj 2022 (Communication from the Ombudsman, 17 May 2022), <https://bip.brpo.gov.pl/pl/content/rpo-miedzynarodowy-dzien-przeciw-homofobii-transfobii-i-bifobii-2022> (12.01.2023)

7. Repertoires of action (strategies and arguments)

Among the main strategies and types of actions used by the anti-gender/anti-feminist movement in Poland are:

Legislative Initiatives:

With the emergence of *Ordo Iuris*, legal actions (including SLAPPS) amplified and several OI members entered the judicial system (including Supreme and Constitutional Courts) and their 'analyses' were often copied into official legal proposals of the government. Anti-gender groups also provide legal help to other initiatives of the kind, defending anti-gender and anti-feminist activists (although with questionable results).

"Stop abortion" in 2010. This was the first civic initiative project in the history of Poland establishing a total ban on abortion. It failed to obtain a majority in the Sejm and was rejected in 2011⁶⁹.

"Stop abortion" in 2013. The bill postulating a ban on abortion in cases where "prenatal tests or other medical indications point to a high probability of severe and irreversible foetal impairment or an incurable life-threatening disease"⁷⁰. The representative of the Legislative Initiative Committee was Kaja Godek. (In November 2015 she established the Life and Family Foundation). The Sejm rejected the proposed bill at first reading⁷¹.

"Stop abortion" in 2016. The draft projected that abortion would be punishable by a prison sentence of three months to five years⁷². In a vote on 23 September 2016, the draft was referred for further work in committee⁷³. On 6 October 2016, the draft was voted on again in the Sejm and was rejected, also with the votes of PIS deputies⁷⁴. Similar projects were also presented in the parliament in 2017 and 2021. From 2010 to 2021, 11 anti-choice bills proposing a complete ban on abortion or severe restrictions on its use were proposed.

"Stop paedophilia" in 2019. The amendment proposed by the draft involves adding to the existing provisions of the Criminal Code the prohibition of: public promotion or praise of "engaging in sexual intercourse by a minor" (§2); the promotion or praise of 'engaging in sexual intercourse or other sexual activity by a minor' in a school environment or in the context of educational activities (§4), i.e. where the child is outside the protection and direct supervision of parents. Due to the end of the term of the Sejm, the project had to be considered anew. In a vote, on 16.04.2020 Sejm decided to refer the project for further work in committee.

⁶⁹ Course of the legislative process, Draft No. 4222,

<http://orka.sejm.gov.pl/proc6.nsf/0/F4616B52A2C73C6BC125789B00453A1D?OpenDocument>

⁷⁰ Rusza inicjatywa ustawodawcza Stop Aborcji, 21 marca 2013, Musiał Marcin, Polonia

Christiana, <https://pch24.pl/rusza-inicjatywa-ustawodawcza-stop-aborcji/>

⁷¹ Organization's website: <https://stronazycia.pl/podsumowanie-roku-2013/>

⁷² <https://tvn24.pl/polska/projekt-calkowitego-zakazu-aborcji-juz-w-sejmie-prawie-pol-miliona-podpisow-ra658703>

⁷³ <https://wiadomosci.dziennik.pl/polityka/artykuly/531594,projekt-komitetu-stop-aborcji-do-dalszych-prac-w-komisji-projekt-komitetu-ratujmy-kobiety-odrzucony.html>

⁷⁴ <https://www.wnp.pl/parlamentarny/wydarzenia/projekt-stop-aborcji-odrzucony-opozycja-kobiety-wygraly-ze-zla-zmiana,15366.html>

"Stop LGBT"- a bill submitted to the Sejm in 2021 by the Life and Family Foundation-proposes, among other things, a ban on equality marches, a ban on "promoting" same-sex relationships or promoting the definition of gender as a phenomenon independent of biological conditioning. According to the drafters, the bill is an expression of concern for "Polish families and children, respect for the Constitution, and in particular its Article 18", as "the aim of the LGBT lobby" is to destroy marriage and "any natural social order". The draft has been forwarded for further work in the Committee on Administration and Internal Affairs.⁷⁵

"Abortion is Murder" (2022) On 28 December 2022 The Life and Family Foundation led by Kaja Godek has submitted a new draft amendment on abortion to the Sejm.⁷⁶ Among other things, the authors want to ban 'public promotion of any action regarding the possibility to terminate a pregnancy', as well as 'public exhortation to terminate a pregnancy'. According to the draft, it would also be prohibited to "publicly communicate about the possibility of aborting a pregnancy inside and outside the country". The authors also want to prohibit "producing, fixing, importing, acquiring, storing, possessing, displaying, transporting or transmitting print, recordings or other objects or data carriers" with prohibited content. The Kai Godek Foundation also wants to amend the Criminal Code. The penalty for 'inducing a woman to terminate a pregnancy' would be up to three years in prison, while if 'the conceived child has reached the capacity to live independently outside the pregnant woman's organism', the penalty would increase to a range of 'from six months to eight years'.⁷⁷

Publications, for instance a guide for parents and teachers, "How to stop a paedophile?", where paedophilia is combined with homosexuality and sex education is treated as moral depravity (published by Pro-Prawo do Życia Foundation)⁷⁸. In 2023 Ordo Iuris continued this line of activism by publishing a booklet instructing business owners, how to refuse services to unliked groups and individuals (such as LGBTQ+) without being accused of discrimination. The booklet also included instructions for hotel owners who could refuse renting a room with double bed for unmarried couples, using the justification of 'brand protection'. Public marches, demonstrations, rallies, as for example "Marches for the Family", which take place in around 120 towns and cities each year. Such events are often opportunities to collect signatures for anti-gender or anti-abortion initiatives and distribute support to local conservative politicians (handing out titles of 'Family Friendly Local Government').

Local policy/public statement proposals, for example The Local Government Charter of Family Rights) it is a new type in a sense that that they are not translated into the national legislation, but it is a strong suggestion from influential institutions lobbying (in this case Ordo Iuris) for the introduction of their proposals at a local level, with the emphasis on presenting this as the official position of the local authorities (but it is not binding law).

⁷⁵ Project website: <https://stoplgbt.pl/>

⁷⁶ <https://tvn24.pl/polska/aborcja-kaja-godek-chce-zaostrzenia-przepisow-dotyczacych-propagowania-przerywania-ciazy-projekt-ustawy-6555192>

⁷⁷ Project website: <https://aborcjatozabojstwo.pl/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/projekt-ustawy-AtZ-final.pdf>

⁷⁸ <https://stronazycia.pl/stop-pedofilii/poradnik/>

Visual campaigns:

Since 2005 anti-abortion street exhibitions in major Polish cities under the slogan Choose Life. The 14 large boards present photographs of human foetuses removed as a result of abortion juxtaposed with, among others, photographs of war victims (organized by the Pro - Right to Life Foundation).

'Stop Paedophilia' campaign, which involves placing posters on vans driving around various cities in Poland and loudly playing slogans indicating that homosexuality is linked to paedophilia⁷⁹.

In Poland when it comes to social media Facebook is the predominant platform for communication both for individuals and for organizations. Twitter, although rather popular among officials and politicians, has never reached the popularity of Facebook. Recently new platforms are trending; these being tiktok, popular mostly among the youngest cohort of the public and the activists, Instagram that is most often used to amplify messages posted on other social media platforms, and Telegram popular mostly among the more radical activists and used mostly during protest events as it allows for communication and crowd control in real time. Most of the communication is done through social media, rather than through the websites of the initiatives as it allows for life communication and interaction with recipients and participants of the movement.

8. Frames of arguments

8.1. Protecting traditional values and families

The basic assumption underlying the anti-gender arguments is that the 'authentic Polish cultural identity' is 'familial', and "the real Polish family" is heteronormative, based on conservative values, and preferably Catholic.

Therefore, one of the most important narratives is the necessity to protect the traditional family model from 'gender- and LGBT-propaganda'/ 'ideology'. By constantly repeating this message, PiS managed to mobilise its voters en masse and, to some extent, demobilise the opposition voters, divided along with LGBTQ+ rights. This narrative played a key role in the victory of PiS and its candidates in both the 2019 general and the 2020 presidential elections, with most voters casting their ballots to protect the traditional family model and 'Polish catholic values'.

8.2. Protecting children

Protecting children from 'gender ideology' and 'LGBT propaganda' is another key narrative. The narrative also connects homosexuality with paedophilia. The opposition is attacked by the government for promoting 'gender and LGBT ideology' for children.

⁷⁹ Emma Powys Maurice (2020), Polish court rules campaign linking homosexuality and paedophilia is 'informative and educational', pinknews.co.uk, 2020-02-20, <https://www.thepinknews.com/2020/02/20/polish-court-anti-lgbt-campaign-homosexuality-paedophilia-fundacja-pro/>

In Poland, the main narrative used against LGBTQ+ people is built on a message about the 'sexualization of children' and 'protection of traditional families'. Key politicians of the right-wing have been spreading the belief that homosexuality and paedophilia are linked phenomena. Right-wing journalists kept repeating that those in favour of LGBTQ+ wanted to teach 4-year-old kids how to masturbate. "This is an attack on the family, and an attack conducted in the worst possible way because it's essentially an attack on children. We will say no to the attack on children. Polish parents have the right to raise their own children. We will not be intimidated. We will defend the Polish family" said PiS leader Jarosław Kaczyński during a campaign rally in 2019. He also warned voters that by supporting the opposition, they would allow nefarious forces to influence the upbringing of their children.

The same argument (child protection) was also used in the civil bills against sex education: "Stop paedophilia", "Stop LGBT", "Tak dla rodziny, nie dla gender" or the "LGBT free-zones" campaign and The Local Government Charter of Family Rights (prepared by Ordo Iuris).

8.3. Western demoralisation (Brussels, gender, LGBTQ+) and "Muslim barbarism" as sources of problems

In Poland (as in other Central and Eastern European countries), due to the cultural isolation of the People's Republic of Poland, the process of women's emancipation proceeded differently. The achievements of successive waves of feminism emerged simultaneously; women in Poland were professionally and politically active earlier than in the West, while at the same time, they were more tightly bound by domestic responsibilities. So, sexual revolution or emancipation of women in the sense it took place in the West did not happen in Poland, though they are not seen as a source of current "problems".

One of the main narratives functioning in the subject is that Polish families as well as Polish and Christian traditions and values are being attacked by the West's/Brussels's ideology of gender and LGBTQ+, named suggestively "ebola from Brussels" (Korolczuk&Graff, 2018). Feminism and LGBTQ+ rights are treated as the source of Western Europe's weakness, which blinds it to the dangers of mass migration. Poland is at the same time the victim and potential saviour of Europe, as its conservative citizens are portrayed as those who are fighting a heroic battle against Western demoralisation (gender and feminism) and 'Muslim barbarism' (refugees).

This anti-feminist and ethno-nationalist rhetoric has been much more pronounced in Poland to vilify refugees as "barbarians" than in Western countries, where for the same purposes femonationalism and homonationalism were used by right-wing actors. However, 'The femonationalistic tropes employed in Germany or Sweden were present in right-wing discourse also in Poland, but the underlying theme of sexual democracy as a core aspect of Europe's culture was lacking' (...) In contrast to femonationalistic discourse, which strategically assumes that the West is uniformly gender progressive, attachment to equality is interpreted in Poland as a sinister plot of the West against the East. (Korolczuk and Graff, 2022:88-89)

8.4. Gender as “ideology” like Marxism or even worse

According to this narrative, cultural Marxists, together with members of the LGBTQ+ community, aim to ban opinions dissenting from the liberal mainstream and subvert the basics of the democratic civil society through undermining marriage, family, and the “natural man and woman roles”. The claims of leading Law and Justice politicians⁸⁰ are in line with those of the Catholic Church hierarchy,⁸¹ who - as archbishop Henryk Hoser, Chairman of the Team of Experts on Bioethics of the Polish Bishops' Conference, Ordinary of Warsaw-Praga⁸² derive gender from Marxism, and indirectly also from Stalinism: “Gender ideology is an offshoot of Marxism and it must not be forgotten that it is a new way of class struggle. Except that the classes become women and men. The proletariat are women and men are the holders, the capitalists who oppress the proletariat. The greatest harm that radical feminism does to women is to masculinise them. (...) Masculinisation existed in Marxism. It was a very strong feature of Stalinist ideology. (...) And this, after all, goes against the vocation of women to give life, not to destroy it.” Moreover, gender is far worse than Marxism: “Gender is more dangerous because it goes further than Marxism. (...)The idea is that the older generation has no impact on the upbringing of the younger generation, and that the young are brought up by their peers.”

Fundamental to the "anti-gender ideology" crusade of the Catholic Church in Poland, Benedict XVI's 2012 statement was distorted in the Catholic Press Agency's reporting (Pokorna-Ignatowicz, 2014). Although the Pope says that gender allows people to question “a previously constituted nature of his or her own flesh, which characterizes a human being. He negates his own nature and decides that it has not been granted to him as a preceding fact, but he is to create it individually”⁸³, he refers to gender as a theory or philosophy of sexuality, whereas the KAI communiqué and Cardinal Hoser's comments already referred to "gender ideology". By changing 'philosophy' to 'ideology', an important semantic shift has been made: philosophy can be debated, ideology must be fought - in the name of some supposed 'non-ideological' truth (Duda, 2016).

In the anti-gender discourse, the reference to human rights is closely linked to human dignity, provided by the rejection of 'gender ideology' or 'LGBT ideology' and remaining faithful to traditional values. As stated on the website of the ultraconservative organization Ordo Iuris, its main field of activity is "the protection (...) of human and civil rights", resulting from the "inherent and inalienable dignity of the human being".

⁸⁰ Suchanow, K (2020), Historia organizacji Ordo Iuris i jej związków z Agendą Europe, w: *Kontrrewolucja kulturowo-religijna. Czy Polsce grozi prawo podporządkowane ideologii chrześcijańskich fundamentalistów?* Wielka Koalicja za Równością i Wyborem, Warszawa, s.24

⁸¹ <https://www.gosc.pl/doc/1638197.Gender-jak-marksizm/2>

⁸² Jędrzejczyk M. (2013), Gender groźniejsze od marksizmu. Wywiad z ks. abp. Henrykiem Hoserem, przewodniczącym Zespołu Ekspertów ds. Bioetycznych Konferencji Episkopatu Polski, ordynariuszem warszawsko-praskim, *Nasz Dziennik*, <https://naszdziennik.pl/wiara-kosciol-w-%20polsce/24344,gender-grozniejsze-od-marksizmu.html> (05.01.2023)

⁸³ Address Of His Holiness Benedict Xvi On The Occasion Of Christmas Greetings To The Roman Curia, Clementine Hall, 21 December 2012 https://www.vatican.va/content/benedict-xvi/en/speeches/2012/december/documents/hf_ben-xvi_spe_20121221_auguri-curia.html, (06.01.2023)

9. Transnational connections

Polish ultra-conservative organizations play an important role in building regional coalitions and transferring know-how. They have since built their own international network to support homophobic and transphobic efforts in other countries in the region. Ordo Iuris serves as the Eastern European hub of the ultra-conservative organizations. One of its strategies is to coordinate the network of like-minded organisations from Central and Eastern Europe.

One of the founders and first president of Ordo Iuris Aleksander Stępkowski, who is a professor of law at the University of Warsaw and served as deputy foreign minister in the Law and Justice government, at the first festival of conservatives, Tradfest, in Zagreb in November 2016 explained the need to build international cooperation: "There is no doubt that our opponents who are promoting the dehumanisation agenda are using international networking. In recent months, the international pressure on Poland has been really great and has come from all sides. We also need such a network. (...) Because neither Poland nor Croatia is strong enough to spread the traditional values agenda to such an extent in other countries. We need to change that. (...) We need to show full determination, and our governments should worry about our disillusionment as much as possible. Otherwise they will ignore us". Today Ordo Iuris has a branch in Croatia, Ordo Iuris Hrvatska⁸⁴.

Poland's closest regional ally in the topic is Hungary. The two countries cooperate most directly through the partnership agreement between the Center for Fundamental Rights (CfFR) and Ordo Iuris, which involves joint lobbying and advocacy against gender- and LGBTQ+-related EU initiatives. Their first common action was the international "petition against EU accession to the Istanbul Convention" in 2020. This action was followed by a joint petition, "Say no to redefining parenthood," supported by pro-family environments from France, Slovakia, Romania, Bulgaria, Hungary, and Ukraine. In 2021, Ordo Iuris and the CfFR jointly organised the Geneva Consensus Declaration Intermarium Regional Conference to support the 2020 anti-abortion declaration, which was signed by 30 largely illiberal or authoritarian governments (Brazil, Egypt, Hungary, Indonesia, and Uganda, along with Russia and the US which later withdrew). In 2021, the two organisations jointly founded a pan-European conservative think tank network, the Alliance for the Common Good (ACG), with conservative organisations from Slovakia, the Czech Republic, and Italy. In 2021, Ordo Iuris established Collegium Intermarium (CI), a new university, which has partnered with Marion Marechal Le Pen's Institute of Social Sciences, Economics, and Politics (ISSEP) and with representatives of the Hungarian government, CfFR, MCC, and the Danube Institute. (Suchanow 2020, Korolczuk and Graff 2022).

Right-wing East European populist parties are copying anti-gender Polish ideas into the local environment, such as the Lithuanian-Polish Union of Lithuania (AWPL). Also Latvia's new Conservative leaders at a meeting with PiS in Warsaw were said to have been inspired by an agenda built on the rhetoric of 'healthy homes - normal homes'. Political ties between PiS and the Eurosceptic group of the European Parliament, the European Conservative Reform Group (ECR), have also been used to share experience in this area. ECR sponsored anti-gender events in Poland, including a two-day conference titled 'Culture Wars' in 2020, with 'gender ideology' as one of the main topics.

⁸⁴ Kontrewolucja kulturowo-religijna. Czy Polsce grozi prawo podporządkowane ideologii chrześcijańskich fundamentalistów? (2020), Wielka Koalicja za Równością i Wyborem, Warszawa, s.24

As the report of Friedrich Naumann Foundation for Freedom (2022) states Ordo Iuris is involved in international organisations crucial to its agenda: it has consultative status at the UN Economic and Social Council (ECOSOC), and it is also active at the UN Refugee Agency (UNHCR) and the UN Commission on the Status of Women (CSW). It participates in the OSCE Human Dimension Implementation Meeting, is active at the Parliamentary Assembly of the Council of Europe, and has official accreditation at the European Parliament. Polish ultra-conservative organisations also have links to the World Congress of Families. The Piotr Skarga Institute, one of the founding organisations of Ordo Iuris, was among the sponsors of the WCF event in Warsaw (2007), and it was a partner in the next editions of the WCF, including the one in Moscow in 2014 (opened by Vladimir Putin). Although the links between Ordo Iuris and Russia are clear (Suchanow 2022), the Polish organisation tries to hide this, as being considered as 'a Russian agent' is very damaging in the anti-Russian Polish society.

There is obvious strong and complicated synergy between anti-genderism and right-wing populism.

"Political actors on the populist right engage in close cooperation with religious organizations and take up the anti-gender narrative and arguments, but only to the extent that these moves are expedient for their political agenda, saturating the anti-gender discourse with nativist and anti-Islam themes. For anti-gender organizations, on the other hand, the rise of right-wing populism presents an opening in the political opportunity structure. Hence, they are eager to collaborate, even though they do not always trust the ideological purity of their allies, and such cooperation does not guarantee the success of specific campaigns." (Korolczuk and Graff 2022:83)

Anti-gender and anti-feminist organizations support each other in their initiatives. In 2015, several NGOs collected signatures for a bill taking away the rights to reliable medical procedures, gynaecological diagnosis and life-saving treatments for the mother. Although the authors of the bill focus on abortion, the act implies potential criminal liability for the doctor and the patient going beyond the fetus. The main organisations directly involved in the project and the collection of signatures were: "Pro - Right to Life" Foundation, Foundation "Centre for Supporting Initiatives for Life and Family", Ordo Iuris Institute for Legal Culture, Rev. Piotr Skargi Association for Christian Culture / Rev. Piotr Skargi Foundation.

10. Explanations of the anti-gender/anti-feminist backlash

In the process of political transformation initiated in Poland in 1989, strong social pressure and the pursuit of a 'thick line' policy, separating all that was associated with the previous system, determined the choice of the then Polish elite of the neoliberal option, despite the low theoretical and practical background associated with it (Dąbrowska-Prokopowska 2018).

The contemporary ultraconservatives' success is seen as an offshoot of neoliberal policies, where every sphere of social life is subject to economisation, all institutions are managed according to the logic of profit maximisation and people are defined mainly by their purchasing power. The dominance of egoism and the acceptance of brutal competition have led to the erosion of the ethics of cooperation. Homo economicus has triumphed (Witaszek, 2020).

As it is stated by Wendy Brown (2003:52) it: “erodes the root of democracy in principle at the same time that it raises the status of profit and expediency as the criteria for policy making.” The result is the socio-cultural crisis triggered by the rage of those who feel lost in the neoliberal race, further reinforced by insecurity, a sense of loneliness and fear.

And it is fear that is the most effective emotion used by ultra-conservatives in Poland in the process of political manipulation. “Fear management” appears as an effective method of controlling or managing entire groups or societies, as it can achieve various political objectives simultaneously (Cywiński et.al.2019).

Anti-genderists argue that if we get rid of these dangerous diseases as gender, feminism, LGBT, it will be possible to rebuild a stable, secure world where the family provides lasting support and human bonds are more important than profit.

In addition to 'fear management', the ultra-conservatives are also conducting a 'dignity revolution' attractive to underprivileged groups. In this revolution, an enemy is needed in order to be able to better build a 'tribal dignity' based on national pride and collective fantasies about wronged people and treacherous elites (Witoszek, 2020). Using the dichotomy of “we-they”, “our-foreign”, on the one hand, anti-genderists point to the image of enemies, portraying them as those whose invasion should be feared and defended against (leftist elites, feminists, gender, LGBT, Brussels), while on the other hand, a “safe haven” and the source of dignity can be found in enduring and unchanging values: traditional family and morality, nation and the Church.

Such argumentation is further reinforced by the Catholic Church, which, despite rapid secularisation, is still an important, opinion-forming actor in this game.

11. Counter-movements

LGBTQ+ counter-movements are mainly organised by NGOs, the largest and most active of which are: Stowarzyszenie Lambda Warszawa (Lambda Warsaw Association), Stowarzyszenie Kampania Przeciwko Homofobii (Campaign Against Homophobia Association), Stowarzyszenie Miłość nie wyklucza (Love Does Not Exclude Association), Fundacja Trans-fuzja (Trans-fusion Foundation), Stowarzyszenie Fabryka Równości (Equality Factory Association), Stowarzyszenie Grupa Stonewall (Stonewall Group Association).

In addition to trainings, workshops and publications on the rights and situation of LGBTQ+ people in Poland, among the most visible activities that the war has mentioned are: civil bills, equality parades, the aforementioned “Atlas of Hate” (Atlas Nienawiści) and social campaigns, such as: the "Rainbow does not offend" campaign in response to prosecution charges of insulting religious feelings by three female activists (in April 2019 activists spread stickers with an image of the Virgin Mary in a rainbow halo. In response to the 'Stop pedophilia' campaign in 2019 organised by the Pro-Life Foundation, which consisted of collecting signatures for a bill to increase penalties for paedophilic acts and criminalise sex education, and bringing out vans on the roads with banners displaying slogans about the alleged links between homosexuality and paedophilia, Stop Nonsense (Stop Bzduram), a Warsaw-

based anarchist-queer collective, was formed to fight homophobia and transphobia. The organisation ended its activities in August 2021. Feminist counter-movements

In 1992, Barbara Labuda and Zbigniew Bujak organised an initiative involving many individuals and social organisations, known as the Bujak Committees. It was then that Poland's first non-governmental organisation dealing with reproductive rights, the Federation for Women and Family Planning, was founded. It was a reaction to the provisions proposed in the bill banning abortion that had been submitted to the Sejm. The aim of the Committees was to collect signatures for a nationwide referendum on the criminalisation of women for illegal abortion, which was one of the provisions proposed in the bill.

The Labuda and Bujak Committees turned into a nationwide movement in favour of the referendum, in which both politicians and social activists, as well as many people whose daily work or social activities were not related to the issue of the right to abortion, actively participated.

Between 1 300 000 and 1 700 000 signatures were collected. Despite meeting the statutory conditions, the Sejm rejected the referendum request and the law was passed in 1993 introducing so called the Compromise (the Act on Family Planning, Protection of the Human Fetus and the Conditions for the Permissibility of Abortion) limiting abortion to only three premises.

In December 1999, it was reported in the press that the police raided a gynaecological office in Lubliniec. The media reported that as a result of an anonymous denunciation of an alleged abortion, the police raided the doctor's office, dragged a woman out of it and transported her for forced gynaecological examinations. News of this event was the impetus for the formation of the feminist collective Porozumienie Kobiet Ósmego Marca, which organised a series of demonstrations and drafted and circulated a letter of protest on the issue. Since this event, also feminist marches called Manifas have been held every year around 8 March. On 4 February 2002, Porozumienie Kobiet Ósmego Marca (Women's Agreement of 8th March) in cooperation with the Women's Information Centre drafted the Letter of a Hundred Women, which was sent to the European Parliament. In the letter, well-known female representatives of science, culture, art, business and politics demanded a democratic debate on the situation of women in Poland. The signatories of the letter expressed concern that "(...) there has been a peculiar agreement between the Catholic Church and the government regarding Poland's accession to the European Union. Namely, the Church will support integration with Europe in exchange for the government's resignation from discussing amendments to the anti-abortion law. The Polish law on the possibility of abortion is - next to Ireland and Malta - the most restrictive in Europe. At the same time, in the field of abortion, the practice is even stricter than the law, as doctors in hospitals - citing the conscience clause - refuse even to perform the procedures provided for in the law in force".

This letter was read out during the Manifa in Warsaw, which took place on 8 March 2002 under the slogan: 'My life, my choice. Three times Yes. Yes to sex education. Yes to contraception. Yes to the right to abortion.'

The topic of abortion in public discourse appeared on the occasion of annual Manifas or other projects and events organised by the broad feminist movement.

In June 2003, the topic of the right to abortion featured prominently in the public debate in connection with the social action of bringing the ship 'Langenort', belonging to the Dutch organisation Women on Waves, to the port of Władysławowo. Polish activists and campaigners for the liberalisation of abortion law were also involved in carrying out this action. The ship housed a motherhood awareness clinic and a doctor's office. Pregnancies were terminated using a pharmacological method by giving the woman abortion pills. It aroused a huge amount of public interest - both supporters and opponents of the right to terminate a pregnancy.

The presence of the Dutch ship brought the discussion about the right to abortion back to the media after a long pause, but only for a while. The topic came to life again in 2007 when the European Court of Human Rights issued a ruling ordering Poland to pay Alicja Tysiąg 25,000 euros in compensation. The doctors decided that Alicja's case (risk of loss of sight caused by pregnancy) did not authorise a legal abortion on health grounds. Alicja had no choice, she gave birth, her sight deteriorated significantly and the case went to Strasbourg. In the ruling, the Court pointed out that Poland lacks clear procedures for legal abortion. The judgment also stressed that penalising doctors for performing abortions leads to a situation where they may be afraid to perform these procedures in accordance with the law. This was the first case of its kind, Alicja Tysiąg was the first to come forward under her full name, and as a result she faced heckling and harassment.

Also in 2007, Marek Jurek, Speaker of the Sejm from the Law and Justice party, together with MPs and deputies of the League of Polish Families, decided to introduce a provision on the protection of the human foetus into the Constitution. The introduction of such a provision would have led to a tightening of the 1993 law. This made the issue of abortion relatively noisy again.

Feminist activists protested in front of the Sejm, and women of the media met with Maria Kaczyńska, wife of the then president. The meeting resulted in an appeal to male and female parliamentarians not to tighten the law. The appeal was signed by, among others, Maria Kaczyńska, wife of the then President of Poland Lech Kaczyński. The motion to amend the Constitution was defeated in the vote. The topic of abortion again disappeared for a longer period of time and returned in 2011 with the legislative committee 'Yes to Women'. The committee was collecting signatures for a bill on informed parenthood and other reproductive rights from August to October 2011. However, without success.

After 2011, the topic of abortion appeared incidentally in public discourse.

In 2014, the topic resurfaced due to the cruel behaviour of Professor Chazan, who concealed serious fetal defects from his patient. A demonstration was held in front of the Sejm, and Chazan himself was dismissed from his position as director of the capital's hospital, but he became a favourite of anti-abortion organisations.

Apart from the Manifas, abortion was discussed at conferences or feminist meetings. The discussions took place in a small group usually around language, strategy, underground. The same group of several dozen people met in front of the Sejm to protest against subsequent 'Stop Abortion' projects.

A breakthrough year for abortion in Poland was 2016. In March, the Warsaw Manifa was organised under the slogan 'Abortion in defence of life', and two weeks later Ordo Iuris announced that, together with the Pro Right to Life organisation, they were submitting a civic project - not only banning abortion completely, but also introducing 'prenatal murder' and punishment for one's having an abortion.

The bill was the harshest possible and, interestingly, caused disapproval even among some organisations opposed to abortion. The Polish Federation of Movements for the Defence of Life disassociated itself from the project and criticised the idea of punishing women for abortions. "Reclaim the choice" demonstrations were held across Poland, and a Facebook group *Dziewuchy Dziewuchom* was created, which to this day is another space where people can seek support before, during and after an abortion pill.

In response to the anti-abortion bill, the Save the Women (*Ratujmy Kobiety*) Committee was set up and developed its bill to legalise abortion. Both anti- and pro-abortion bills were presented in the Sejm at the same time - at the end of September 2016. At the same time, in fear of drastic abortion laws, Women's Strikes - the largest demonstrations on abortion in Poland since the ban - took place in the streets of many Polish towns and cities. The accumulation of protests occurred on 3 October, the so-called Black Monday.

In October 2020, the Constitutional Court stated that the premise allowing abortion in the case of fetal defects was unconstitutional. The Women's Strike took to the streets again and, despite the pandemic Covid-19, gathered tens of thousands of people across the country for protests. The protests continued until spring 2021.

The academic literature on the subject points out that the women's protests that began in 2016 should be placed in the broader context of the changing relationship between Polish society (especially young society and women) and the Church. 'For women it was obvious that what needs to be challenged is not only right-wing populism but also its ultraconservative allies, as well as the political power of the Catholic Church itself.' (Korrolczuk and Graff, 2022:139).

In 2021 the citizens' bill committee "Legal Abortion. No compromise" was presented in the Sejm. More than 200,000 signatures were collected, but the bill was rejected.

12. Other important issues

Poland is in an accelerated trend of secularisation. According to a report by the PEW Group, Poland is the country where religiosity is declining at the fastest rate in the world. This is observed along various indicators confirming religiosity: self-declared regular attendance at Sunday mass: about 40% for the 60+ age group and 26% for the 18-40 age group, or participation in religion classes conducted in schools (in total, about 25% of high school students participate in such classes, in some parts of the country there are schools where religion is not taught at all due to lack of interest of students). This reduces the impact of the Church on the young people and forces the ant-gender and anti-feminist movements to seek support from the officials and not from the regular people.

The spread of the feminist protest: from metropolitan cities to small towns and cities

During both the 2016 and October 2020 protests, in addition to demonstrations in large cities, there were numerous protest events in smaller provincial towns. In 2016, the fact that protests were held across the country, including in small provincial towns whose residents are the main electoral force of the Law and Order Party in government, was one of the key factors in the success of the protesters and the maintenance of the so-called abortion compromise at the time.

Radicalisation of discourse

Attention was drawn to the new, more radical language that has been used by feminist activists and protesters. Firstly, numerous slogans are repeated during the protests, displayed on banners and used in online communication: "the revolution is a woman" and the even more widespread "this is war!". Secondly, the most frequently shouted slogans are "fuck off" and "Fuck PiS", sometimes written down as ***** ***, under the name of a new social movement that has so far been active mainly online.

13. Conclusion

Anti-gender and anti-feminist movements are a relative novelty in Poland. Although they are based on solid foundations of Polish prejudices and patriarchal vision of family and gender regimes, it was around the early 2000s, thanks to international connections when this approach developed. Around 2012, the issue became a part of public discourse, often accompanied by the term 'ideology'. The rise of anti-genderism can be connected to an observable shift in the reasoning of the Polish far-right that took up the concept of 'cultural Marxism'. The term cultural Marxism often appears in public debates in Poland as well as in politicians and clergymen speeches. It also entered the schools' curriculum with the newly introduced course 'history and contemporality' (historia i teraźniejszość), and in particular in first textbook for that course approved and recommended by the Ministry for Education and Science, written by a historian Wojciech Roszkowski. The term became a sort of a pick lock key for the majority of the right, but -as with other key concepts on the contemporary right, such as 'gender ideology' – are unclear, blurry, and vague, which makes them more useful for the right-winger politicians.

This shift can be observed among many far-right populist politics around the world, resulting in an enemy difficult to identify (in more precise terms, hence the use of the concept of 'ideology'), but resulting in a perfect social scarecrow that allows to mobilise the masses. Cultural Marxism is strongly associated (by the far right) with 'gender ideology' and anti-genderism is often portrayed as part of the struggles against contemporary (and often imagined) Left. Here the international links (at least in discursive terms) are clearly visible. In The Wanderer Catholic newspaper article "The Frankfurt School: Conspiracy to Corrupt" (December 2008), Timothy Matthews said that the Frankfurt School was "Satan's work" and listed their eleven alleged culture-war aims:

- Codification of hate crimes
- Causing constant social changes to provoke confusion
- Teaching children sex and homosexuality
- Weakening the authority of schools and teachers
- Mass immigration to destroy national identity
- Promoting alcoholism
- Reducing church attendance
- Weakening the legal system and causing it to be biased against crime victims
- Making people dependent on the state or welfare
- Controlling the media
- Encouraging family breakdown

With the exception of the welfare system (social transfers are highly promoted by Law and Justice and opposition to social welfare in Poland is a domain of liberal opposition), majority of the above-mentioned points could be used to justify an anti-gender or anti-feminist campaign in Poland. The points “Codification of hate crimes” and “Weakening the legal system and causing it to be biased against crime victims” reveal one - slightly hidden - aspect of the anti-gender campaigns. On the one hand right wing media, publicists and other actors mentioned in this report often openly speak out against political correctness, complaining that it is a tool for silencing them and that it takes away from them their freedom of speech, the right to make jokes and hold to their values and beliefs. The second argument is used portraying them as victims of hate crimes, with appeals to introduce gender equality or the right to abortion being a brutal attack on them. In the recently published (with a generous support from the PiS controlled Ministry of Justice) report on ‘Christianophobia’ in Poland, vast majority of described ‘attacks’ on Christians and Catholics in Poland are internet memes.

The anti-gender and anti-LGBTQ+ mobilisation in Poland is largely ideology-driven, reinforced by some politicians, public figures and institutions (Ordo Iuris, Kaja Godek, Konfederacja, Grzegorz Braun, Janusz Kowalski, ONR with Robert Bąkiewicz) and the Catholic Church (Father Dariusz Oko, Father Tadeusz Rydzyk, archbishops: Józef Michalik, Henryk Hoser, Marek Jędraszewski). The Catholic Church in Poland actively and directly contributed to the formation of public opinion and – being aware of their political power – catholic hierarchs influenced political decisions of all subsequent governments.

Law and Justice (Prawo i Sprawiedliwość, PiS) in Poland, have played a central role since the mid-2010s and has been using the radical populist strategy for gaining and keeping political power, which is based on traditional, catholic values and on the fear of anything that does not embody those values. PiS is building an increasingly authoritarian state by dismantling the democratic system based on the rule of law and checks and balances, eliminating independent institutions, controlling the public discourse, curbing civil liberties and polarising society. To disguise this, the country is pictured as being constantly under attack by enemies, such as the alleged 'gender and LGBT ideology'. The main author of this term and the institution that defined the "enemy" and introduced it into public discourse is the Catholic Church, which also has pictured it as something that is attacking 'normality', conservative values, children, and families. The anti-gender mobilization picked up especially in 2013 and early 2014.

In 2015 the PiS party won the election partially because of the anti-refugee outcry, and since then successive opponents of the party have been hand-picked and presented to the public as new enemies of the nation and the state. In 2019 PiS started to attack LGBTQ+ people. In the 2019 and 2020 elections the enemies were “LGBT ideology”, “gender ideology” and feminists. In the perspective of the next elections (parliamentary in autumn of 2023, presidential in 2024) one can assume these narratives will be recycled again.

14. Timeline

15. List of anti-gender/anti-feminist organizations

List of the anti-gender and anti-feminist organizations and initiatives (POLAND)

Name of the organization (original)	Name of the organization (English)	Anti-gender or anti-feminist?	Logo of the organization	Head of the organization (in the period 2010-2021)	Web-page (social media)	Size of the organization (if available)	Comment (brief description)
Fundacja Życie i Rodzina	Life and Family Foundation	Anti-feminist, anti-gender		Kaja Godek	https://www.facebook.com/fundacjazycieirodzina/ https://www.zycierodzina.pl/	n/a	
Fundacja Pro-Prawo do Życia	The Pro - Right to Life Foundation	Anti-feminist, anti-gender		Mariusz Dzierżawski	https://stronazycia.pl/ https://www.facebook.com/FundacjaPro/	n/a	
Fundacja „Centrum Wspierania Inicjatyw dla Życia i Rodziny”	The Foundation "Centre for Supporting Initiatives for Life and Family"	Anti-feminist, anti-gender		Paweł Ozdoba	https://czir.org/ https://www.facebook.com/centrumzyciairodziny/		
Stowarzyszenie Ruch 4 Marca	March 4th Movement Association	Anti-feminist, Anti-gender			http://lodz.ruch4marca.pl/ https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=100066771926240&paipv=0&eav=		

					AfbRLQONR5LJxAfRCUbgpSaWVCcETczxiHh0iqDniUnqJaMxoPLs5wxcdTzmlHv7CnM		
Fundacja Instytut na rzecz Kultury Prawnej Ordo Iuris	The Ordo Iuris Institute for Legal Culture Foundation	Anti-feminist, Anti-gender		Jerzy Kwaśniewski	https://ordoiuris.pl/ https://www.facebook.com/ordoiuris/		
Instytut Ordo Caritatis	Ordo Caritatis Institute	Anti-feminist, Anti-gender		Bogusław Kiernicki	https://www.fundacjaswietegobenedykta.pl/institut-ordo-caritatis/		
Stowarzyszenie Rodzin Wielodzietnych Warszawy i Mazowsza	Association of Large Families of Warsaw and Mazovia	Anti-feminist, Anti-gender			https://www.wielodzietni.org.pl/ https://www.facebook.com/Stowarzyszenie-Rodziny-Wielodzietnych-Warszawy-i-Mazowsza-238291876335453/		

Stowarzyszenie Padagogów Natan	Association of Padagogues Natan	Anti-feminist, Anti-gender		https://szkolenia.natan.pl/ https://www.facebook.com/Stowarzyszenie-Pedagog%C3%B3w-NATAN-122593937754090/		
Związek Podhalan w Polsce	Polish Podhalan Association	, Anti-gender		https://związek-podhalan.com/ https://www.facebook.com/związekpodhalanwpolsce/		
Instytut Ona i On	She and He Institute	Anti-feminist, Anti-gender		http://onaion.org.pl/ https://www.facebook.com/people/Instytut-Ona-i-On/100066997384750/?p_aipv=0&eav=AfZEEKcr_KcJ_tks2Z7hYieVoZnxnn9I6AZBnwcUTATneGRjEptS58ROHZ8mWiH_oQCU&rdr		

Konfederacja Kobiet RP	Confederation of Polish Women	Anti-feminist, Anti-gender		https://konfederajakobiet.pl/ https://www.facebook.com/konfederajakobiet/		
Fundacja Mamy i Taty	Mam and Dad Foundation	Anti-feminist, Anti-gender		https://serwisrodzinny.pl/ https://www.facebook.com/FundacjaMamyiTaty/		
Stowarzyszenie Rodzice Chronią Dzieci	Parents Protecting Children Association	Anti-feminist, Anti-gender		https://rchd.pl/		

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SLOVENIA

Rok Smrdelj

1. Introduction

Since its independence in 1991, there have been numerous attempts in Slovenia to restrict existing sexual and reproductive rights and to prevent the enactment of equality policy legislation that expands these rights. However, actors and initiatives that attempt to abolish reproductive and sexual rights, have in the last decade taken over new political tactics and a new discourse that, like gender equality policies, relates to human rights. In many ways, this movement has adopted strategies and discourse previously used only by activists in the feminist and LGBT movements (Antič Gaber & Kuhar, 2019: p. 101). The existing literature (e.g., Kuhar, 2017) refers to this countermovement as anti-feminist and anti-gender movement.

In this report, we examine the existing literature that presents, analyzes, and discusses anti-feminist and anti-gender movement in Slovenia, their campaigns, and the issues that the actors in this movement address. According to our working definitions for the FIERCE project, the term anti-gender actors includes all actors who use “gender ideology” or “gender theory” or “genderism” as a key term/concept in their rhetoric and actions. There is a broad network of actors that are considered part of the current anti-gender movement. This network includes citizens' initiatives or organizations of “concerned citizens”, family associations, pro-life groups, radical nationalist parties, right-wing populists, etc. The term anti-feminist actors, on the other hand, refers to actors who reject some or all forms of feminism, its political struggles for equality, and its principles. There are various forms of antifeminism, but generally they are based on the belief that the traditional gender division of labor is natural, or that women's rights and equality negatively affect men's rights and position in society, without necessarily using conceptual devices such as “gender ideology” or “genderism” and without assuming the features of conspiracy theories.

However, as we will show in this report, anti-feminist actors and organizations in Slovenia refer to “gender theory”. In the case of Slovenia, therefore, we cannot speak of an anti-feminist movement and an anti-gender movement as two separate entities that differ in whether they use “gender theory” as a frame of reference for their rhetoric. In contrast, in Slovenia, both anti-feminist and anti-gender actors refer to “gender theory”. Therefore, we can speak of a unified, interwoven movement that is similar not only in rhetoric, but also in the fact that the actors are connected and have common allies. Within this broader movement of anti-feminist and anti-gender actors, we can distinguish between actors primarily focused on the issue of reproductive rights (e.g., abortion, medically assisted reproduction)¹ and those primarily opposed to LGBT rights. Tentatively, we can say that the former are closer to the agenda typical of the anti-feminist movement, while the latter are closer to the agenda typical of the anti-gender movement.

In this introduction, we first explain how we collected the existing studies that are in focus. Then, we briefly present the main features of the research dynamics on anti-feminist and anti-gender movement in terms of who is writing about it, how frequently studies have appeared in the last decade, and the

¹ In this report, the term »single women's right to medically assisted reproduction« refers to access to all types of assisted reproduction technologies and procedures (e.g., artificial insemination, in vitro fertilization).

main issues addressed in the collected documents. In the last part of the introduction, we explain the main gender/LGBT policies that engaged with anti-feminist and anti-gender actors in Slovenia in the period 2010–2021.

1.1. How were the studies collected?

The studies were collected through the Slovenian national bibliographic system Cobiss under the following keywords: »anti-gender movement«, »anti-gender campaigns«, »anti-gender politics«, »LGBT ideology«, »gender ideology«, »gender theory«, »anti-feminist movement«, »anti-feminist campaigns«, »anti-feminist politics«, »anti-feminism«, »in vitro fertilization«, »abortion«, »same-sex partnerships«, »family code«, and »ZZZDR«. The last five keywords refer to the issues that the anti-feminist and anti-gender movement has been most concerned with in Slovenia in the last decade. Moreover, the last keyword is an abbreviation for the proposed amendment to the law, which provided for the legal equality of heterosexual and same-sex partnerships in 2015 in Slovenia.

In the Cobiss database, we searched for documents that contain any of the above keywords. We received a large number of hits, which we limited to the following documents: scientific articles, book chapters, monographs, conference papers, and other scholarly texts that chose the anti-feminist and/or anti-gender movement in Slovenia as their object of study and appeared in the period 2010–2021. We also considered all kinds of texts that cannot be classified as scientific but are usually produced by non-governmental organizations, movements, journalists, etc., and therefore also represent a relevant and credible source of information on the topic in focus.

1.2. The Main Features of the Research Dynamics

In the period 2010–2021, five studies were published dealing with activities related to the anti-feminist movement in Slovenia. Two studies deal with the right to abortion (Kralj et al., 2021; Mencin Čeplak, 2016), two with the single women's right to medically assisted reproduction (Cukut Krilić, 2013; Furlan et al., 2020), and one study deals with both of the above issues as well as same-sex marriages (Šabec et al., 2021). The right to abortion is the main issue that triggers the organized activity of the anti-feminist movement in Slovenia. Although the single women's right to medically assisted reproduction is the notable subject of the above-mentioned studies, this issue has not been the main topic of the anti-feminist actors in the last decade, as it was relevant two decades ago, when the law depriving the single women's right to medically assisted reproduction was successfully passed in the Slovenian Parliament. Two other issues are mentioned in the above studies, namely the decriminalization of prostitution and the ratification of the Istanbul Convention. However, these two issues are only briefly mentioned in the studies, as they did not play a major role in triggering the anti-feminist movement in Slovenia.

In contrast to the literature on the anti-feminist movement, the literature on the anti-gender movement is more extensive. For the period 2010–2021, we can find eleven studies on the anti-gender movement in Slovenia (e.g., Antić Gaber & Kuhar, 2019; Gorjanc & Fišer, 2018; Kuhar, 2015a; 2015b; 2017; Kuhar & Pajnik, 2020; Kuhar & Zobec, 2017; Pajnik et al., 2016; Smrdelj et al., 2021; Sobočan & Pollak, 2016;

Šabec et al., 2021).² All of these studies on the anti-gender movement in Slovenia focus on the marriage equality debate in Slovenia in 2009–2012 and/or 2015.

The main reason that there are more studies on the anti-gender movement than on anti-feminist movement is that the issues that mobilized the anti-feminist movement (e.g., abortion) have not been particularly present in the Slovenian public sphere in the last decade, probably because no significant legislative changes have been made on this issues. On the other hand, anti-gender actors were triggered by two legislative attempts to provide equal legal protection and recognition for heterosexual and same-sex couples in Slovenia (the first in 2009, the second in 2015) that strongly polarized the Slovenian public, which is probably the reason that they received more scholarly attention.

All fifteen studies representing the field of anti-feminist and anti-gender movement in the period 2010–2021 in Slovenia were produced by scholars, while we did not find any literature authored by representatives of non-governmental organizations, movements, journalists or other non-academic organizations. The reason for this may be that feminist and LGBT organizations conducting their own studies focus on examining discrimination against members of their own communities rather than on studying their countermovement.

Almost all studies representing the field of anti-feminist and anti-gender movement in the period 2010–2021 in Slovenia are from the period after 2015, with the exception of study by Cukut Krilić (2013) that originated in the first half of the previous decade. This means that the anti-feminist and anti-gender movement in Slovenia gained most of scholarly attention after the referendum on family legislation in Slovenia in 2015.

1.3. The Key Gender/LGBT policies in the period 2010–2021 in Slovenia

As outlined above, according to the collected literature, the main gender/LGBT policies that engaged anti-feminist and anti-gender actors in Slovenia were related to the following areas: 1) the right to abortion, 2) the single women's right to medically assisted reproduction, and 3) marriage equality, including same-sex adoptions.

With respect to the right to abortion, the Slovenian regulation of abortion is one of the most liberal in Europe. Under the *Health Measures in Exercising Freedom of Choice in Childbearing Act* (slo. *Zakon o zdravstvenih ukrepih pri uresničevanju pravice do svobodnega odločanja o rojstvu otrok*) (1977) women have access to abortion on demand during the first 10 weeks of pregnancy. After the first 10 weeks, authorization by a two-tiered commission is required to minimise risk to the health of the pregnant woman and her future pregnancies. If a woman is under 16, her parents must be notified unless she has been recognised as having full legal capacity to earn her own living. Abortion may be performed only in general, specialised and clinical hospitals with organised gynaecological and obstetric or surgical services, as well as in other authorised health care facilities, with at least 80% of the cost of the procedure covered by health insurance. The *Freedom of Choice in Childbearing* (slo. *svobodno odločanje o rojstvih otrok*) is even a constitutional category (Article 55 of the *Slovenian Constitution*, slo. *Ustava Republike Slovenije*), first enshrined in the 1974 *Constitution* (at the time Slovenia was part of Yugoslavia) and retained in the 1991 *Constitution* of the independent Slovenia (Mencin Čeplak, 2016:

² We listed Šabec et al. (2021) both here and above as they discuss issues related to anti-feminist and anti-gender actors.

pp. 1374–1375). The number of abortions has declined significantly since the 1980s (see Graph 1 below). This is due to the good implementation of reproductive health rights, including reproductive education, provided by the public health system in Slovenia.

Graph 1: Number of Abortions since 1980s in Slovenia (source: National Institute of Public Health, NIJZ).

While the right to abortion is regulated in an exemplary manner, single women in Slovenia are legally barred from medically assisted reproduction. Since 1977, all women in Slovenia have had the right to medically assisted reproduction. In 1999, under the conservative government, a new law was passed limiting the right to medically assisted reproduction to women in a heterosexual relationship. The left-wing parties proposed an amendment to grant all women the right to medically assisted reproduction regardless of their relationship status. The amendment was rejected on a public referendum, initiated by some conservative MPs and Aleš Primc, one of the key anti-feminist and anti-gender actor in Slovenia (Kuhar, 2017: p. 229). However, two attempts were made in 2013 to review the constitutionality of the 1999 law, and one in 2014, but all three requests were rejected due to procedural processes that allowed the Constitutional Court not to evaluate the content of the proposed initiatives (Furlan et al., 2020: pp. 6–7). However, in October 2020, the legal review of the constitutionality of the law was again introduced by The Left party with co-signers from some other political parties (Masten, 2020). The initiative is still pending before the Constitutional Court. Finally, in February 2021, the Constitutional Court declared unconstitutional the article of the law that prohibits medically assisted reproduction for women in partnerships older than 43 years. The request for a constitutional review was filed by the complainant, who had been denied insurance reimbursement for medically assisted reproduction abroad (Kosmač, 2021).

As mentioned above, the third area, marriage equality, received the most public attention in Slovenia in the last decade, compared to the right to abortion and single women's right to medically assisted reproduction. The organized LGBT movement in Slovenia emerged in the early 1980s, ten or more years before similar movements appeared in other post-socialist countries (Velikonja & Greif, 2012). Nevertheless, it took over 30 years for Slovenia to become the first East-European country to introduce full marriage equality, including same-sex adoption, in its legislation in the summer of 2022. The history of LGBT politics in Slovenia is determined by two interesting facts. First, Slovenia is the only country in the world where the right-wing political coalition passed the first national legislation addressing the

rights of same-sex couples (Antić Gaber & Kuhar, 2019: p. 109). And second, Slovenia is the only country in the European Union where a referendum on equality of rights between heterosexual and same-sex couples was held twice, first in 2012 and then again in 2015 (Kuhar, 2017: pp. 224).

The first piece of legislation in the area of same-sex partnerships is the *Civil Partnership Registration Act* (2005), which was prepared by the right-wing government. The law granted only limited rights to same-sex couples and maintained marriage as an institution reserved only for heterosexual couples (Antić Gaber & Kuhar, 2019: p. 109). The first attempt at marriage equality dates back to 2009, when the left-wing government presented a reform of the *Family Code*. This new code, which replaced the previous one from 1976, introduced an inclusive definition of the family that covers all forms of biological and social parenthood, marriage equality, and the right of same-sex couples to joint adoption. The changes brought by the code were the subject of public controversy for a long time. The code was finally passed by Parliament in 2011 in a significantly slimmed-down version compared to the original 2009 version: the option of joint adoption was removed from the law, as was the inclusive definition of marriage, which remained an exclusive institution for heterosexual couples. The law introduced civil partnership for same-sex couples, which had more or less the same legal consequences as marriage. Nevertheless, the new Family Code was repealed in 2012 after a public referendum initiated by the newly formed coalition of »concerned citizens« named *Civil Initiative for the Family and the Rights of Children* (slo. *Civilna iniciativa za družino in pravice otrok*) (Kuhar, 2017: pp. 216–217).

The second attempt at marriage equality was made in 2015, when the Slovenian Parliament adopted amendments to the *Marriage and Family Relations Act* (1976) that introduced marriage equality into Slovenian legislation for the second time. However, the same group of »concerned citizens« – this time renamed *Children Are at Stake* (slo. *Za otroke gre*) – again called for a referendum. They managed to collect more than 80,000 signatures which is twice the number needed for the initiation of a referendum in parliament. In December 2015, the majority of voters voted against marriage equality (Kuhar, 2017: p. 217). After the second rejection of same-sex partnership legislature at the referendum, independent MP Jani Möderndorfer proposed a new law on same-sex partnerships, which was identical in content to the compromise version of the 2009 *Family Code*. The law, which put heterosexual and same-sex couples on almost equal legal footing (with the exception of joint adoption and the right to medically assisted reproduction in a same-sex partnership), but kept the institution of marriage and civil partnership separate, was passed by Parliament in April 2016 and entered into force in February 2017 (Antić Gaber & Kuhar, 2019: p. 112).

A turning point in the history of the struggles for marriage equality in Slovenia occurred in July 2022, when the Constitutional Court ruled that the regulation under which only persons of the opposite gender can enter into marriage is unconstitutional. The Constitutional Court ordered National Assembly to repeal the unconstitutionality within six months. In October 2022, the National Assembly adopted amendments to the *Family Code* that represent marriage equality (STA, 2022). For the first time in Slovenia, equality of rights between heterosexual and same-sex couples has been recognized by the Constitutional Court and therefore cannot be overturned by referendum or legislative procedure.

2. The History of the Anti-feminist/Anti-gender Movement and its Context

2.1. Anti-feminist movement

The anti-feminist actors became publicly visible in Slovenia in the last decade through two »pro-life« events: 1) a rally of anti-abortion activists in front of the Gynecological Clinic in Ljubljana, which began in 2015, and 2) an event called the *March for Life* (slo. *Pohod za življenje*), which has been held four times so far, first in 2014 and then again in 2020, 2021, and 2022.

The anti-abortion rallies in front of the gynecological clinic in Ljubljana began in 2015 and were strongly supported by the RCC and right-wing media. *God's Children Institute* (slo. *Zavod božji otroci*), which organized the rallies, is part of the international *40 Days for Life* project, which includes prayers for »an end to abortions at the Ljubljana clinic«. In response to the rallies, some individuals and non-governmental organizations sent an open letter to some of Slovenia's highest political representatives in February 2016, warning them that the location of opposition to the realization of the right to artificial abortion enshrined in the Constitution is inappropriate, as such a choice of location undoubtedly means strong pressure on women and health workers. The letter urged the addressees to take action and protect women from the pressure of opponents of reproductive rights. The letter urged the addressees to take action and protect women and health care workers from pressure from opponents of reproductive rights (Kralj et al., 2021: pp. 59–60).

The open letter triggered strong reactions, including an article published on 24kul.si, the main portal of the anti-feminist and anti-gender movement in Slovenia, under the title *List of abortion lobby members who oppose the right to life of unborn children* (Belin, 2016). Later, the same article was renamed to read »unborn boys and girls« instead of »unborn children«. The article stated that »members of the abortion lobby« advocate »the extinction of the Slovenian nation and Slovenian culture«. The signatories, it says, are the messengers of the »culture of death« that »endangers Christianity«. For insult to honor and good name, some of the signatories filed criminal charges in May 2015 against the moderator of the website 24kul.si Tadej Strehovec, the then-secretary general and official public relations officer of the Slovenian Bishops' Conference, the highest body in the hierarchy of the RCC in Slovenia. When Strehovec's trial began in October 2018, his supporters organized protests in Ljubljana's Prešeren Square and outside the courthouse every time he was summoned to court. Prominent politicians, members of right-wing conservative parties, and civil society initiatives and organizations supported by the Slovenian RCC were among the demonstrators. Aleš Primc, then head of the *Civil Initiative for the Family and the Rights of Children*, and Archbishop Anton Stres were also speakers on the protests. After a long and complicated procedure, the court issued a decision in December 2019, according to which the portal 24kul.si had to remove all incriminated articles concerning the plaintiffs and lift the secrecy of the court proceedings. In March 2019, however, the court dismissed the charges against Strehovec because it was not possible to prove directly that he was the author of the article, as the content of the incriminated article could be viewed and edited by various people (Kralj et al., 2021: pp. 59–62).

The next »pro-life« event that has strengthened the activity of the anti-feminist movement in Slovenia is the so-called *March for Life*, first organized in 2014 by the *God's Children Institute* as a counter-event against the conference of the *International Federation of Professional Abortion and Contraception Associates*. Participants in the anti-conference rally carried giant photos of aborted fetuses to »show the real truth about abortion«. At the beginning of January 2020, several »pro-life« initiatives founded

the *March for Life Organizing Committee* (slo. *Organizacijski odbor pohoda za življenje*). Its main purpose was to prepare the second »March for Life« in Slovenia (Kralj et al., 2021: p. 63).

Months before the march, people were invited to fill out the registration form for the march on the websites of pro-life organizations, including 24kul.si, prepare homemade banners and posters for the march, and bring their children to the march. Urša Cankar Soares, the coordinator of the organizing committee, spoke about the march in interviews for all conservative-oriented media in Slovenia. Among other things, the committee launched a prayer campaign for unborn children, whose goal was 700,000 *Hail Marys* for the 700,000 unborn children who have died in Slovenia in the last 70 years, since abortion was legalized in 1952. Organizers asked people to sign a document called the *Declaration for Life*, in which signers advocated respect for life from natural conception to natural death. They presented emotionally charged testimonies of women who spoke about their »post-abortion syndrome« and of women whose intimate relationships ended because they chose to have an abortion. Articles abounded in all conservative media, especially on the Internet, about the dangers of indoctrination with »gender theory« (Kralj et al., 2021: pp. 63–65), which also shows how anti-feminist initiatives are closely intertwined with anti-gender movement.

The rally, which began on October 3, 2020, in front of St. Jacob's Church in Ljubljana, was also attended by several prominent representatives of the political right in Slovenia (i.e., Alenka Jeraj, a member of the Slovenian Democratic Party (SDP), and Tadeja Šuštar, a member of New Slovenia–Christian Democrats (NSi), as well as Aleš Primc, leader of the newly established *Voice for Children and Families party*, which was established from the anti-gender movement after the second referendum on marriage equality. The organizers stated that between 500 and 600 people attended the rally, while the police estimated their number at around 200. The conservative media reported the rally as a great success, but at the same time complained that the national media and right-wing newspapers did not pay enough attention to it (Kralj et al., 2021: pp. 64–65).

2.2. Anti-gender movement

Although women's reproductive rights are a frequent target of the Slovenian anti-feminist and anti-gender movement (Kuhar, 2017: p. 215), the main trigger for the rise of the anti-gender movement in Slovenia were attempts to introduce an inclusive and non-heteronormative definition of family and marriage into Slovenian legal system (Kralj et al., 2021: pp. 52–53). As we explained in the previous section of this report, there are two such moments in Slovenia, namely the referendum on the *Family Code* (2012) and the referendum on same-sex partnerships (2015). Most of the activities of the anti-gender movement were aimed at the aforementioned referenda (Kuhar, 2017: p. 215).

The beginning of the anti-gender movement in Slovenia can be traced back to 2009, when the left-wing government presented a reform of the *Family Code*. The proposed changes were most strongly attacked by the *Civil Initiative for the Family and the Rights of Children*, founded in 2009 by Aleš Primc, a graduate philosopher, a former member of the conservative Slovene People's Party who presented himself as a »concerned father« (Kralj et al., 2021: p. 57). Opponents of the law built their campaign on the idea of a multi-faceted dangerous homosexuality that threatens children, the traditional family, and gender roles, and thus the future of the Slovenian nation. The initiative launched a campaign to collect 40,000 signatures to demand a referendum about the *Family Code*. The main mobilization medium of the campaign was the online portal 24kul.si, founded by the KUL.si Institute and initially hosted on the

official server of the Slovenian RCC. The campaign was successful and on February 3, 2012, the *Civil Initiative for the Family and the Rights of Children* provided the necessary signatures for the referendum. The *Family Code* was rejected in a referendum on March 25, 2012, with 55% of the vote, with 30% of eligible voters casting ballots (Kralj et al., 2021: pp. 55–57).

The second attempt at marriage equality began in December 2014, when the United Left party introduced a proposal to amend the *Marriage and Family Relations Act* (1976) in the parliamentary procedure, assuming that marriage can be contracted by »two persons« and not only by »man« and »woman«, as was the case until then. The National Assembly approved this proposal in March 2015.

The proposal re-activated the anti-gender movement, which grew stronger after the first referendum and their member organizations became stakeholders in issues related to intimate citizenship. In February 2015, Aleš Primc, who was already active during the first referendum campaign, and Metka Zevnik, a new actor in anti-gender movement in Slovenia, founded a new civic initiative called *Children are at Stake*. The RCC strongly supports the aforementioned initiative, which organized a rally with several thousand people in front of the Parliament in March 2015 and started collecting signatures for a referendum against the aforementioned law amendment. By the end of March they have succeeded in collecting twice the number of required signatures. The initiators of the amendment tried to prevent the referendum, arguing that it was inadmissible because it interfered with fundamental human rights and was therefore incompatible with Article 90 of the Slovenian Constitution. In April 2015, the *Children are at Stake* appealed the National Assembly's decision that the referendum was inadmissible, which the Constitutional Court upheld and allowed the referendum to proceed. In the referendum held on December 20, 2015, 64% of voters rejected the proposed amendment to the law, with a turnout of 36% (Kralj et al., 2021: p. 58). After 2015 the activities of the anti-gender movement continued in different shapes and forms, but they were no longer as visible as during the referendum campaign. In July 2022, after the Constitutional Court ruled in favor of marriage equality, the movement again began collecting signatures for a referendum, but the campaign did not receive much public attention, probably because a referendum cannot be held on the Constitutional Court's decision.

3. Actors

The network of actors in the anti-feminist and anti-gender movement in Slovenia consists of various pro-Catholic groups, organizations, »institutes«, pro-Catholic conservative media, etc., known to the Slovenian public as part of a network that increased its political power and public visibility in the 2012 and 2015 referendum campaigns (Kralj et al., 2021: p. 163). As already elaborated in the introduction to this report, the anti-feminist and anti-gender movement in Slovenia do not generally represent two separate phenomena, but rather a single, interconnected movement, as the same actors are involved in the actions against reproductive and sexual rights. In the following, we present main anti-feminist and anti-gender organizations, actors or organizing Committees in Slovenia:

- *The Institute for Family and the Culture of Living* (slo. *Zavod za družino in kulturo življenja*). The aforementioned institution describes itself as a non-profit civil society organization founded in 2009. Its founder and director is Franciscan monk Dr. Tadej Strehovec, the already mentioned member of the Justice and Peace Commission, secretary general and spokesman for the Slovenian Bishops' Conference, and assistant professor of moral theology and applied ethics at the Faculty of Theology. In 2009, *The Institute for Family and the Culture of Living* and *Civil*

Initiative for the Family and the Rights of Children founded the Slovenian online news portal 24kul.si, the most prominent portal of the anti-feminist and anti-gender movement in Slovenia (Kralj et al., 2021: p. 52). The portal was originally hosted on the official server of the Slovenian RCC (Kralj et al., 2021: p. 57).

- *Iskreni* (eng. *Honest*) Institute, institute for the culture of life (slo. *Zavod Iskreni, zavod za kulturo življenja*). It describes itself as an organisation with Christian and conservative values that grew out of the online portal Iskreni.net, which began its work in 2004. It advocates for a »culture of life« whose content relates to the rejection of abortion, contraception, vaccination, sexual and reproductive rights of LGBT persons. They actively opposed the adoption of the *Family Code*. During the right-wing government of Janez Janša (2020–2022), when Janez Cigler Kralj, one of the co-founders of this institution, was Minister of Labour, Family, Social Affairs and Equal Opportunities, the Iskreni insitute received significant funding (Kralj et al., 2021: p. 52).
- *Civil Initiative for the Family and the Rights of Children* (slo. *Civilna iniciativa za družino in pravice otrok*). It was founded in 2009 by Aleš Primc and was the central anti-gender actor during the first referendum campaign. During the second referendum campaign, the initiative was renamed *Children are at Stake*, which was composed of initiatives and groups opposed to the adoption of the amendment on equal rights for heterosexual and same-sex couples (Kralj et al., 2021: p. 52). In 2016, the *Children are at Stake* renamed to *Movement for Children and Families* (slo. *Gibanje za otroke in družine*) and transformed into a political party *Voice for Children and Families* (slo. *Glas za otroke in družine*). The party program advocates traditional Christian values; in the area of reproductive rights, the use of the »controversial term embryo« is rejected and replaced by the term »unborn child«; in »Slovenian families« the birth rate should increase from 1.5 to 3 children so that »the Slovenian nation, language and culture are preserved«. On sexual rights, the program espouses the familiar views that »gender theory« is dangerous because it threatens binary gender relations and traditional understandings of gender and parental roles. As they violated the rules on the composition of the electoral lists (they did not respect the gender quota rules), their electoral list was rejected and they did not stand in the elections. The party leader referred its potential voters to SDP or other conservative parties that had the possibility of entering the parliament (Kralj et al., 2021: p. 59).
- *The Voice of Grandparents* (slo. *Glas starih staršev*). This association was founded in 2014, and its president is the former teacher and educator Metka Zevnik, who describes her political involvement in the movement through her role as a grandmother of six children and mother of three. She became the focus of media attention during the second referendum campaign as co-leader of the *Children are at stake*. The association is closely related to the *Children are at stake* and claims that Slovenian legislation pushes grandparents out of families because it does not recognize their educational and caring role (Kuhar, 2017: p. 217).
- *Family initiative* (slo. *Družinska pobuda*). It was founded in 1998 as an association to promote traditional family values and rejects equal rights for LGBT people (Kralj et al., 2021: p. 52). Its president is Tomaž Merše, who presents himself as a father of five children (Kuhar & Pajnik, 2020: p. 174).

- *God's Children Institute* (slo. *Zavod božji otroci*). This is a Catholic »pro-life« initiative, supported by the Slovenian RCC, which defines itself as a protest movement against abortion. For several years in a row, they organized forty-day prayers against abortions in front of the gynecological clinic in Ljubljana and in front of the maternity ward (Kralj et al., 2021: p. 52).
- *I'm Alive* (slo. *Zavod Živ!m*). This initiative is a private »pro-life« institution established in 2011. As part of the »Week of the Child« in October 2016, it displayed a propaganda film on the façade of the Franciscan Church in the center of Ljubljana, depicting abortion as a crime. A public awareness campaign against reproductive rights with many »pro-life« messages was prepared by this initiative in 2019 and 2020 (Kralj et al., 2021: p. 52).
- *March for Life Organizing Committee* (slo. *Organizacijski odbor pohoda za življenje*). It was founded at the beginning of January 2020 by several »pro-life« initiatives. Its main purpose was to prepare the second »March for Life« in Slovenia, which took place in October 2020 in Ljubljana. The coordinator of the committee was Urša Cankar Soares, who describes herself as a mother, wife, devoted Catholic and former party girl who left everything and followed Jesus. Tadej Strehovec invited her to join the committee (Kralj et al., 2021: p. 63). Besides in 2020, March for life was also organized by this committee in 2021 and 2022.
- *Biser* (eng. *Pearl*) – *Institution for counseling, monitoring, education and assistance for people in need Maribor* (slo. *Biser – zavod za svetovanje, spremljanje, izobraževanje in pomoč osebam v stiski Maribor*). The institute was founded in 2017 by Tomaž and Andrejka Kričej. It operates the website *Woman's Decision*, which provides »a selection of information and experiences for pregnant women, women who have had an unplanned pregnancy, and women in doubt about having an abortion«. Under the guise of helping women in distress because of unplanned pregnancies, the portal propagates against abortion. The activities of the institute are supported by six Slovenian municipalities, the longest and largest of which is the municipality of Maribor.
- *Identitarian movement* (slo. *Generacija identitete*). This movement is the Slovenian branch of the *European Identitarian movement*, which actively opposes the rights of LGBT people. In the spring of 2021, this movement was banned in France, but in Slovenia it is associated with the youth of the party SDP (Kralj et al., 2021: p. 52).

As emphasized above, it is difficult to decide whether a particular actor is merely anti-feminist or anti-gender, since all of them have referred to gender theory in recent years, regardless of the activities in which they are involved. For example, Aleš Primc, the leading figure during the two referendum campaigns on same-sex partnerships, was actively involved in the referendum campaign against single women's right to medically assisted reproduction in 2001. In 2003, he also opposed against the decriminalization of prostitution in Slovenia, but he failed to collect enough signatures to call a public referendum (Kuhar, 2017: p. 217). In addition, he often says that his party *Voice for Children and Families* advocates for the right to life of every unborn child (Kralj et al., 2021: p. 164).

Nevertheless, it is true that Aleš Primc, Metka Zevnik, and Tomaž Merše were the leading anti-gender figures of the last decade in Slovenia, as they were the most prominent opponents of LGBT rights. We

can add to this trio also Vesna Vilčnik, a journalist who regularly laments that she grew up in a family with only one parent, and claims to know from her own experience that a child needs a mother and a father. She was president of Plum (Češplja – a derogatory term for a female sexual organ), which was active until 2018 and whose goal was to raise awareness of “sexual energy and healthy sexuality”. They all worked closely with the RCC, especially with Tadej Strehovec (Kuhar & Pajnik, 2020: p. 174), another leading anti-gender figure in Slovenia. Another important figure in the last decade, publicly known for her “pro-life” activities, is Urška Cankar Soares, the coordinator of the organizing committee of the March for Life.

4. Allies

In Slovenia, anti-feminist and anti-gender actors are supported by two types of allies who do not consider themselves part of the anti-feminist/anti-gender movement: The first ally is the RCC and the second is right-wing political parties and media. There are also some individuals who are part of academia – although scientific credentials of some of them may be questioned – who speak out in public in support of the anti-gender movement. During both referendums, some musicians and actors also came out in support of the movement. Similarly, the opposite side, which advocated marriage equality, was supported by a number of prominent public figures in Slovenia.

Slovenian RCC encourages the establishment of lay organizations to spread its own ecclesiastical messages. Indeed, the public in Slovenia pays particular attention to the separation of church and state, which is also enshrined in the Slovenian constitution. Therefore, the RCC strives to »secularize« its public image by establishing or supporting satellite organizations, movements, and initiatives that spread its messages, influence, and ideology, and through these organizations, the RCC carries out the »clericalization« of Slovenian society. Moreover, the Slovenian public's trust in the RCC is low, especially after the financial speculations in the Archdiocese of Maribor (Kralj et al., 2021: p. 51), which became known to the general public at the end of 2010 and had a negative impact on the public image of the RCC in Slovenia. The »moral« position of the Church has been weakened in the Slovenian public by the scandals (Smrke, 2016), and furthermore, the discourse based on the holy scriptures no longer has a mobilizing effect (Kuhar, 2015a; 2015b), which is why working in the background of the Primc's civic initiatives of the »concerned citizens« seemed to be an effective solution for the Church to spread its message (Kuhar, 2017: p. 219).

It is also worth noting that successful cooperation between anti-gender activists and the Slovenian RCC was envisioned long before the rise of anti-gender movements in Europe. In 2002, the Slovenian Catholic Church published a comprehensive action plan entitled *Choose Life*, the final document of the Church's Plenary Assembly in Slovenia. Among other things, the document envisaged the establishment of various organizations for lay people – such as the Primc Civic Initiative – to help spread the Church's message (Kuhar, 2017: p. 220).

The anti-feminist and anti-gender organizations and civic initiatives discussed in the previous section present themselves as non-confessional organizations, as a mass movement of »concerned citizens«, but are in fact satellite organizations of the RCC (Kralj et al., 2021: p. 52; Kuhar & Pajnik, 2020: p. 173). Through the satellite organizations and initiatives, the RCC aims to establish itself as a moral authority on sexual and reproductive rights, with the goal of incorporating its doctrine on gender and sexuality into the state's legal norms (Kuhar, 2017: p. 219).

However, the Slovenian RCC wants to hide in public its satellite role in the case of anti-feminist and anti-gender organizations. For example, Tadej Strehovec, one of the central anti-gender actors who comes from the ranks of the RCC and collaborates with all prominent Slovenian anti-feminist and anti-gender activists (e.g. Primc, Zevnik, Merše, Viličnik, Cankar Soares), claims that the *Institute for Family and the Culture of Living* is his private initiative and is not affiliated with the RCC. However, the fact is that it is located at the same address as one of the parishes in Ljubljana and its website was originally hosted on the official server of the Slovenian RCC (Kuhar, 2017: pp. 219–220). The fact that Strehovec spread a professional, secularized image rather than visually connecting with the church can also be seen in the fact that he rarely appeared in public in priestly attire. This corresponded to his mostly seemingly secularized discourse in the media and parliamentary debates (Kuhar & Pajnik, 2020: pp. 173–174), although he did speak publicly on behalf of the RCC on the *Family Code* and participated as its representative in the second reading of the Code in the parliamentary Commission on Labor, Family, Social Policy and People with Disabilities (Kralj et al., 2021: p. 57).

As indicated earlier in this report, right-wing political parties are another important ally for anti-feminist and anti-gender organizations and actors in Slovenia. Let us summarize the examples highlighted earlier in this report that show the close connection and sympathy between anti-feminist and anti-gender activists and right-wing political parties. First, when Strehovec's trial began in October 2018 for a controversial article posted on his institute's website 24kul.si, his supporters organized protests in Ljubljana's Prešeren Square and outside the courthouse every time he was summoned to court. Among the demonstrators were also prominent politicians, members of right-wing conservative parties. Second, several prominent representatives of the political right in Slovenia (i.e., Alenka Jeraj, a member of the party SDP, and Tadeja Šuštar, a member of NSi, as well as Aleš Primc, who was already known as the leader of the *Voice for Children and Families party at that time*) also participated in the March for Life rally that took place in Ljubljana in October 2020. Third, since Primc's *Voice for Children and Families party* was unsuccessful in the state elections, he referred their potential voters to SDP or other conservative parties that had the possibility of entering parliament (Kralj et al., 2021: p. 59). Last but not least, the Identitarian movement, which actively campaigns against the rights of LGBT people, is associated in Slovenia with the youth of the party SDP.

5. Themes and Agendas

Our research project focuses on five thematic policy areas: (1) labor market, (2) health & reproductive rights, (3) migration, (4) LGBT rights and (5) gender-based violence. The second area (health & reproductive rights) was the trigger for the establishment of the anti-feminist movements in Slovenia in the last decade, especially in the case of the right to abortion. On the other hand, the fourth area (LGBT rights) was the main reason for the emergence of the anti-gender movement in Slovenia in 2009.

According to our literature review, there is no evidence that other three thematic policy areas triggered any anti-feminist and/or anti-gender activities in Slovenia. The only exception is the area of migration which some of the studies analyzed touch upon in the context of the Primc's *Voice for Children and Families party*. Although the party has not been very successful in elections, it is still formally active and occasionally participates in conservative, politically right-wing initiatives, such as the political campaign against the adoption of the Marrakesh Declaration, which, in their opinion, threatens the European Union and the European way of life by admitting non-Christian immigrants (Kralj et al., 2021: p. 59). Another example related to migration is provided by Sobočan & Pollak (2016: p. 177), who show that

the political struggle for marriage equality is also perceived as linked to migration politics, as both are constituted as a radical left political agenda: by allowing one, we open the doors for the other. Thus, the nation is threatened not only by LGBT activists as such, but also by the leftist political agenda at the intersection of pro-LGBT and pro-migrant politics.

6. Repertoires of Action (Strategies)

The main strategy used by anti-feminist actors in Slovenia to spread their agenda is the personification of the foetus. Photos of smiling foetuses, of foetuses sucking their thumbs, and photos of bloody, dismembered foetuses, stories told by an »unborn daughter« or »unborn son« to her mother just before being aborted, and stories of abortion survivors published on 24kul.si are among the most effective and persuasive strategies for personifying the foetus. This approach has paved the way for political propaganda without words – it can influence voters from all parts of the political spectrum. Not only because the use of images creates the impression that photos »speak for themselves«, that they tell the real truth, but especially because one can identify with a foetus (Mencin Čeplak, 2016: p. 1380).

Three examples can be identified in the collected literature in which the strategy of personifying the fetus was used. First, when the *God's Children Institute* organized the »March for Life« in 2014 as a sign of protest against the conference of the *International Federation of Professional Abortion and Contraception Associates* in Ljubljana, the participants carried large placards with photos of aborted fetuses, which were supposed to represent »the real truth about abortion« (Kralj et al., 2021: p. 165). Second, when Aleš Primc was a guest on the Slovenian television show *Studio City* on May 30, 2016, he showed the audience a photo of a 12-week-old fetus and expressed his wish that Slovenia recognize it as a child (Mencin Čeplak, 2016: p. 1380). The third example is the public display of the film depicting abortion as a crime on the facade of the Franciscan Church in Ljubljana. The film, which was played continuously for several hours each day, depicts the fetus as a child in a psychological sense, as it shows the child's reflexes as its emotional reactions, although the child learns these reactions only through socialization. The film also emphasizes the uniqueness of DNA, as if all the important characteristics of a human being are fixed at birth. It ends with the slogan »choose life«, accompanied by a photograph of a heavily pregnant woman, implying that abortions are performed on heavily pregnant women at their request. . The campaign described was also supported by the Slovenian Bishops' Conference, which emphasized in a press release, among other things, that by supporting this project it was following the »principle of zero tolerance towards violence against unborn children«, while Primc's political party responded to protests against the public displaying of the film by demanding that the unborn child's right to life be included in the constitution (Kralj et al., 2021: p. 165).

A very notable strategy used by anti-feminist actors in Slovenia to spread their agenda is also the organization of public events, such as the *40 Days for Life* project or the March for Life. In addition, appeals to the political elite are also a common strategy, such as the (failed) attempt to persuade the Slovenian government not to ratify the Istanbul Convention because it allegedly requires the incorporation of »extreme ideas of gender theory« into national legislation and school programs (Antić Gaber & Kuhar, 2019: p. 118).

On the other hand, the existing literature discusses the strategies of the anti-gender movement in more detail, as anti-gender actors were very active during both referendum campaigns and developed many strategies to achieve their goals. What strategies did they employ? First, the anti-gender movement in

Slovenia employs various communication strategies and uses different channels to spread their populist messages, including online petitions, chain emails, round tables, public meetings and *Family Day* (as a counter to the *Pride Parade*), active participation in parliamentary hearings on draft legislation, and social media and the Internet. These communication channels were also used to raise funds, sell merchandise, and publish scandalous »life stories« (most often originating from dubious US online media) about the terrible effects of »gender theory«. They also collected signatures from their supporters on their website, 24kul.si. Although they had no formal legal effect, hundreds of signature pages were showed every time the leader of the campaign had the opportunity to speak publicly (Kuhar & Pajnik, 2020: p. 179).

In terms of online message dissemination, the website 24kul.si, which served as the official website of Primc initiatives and proved to be a powerful tool for promoting anti-genderism and mobilizing support, played a central role in referenua's campaigns. The website illustrates how the Internet in general, and social media in particular (see Gorajnc & Fišer (2018) for Twitter analysis), are becoming an important platform for populist efforts aimed at turning ordinary people against the liberal establishment (Kuhar & Pajnik, 2020: p. 174). In terms of Internet use, it is also worth noting the strategy used by anti-gender actors during the referendum campaigns, which followed the example of some other anti-gender initiatives around the world: they used the tactic of chain emails to target as many citizens as possible, sending e-mails to politicians, researchers, academics, and other public figures who support LGBT rights. Every hour, individuals received hundreds of identical messages, frequently resulting in complete blockage of their electronic mailboxes. (Kuhar, 2017: p. 218).

Close cooperation with the Slovenian RCC is also one the main strategies of anti-gender actors. For example, the anti-gender movement's messages were read during Sunday Masses or were available on local parish websites. While the movement was collecting the required 40,000 signatures for the initiative calling for a public referendum on marriage equality, Strehovec sent a letter to all priests in Slovenia asking them to invite parishioners to sign the referendum initiative during Sunday Mass and directing them to the institution's website 24kul.si for more information. Priests were also instructed to arrange transportation for their congregation to the municipality offices where signatures were officially collected (e.g., private cars or busses) (Kuhar, 2017: p. 220). In addition, Aleš Primc gave lectures and delivered public speeches in churches and parishes, urging the faithful to vote against the adoption of the proposed law (Kralj et al., 2021: 57). In addition, Primc also gave a speech at the annual Catholic pilgrimage to Brezje in 2011 (Kuhar & Pajnik, 2020: p. 180).

Another important tactic used by anti-gender activists is networking and lobbying with key government institutions or government-related entities. They try to nominate their own people to expert committees and other government bodies, so they become part of advisory or decision-making committees. For instance, some members of the movement became members of government expert councils, such as the Expert Council for the Family at the Ministry of Labour, Family, Social Affairs and Equal Opportunities and the Expert Council for AIDS at the Ministry of Health. The movement has also become a recognised stakeholder on sexual citizenship issues: Its representatives are invited to parliamentary readings of proposals for new laws in the field of family policy, reproductive health, the fight against discrimination, and gender equality (Kuhar, 2017: p. 228).

Initiating public controversies over certain content in public schools that anti-gender actors claim represents »gender theory« is also an important strategy. The moral panic that arose in some schools

and among some parents led to self-censorship by teachers, who increasingly avoided topics that were constructed as problematic by such discussions, e.g., different family forms, gender equality, homosexuality, etc. (Antić Gaber & Kuhar, 2019: p. 118). In Slovenia, the brochure *Love is Love* (slo. Ljubezen je ljubezen), which Amnesty International used in its extracurricular workshops in schools on human rights based on »gender identity« and sexual orientation, was discussed in parliament as evidence that »gender theory« is spread among »our children in schools« without parental consent and even without informing parents. Pressure was brought to bear on the Minister of Education to prevent the use of the brochure, which, according to the anti-gender movement, served to re-educate children in the spirit of »gender theory« which does not recognize the existence of natural female and male sex (Kuhar & Zobec, 2017).

An important activity strategy of anti-gender actors is also the collection of financial reports of those LGBT and feminist non-governmental organizations in Slovenia that have received funding from the state budget. Public ministries and other government agencies are required to provide such information, which is considered to be information of a »public nature«. The result was the publication of tendentious articles on the website 24kul.si with exaggerated information about the enormous sums of money that these organizations allocate for the promotion of »gender theory«, the promotion of Christianophobia and practices of social engineering among Slovenian citizens. Such initiatives also put pressure on public institutions, which began to censor themselves and became less and less willing to financially support projects on gender and sexuality (Kuhar & Pajnik, 2020: pp. 180–181).

An important part of the strategy to spread the anti-gender agenda is also the choice of appropriate visual material and discourse (see next section for the detailed summary of the main anti-gender frames of arguments and discourses). For example, during the first referendum campaign, the Primc initiative had the silhouette of a »normal family« in the movement's logo, which was replaced during the second referendum campaign by the image of a boy and a girl hiding behind a hand, which will stop the destructive »gender theory«. The change from the nuclear family to the boy and girl hiding behind each other's arm may be related to the movement's increased focus on grandparents and extended families, although protecting the nuclear family and especially children remains its main goal (Kuhar, 2017: p. 217). In both cases, there is the image of a child or children in a logo, who were the main ideological signifier of the movement.

In the context of the strategic choice of discourse to appeal to the public, anti-gender activists used outdated, traditionalist, homophobic, and sexist claims with which they mainly addressed »defeated groups« who felt that they had lost their positions of power due to enforced tolerance, political correctness, and the alleged exaggeration of equality policies. They were told that they had lost their voice and the right to free expression, which they would regain when the corrupt elites were defeated and the natural order was re-established (Kuhar & Pajnik, 2020: p. 181).

Since the main target audience was also »defeated groups« of people, overtly stereotypical vocabulary and images were also part of the strategy for communicating with the public. For example, flyers were distributed with semi-pornographic photographs of gay iconography of clothed people with the caption, »Do you wish people like these would become parents?«. Another approach in the campaign against the LGBT rights was to appeal to other »disadvantaged« populations or movements, such as the anti-vaccination movement. In this case, opponents of the LGBT rights established and abused a discourse

of victimization: because you do not want your children vaccinated, the state may take them away from you and give them up for adoption to homosexuals who will abuse them (Kralj et al., 2021: p. 57).

7. Frames of Arguments and Discourses

Discursive frames that anti-feminist and anti-gender actors in Slovenia use in their rhetoric are well documented in the existing literature. The following section presents the main frames of arguments and discourses that appear in connection with the main topics that preoccupies anti-feminist and anti-gender movement in Slovenia: 1) the right to abortion, 2) single women's right to medically assisted reproduction, and 3) marriage equality. According to Šabec et al. (2021), all counter-discourses established by anti-feminist and anti-gender actors on these three issues are determined by heteronormativity and the tendency to biologically reproduce the »nation« that is allegedly threatened if these rights are legalized.

Regarding the arguments and discourses related to single women's right to medically assisted reproduction, we first present the study by Furlan et al. (2020), which summarizes the main arguments against single women's right to medically assisted reproduction:

- single women as users of medically assisted reproduction create new family forms that do not conform to heteronormative ideals;
- the single woman assumes the role of fatal destroyer of happy families as she destroys the established structure of the nuclear family ideal;
- single women are assumed to be secretly homosexual, which is a pathologization based on the belief that homosexual sexual practices are morally reprehensible and that gays and lesbians are therefore likely to be less suitable for child rearing than heterosexual (or single) parents;
- when a woman uses medically assisted reproduction, reproduction is separated from sexuality and the man is excluded from the reproductive process, which is not in accordance with patriarchy.

Moreover, Cukut Krilić (2013) analyzed the content of the press in Slovenia on the topic of medically assisted reproduction in the period 1983–2011. An analysis of print media reporting of the referendum on the right of single women to access medically assisted reproduction in 2001 revealed that opponents of the proposal, including anti-feminist actors, referred in particular to the naturalistic assumption that the so-called natural family consists of mother, father, and children. Opponents of the proposal emphasized the child's right to know both parents. Less present, but still noticeable, was the opinion that the possibility of medically assisted reproduction for single women would increase the number of same-sex couples with children.

With respect to the arguments and discourses related to the right to abortion, it should first be emphasised that common to all anti-abortion discourses is the assumption that the foetus is a person and therefore a bearer of human rights, and therefore that any abortion is murder. All abortion is directed against the »unborn child«, as they consistently refer to the »embryo«; for some, it is also an evil against the nation and even against a woman who chooses to have an abortion (Kralj et al., 2021: p. 166). From here on, anti-abortion discourses can be divided into two groups, depending on who they are directed at. The first group openly and aggressively defends the thesis that abortion is murder, a

crime against the unborn child, against nature, against the nation, against women (since it is directed against her essence, i.e. motherhood), and even more aggressively against the supposed culprits, i.e. liberal legislators and abortion rights advocates, who are seen as part of a communist conspiracy (Mencin Čeplak, 2016: p. 1382). As a rule, these discourses do not condemn women who choose to have an abortion, but rather women who advocate for accessible, safe abortion. These women are labelled as murderers, such as in the text in 24kul.si that was the subject of a criminal prosecution (Kralj et al., 2021: p. 166).

The strategy of the second group appears to be less aggressive at first glance, as it employs a passive-aggressive discourse. It addresses the moral majority, especially women: the anti-feminist activists who stand in front of the maternity hospital and try to prevent women from having an abortion; articles and images that tell the truth about the »baby killing propaganda«; counsellors who know the true nature of women and therefore know that every woman feels guilt about abortion, even if she is not aware of it herself (Mencin Čeplak, 2016: p. 1982). It is important to emphasise that this turning to women, addressing women's suffering, and addressing women who in their hearts (supposedly) want to become mothers but are prevented from doing so by cruel circumstances, is the new feature of current anti-abortion discourses that deserve special analysis, mainly because they are both true and manipulative. True because many women actually suffer, because the female body is often abused, and because in unequal power relations we often have no choice but to trust those on whom we depend. They are manipulative because many women do not suffer, and they are also manipulative, and especially so, because this same »empathic comfort« constantly promotes and perpetuates women's guilt by labelling abortion »murder« (Mencin Čeplak, 2016: p. 1381).

The second group, at first glance empathic, has another peculiarity. It is also characteristic of it that it pronounces condemnations of abortion in a condescending manner and tries, more or less politely, to lower the moral and professional credibility of the defenders of the availability of safe abortion. Supporters of the right to abortion are accused of insufficient knowledge of the history of feminism, since the first feminists allegedly opposed the legalization of abortion; of being unaware of Article 55 of the *Slovenian Constitution*, which in their opinion should not refer to access to a safe abortion procedure, but to the decision to have or not to have a child; of having little idea of scientific research proving how psychologically and physically traumatic and life-threatening an abortion is. They say that they are merely proclaiming the silenced truth about the suffering of »unborn children«, their mothers and fathers. There is a personification of the fetus referred to as the »unborn child« or simply »child« as well as emotionally charged stories of women who allegedly suffer from what is called as »post-abortion syndrome« (Kralj et al., 2021: pp. 166–167).

Since the anti-gender movement is examined to a greater extent than the anti-feminist movement in Slovenia, frames of arguments and discourses are comprehensively addressed in the present studies. However, over the period of the two referenda campaigns, anti-gender actors developed a set of argumentation techniques, rhetorical strategies, and discourses on the basis of which they successfully mobilized large masses of citizens to vote against equal rights for heterosexual and same-sex couples in both referenda. What patterns of argumentation did they use?

As the broadest framework that anti-gender actors used in the public sphere, we can determine what Kuhar (2017) calls the essentialist discourse that emerged in response to the government intervention in the culturally hegemonic notion of family and marriage as »natural« institutions. The logic of the

essentialist discourse can be defined as follows: Marriage equality is a threat to the (traditional) family, fatherhood and motherhood, and above all to innocent children and – as a consequence – to the future of the Slovenian nation. By appropriating the nationalist sobbing about a »small Slovenian nation« facing a »demographic winter« they succeeded in constructing same-sex couples and families (and, more recently, transgender persons and abortion advocates) not only as Others within the nation, but also as someone who is against the nation (Kuhar, 2017: p. 225).

Another important discursive framework of the anti-gender movement is based on the belief that political demands for equality between heterosexual and same-sex couples are incompatible with »nature« and »normality«. The focus is on »real« gender roles, which are largely perceived as biological givens that are ahistorical and crucial to the reproduction and continuation of the nation. Male and female identities are biologically determined. Because the two genders are biologically distinct, they also play distinct social roles, and any intervention in such a binary system is understood as an (undesirable) social experiment. According to the opponents of LGBT rights, the special role of women is mainly due to the fact that they bear and raise children, whereas men have the role of breadwinners. Moreover, opponents of the LGBT right do not oppose the legal rights of same-sex couples as long as this institution or their relationship is not called »marriage« and their relationship with their children is not called »family« (Pajnik et al., 2016).

The next important discursive element is the construction of fear against the LGBT community because children adopted by same-sex couples are seen to be at risk (Kuhar, 2017). Precisely because of the successful construction of fear that same-sex couples will adopt »innocent« children, »children« have become the most important mobilizing signifier of the anti-gender movement (Smrdelj, 2020; Smrdelj et al., 2021). However, protagonists of the anti-gender movement claim that »our children« and consequently »we« as a nation (in-group) are threatened by homosexuals (out-group) who will adopt »our children« and take over »our« institutions (Kuhar & Pajnik, 2020: p. 176). Although leaders of the anti-gender movement never explicitly claimed that homosexuals sexually abused (their) children, they implied it. Because it was unspoken, it became all the more effective: implicit insinuations of (physical/verbal/symbolic) sexual abuse of children's innocence evoked images of unnatural and deviant homosexuals (Kuhar, 2017: p. 225). In addition to those »we« have to fear (i.e. homosexuals), the »enemies« of the child's welfare are also the problem, namely LGBT activists who try to impose the »gender theory« (Kuhar & Pajnik, 2020: p. 176). However, children are not only at risk from homosexuals and their advocates, but also from homosexual content in public schools that endangers their education (Kuhar, 2017: p. 222).

Another important discursive technique is the appropriation of the concept of human rights (anti-gender actors claim that they advocate for the rights of children and families, the right to free speech and the right to religion, for human life), as well as the appropriation of a broader liberal discourse (e.g., solidarity, democracy, freedom, active citizenship) (Kuhar, 2010; Smrdelj et al., 2021). On this basis, they establish homophobic and discriminatory attitudes disguised with seemingly rational, supposedly scientific arguments strategically developed to arouse emotions and power derived from existing prejudices (Kuhar & Pajnik, 2020: p. 178). A similar discourse is also used by the RCC, which has replaced the largely ineffective and outdated »biblical discourse« (which failed to mobilize large crowds for their political cause) with the »rational discourse« of science, which has been shaped into appealing and populist common sense statements. In this way, they no longer attempt to explicitly show that homosexuality is an abomination. They prefer to base their counter-arguments on concern for the

welfare of children and the preservation of the »natural« union between a man and a woman. The goal is the same (exclusion of gays and lesbians), but the approach is different (protection of family and marriage). In this way, the Church secularizes its discourse in order to »clericalize« society (Kuhar, 2015a; 2015b).

An important technique is also the use of »pseudoscientific« discourse (Vezjak, 2018), which can come from suspicious, unsubstantiated, and falsifying scientific sources or from discredit or manipulate existing scientific knowledge. As anti-gender actors fight against »academic elites« who want to impose »gender theory« on »ordinary« citizens, they try to establish a »scientific« discourse by mainly referring to (American) scholars (such as Mark Regnerus or Judith Reisman) who are academically discredited in the local environment but effectively spread their ideas outside their country of origin (Kuhar, 2017: p. 226).

In the last part of this section, we will discuss the role of the term »gender theory« in the rhetoric of anti-gender actors in Slovenia. As already outlined in this report, during the first referendum, opponents of marriage equality had not yet formulated their arguments with reference to »gender theory«, but had already created a discursive substance that then developed into »gender theory« as an empty signifier during the second referendum (Kuhar, 2017: p. 224).

The main anti-gender actors who discussed the term »gender theory« came from the ranks of the RCC. It is therefore not surprising that the term »gender theory« at first did not appear in »centrist« and »progressive« media and is predominantly present in (pro)catholic conservative media (Sobočan & Pollak, 2016). In general, however, the term »gender theory« – sometimes referred to as »gender ideology«, less often as »genderization« – refers not only to marriage equality, but means much more. It is said to be the hidden agenda of radical feminists and homosexual activists who want to prepare a cultural revolution: the promotion of gender fluidity and the denial of the biological (i.e., natural) facts of sexual complementarity. »Gender theory« is thus constructed as a social engineering project in which men are no longer male and women are no longer female, and we are free to choose our gender and sexual orientation, even »several times a day« (Kuhar, 2017: p. 222).

Tadej Strehovec referred to »gender theory« as »Marxism 2.0«. He argues that »Marxism 2.0« redirects the class struggle into a struggle between the genders: the struggle is no longer in the relationship between the bourgeoisie and capital against the working class, but in the relationship between men and women. Likewise, the goal of the revolution is no longer socialism, but the so-called gender society. On the other hand, Branko Cestnik explains that »gender theory« emerged from the insights of socialists who realized that socialism can be achieved not only through a social revolution, but also through a cultural revolution. Gender theory is therefore a project of the cultural revolution that aims to change minds and thinking (Kuhar, 2017: p. 221). The Slovenian specificity of the use of »gender theory« by anti-gender actors is that it is not primarily conceived as an ideology imposed by the West and international institutions such as the EU and UN, but rather as a new kind of Marxism that resonates and mobilizes much more effectively than any attempt to present it as a modern form of Western colonization (Kuhar, 2017: pp. 222–223).

For the RCC, »gender theory« also embodies a new scapegoat and a new tool for self-victimisation. After the fall of its main oppressor, the communist regime, the RCC uses a »gender theory« as a substitute, allegedly produced and promoted by the same »forces of continuity« (former communists), which leads

the RCC to compare the »gender theory« to a totalitarian ideology (Kuhar, 2017: p. 221). On the website 24kul.si, under the tab »Gender Theory«, articles are published that define »gender theory« as a cunning and hidden plan that was elaborated in secret by the (leftist) elites and is now carefully implemented in school curricula and (supra)national policy documents (Kuhar, 2017: p. 223).

To sum up, »gender theory« in Slovenia is defined mainly by representatives of the RCC, but it also represents a »symbolic glue« (Kováts & Põim, 2015), a common framework of different groups (anti-gender actors and organizations, RCC, right-wing political parties, etc.) that condenses the different discourses of these groups into one big threat, which they understand as either an attack on nature, the nation, or normality (Kuhar, 2017: p. 229).

8. Transnational Connections

Anti-feminist and anti-gender actors/organizations in Slovenia are connected with the EU and transnational anti-feminist and anti-gender actors/organizations. This connection can be seen in the fact that local actors and organizations adopt the actions, strategies and discourses of transnational actors. The yellow trademark colour, used in the Primc Initiative logo, for example, was also used in the California campaign against Proposition 8. It is likely that the Slovenian movement did not use the colours pink and blue because the La Manif pour Tous – which's trademark colours were copied by many national movements in Europe – did not exist at the time the Primc initiative was founded. California could therefore be an alternative source of inspiration for Slovenian activists (Kuhar, 2017: p. 229). Moreover, the technique of sending chain messages during the second referendum campaign was adopted by two transgender anti-gender online platforms and / or organizations CitizensGO and European Dignity Watch (Kuhar & Pajnik, 2020: 180).

In addition, they are involved in international anti-feminist and anti-gender projects and initiatives. For instance, the *God's Children Institute* is part of the international *40 Days for Life* project. In 2015, Robert Colquhoun, head of the international campaigns of this organization, visited the *God's Children Institute* in Ljubljana and its campaign leader Matjaž Venta, who was preparing the second year of the forty-day prayers in front of the Clinic of Gynecology and Obstetrics in Ljubljana (Kralj et al., 2021: p. 53). In addition, most anti-feminist actors in Slovenia participated in the *Mum, Dad and Kids« European Citizens Initiative*, which collected signatures to »support the identity of the family and marriage«, but they were not very successful, as among the 14 countries where signatures were collected, Slovenia ended up at the bottom (Kralj et al., 2021: p. 53). Moreover, none of the anti-gender actors whose activities were primarily directed against LGBT rights were among the initiators of the above-mentioned European initiative. All this indicates that Slovenian anti-feminist and anti-gender movement does not play an important role at the European level (Kuhar, 2017: p. 228), but they adopt the actions, strategies and discourses from other national and transnational actors.

Moreover, the international coalition of opponents of sexual and reproductive rights is an important source of financial and organisational support for local actors. In June 2021, a report by the European Parliamentary Forum on Sexual and Reproductive Rights entitled *Tip of the Iceberg. Religious Extremist Funders against Human Rights for Sexuality and Reproductive Health in Europe 2009–2018* pinpoints the funding sources of sexual and reproductive health opponents in Europe. On page 92 of this report, *Iskreni Institute* is named as a recipient of 130,000 euros in 2020 from European funds transferred to it by the Ministry of Labour, Family, Social Affairs and Equal Opportunities during the period when the

ministry was headed by Janez Cigler Kralj, one of Zavod Iskreni's founders. The report also shows that the main funders in Europe are closely connected to the RCC (Kralj, et al., 2021: p. 53)

To summarize, all of the above-mentioned international connections and collaborations are rarely highlighted in public because anti-feminist and anti-gender actors understand that raising concern and sparking episodes of moral panic is a far more effective element of strategy for gaining public attention than exposing international collaborations with other related actors in organizations abroad. (Kralj et al., 2021: p. 52).

9. Explanations of the Anti-Gender/Anti-Feminist Backlash

In the collected literature there are no explicit explanations and interpretations for the emergence and success of the anti-feminist movement in Slovenia. The anti-feminist movement did not have an opportunity to establish itself as an important political actor, as there were no visible legislative changes in the field of reproductive rights on the political agenda in Slovenia in the last decade. On the other hand, the recent success of the anti-gender movement in Slovenia is well explained in the existing literature, but more structural interpretations of the emergence of the anti-gender movement in Slovenia are missing. In the following, I summarize Kuhar's (2017) interpretation of its successes.

According to Kuhar (2017: pp. 223–224), the anti-gender backlash and the introduction of the concept of »gender theory« were politically effective for several reasons, the three most important of which are: 1) the timing of the debate, 2) the resonance of the naturalistic discourse of common sense, and 3) the creation of a politics of fear based on self-victimisation.

Regarding the timing of the debate, it is important to note that Primc's initiative arose shortly after the Slovenian government announced the reform of the *Family Code* in 2009. From that point until the 2012 referendum, Primc and his supporters built a strong network throughout Slovenia, drawing heavily on the already established networks by RCC and right-wing political parties. The same networks were activated during the second referendum, and grandparents were part of the new target group, not only because they are older people with typically more conservative views and represent a large social group in the aging Slovenian society, but also because the emotional references to the »innocent child« – which is the entry point into the anti-gender movement discourse and can be found in the logo Primc's initiative – mean a convenient identification of grandparents with the experiences they have with their grandchildren. At a time when anti-gender movements were becoming recognizable political actors in Europe, the Slovenian movement had already won a referendum, became politically relevant and self-confident, and defined the issues of »gender theory« as an important point of political struggle that could mobilize thousands of people. During the first referendum, opponents of marriage equality had not yet formulated their arguments with reference to »gender theory«, but had already created a discursive substance that then developed into »gender theory« during the second referendum (Kuhar, 2017: p. 224).

With respect to the resonance of the naturalistic discourse of common sense it should be considered that the government proposal on marriage equality interfered with culturally hegemonic ideas about family and marriage as »natural institutions«. Therefore, anti-gender actors skillfully based their counter-discourse on strengthening essentialist and naturalistic frameworks as common sense, while at the same time they interfered with strongly emotionally colored heteronormative beliefs and values

about the family, children or the nation. This allowed their arguments to resonate widely and mobilize large crowds against the two referendums on same-sex partnerships (Kuhar, 2017: pp. 225–226).

The third reason explaining the success of the anti-gender movement in Slovenia is self-victimization, which refers to the image of the oppressed majority vis-à-vis the corrupt elites. However, the term »elites« has been used as a rather fluid term: Depending on the context, elites can stand for many groups of people – from politicians and academics (who develop ideas on »gender theory« in the ivory towers of universities) to non-governmental activists and journalists. On the other hand, the self-victimizing discourse was directed specifically at Catholics. The movement coined the term »Christianophobia« as an antipode to homophobia to show that the real victims of the marriage equality debate are Catholics who are labeled homophobic simply because they oppose same-sex marriage. They would be denied the right to free speech, stigmatized as backward, and as such increasingly marginalized in our society. To sum up, the reason that the discourse of self-victimisation was so successful was that anti-gender activists primarily targeted »defeated groups« who are socially impoverished, addressing them as victims of the social system run by the elites who are the source of threat to »us« and »our« nation. Therefore, the referendum must be voted against LGBT rights to resist these elites and ensure a better future (Kuhar, 2017: pp. 226–228).

10. Counter-movements

As for the counter-movement that might have emerged in response to activities related to the anti-feminist movement in Slovenia, no such cases are examined in the existing literature. In fact, no such counter-movement existed, since the anti-feminist movement was not perceived as an important political figure thus far, in contrast to the anti-gender movement, which was able to celebrate itself by winning two referendums. The only response to the activities of anti-feminist actors documented in the existing literature is a February 2016 open letter addressed to Slovenia's highest political representatives, sent by some individuals and non-governmental organizations in response to the anti-abortion rallies outside the Ljubljana gynecological clinic in 2015. As already mentioned in the report, the letter urged the addressees to take action and protect women and health care workers from pressure from opponents of reproductive rights (Kralj et al., 2021: pp. 59–60).

On the other hand, the activities of the anti-gender movement in connection with the two referenda triggered LGBT activists, feminists, and some politicians, who formed a coalition and joined forces to oppose the increasingly successful and influential anti-gender movement in Slovenia. While they have been successful in discrediting some of the claims of anti-gender activists, they have generally failed to effectively counter their populist rhetoric. While the LGBT community »defended« itself with rational language during the first referendum, offering rational, often scientific language based primarily on sociological and psychological research (Vezovnik, 2015), it changed its discursive tactics during the second referendum, following examples from abroad, particularly the American and Irish debates. Thus, more emotionally charged rhetoric emerged, referring to love being the same regardless of the gender of the partners. Neither the first nor the second strategy was successful, not least because the LGBT community lacked political background and clear political support in the pre-referendum period, when the broadest segments of the population needed to be addressed by them. However, this was not the case for the anti-gender activists who were supported by the RCC and right-wing political parties (Antić Gaber & Kuhar, 2019: p. 111). The coalition that opposed the anti-gender movement dissolved immediately after the referendum as members returned to their specific areas of interest and work. In

many ways, the opposition to the anti-gender movement was far from what anti-gender activists portrayed about LGBT activists: a strong and united front fighting together for gender equality and LGBT rights (Kuhar & Pajnik, 2020: pp. 178–179).

In addition to the above interpretation of why the LGBT movement was unsuccessful in addressing its own agenda in comparison to the anti-gender movement, it is also important to note that the populist strategies and rhetoric used by anti-gender activists in both referendum campaigns worked in part because the counter-movement did not insist on counter-initiatives enough and underestimated the actions of anti-gender actors. It was believed that such outdated, traditionalist, homophobic, and sexist claims would not resonate in the supposedly tolerant and progressive Slovenian society. As already mentioned in the previous section, anti-gender activists primarily targeted »defeated groups« who felt that their position of power had been compromised due to enforced tolerance, political correctness and alleged exaggeration of gender equality policies. They were told by anti-gender movement that they had lost their voice and the right to free expression, which they would regain once the corrupt elites were defeated and the natural order was restored (Kuhar & Pajnik, 2020: p. 181).

11. Other Important Issues

With respect to other important issues, we should highlight the experience of conducting interviews with anti-gender actors from Primc's initiative by Pajnik et al. (2016). Most of the actors refused to participate in the interviews, probably because the study was conducted by the Peace Institute, which actively supported the Family Code and was critical of the populist rhetoric and actions of the Primc's initiative. The fieldwork experience indicates that some actors no longer wanted to comment on the »old story« or be connected with it. It is also likely that their refusal to cooperate was jointly orchestrated. Finally, Pajnik et al. (2016) conducted interviews with few opponents of the Family Law, who often made the same arguments as actors from Primc's initiative. Based on the experiences of Pajnik and co-workers, further research needs to consider how to approach anti-gender actors so that they do not refuse to participate.

12. Conclusion

In this report, we examine the existing literature on feminist and anti-gender movement in Slovenia. In the period 2010–2021, five studies were published dealing with the anti-feminist movement in Slovenia. The right to abortion is the main issue that triggers the organized activity of the anti-feminist movement in Slovenia. Although the single women's right to medically assisted reproduction is the notable subject of the above-mentioned studies, this issue has not been the main topic of the anti-feminist actors in the last decade. On the other hand, we can find fourteen studies on the anti-gender movement in Slovenia for the same period. Almost all studies on the anti-gender movement in Slovenia focus on the legislative attempts to introduce marriage equality in Slovenia in 2009 and/or 2015.

The anti-feminist movement became publicly visible in Slovenia in the last decade through two »pro-life« events, namely a rally of anti-abortion activists in front of the Gynecological Clinic in Ljubljana, which began in 2015, and an event called the March for Life, which has been held four times so far, first in 2014 and then again in 2020, 2021, and 2022. The main trigger for the rise of the anti-gender movement in Slovenia represents two attempts at marriage equality that resulted in the referendum on the *Family Code* (2012) and the referendum on same-sex partnerships (2015).

In relation to actors, the anti-feminist and anti-gender movement in Slovenia consists of various pro-Catholic groups, organizations, »institutes«, pro-Catholic conservative media, etc., known to the Slovenian public as part of a network that increased its political power and public visibility in the 2012 and 2015 referendum campaigns. In Slovenia, anti-feminist and anti-gender actors are supported by three types of allies who do not consider themselves part of the anti-feminist/anti-gender movement: Roman Catholic Church, right-wing political parties and some individuals from academia and public life.

The main strategy used by anti-feminist actors in Slovenia to spread their agenda in case of opposition to the right to abortion is the personification of the foetus. Anti-gender actors, on the other hand, develop much more diverse and nuanced techniques to oppose LGBT rights. For example, they use different communication strategies and different channels to spread their populist messages. In addition, they lobby important government institutions; they collaborate with the Slovenian RCC; they initiate public controversies about specific content in public schools that allegedly promotes »gender theory«; they collect financial reports of those LGBT and feminist non-governmental organisations in Slovenia that have received funding from the state budget; and they use persuasive visuals and populist discourse targeting different social groups, from grandparents to those identified as »defeated« or »left behind« due to leftist (and former communist) political elites in Slovenia.

All counter-discourses used by anti-feminist and anti-gender actors in Slovenia are, in essence, motivated by the parameters of heteronormativity and the tendency toward biological reproduction of the »nation«, which is supposedly threatened if reproductive and sexual rights are legalized.

With respect to transnational connections, anti-feminist and anti-gender actors/organizations in Slovenia are linked to the EU and transnational anti-feminist and anti-gender actors/organizations. This connection can be seen in the fact that local actors and organizations adopt the actions, strategies and discourses of transnational actors. In addition, they are involved in international anti-feminist and anti-gender projects and initiatives. Moreover, the international coalition of opponents of sexual and reproductive rights is an important source of financial and organisational support for local actors.

The anti-gender backlash and the introduction of the concept of »gender theory« were politically effective for several reasons in Slovenia. According to Kuhar (2017), three most important reasons for success of anti-gender movement are: the timing of the debate, the resonance of the naturalistic discourse of common sense, and the creation of politics of fear based on self-victimisation. Although the counter-movement has emerged in response to the increasingly successful and influential anti-gender movement in Slovenia (e.g., LGBT activists, feminists, and some politicians), they have generally failed to effectively counter its populist rhetoric, resulting in the failure of two referendums on family legislation in Slovenia.

The review of the literature on the topic of anti-feminist and anti-gender movements in Slovenia also revealed some blind spots that can be the basis for future research steps. The main blind spot is the neglect of the anti-feminist movement in existing studies, probably because anti-feminist movement was not as visible in the public as the anti-gender movement. Future research needs to focus on the activities of the anti-feminist movement awakening in Slovenia, as evidenced not only by individual events in the last decade (e.g., prayers outside a women's clinic), but also by the *March for Life*, which took place this year for the third year in a row. Special attention should be paid to seemingly liberal discourses that use populist and non-aggressive rhetoric to oppose abortion and focus on women's

suffering. As Mencin Čeplak (2016) pointed out, this is the new feature of current anti-abortion discourse that deserves special analysis.

Another blind spot in the research field of the anti-feminist movement is the issue of single women's right to medically assisted reproduction, which is a politically relevant issue in Slovenia. As we have shown in this report, there have been many attempts for a constitutional review of the law governing this area to constitutional review in the last decade, but existing studies focus mainly on the 2001 referendum and do not address current events. Public discourse, media reporting, social media debates, and political discourse in parliament should be studied in the future in the context of single women's right to medically assisted reproduction.

The next research step can also be to examine how anti-feminist and anti-gender activists used the »hybrid media system« to spread their own ideological agenda. How did the logic of hybrid media help them spread their messages? The same question should be examined in the case of LGBT rights activists' communication strategies. Were they less successful because they did not use different types of media as skillfully as the anti-gender activists? Is logic of social media better suited to spread populist (short) messages?

The counter-movement that emerged in response to the increasingly successful activities of anti-gender actors during the referendum campaigns should also merit a special research focus. The main question here is how they responded to anti-gender actors appropriating a discourse and technique that they themselves had used for decades (namely, the liberal discourse of equality and human rights). More generally, the question is how to respond to a seemingly liberal discourse that follows the principles of democratic debate but is in fact discriminatory, even if its discriminatory nature does not manifest itself precisely because it presents itself as liberal. How to fight against discourse that, on the surface, does not threaten democracy but respects its rules?

13. Timelines

Figure 1: Timeline of events related to single women's right to medically assisted reproduction

Figure 2: Timeline of events related to the right to abortion

Figure 3: Timeline of events related to marriage equality

14. List of the anti-feminist and anti-gender organizations and initiatives in Slovenia

Name of the organization (original)	Name of the organization (English)	Antigender or antifeminist?	Logo of the organization	Head of the organization (in the period 2010–2021)	Web-page (social media)	Size of the organization (if available)	Comment (brief description)
Zavod za družino in kulturo življenja	The Institute for Family and the Culture of Living	Both		Tadej Strehovec	Web: http://24kul.si/ FB: https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=100077434144469 Twitter: https://twitter.com/kulsi24	The institute has 5 full-time employees and 40 contract employees.	It represents itself as a non-profit civil society organization founded in 2009; its online portal is 24kul.si, the most prominent portal of the anti-feminist and anti-gender movement in Slovenia.

Zavod Iskreni, zavod za kulturo življenja	Iskreni Institute, institute for the culture of life	Both		Igor Vovk	Web: https://www.iskreni.net/ FB: https://www.facebook.com/iskreni.net Twitter: https://twitter.com/iskreninet	3 or 4 full-time employees	It describes itself as an organisation with Christian and conservative values that grew out of the online portal Iskreni.net, which began its work in 2004. It advocates for a »culture of life«.
Za otroke gre	Children are at Stake	Anti-gender		Aleš Primc	Web: http://24kul.si/koalicija-zaotroke-gre FB: https://www.facebook.com/Zaotroke-gre-646841078755940 Twitter: https://twitter.com/zaotrokegre	n/a	Leading Slovenian antigender organization that presents itself as a

							coalition of concerned citizens (parents and grandparents) ; the initiative is a successor of Civil Initiative for the Family and the Rights of Children, founded in 2009 by Aleš Primc.
Glas starih staršev	The Voice of Grandparents	Anti-gender		Metka Zevnik	Web: / FB: https://www.facebook.com/zavnuke/ Twitter: https://twitter.com/ZdrMetka	n/a	The association is closely related to the Children are at stake and claims that Slovenian legislation pushes grandparents

							out of families because it does not recognize their educational and caring role.
Družinska pobuda	Family initiative	Anti-gender		Tomaž Merše	Web: https://www.druzinskapobuda.si/ FB: https://www.facebook.com/DruzinskaPobuda Twitter: https://twitter.com/druzpob	n/a	NGO active in protecting »natural traditional family« of a father, a mother and children.
Zavod božji otroci	God's Children Institute	Anti-feminist		Marija Marolt	Web: / FB: https://www.facebook.com/bozji.otroci/ Twitter: /	n/a	This is a Catholic »pro-life« initiative, which defines itself as a protest movement against abortion.

Zavod Živ!m	I'm Alive	Anti-feminist		Darja Pečnik	Web: https://www.zavod-zivim.si/ FB: https://www.facebook.com/zavodzivim Twitter: https://twitter.com/zavodzivim	n/a	A private »pro-life« institution established in 2011.
Organizacijski odbor pohoda za življenje	March for Life Organizing Committee	Anti-feminist		Urša Cankar Soares	Web: https://pohodzazivljenje.si/ FB: https://www.facebook.com/pohodzazivljenje Twitter: https://twitter.com/PohodZaZiv	n/a	Initiative was founded at the beginning of January 2020 by several »pro-life« initiatives; its main purpose is to prepare »March for Life« event.
Biser (eng. Pearl) – Institution for counseling, monitoring, education and assistance for	Biser – zavod za svetovanje, spremljanje, izobraževanje in pomoč	Anti-feminist	n/a	Tomaž & Andrejka Kričej	Web: https://www.zenskaodlocitev.si/impresum/ FB: /	n/a	The institute was founded in 2017 by Tomaž and Andrejka Kričej. It operates the

people in need Maribor	osebam v stiski Maribor				Twitter: /		webiste Woman's Decision, which provides »a selection of information and experiences for pregnant women, women who have had an unplanned pregnancy, and women in doubt about having an abortion«.
Generacija identitete	Identitarian movement	Anti-gender	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	This movement is the Slovenian branch of the European Identitarian movement, which actively opposes the rights of LGBT people.

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SPAIN

Eduardo Romanos, Igor Sádaba

1. Introduction

For decades, anti-gender or anti-feminist movements in Spain were not addressed academically or in research¹. They did not become the subject of academic analysis until a few years ago. Partly because these counter-movements² hardly existed, did not manifest themselves or because they were highly institutionalised and concentrated in the Spanish church, and partly because there was not much visible activity of the feminist movement either. However, in the last decade and a half or so, the academic world has begun to address anti-feminism and anti-gender as an object of research, in parallel to the international scientific production on the issue (Jiménez, 2021). Given that the beginning of "anti-gender ideology" campaigns dates back to the mid-1990s (Patternote & Kuhar, 2018), it is only natural that the academic world has been somewhat slower. At the same time, academic gender studies have also changed radically in recent years³.

In fact, it is only in 2007 that we find academic publications on anti-feminism in Spain (del Prado et al., 2007). Since about 2015, the increase in publications on these issues has become more evident, due to La Manada case⁴ (2016-2019) and the rise of the far-right political party Vox (since approximately 2018), scientific production has intensified even more. This field is mainly written by academics (Emmanuela Lombardo, Sonia Núñez Puente, Elisa García Mingo, J. Ignacio Pichardo, Alba Alonso, Julia Espinosa, A. Bernárdez-Rodal, Gracia Trujillo, Almudena Cabezas, María Jesús Gámez), most of whom belong to Spanish universities or research centres. There are also publications by some journalists, mostly women (Nuria Alabao, Barbijaputa, Celeste López, Patricia Gosálvez, Irene García Durán, etc.), by influencers in certain social media (Noemí López Trujillo, Anita Botwin, Andrea Momoitio, etc.) and by female politicians (Clara Serra, etc.) and by some NGOs or associations. Certain publications or magazines in the feminist world have also focused on this (Pikara Magazine). The method of collecting references was based on searches in some academic search engines (Google Scholar) or in the Web of Knowledge and Scopus databases, using terms such as "Spain + anti-feminism", "Spain + anti-feminist", "Spain + anti gender". Specific searches were also carried out in Google or in national databases (Dialnet).

In general, the spectrum of topics has been growing and widening. Recently, Bonet-Martí has summarised their journey in the following terms: "In Spain, studies on anti-feminism have developed mainly in the field of history (Aguado & Ortega, 2011) and in literary studies. Despite not being an entirely consolidated line, it is worth highlighting the analysis by Alonso and Paleo (2017) on the

¹ It is worth mentioning at the outset of this report that in Spain it is difficult to differentiate anti-feminist or anti-gender actors, groups and movements as something separate or easily distinguishable. Most of them are both. For this reason, throughout the report we will not differentiate between them unless it is very obvious or necessary.

² This is one way of interpreting it in terms of the concept of counter-movement, developed by Resource Mobilisation Theory (Meyer & Staggenborg, 1996) which defines it as "a set of opinions and beliefs in a population opposed to a social movement" (McCarthy & Zald, 1977, pp. 1217-1218).

³ "This new situation, however, convinced those who, in recent years, hoped to see the future of gender studies in the comfortable academic ivory tower of publishing in peer reviewed journals, that their dream turned out to be a fragile illusion" (Petö, 2017).

⁴ Gang rape of an eighteen-year-old girl by five men on 7 July 2016 in Pamplona during the San Fermin festival. The rapists were members of a WhatsApp group called "La Manada". The case, which was considered in two courts (at provincial and regional level) as sexual abuse, had significant media and social media coverage. It was finally reviewed and sentenced by the Supreme Court on 21 June 2019, which considered it a rape.

impact of the anti-abortion movement; the article by Martínez-Jiménez and Zurbano-Berenguer (2019) on post-machismo in social networks; the comparison between France and Spain in relation to anti-feminist reactions against the Gender Violence Law by Andriamandroso (2019), the work by Bonet-Martí (2020) on the discursive strategies of anti-feminism in social networks in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic and that of Núñez Puente and Gámez Fuentes (2017) on the strategies of appropriation of the place of the victim by anti-feminist groups. The work carried out by Blázquez, Cornejo and Pichardo from the Department of Anthropology at the Complutense University of Madrid, who have maintained a line of research on Catholic anti-feminism in connection with international anti-gender networks, deserves special mention" (2020: 64-65).

2. The history of the anti-gender/anti-feminist movement and its context

Historically, the Franco dictatorship (1939-1975) had considered the "pure woman" (Morcillo, 2000) as the model of womanhood, centred on the Catholic family and submission to her husband. Anything that departed from this housewife model was anti-religious. Although there are those who find waves of anti-feminism already in the Second Republic (1931-1936) (Ortega, 2019), it does not seem that they existed beyond the traditional models and the church. During the transition to democracy (1975-1982), feminism was identified with secularism and anti-feminism with clericalism (Moreno, 2011). We mention this because it is important to historically link Francoism with current anti-feminism, as there is a direct connecting thread according to some authors (Grünell, 1994; Morcillo, 2000; Moreno, 2011). With the cultural dominance of the Catholic Church and no major feminist movements active, anti-feminist and anti-gender actors were not active for much of Spain's history (Álvarez-Benavides & Jiménez, 2021).

In general, the explanation for the emergence of the anti-feminist and anti-gender movement in recent Spain rests on two interrelated processes: the implementation of laws, norms or regulations related to gender equality or the LGBTBIQ movement and the visibility of feminism (see section 9 of this report for a more detailed sequence). The LGBTBIQ movement's laws and advances in rights (Calvo & Trujillo, 2011), such as same-sex marriage (2005) or the 2007 gender identity law, have been small milestones that have generated debate in public opinion and direct confrontations (Blázquez, Cornejo and Pichardo, 2018). Feminism's alliances with the LGBTBIQ movement (Platero & Ortega-Arjonilla, 2016) have transformed feminism itself, on the one hand, and its position on the political chessboard, on the other. Many of the advances of the anti-gender movement take place as counter-programming or counter-advances to some legal or legislative measures. If we understand elections, laws or regulations as political events, these have also been moments of rise of anti-feminism. At the same time, the visibility of feminist mobilisations (8M demonstrations, protests against La Manada and specific judicial decisions, MeToo-style denunciations, etc.) has generated an increase in anti-gender action. As a counter-movement, anti-feminism has been strengthened in each event and demonstration of feminist strength.

Therefore, beyond its emergence, the growth of the anti-feminist and anti-gender movement is mainly linked to certain elements: 1) politically, to the consolidation of extreme right-wing political parties (mainly Vox) and their militancy, 2) socially, to the existence of an active network of Catholic associations (small, medium and large), 3) technologically, to the use of certain informal digital politics (Internet and online communities) and 4) in terms of movements, the reaction to the institutional processes on gender issues discussed in the previous paragraph. Firstly, various authors argue that Vox is currently the most visible head of anti-feminism, to which it has given its basis and foundation (Espacio Público, 2021; Rivas, 2021; Alcaide, 2022; Cabezas, 2022; Bernárdez-Rodal et al., 2022), and

that part of its political programme and discourse is oriented there: "In this scenario, Vox has made anti-feminism one of its ideological banners from which it articulates other elements of its ideology. It has revived debates that have been overcome in the political sphere and that no longer generated excessive controversy, such as the need for laws against male violence or in favour of gender equality, putting these social conquests at risk, as different feminist sectors and political parties have denounced" (Alabao, 2019: 216-218). For Vox, feminism represents the centre of the evils of modern society and the decadence of a Spain in dispute, so that its anti-feminist plea and against 'gender ideology' is imbricated with ultra-nationalism, anti-immigration discourse, the defence of traditional values and everything that calls into question the territorial, identity and ideological unity of its Spanish 'being'." (Álvarez-Benavides & Jiménez, 2021: 2). Vox is not the only political party doing anti-feminist work⁵, but it is the main one and its presence in public opinion is quite frequent. Through institutions, political declarations, rallies, programmes, acts, positions, writings, articles in the media, etc., they generate an anti-gender environment and spread criticism of feminism and feminist movements and policies. In this regard, it is worth mentioning that some local governments (City Councils, Autonomous Communities, etc.) in which Vox participates, such as the Andalusian Parliament or the government of Castilla y León, have tried -sometimes, successfully, as we will see below- to undo or dismantle some LGBTBIQ or gender measures/laws.

Secondly, other authors such as Cornejo and Pichardo (2018) argue that there is a "lay Catholic activism" (2018: 524) that, in the form of a network, is responsible for disseminating the discourse of "gender ideology" promoted by the Catholic Church. Within that network, Hazte Oír (which emerged as part of the emerging anti-gender movement) and the Spanish Family Forum (closer to anti-feminism) stand out. Both are genuine anti-feminist think-tanks that have used a variety of strategies. On the one hand, by lobbying through their multiple political connections with various groups, parties and institutions. On the other hand, through public opinion and the media. They also call for actions, demonstrations and protests on a regular basis.

Thirdly, the growth of anti-feminist attitudes has had to do with digital communication. The movement has grown and expanded on the Internet thanks to the dissemination of some specifically anti-feminist influencers or youtubers, and also thanks to the existence of certain channels, forums or online discussion groups where misogyny and anti-gender discourses have spread (Idoiaga et al., 2020; Nuñez Puente et al., 2021; Villar-Aguilés & Pecourt, 2021; García Mingo & Díaz, 2022).

3. Actors

We can classify the main actors of the anti-gender/anti-feminist movement in Spain into four main types: 1) The Catholic Church; 2) Secular associations such as Hazte Oír and Foro Español de la Familia; 3) Political parties, especially Vox, but not only; and 4) Communicators and influencers on social networks or in the media. These groups of actors are relatively different in their social composition, their strategies, their repertoires of action and their size or political influence, although all of them have at some point positioned themselves against measures, proposals and rights proposed by feminism or LGBTBIQ groups. In general, they share a similar agenda against some developments such as same-sex marriage, abortion, sex education, trans issues, and so on.

⁵ "Since 2011, when the Popular Party came into government, the word "gender" has been eliminated from official documents, legal texts, calls for projects, public policies, etc., and has been replaced by other terms such as "women" or "equality" (Cornejo & Pichardo, 2017).

We have already mentioned the role that the Catholic church has historically played in the Spanish anti-gender movement. The hierarchy of the Catholic Church was very active in the fight against the laws passed on gender issues by the government of José Luis Rodríguez Zapatero (2004-2011), "with different bishops and cardinals who not only signed and published doctrinal documents, but also participated in demonstrations, promoted masses in defence of the Catholic model of family as the "natural family" (Blázquez, Cornejo & Pichardo, 2018: 53). However, its importance within the Spanish anti-gender and anti-feminist movement has declined in recent years, in favour of other secular organisations and political parties.

Regarding the second group of associations, we comment on the most relevant ones:

Hazte Oír (HO) is a Spanish ultra-right wing, ultra-Catholic and ultra-conservative association, founded by Ignacio Arsuaga in February 2001 with the purpose of carrying out signature campaigns through the Internet on issues mainly related to the family and education, focused from a Catholic and conservative point of view. Its role in the anti-gender movement is indisputable: "HO is the organisation that leads a new type of initiatives specialised in attacking sexual and reproductive rights, in the doctrinal logic of the "gender ideology" and in parallel to the agenda of the extreme-right" (Cornejo & Pichardo, 2018: 533). HO was part of the Spanish Family Forum for several years, but on 18 October 2009 it left it due to mutual disagreements. Since 2013 it has been part of the pressure group CitizenGo, an organisation with similar characteristics founded by HO itself. In May 2013 it was declared a public utility association by Interior Minister Jorge Fernández Díaz (PP), which entitled it to gain tax and economic benefits, as well as free legal aid. In February 2019, the revocation of its status as a public utility association by the Ministry of the Interior was announced.

Foro Español de la Familia (FEF; sometimes simply Foro de la Familia) is a Spanish civil association that defends the "traditional family", opposes abortion and euthanasia and it is very close to other pro-life organisations, such as Hazte Oír, and the Catholic Church, which have actively supported its mobilisations. FEF claims to represent more than 4 million families through its 5000 federations and associations. It is chaired by Mariano Calabuig and "Although in their self-presentation they emphasise the idea that they do not have a religious approach to the family, the largest and most influential associations of the FEF are explicitly or implicitly Catholic. These include the Catholic Association of Propagandists, the Catholic Pharmacists Association, the Catholic Confederation of Parents, the Association for Conscientious Objection, Family Life Institute - S.O.S Family, More Human Foundation or the Natural Family Planning Trainers. In addition, Catholic ecclesial movements such as the Legionaries of Christ and its lay branch, Regnum Christi, also participate in the Forum, represented by foundations such as Altius or Dif, as well as the presence of significant individuals belonging to Opus Dei in associations such as Evangelium Vitae and Fundación Familia, Sociedad y Educación. Also the president of the Forum, Benigno Blanco, is known as a supernumerary member of Opus Dei. The mission of the FEF includes the defence of the family in the doctrinal terminology of the Catholic Church (including expressions such as "gender ideology"), the defence of marriage as an "essential" institution (opposed to same-sex marriage), the defence of human life as "inseparable from the family" (opposed to the voluntary interruption of pregnancy and other feminist claims) and the defence of the "right of parents to educate their children in freedom" (which is the slogan used to defend the religious curriculum in schools, the segregated education of boys and girls and the rejection of the teaching of gender equality or sex education in schools)" (Cornejo & Pichardo, 2018: 532).

In the third group (political parties), Vox stands out. Founded in 2013, Vox is a far-right political party currently led by Santiago Abascal⁶, with Jorge Buxadé, Javier Ortega Smith and Reyes Romero as vice-presidents, and Ignacio Garriga as secretary general. The party first entered the Spanish parliament in the April 2019 general election, and became the country's third largest political force after the Spanish general election in November 2019, in which it won 3.6 million votes and 52 seats in the Congress of Deputies. Vox leads much of contemporary anti-feminism in Spain (de la Calle, 2022; Sen, 2022), as pointed out by numerous studies that consider that it now represents a novel and different stance to traditional Catholic anti-feminism: "Most academic, collectivist and journalistic approaches tend to link these anti-feminist positions to Catholicism, whose influence is still notable. However, Vox presents a novelty with respect to other parties by integrating a more secularised variant of anti-feminism. Although it uses common terms, arguments and discursive nodes, it does not always emphasise the religious dimension of its proposal. Its anti-feminism is ambivalent and is not reduced to actual Catholicism". (Álvarez-Benavides & Jiménez, 2021: 2). Its two main strategies have been: "firstly, the opposition of the extreme right to the politics of gender violence through various strategies, such as the denial of the gendered nature of violence against women and the inversion of the roles of victim and aggressor, and secondly, the party's representation of feminism, which ranges from its direct delegitimisation of feminism as an enemy of the Spanish nation to a parasitical-opportunist appropriation through the defence of a 'Spanish feminism'" (Cabezas, 2022a: 320).

In the fourth group of cyberantifeminism, some figures stand out. Alfonso Gallardo, better known as Roma Gallardo (1988-), is a Spanish youtuber and writer known for giving controversial political and social interviews on issues such as feminism, bullfighting and Vox's push for the 2019 Spanish elections, asking the interviewee about their convictions and how much they know about their ideology. Sergio Candanedo (1988-, Madrid), also known as Un Tío Blanco Hetero/UTBH ("A White Straight Guy"), is a Spanish YouTuber. Active since 2018, he criticizes sociocultural concepts like feminism, gender studies and political correctness. His first video, which addressed the consequences of the Me Too movement, was uploaded to YouTube on 2 February 2018. He introduced then his characteristic visual style, in which he monologues to the camera while wearing a white lycra mask (nicknamed by himself his "human condom" and based on Batman's attire), a black hoodie and plastic sunglasses. As he explained later, he chose this appearance not only to hide his identity and stand out, but also to divest himself of his individuality and to represent ironically the "white heterosexual" collective in the gender perspective's own terms. In addition, there are online anti-feminist networks in some forums (Forocoques, for example) that have threatened journalists from La Marea, Eldiario.es and Pikara Magazine (or Barbijaputa) and that could perhaps also be considered "actors".

In general, among the main anti-feminist and anti-gender actors in Spain (especially within Catholic associations and some political parties) there are few women (although there are some) and almost no young people. The composition of many of them is reduced to older men. However, this is not a subject that appears in detail in the literature. When analyzing how political parties design their candidates' lists for recent elections (such as the 2019 parliament national elections) women are placed in the lists in positions that have very low chances to win the seats at stake. In Vox, in general, there is a certain presence of middle-aged women among its leaders: Rocío Monasterio and Macarena Olona. The latter has just left the party due to differences with the leadership. However, there is a certain number of women and a female presence in the party (14 women MPs out of 52 seats), such as Reyes Romero, Rocío Meer, Carla Toscana, Mireia Borrás, Alicia Rubio and Reyes Romero. In this

⁶ Before the creation of Vox, Abascal was long a member of the People's Party (PP), served as legislator in the Basque Parliament, founded the Spanish nationalist Fundación para la Defensa de la Nación Española (DENAES) and exerted the role of director of publicly funded entities of the Community of Madrid.

respect, studies indicate that: "The discourse of Vox women themselves is a very useful tool in the fight against feminism, because it is Vox female members and supporters who "denounce" the inequality, the injustice and the social rupture that - according to this party ideology- are produced by policy measures with a gender perspective. At the same time, a polarized image of women is painted: the "true women" versus the "feminist women", a polarization that Vox tries to legitimize through the voice of women themselves" (Alcaide, 2022: 276). In the Popular Party, Isabel Díaz Ayuso, President of the Community of Madrid since August 2019, currently stands out and has taken it upon herself to criticise feminism several times (Chouza & Mateo, 2022). The role of these women, in some cases, has been to present themselves or make these formations visible in a pluralistic way or by proposing an alternative to feminism, but in others by spreading anti-gender or anti-feminist messages themselves.

On the other hand, Vox has a section dedicated to young people and its macro-events (rallies, parties, festivals, meetings...) have also included themes or shows or formats aimed at this population. Not surprisingly, a large part of the vote received by this political party is a youth vote (Villanueva, 2022). Beyond the vote, many young university students have joined and actively participate in Vox (20M, 2020).

4. Allies

In reality, as there are several different types of organisations, they are all allies of each other, sometimes acting as direct actors and sometimes as allies. However, in general, there is a great ally, often invisible, which is the Catholic Church itself or some of its institutions (the Episcopal Conference). Although we have previously mentioned it as an actor, in recent years it has ceased to have a leading role and it is no longer seen as an active subject, but rather as a shadow ally. This may be due to the strong process of secularisation that took place in Spain with the transition to democracy, but also to the fact that other groups and associations have been created and are now active, and so the Spanish church has been able to remain in a strategic background. Something similar is happening with political parties such as the Partido Popular and Ciudadanos which, although they have not always been openly anti-feminist, have collaborated in the criticism of left feminism.

In addition to these two actor-allies (Spanish Church and PP/Ciudadanos), it is worth mentioning the following as usual allies:

- Some radical right-wing extremist or neo-Nazi groups such as España 2000, Hogar Social de Madrid, Democracia Nacional, Falange Española de las Jons, etc.
- Some journalists, writers or opinion makers are potentially allies of anti-feminism. For example, Mario Vargas Llosa, Cayetana Álvarez de Toledo, Álex Grijelmo, Juan Manuel de Prada, etc.
- Media outlets such as ABC, La Razón and COPE through their publications, positions and editorial lines.
- Likewise, influencers and youtubers who are not directly anti-feminist but are critical of the feminist movement, laws and actions. Some examples would be: ElXocas, Dalas Review, Álvaro Reyes, Javier Oliveria, Álvaro Ojeda, Wall Street Wolverine, Naim Darrechi, Soto Ivars, Santiago Armesilla, etc.
- In this line, there have been TV presenters such as Pablo Motos who have harshly criticised gender laws or some feminist political leaders.

- Anti-gender or anti-trans rights feminists, known as TERFs (Trans-Exclusionary Radical Feminists), who have sometimes collaborated with extreme right-wing media or gatherings, could be considered allies. For example: Lidia Falcón and her Feminist Party, or Feminist Teachers for Coeducation (<https://dofemco.org/>), who disseminate materials against the trans law.
- There are even educational or academic institutions, such as the University of Navarra, a private religious university run by the Opus Dei, where the I International Congress on Gender Ideology took place. There are also some publications within the academic field to be taken into account⁷.

Moreover, some anti-feminist and anti-gender actors have links to judicial and ecclesiastical institutions (Cubells & Casamiglia, 2018; Albertín et al., 2018). Bustelo (2016) and Ortega and Felez (2020) argue that there are "indelible markers of Spanish antifeminism" that are found, among other places, in the bowels of the state and its institutions. In the legal sphere we can also situate as allies Abogados Cristianos, a nationwide civil foundation founded in 2008 which, according to its constitution, legally defends the values of Christianity. It is known for being active in the defence of religious feelings, a figure that exists in the current Spanish legal system, specifically in the Penal Code.

The relationship between some of these associations, some political parties and Catholic groups and the church is intense. Among other things because many of the participants in these groups also belong to the Catholic Church. Some of these people have moved from political institutions (parties or government) to these groups and organisations, such as Jorge Fernández Díaz. Many of VOX an PP politicians belong, for example, to Opus Dei⁸.

In general, there is a combination of religious and non-religious (clergy/laity) actors and individuals in these anti-feminist and anti-gender movements but with a very strong weighting towards Catholic groups (Cornejo-Valle & Pichardo, 2018). In the academic literature there is a division between those who consider that it is still the Catholic lobby that leads this anti-feminist backlash (Cornejo-Valle and Pichardo 2020, for example) and those who believe that Vox represents an overcoming of the old Catholic anti-feminism and, thus, a secularised and modernised anti-gender movement (Alvarez-Benavides & Jimenez, 2021).

Historically, the transition to democracy (1975-1982) saw the emergence of new citizenship rights for women which, however, were shaped by the redefinition of state-church relations (Moreno, 2011: 307-308). Anti-feminism was initially associated with Catholicism. However, the church had ambivalent positions between a defence of classical Catholicism and certain openness to new realities (e.g. divorce). In classical Catholic culture, an anti-feminism emerged as opposition to female emancipation, accusing feminist movements of being against Catholic morality (Moreno, 2011: 323). But anti-feminist positions came from various quarters: the Episcopate (Episcopal Conference), political parties such as Alianza Popular and Fuerza Nueva, groups such as Acción Familiar, organisations such as Hermandad Sacerdotal, Asociación pro Vida, etc. During the transition an anti-feminism also flourished outside clericalism and within the reactionary right wing close to Francoism: Fuerza Nueva and Guerrilleros de Cristo Rey, Falanges, Confederación Nacional de exCombaientes and

⁷ See Monograph number 778 (2016) of the journal *Arbor*, of the Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC), entitled: "Are there women beyond feminism? From the struggle for gender equality to transhumanism/posthumanism".

⁸ "The 74 Most Influential Faces of Opus Dei" (<https://www.publico.es/sociedad/74-rostros-influyentes-opus-dei.html>).

the newspapers Arriba and El Alcázar, which considered the Episcopal Conference to be excessively prudent.

In any case, it is worth mentioning that a large part of the anti-feminist and anti-gender network is made up of a network of small Catholic associations and groups, more or less explicitly linked to the Church and the Episcopal Conference, but which in general have been called "lay activism" (Blázquez, Cornejo-Valle & Pichardo, 2015; and Cornejo & Pichardo, 2018).

5. Themes and agendas

If we look at the anti-rights agenda of the anti-gender and anti-feminist movement we can identify at least 4 main issues (Alabao, 2022a):

- 1) Abortion: one of their priority objectives is the limitation of sexual and reproductive rights and abortion is historically one of the fundamental battles around the world. At the national level, although there are laws that guarantee it within the first 14 weeks and in certain cases after that (Law 2/2010 reformed in 2015 by the Popular Party and with a proposal to extend rights and eliminate obstacles in 2022), these groups are trying to reverse the situation and make legislative or institutional modifications in addition to putting pressure on abortion clinics.
- 2) Equality legislation and Equality institutions (such as the Ministry of Equality): This happens with all equality laws, but especially with those related to gender violence (Organic Law 1/2004, of 28 December, on Comprehensive Protection Measures against Gender Violence). In recent years there has been an important battle regarding the ratification or implementation of the Istanbul Convention (the main international treaty on gender-based violence promoted by the Council of Europe). Anti-feminist groups question most of the measures implemented in recent years and try to limit or eradicate them at local or national level.
- 3) Sex education: In recent years there has been opposition to sex and egalitarian education in schools related to 'parental PIN' (a way for parents to decide on certain types of content and teachings given to their children). This issue manages to widely mobilise the moral panics of social conservatism as it touches on issues related to sexuality, feminism, but also sexual and gender identity (Venegas, 2021). At least three autonomous communities governed by the PP - Murcia, Andalusia and Madrid - could end up implementing the 'parental PIN' at the behest of Vox.
- 4) LGBTIQ rights (Peñas et al., 2018): Some political parties and Catholic organisations resist conquests with broad social support such as same-sex marriage or same-sex adoption, but they also try to curb new rights such as trans laws or raise discourses against trans people.

In relation to the areas addressed in the FIERCE project, it can be said that the most relevant issues are:

- (1) labour market: they have had very little impact on this issue, but in general the Spanish anti-gender and anti-feminist movements have always accepted, normalised and naturalised the gender pay gap and have opposed some positive discrimination initiatives or the extension of maternity leave, but it has not been an area of conflict despite the fact that feminism has linked the situation of women with precariousness (Alabao, 2020).
- (2) health & reproductive rights: this is an area where there has been a lot of activity, mainly on abortion and termination of pregnancy (Ministry of Equality, 2022). Alonso and Paleo Mosquera

(2017) mention the introduction of a new interpretative framework revolving around the 'protection of life' by certain political groups that oppose the advancement of women's health and reproductive rights in 2013-2016.

(3) migration: although, in general, the far right is more dedicated to promoting restrictions, migration controls and blocking investigations related to institutional racism, the importance of migration has appeared to be linked to parties such as España 2000, Plataforma per Catalunya and others. However, in recent years, immigration has not been a central issue linked to anti-feminism, but also linked to migrant unaccompanied minors (MENAs). These minors have often been accused of being the real culprits of all kinds of crimes, including rape and sexual assault. By acting as scapegoats they serve to distort some debates on gender-based violence.

(4) LGBTQ+ rights: In the last decades there has been an advance in the rights and legal protections of the LGTBI community in Spain. However real equality has not yet been achieved and it still exists discrimination against LGTBIQ community in all areas, especially in the workplace. These discriminations end in attacks against people based on their sexual orientation and/or gender identity or expression. These are the third most frequent type of hate crimes. In addition to national and regional laws in force, Spain has one bill –already approved by the Congress, missing then just the approval of the Senate– whose objective is to achieve real equality in LGTBI matters and to recognize the right to gender self-determination at the national level (Córdoba, 2021).

(5) gender-based violence: anti-feminist groups have shown themselves to be opposed to gender-based violence laws, to specific laws against male violence (they speak of domestic violence) and to equating sexual aggression with rape (Bernárdez-Rodal et. al., 2021).

Bonet-Martí (2020) approaches the issues from a completely different perspective (not classic issues but agendas) and indicates that: "Anti-feminism is a plural and complex phenomenon and the issues addressed are wide-ranging. However, we consider it relevant to highlight three current debates: the growth of cyber-anti-feminism, the growth of anti-feminism of the populist right and the attempts of appropriation of feminism by the radical right and religious anti-feminism" (p. 67-68).

All these issues and questions are problematic for actors in the Spanish anti-gender and anti-feminist movement. This is because, in general, the advances of the feminist movement and the expansion of rights, not only for women but also for the LGTBIQ collective, are perceived as a deterioration of traditional models of life and as expensive fads or whims of the left that squander public resources. In a nutshell, it could be expressed as:

- Feminism destroys or impoverishes the traditional family.
- Feminism undermines Catholic morality and national identity.
- Feminism challenges the cultural and moral hegemony of the church.
- Feminism is a youth or leftist women's fad.
- Feminism appears as a contradiction or a fad.
- Feminism requires economic resources that it wastes.
- Feminism appears to be linked to the left and is a highly ideologised trend.
- Feminism disrupts established social structures and routines (it makes relations between men and women more difficult).

- Feminism blames men (generating an atmosphere of suspicion or war) and represents a hate speech.

In general, Spanish anti-gender and anti-feminist actors blame these problems on the feminist movement or on some women from political parties who seem to be leading feminist mobilisations (Irene Montero, Ione Belarra, Yolanda Díaz, etc. at present) and on certain political leaders who have implemented the measures or have allowed them (Pedro Sánchez, etc.). With regard to the feminist political movement in general, there does not seem to be any relevant or outstanding figure right now or in recent years, but it has been pointed out when some women have spoken out in public opinion, media or social networks in a clear way in favour of the movement or its postulates (Irantzu Valera, Leticia Dolera, Penélope Cruz, Amarna Miller, Pamela Palenciano, Cristina Fallarás, Margarita Salas, Rozalén, etc.).

Many of these anti-gender and anti-feminist movements do not propose concrete solutions, but rather oppose measures and changes. In other words, they have an anti-progress or anti-new rights attitude, but do not elaborate or develop measures or solutions much. One could cite a few such as:

- Restrict and, in some cases, abolish abortion rights and reproductive rights.
- Implement subsidies to families in general and large families in particular.
- Implement and incentivise aid to the Spanish Catholic church.
- Withdraw and repeal some laws and most regulations related to gender equality and gender-based violence. This implies in many cases a return to past legislation.
- They also propose to withdraw subsidies on the assumption that laws on gender violence or equality education are a waste of money or a way of financially feeding (feminist) groups that benefit from them or literally live off them.
- They also propose making general laws without a gender perspective (domestic violence law) in which men and women are put on an equal footing without any kind of structural inequality and which are based on the family.
- Allowing education à la carte, so that parents can prevent their children from being taught sexual or gender education (Parental Pin).
- Not allowing the advancement of LGBTBIQ or transgender legislation.
- In some cases they even talk of abolishing feminism itself, which they consider nothing more than a new oppression: "Vox presents feminism as an oppressive movement that seeks to subjugate and almost destroy men. The discourse of Vox's own women is a very useful tool in their fight against feminism, since it is they, their militants and sympathisers who "denounce" this situation of inequality, injustice and rupture of society to which, according to their ideology, policies with a gender perspective lead us" (Alcaide, 2022: 276).
- At least it does aim to prevent feminism from speaking in the name of all women.

These measures are justified on the basis of a number of benefits:

- Avoiding tension and/ or conflict.
- Avoiding radicalism or confrontational positions.
- Avoiding ideological or ideologised versions.

- Implementing general policies or policies for the whole population (including men) and not sectoral policies.
- Implementing traditional policies that respect certain values.
- Supporting families and protecting the traditional family as the basis of society.
- Protecting children, preventing sexual perversions and psychological problems.
- Reducing costs and enabling savings.

The literature on the Spanish anti-gender and anti-feminist movements hardly addresses the issue of the impacts of these movements, but we can point to these groups having some effect on political and legal decision-making:

- They have at least slowed down some legal or judicial decisions (Espacio Público, 2021). Now with the "Only Yes is Yes" law (Sexual Freedom Guarantee Act) many judges have used it to reduce sentences for rapists.
- Some laws have been withdrawn or regulations have been amended. For example, laws have been reformed, such as the abortion law (reformed in 2015 to require "the express consent of the holders of parental authority" for abortion in the case of women aged 16 to 18).
- They have opened debates in public opinion producing general doubts and questioning.
- Public accusations and attacks have been generated against some feminist policies or specific individuals.
- They have succeeded in altering some educational measures. The Organic Law 8/2013 for the Improvement of the Quality of Education (LOMCE) was a step backwards in this sense, as it eliminated the subject of Education for Citizenship and Human Rights included in the LOE. It also altered the previous Organic Law on Education (LOE) 2/2006, which explicitly included content related to sex education and the recognition of affective-sexual diversity.

How the general public responds to the demands of the anti-gender and anti-feminist movement in Spain is not a simple question because there are no studies on the subject either. Some consider that the mere fact that we are talking about anti-feminism is already a symptom of how public opinion is changing: "There are no surveys to prove it, but the anti-feminist reaction in Spain could be growing. The clearest indicator is among young people. In schools and high schools, teachers warn of the positions of many teenagers who publicly bounce back when they talk to them about feminism or male chauvinist violence. There are also a significant number of anti-feminist influencers who reach out directly to young people, twisting arguments and selling "rebellion". To think about the rest of society, we can only talk about intuitions." (Alabao, 2022b) . Recently there have been a small number of surveys coming out sporadically on the rise of machismo among young people (Valdés, 2022).

6. Repertoires of action

Since 2011, the anti-gender movement has not been able to reedit the massive protest demonstrations, –organised by the Episcopal Conference and various secular organizations, including FEF and HO–, that brought hundreds of thousands of people to the streets in the previous decade

against the gender laws of the first Zapatero government (2004-2008) and served as an example to other anti-gender movements in Europe (Paternotte 2015, in Cornejo & Pichardo, 2017).

In subsequent years, FEF has continued to organize demonstrations, such as those called since 2014 with the title "Every Life Matters" (or similar) against abortion (and in more recent editions, against euthanasia), but with a much smaller turnout. For its part, HO has launched several campaigns using different forms of action. In 2014, it launched #YoRompoConRajoy: a telephone harassment campaign which consisted on calling the PP headquarters to complain about the government tolerance for the gender laws passed by the previous Socialist government (same-sex marriage and abortion reform) with the aim of jamming phone lines. That campaign had its continuity the following year with the dissemination of posters, banners and placards with the slogan "A vote for [Cristina] Cifuentes is a vote for abortion" against the –in their opinion moderate– PP candidate for the elections to the Presidency of the Madrid Region.

Since its founding, HO has launched various petitions and other online actions to attack sexual and reproductive rights. However, one of HO's most visible and impactful forms of action has been the circulation of buses with eye-catching messages and images on their sides. In 2017, the Association of Families of Transgender Children Chrysalis launched the campaign "There are girls with penis and boys with vulva" to raise awareness of child transsexuality. HO initiated a petition for its withdrawal and launched a bus painted orange and with the message "Boys have penis, girls have vulva. Don't be fooled. If you are born a man, you are a man. If you are a woman, you will remain a woman". Institutions, parties, unions and NGOs criticised the HO campaign and, although they did not succeed in its withdrawal, the bus was temporarily blocked by the local government of Madrid (Gálvez, 2017). As a result of this campaign, in 2019 the socialist Ministry of Interior withdrew HO's status as a public utility entity, which had allowed it to receive aid and subsidies, in a decision that was later endorsed by the National Court as it understood that this type of actions "failed to comply with the duty to promote the general interest". HO buses have continued to circulate in subsequent campaigns, even outside Spain, for example, in front of the United Nations headquarters in New York and also in Colombia and Chile, sponsored by the transnational network CitizenGo [CG], founded by HO itself (Cabezas González, et. al., 2021).

On the occasion of the feminist strike of 8M in 2019, HO-CG circulated another bus with the slogan "It's not gender violence, it's domestic violence. Gender laws discriminate against men", in which it called on the leaders of the Spanish right-wing parties, all of them men (Pablo Casado for the PP, Albert Rivera for Ciudadanos and Santiago Abascal for Vox), to "repeal gender laws". The message was accompanied by an image of Adolf Hitler wearing make-up with painted lips and rouge and a military cap decorated with the feminist symbol and the hashtag #StopFeminazis. Again, the bus was banned, but it served to disseminate terms such as "feminazi", used by Vox during the electoral campaign along with others such as "supremacist feminists", "gender dictatorship" and "totalitarian feminism" (Cabezas Fernández, 2022a, 2022b).

Vox has also used counter-acts and boycotts of institutional acts to express its rejection of feminist demands and of general consensus against gender-based violence. Thus, on the occasion of the 8M protest in 2020, Vox organized a rally at the Palacio de Vistalegre in Madrid where its leaders labeled the mobilizations called that day by the feminist movement as a "coven". On several occasions, Vox representatives have opposed the minutes of silence and acts of homage to the victims of gender-based violence, even calling for counter-acts of homage to "all victims".

At the same time, Vox has developed a "parasitic-opportunistic appropriation of feminism: parasitic because it aims to damage feminism by appropriating its legitimacy; opportunistic because this appropriation was used to counterattack feminism at a moment of recent support and legitimacy"

(Cabezas Fernández, 2022b: 206-207). At the end of 2018, shortly after the elections to the Andalusian Parliament, Rocío Monasterio, one of Vox's leaders, was portrayed as Rosie the Riveter, the icon of the working women of World War II who became a global feminist icon. She did so for a conservative media outlet with the intention of creating a femonationalist counterpoint against the "feminazis". On the occasion of the 2019 8M feminist mobilization, Vox launched a three-minute video on social networks titled "Vox women break the March 8 feminist strike" accompanied by the hashtag #NoHablesEnMiNombre (#DontSpeakOnMyBehalf). In the video, Monasterio denied gender inequality in Spain, attacked "supremacist feminism" that seeks to "criminalize" men by imposing an "ideological burqa" that misinterprets reality. In other videos and campaigns, Vox has continued to defend femonationalist positions, presenting Spain as a place where, thanks to historical figures of liberal feminism such as Concepción Arenal, Clara Campoamor and Emilia Pardo Bazán, equality between men and women has been achieved, and it is no longer necessary to continue fighting for women's rights (Alabao 2021: 517). According to them, the sexist are others, specifically, the Muslims.

In relation to the recent growth of cyberantifeminism, some authors point to two relevant dimensions: on the one hand, the expansion of rumors and post-factual truths in relation to antifeminism (Ringrose, 2018; Bonet-Martí, 2020) and, on the other hand, the growth of cyber-violence (Vergés-Bosch, 2019).

7. Frames of arguments

In the anti-gender and anti-feminist discourse in Spain, "gender ideology" is a master frame that "serves to unite diverse actors and struggles and has shown itself to be a powerful social mobilizer, a good activator of the 'moral panics' of moral conservatism" (Alabao, 2021: 505). The expression "gender ideology" appeared for the first time in a document of the Spanish Catholic Church in 2001. In the pastoral instruction entitled "The family, sanctuary of life and hope of society" the bishops denounced the attempt of the "gay lobby" and "radical feminism" to present sexual differences as a mere cultural product to confuse young people and liberate women. However, the term did not become popular until the coming of the socialist José Luis Rodríguez Zapatero to office in 2004 (Cornejo and Pichardo, 2018: 530). Today "gender ideology" is a frame widely shared and employed by the Spanish far right, thus aligned with the radical right parties of Eastern Europe (Orban's Hungary or Law and Justice's Poland) in their combat.

For anti-gender and anti-feminist actors in Spain, "gender ideology" is a problem that threatens the "natural order of things", which they understand as a divine order, as it maintains that sexual norms are socially constructed and naturalized and that cultural differences between men and women are learned. In their conception of the world, sex differences are harmonious and need no correction. The difference between men and women is complementary and immutable: each in his/her place, which would also be valid for classes and borders (Alabao, 2021: 526).

Those responsible for "gender ideology" are basically associations of "supremacist feminism", gay lobbies that "claim to represent all homosexual people", and progressive politicians. The discourse of "gender ideology" includes a whole set of terms, expressions and ideas to denounce both the problem and those responsible for it: "subsidized radical feminist organizations" and "gender lobbies" use false denunciations, "misnamed gender-based violence" and "false concepts such as gender, [which] violate the fundamental rights of part of the population and generate groups of privileged citizens" to impose "ideological laws", "discriminatory measures" and "laws of legal inequality", all measures designed "to encourage and finance the war between the sexes" in an "unacceptable judicial interference in

the private lives of citizens based on the presumption of guilt of the male in the face of a 'de facto' consensual relationship" (Ramos, 2021: 71 and ff.).

The anti-gender and anti-feminist movement in Spain proposes a series of measures as solutions to the problem of "gender ideology":

- The defense of the traditional family against same-sex marriage, and measures promoting the birth rate and supporting large families (Vox includes in its program a Ministry of the Family). In their understanding, the traditional family pre-exists the State and must be preserved because it "guarantees gender subjection and its order" (Alabao, 2021: 515).
- The replacement of the law against gender violence with a law against intrafamily or domestic violence "that does not prejudge the sex of the aggressor, adequately respects the presumption of innocence, does not institute a huge 'gender' bureaucracy and does not facilitate the massive rain of subsidies to supremacist feminist associations" (extracted from the Vox document with 19 proposals to support the investiture of the Partido Popular candidate for the Junta de Andalucía, Juanma Moreno, quoted in Alabao, 2021: 519).
- Freedom of education, which means on the one hand support for semi-private schools by maintaining (and further promoting) the public financing of religious schools, and, on the other, measures against sexual and egalitarian education, such as the parental PIN, which the Popular Party, at the request of Vox, tried to implement in the Region of Murcia in 2019.
- The defense of life against abortion and euthanasia. Some sectors defend banning abortion while others propose some restrictions, such as forcing pregnant women to listen to the heartbeat through an ultrasound before having an abortion or that abortion is not covered by public health.

Vox and other anti-gender and anti-feminist actors also employ the so-called "demographic winter" as a frame for the racialization of sexual politics or "racialization of sexism" (Farris, 2017). As noted above, they point out that sexists are others, in this case immigrants and especially Muslims, who have cultural practices that harm and denigrate women: "We strongly reject the continued abuse and humiliating treatment of women in many non-Western countries where sex trafficking, forced marriage or ablation are systematic practices, which undermine women's dignity and privacy" (Vox Twitter, 11/25/19 on the occasion of the International Day against Violence against Women). They criminalize foreigners, who would come to expand these discriminatory practices in Spain. Vox leaders use false data to accuse foreigners of the majority of sexual crimes (in an election debate in 2009 Abascal claimed that 70% of multiple rape cases in Spain were committed by foreigners) and urge the banning of Muslim practices and symbols (such as the Madrid government permission to schools to ban the veil).

Those responsible for the "demographic winter" are basically immigrants (especially Muslims), feminists (who defend the right to decide) and progressive politicians (who allow and encourage illegal immigration). In electoral campaigns, Vox has employed the discourse of the "Reconquest of Spain" against these and other enemies, in a frame that "reveals how nativism, authoritarianism and masculism are intertwined in [a] de-democratizing project" (Cabezas Fernández, 2022b: 209), à la Trumpian MAGA (Make America Great Again). Gender "has allowed Vox to establish its identity, markedly masculinist, and differentiate itself from competing center-right parties" while "defining feminism as the enemy of the nation, with unprecedented virulence" (Cabezas Fernández, 2022b: 210).

Some of Vox's solutions to the "demographic winter" are similar to those defended against the "gender ideology", such as the defense of life (repealing the abortion law to make it more restrictive) and the defense of the traditional family (promoting a State pact for the family that implies the protection of large families, increases in bonuses for children and the creation of a universal benefit

of 100 Euros for each child à la Law and Justice in Poland). They also add the defense of the nation against progressive values and measures (and their feminist and separatist allies).

8. Transnational connections

Several authors have stressed the importance of Spain in the international anti-gender scene, both in its early developments as a "European laboratory" (Cornejo-Valle and Pichardo, 2017) where to test campaigns against same-sex marriage and against abortion, and in its current configuration, as "a nodal point in anti-gender geopolitics" (Cabezas Fernández, 2022b: 194). Within that international scene plays an important role the "cyber-lobby" (Cornejo-Valle & Pichardo, 2017) created by HO and its international sequel CitizenGo. In addition, several HO members have been accused of being part of the sect El Yunque, a paramilitary organization founded in Mexico in 1955, for which they would be recruiting young people (Cornejo-Valle and Pichardo, 2017).

HO has had a strong presence in international anti-gender forums. In 2012, it organized the World Congress of Families (WCF) in Madrid, for which it obtained funding from large Spanish fortunes (Bayo, 2021). It has also participated as a partner in other editions. WCF is an American organization that promotes conservative Christian values and ideas internationally. It opposes same-sex marriage, homoparental adoption and abortion while supporting a society built on "the voluntary union of one man and one woman in a lifelong covenant of marriage" (Urquhart, 1999). In 2014, HO participated in the Global Marriage Forum that the International Organization for Marriage (IOM) hosted in Washington. IOM is promoted by the US National Organization for Marriage (NOM), a non-profit political organization established to work against the legalization of same-sex marriage in the United States. It was formed in 2007 specifically to pass California Proposition 8, a state prohibition of same-sex marriage. The group has opposed civil union legislation and gay adoption, and has fought against allowing trans individuals to use bathrooms that accord with their gender identity.

In 2013, HO created CitizenGo, an international organization that has launched and participated in various international campaigns. In 2014, it was one of the participants in a disinformation campaign against the resolution known as the "Estrela Report" on the provision of sex education in schools and guaranteeing safe access to abortion, which was being discussed in the European Parliament. The main objective of the campaign was, through mail bombing, to make the work of parliamentarians impossible, although some messages even included direct threats. CitizenGo Africa opposes the decriminalization of homosexuality in Kenya. CitizenGo has also launched signature collections and boycotts against audiovisual and entertainment companies, for example, calling for the cancellation of a gay pride parade at Disneyland Paris (the parade finally took place on June 1, 2019) and for Netflix's taking a stand against a bill in the State of Georgia (finally passed), which prevents abortion from the moment the embryo or fetal heartbeat is detected. CitizenGo supports discriminatory and restrictive laws in other countries. It has shown its opposition to the decriminalization of homosexuality in Kenya and in 2013 signed a statement of support for a Russian law whose stated aim was to protect children from "exposure to homosexuality."

In Spain, CitizenGo has maintained a close collaboration with Vox: Ignacio Arsuaga, founder of both HO and CitizenGo, has acknowledged "indirectly" financing the party, with whom they felt "totally aligned". CitizenGo has awarded its annual prize in several editions to leaders of the party (and to some of its international allies, such as Orbán). In addition, it has actively participated in electoral campaigns in favor of Vox. On the occasion of the 2019 general elections, CitizenGo launched the campaign "Vota Valores" (Vote Values) in which several buses with that slogan accompanied by quotes aimed at disparaging the leaders of other political parties toured various cities. The relationship,

however, has become complicated in recent years, reaching the point of rupture. According to CitizenGo, Vox's position in regional government agreements with the PP (Andalucía, Murcia, Madrid) is too lukewarm on anti-gender issues.

9. Explanations of the anti-gender/anti-feminist backlash

The anti-gender reaction arose in Spain against important gender laws of the PSOE governments of José Luis Rodríguez Zapatero: a law against gender-based violence (2004); a same-sex marriage law (2005); a gender identity law (2007) that introduced the right to the rectification of the registry mention of sex provided certain prerequisites (a minimum two year hormone therapy and a gender dysphoria diagnosis); an equality law (2007) that introduced parity in electoral lists; a new abortion law that allowed for the first time free termination of pregnancy during the first 14 weeks (2010); and a new education law (2006) that included sex education, training in gender equality and the fight against homophobia in public schools. Catholic actors stand out in the mobilization of this reaction. The Episcopal Conference, which played a preponderant role at the beginning, gradually gave way to secular actors such as HO or the Spanish Family Forum. This mobilization enabled the PP to reform the 2010 law introducing parental permission for abortion for minors aged 16 to 18 (2015). During this period, the Popular Party government of Esperanza Aguirre in the Community of Madrid (2003-2012) became "the great laboratory of the neo-con", financing "profusely with public funds anti-abortion or religious organizations linked to the most fundamentalist sectors of the Church and the media close to it" (Alabao, 2021: 506).

The national government changed color in 2011, when the Popular Party of Mariano Rajoy came to power, who finally did not give the battle against the PSOE's abortion law, even though it was in his electoral program. The Minister of Justice, Alberto Ruiz-Gallardón tried to reform the abortion law and finally resigned, apparently because of the feminist mobilization and because Rajoy decided not to reform the law, after months of controversy saying that they were going to do so. Nor did he dare to repeal same-sex marriage. Their space will be occupied by the far-right party Vox from 2013, which manages to attract the neo-con and anti-gender sector disenchanted with the PP, pushing the development of the anti-gender movement in Spain, which has been "a turning point" in that context by expanding its audience and providing it with greater legitimacy (Cabezas Fernández, 2022b: 195). The leaders of Vox have set themselves up as "defenders of the 'politically incorrect', the only ones who dare to speak the truth and shake the 'progre[ssive] consensus' in the face of the 'cowardly right' represented by the PP" (Alabao, 2021: 524). Faced with the rise of Vox, the PP has been forced to extreme its positions on anti-gender and anti-feminist issues. Thus, in April 2020, the PP did not support the validation of the "Decree-Law on urgent measures for the protection and assistance to victims of gender violence in the face of the coronavirus crisis".

Beyond this overview of the evolution of the anti-gender/anti-feminism backlash, we can group the different factors that explain the emergence of these movements according to the following categories:

- **Political factors.** Some authors situate the rise of the anti-gender movement in a broader process of "de-democratisation" or deterioration of democracy. Since democracy is a necessary condition (and prerequisite) of the feminist movement as well as an ally, any problem in the democratic situation affects feminism: "We argue that neoliberalism, authoritarian shifts, and political corruption are three key dimensions of the processes of de-democratization in Spain that contribute to oppose gender equality" (Alonso and Lombardo, 2018: 79). In general, this view argues that, after the Great Economic Recession, an authoritarian period emerges in which feminism is confronted in the same way as LGTBQ

rights and other minorities. Along these lines, numerous studies link the rise of anti-feminism to the emergence of a specific political actor such as the Vox party and the manifestations of the extreme right (Álvarez-Benavides & Jiménez, 2021; Alcaide, 2022; Pichel-Vázquez & Enguix, 2022). In the last years, Western democracies have been experiencing a far-right momentum and Spain is no longer an exception (Turnbull-Dugarte 2019 cited in Pichel-Vázquez & Enguix, 2022: 466). In relation to other countries (post-communist countries, for example), some authors consider that there has been a triple confluence in relation to reactionary populism (Fabián, 2022: 293): "the feedback between conservative, expressively patriarchal, and populist forces and their embracing of anti-genderism".

- Economic factors. The economic crisis following the 2008 recession appears as a factor that destabilises politics in general and gender politics in particular (Alonso and Lombardo, 2018): "The austerity policies that the EU and the Spanish government have enacted in response to the economic crisis are changing the Spanish gender regime in neoliberal and conservative directions, threatening progress towards a more public rather than domestic gender regime" (Lombardo, 2017: 210). In other words, cuts in social or welfare policies have generated a "restructuring of the equality machinery, retrenchment of the welfare state, neoliberal employment policies, stagnation of women's representation and the restriction of abortion rights" (Ibidem). Some consider that the crisis has simply exacerbated inequalities and this has made it impossible to maintain certain policies (Salazar, 2016), intensifying discomfort, crises, violence and sensitivities regarding identities, minorities and inequalities.
- Cultural factors. Other views, such as that held by Kováts (2018), consider the existence of a cultural and general crisis in society as a whole. Anti-gender fundamentalism points to societal crisis phenomena going beyond gender equality and LGBTQ rights. These movements and their success are symptoms and consequences of deeper socio-economic, political and cultural crises of liberal democracy. Álvarez-Benavides and Jiménez (2021: 7-9) also add the idea that Vox is really a success of the extreme right in terms of cultural warfare or "cultural counter-programming" in the face of certain advances of the left and of centre or centre-left governments.
- Factors of movement/counter-movement dynamics. The recent growth in visibility, participation and activity of the feminist movement has been an unquestionable fact in Spain (see the Working Package 2 report on Spain). However, the institutionalisation of the movement, its capacity to influence, modify or promote laws and measures, obtain resources, etc. is also indisputable. This has generated a certain unease among traditional or Catholic sectors about this presence or empowerment. Patternote and Kuhar, for example, consider that "Anti-gender campaigns in Europe are reactions to the results of the UN conferences of Cairo and Beijing" (2018: 6). In Spain, given its peculiar situation in terms of territorial model and independence movements, some have also linked the rise of the far-right to certain independence movements (especially the Catalan one) although this would not in itself explain anti-gender or anti-LGTBIQ. These types of movement/anti-movement explanations are the most frequent in the literature on Spain due to the presence and strength (already institutionalised) of feminism and the independence movements (Rivas, 2021; Cabezas, 2022).

10. Counter-movements

Spanish anti-gender and anti-feminist movements are considered counter-movements to the LGBTIQ and feminist movements and their successful campaigns in favour of same-sex marriage and LGBTIQ rights in general, including trans rights, the right to voluntary termination of pregnancy, gender-based violence laws and protections and equality rights. Thus, there is no literature on counter-movements to the anti-gender and anti-feminist movements, as so far there has not been any new aligning or alliance of feminist, LGBTIQ and, in general, democratic forces to fight the recent wave of anti-gender and anti-feminist mobilizations.

11. Conclusions

Historically, the anti-feminist and anti-gender movement did not exist in Spain as such or was simply linked to the dictatorship or the Catholic church. However, the phenomenon has expanded in recent years, also becoming a growing field of research in the last decade. Scholars seek to understand the political, economic, cultural and anti-feminist factors, etc. that have facilitated the emergence of new far-right political parties (Vox) and new spheres in which anti-feminism and anti-genderism are on display. The main actors of anti-feminism in Spain are these radical right-wing parties, a network of Catholic and pro-life associations and digital influencers. However, around them, there are a series of allies such as the media, journalists, other traditional right-wing parties, television presenters or anti-Trans and anti-gender feminist groups. Although they have not achieved broad social support, not even among the youth, they elaborate discursive frames that are oriented towards gender-based violence, reproductive rights, LGBTIQ rights, labour market, etc.

In Spain, the anti-gender and anti-feminist movement uses various forms of action, from petitions to harassing political authorities, to circulating buses with high-impact slogans and images. They also organize demonstrations, although not with as many participants as those led by the Catholic Church at the beginning of the millennium. In recent years, cyber-antifeminism has also grown with the expansion of rumors, fake news and acts of cyber-violence. The main frames of the movement are the so-called 'gender ideology' and the 'demographic winter', whose responsables would be feminist and gay associations, progressive politicians and, in the case of the 'demographic winter', also immigrants.

The Spanish case is important in the development of a transnational anti-gender and anti-feminist movement, both in its origin as a laboratory of campaigns against same-sex marriage and against abortion, and in its subsequent development through the activity of international organizations founded by Spanish actors (such as CitizenGo). Recently, the Spanish movement has gained momentum through the far-right Vox party, which has achieved a preponderant position, displacing other actors, such as the Catholic Church or secular organizations, which led the campaigns against the gender laws implemented by the PSOE in the past.

12. Timeline

Timeline of key moments in the development of the anti-gender movement in Spain (2011-2022):

- 2012, May 25-27: World Congress of Families hosted in Madrid by HO.
- 2014, September 23: Ruiz-Gallardón dismiss after unsuccessful reform of the abortion law.
- 2014, October 8: campaign #YoRompoConRajoy launched by HO-CG.
- 2014, November 22: campaign 'Every Life Matters' launched by FEF.

- 2015, May: campaign 'A vote for Cifuentes is a vote for abortion' launched by HO.
- 2016, July 17: an eighteen-year-old woman was raped by five young men (La Manada), becoming one of the most famous and controversial cases of sexual violence in Spain.
- 2017, February: transfobic bus by HO.
- 2018, June: mass protests against the release of some of the accused of La Manada.
- 2018, November: demonstration by FEF in Madrid against the draft of a new abortion law.
- 2019, November: campaign 'Vote Values' by HO-CG in the electoral campaign.
- 2019, March 8: 'Feminazis' bus by HO-CG.
- 2019, February: HO loses status as a public utility entity.
- 2019, September: Parental PIN implemented in Murcia by Regional Government.
- 2019, November: Vox wins 52 MPs in national elections, the highest number in its history.
- 2020, March: Vox's proposal to replace the law on gender-based violence with another on domestic violence.
- 2020, March 8: anti-feminist rally by Vox in Vistalegre.
- 2022, June 26: demonstration with more than 200 organizations against abortion and euthanasia in Madrid.
- 2022, December 16: protest of TERF organizations against the trans identity law.

13. List of anti-gender/anti-feminist organizations

Name of the organization (original)	Name of the organization (English)	Antigender or antifeminist?	Logo of the organization	Head of the organization (2010-2021)	Web-page (social media)	Size of the organization (if available)	Comment (brief description)
Hazte Oír	“Make yourself heard” (Citizen Go)	Both		Ignacio Arsuaga	https://citizengo.org/hazteoir	7000 thousand partners	The main and most visible anti-gender and anti-feminist organisation or association in Spain, although it is not very big and quite controversial.
Abogados cristianos	Christian lawyers	Both	ASOCIACIÓN ESPAÑOLA DE ABOGADOS CRISTIANOS	Polonia Castellanos	https://abogadoscristianos.es/	More than 20900 followers on Twitter	Organisation dedicated to fighting for Christian values in general by opposing feminism and LGTBIQ rights through complaints and lawsuits.
Foro de la Familia	Family Forum	Antifeminist		Ignacio García-Juliá	https://www.forofamilia.org/	More than 19300 followers on Twitter	This is the largest organisation in Spain dedicated to protecting and promoting traditional and Catholic family values and which mobilises and organises numerous events and protests.
Federación Española asociaciones pro vida	Spanish Federation of Pro-Life Associations	Antifeminist	FEDERACIÓN ESPAÑOLA DE ASOCIACIONES PROVIDA	Alicia Latorre	https://provida.es/feapv/	More than 3900 followers on Twitter	It is a voluntary Non-Governmental Organisation, which promotes respect for all human life from conception to natural extinction. It has its origins in the first Pro Life Association in Spain, which emerged in Barcelona in 1977. It has been recognised and registered in the register of

							Associations of the Ministry of the Interior since 1981.
Vox	Vox	Both		Santiago Abascal	https://www.voxespana.es/	65.000 members	Vox is a Spanish political party of ultra-conservative and ultra-nationalist ideology founded on 17 December 2013.
Asamblea por la Vida, la Libertad y la Dignidad	Assembly for Life, Liberty and Dignity	Both		Alfonso Bullón de Mendoza y Gómez de Valugera	https://www.acdp.es/asamblea-por-la-vida-la-libertad-y-la-dignidad/	Not available	It integrates 150 organizations and associations
NEOS	NEOS	Both		Jaime Mayor Oreja, María San Gil and others	https://xn--neosespaa-s6a.es	More than 9300 followers on Twitter	"From Christian foundations, NEOS aims to show the right course in the face of the relativism and the destruction of the social order that are trying to be imposed in Spain today."
Padres por la Verdad	Parents for the truth	Both		Not Available	https://www.facebook.com/PadresxlaVerdad	Not available. Nearly 26,000 subscribers to his Telegram channel	Anti-vaccine group and close to conspiracy theories
Asociación Nacional de las Víctimas de la Violencia Doméstica	National Association of Victims of Domestic Violence	Antifeminist		Not Available	https://anavid.es/nosotros/qui-enes-somos	More than 4000 followers on Twitter	Group that denies gender-based violence and considers it only as part of general domestic violence.

Plataforma Cada Vida Importa	Every Life Matters Platform	Both		Not Available	https://www.cadavidaimporta.es/ (Forwards to https://www.forofamilia.org/)	More than 6300 followers on Twitter	Group oriented towards opposing abortion and reproductive rights
Asociación Nacional de Afectados del Síndrome de Alienación Parental	National Association of People Affected by Parental Alienation Syndrome	Antifeminist		Not Available	https://www.anasap.org/	Not Available	This organisation denounces that sons and daughters are alienated and manipulated by their mothers and that they are under a parental alienation syndrome.
Profesionales por la Ética	Professionals for ethics	Antifeminist		Not Available	https://profesionalesetica.org/	8000 followers on Twitter	They declare: "We recognise the natural family, based on marriage between a man and a woman, as the basic nucleus of society and the engine of its development."
Asociación Enraizados - Católicos en la vida pública	Enraizados Association - Catholics in Public Life	Both		Not Available	https://enraizados.org/	4500 followers on Twitter	Ultra-Catholic group that defends traditional Christian values and opposes any change in the family, calling for protests and demonstrations.
Alianza Contra el Borrado de las Mujeres	Alliance Against the Erasure of Women	antigender		Not Available	https://contraelborradodelasmujeres.org/	8200 followers on Twitter	Grouping of various feminist associations against trans laws and LGBT rights, considering that these advances cut back on women's rights and "erase" them.

Table 1: List of anti-gender/anti-feminist organizations

14. References

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TURKEY

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1. Introduction

Studies of anti-gender movements comprise a relatively new scholarship in Turkey. It can be considered to be part and extension of the feminist scholarship studying the growing conservatism of the AKP government in power since 2002. Thus relevant studies can be grouped under two chronological categories: The first is a larger feminist scholarship, which has been actively documenting and theorizing the growing anti-feminist and lately anti-gender developments in government discourse, practice and policy since the early 2000s. The second is a more recent body of work pointing to the emergence of men's rights activism and the spread of anti-feminist and anti-gender ideas among radical conservative groups, many with connections with the government.

The literature often marks the 2007 elections, 2010 plebiscite, 2011 and 2015 elections and the 2017 transition to a presidential system as landmark moments in the aftermath of which the government has intensified its anti-feminist policy making and discourse. In addition, the scholarship pays attention to the banning of the Pride Parade in 2015 and the Feminist Night March in 2019 as turning points in which non-governmental right wing groups intensified their anti-feminist and anti-gender campaigns. A third landmark year is 2021, which is when the president signed a decree announcing the country's withdrawal from the Istanbul Convention.

The main issues that stand out in the Turkish case include the following. First, there is the mobilization against Turkey's participation in international conventions. The second is a broad discourse of familism and tradition, which disparages not only non-heterosexual families and LGBTQI rights in general, but also propagates against policies such as those that ban underage marriages, take measures against domestic violence and protect alimony rights in cases of divorce. Abortion, a legal right in Turkey, has also been coming under attack. While the term gender has not been problematized to the extent it has by other anti-gender mobilizations, we can say that there is a palpable building up of a discourse against gender equality as a Western import and threat, one that is often replaced by terms such as gender equity/justice, argued to fit with the "Turkish and Islamic traditions and culture" in the sense that they are conceptualized as recognizing and doing justice to women and men's biological destinies and complementary nature in families.

2. The history of the anti-gender/anti-feminist movement and its context

The literature on anti-feminist and anti-gender mass mobilization is in broad agreement that the spread of these discourses via journalists, Islamic intellectuals and the formation of right-wing non-governmental organizations is relatively new, a phenomenon that dates back to the early 2010s (Eslen-Ziya & Bjørnholt, 2022). Yet, most also emphasize that these movements have found fertile ground in and built on existing right-wing state policies and discourses, regarding gender equality, women's rights and LGBTQI rights. In fact several authors argue that until the late 2010s, the AKP government has been the only subject of anti-feminist and anti-gender action and discourse (Kourou, 2021; Özkazanç, 2020).

In this sense, earlier key moments in the mobilization are those incited by government actors. For example, in 2008 the idea that every family should have at least three children was voiced for the first time (Yazici, 2012). This marks a key moment in how desirable families are defined moving forward and how the demographic fear is linked to the control of women's bodies (Günaydın, 2021; Güneş-Ayata & Doğangün, 2017; Korkut & Eslen-Ziya, 2016). This "need" for three children per family then has been articulated by all key political actors, ever since then (Akkan, 2018; Diner, 2018; Korkut & Eslen-Ziya, 2016). A corollary of this familialism has been the government stance against abortion. In 2012, the president resembled abortion to a massacre carried out by the Turkish Armed Forces near the border, based on faulty intelligence. This discourse was followed soon by a policy proposal to restrict and ban abortion, withdrawn only when there was wide scale feminist mobilization. While abortion is still legal in Turkey, its accessibility in public hospitals has been severely restricted in practice (O'Neil et al., 2020). Another key moment of anti-gender politics incited by the government was the banning of the annual Pride Parade in 2015 on the grounds that it conflicted with religious sensitivities heightened in the holy month of Ramadan (Mutluer 2019, Savcı 2020). The Pride Parades, held annually in Istanbul since 2003, had drawn in participants up to 50,000 in its later years (Savcı 2020). Mutluer (2019) sees in this event the completion of AKP's transformation from a party that had been pragmatically inclusive of LGBTQI in its earlier days in the government to one that is openly conservative, defending heterosexual families, speaking against LGBTQI, and mixing in its discourses ideas such as traditional family values, nationalism and religiosity.

The second half of the 2010s is when men's rights organizations started being established. The 2012 feminist mobilization against abortion ban is seen as a key event against which this backlash mobilization began organizing (Eslen-Ziya & Bjørnholt, 2022). These organizations started campaigning against the legal achievements of the women's movement in previous decades. Although, earlier, scholars were ambivalent about their success (Özkazanç, 2019b), a series of victorious moments appear in the literature: the inclusion of many demands of these organizations in the report of the parliamentary investigation commission, widely called the Divorce Commission, in 2016 (Ayata & Candaş, 2018; Coşar, 2021; Kandiyoti, 2019), the citation of the policy goal "bring fairness to the alimony system" in the 2018 Presidential Executive Program (Özcan, 2020), the cancellation of Higher Education Council's Gender Equality Position Paper in 2019 (Göker and Polatdemir, 2022), and finally culminating to the withdrawal from the Istanbul Convention with a midnight presidential decree in 2021 (Altan-Olcay & Oder, 2021).

The literature records the year, 2019, as the turning point in which various actors intensified their anti-gender and anti-feminist efforts, with the backing of the AKP government. Özkazanç (2019b) points to February 2019 when op-ed columnists in pro-government newspapers suddenly and in a concerted fashion began writing slanderous op-eds about the terms gender and gender equality. This was soon followed by synchronous attacks on the Feminist Night March which has been held annually on March 8 since 2003, attracting significantly higher turnouts in successive years. For the first time in its history, the March was attacked by police forces (Çağatay et al., 2022; Ünal, 2021) To legitimize police violence and to further smear the March 8 celebrations, maintained to be a peaceful rally for the past sixteen years, the next day on March 9 the same groups backed by the President spreaded a news that protestors booed the *ezan* (call to prayer). This moment showed how anti-gender actors have become determined in 2019 to mobilize the religious sensitivities frame to grow their constituency against feminist and LGBTQI activisms (Çağatay et al., 2022; Özkazanç, 2019b; Savcı, 2020).

The most notable development in the anti-feminist and anti-gender mobilization happened, again in 2019, when a social media campaign was launched against the Istanbul Convention, under the hashtag *istanbulconventionkills* (Ünal, 2021). The campaign attacked not only feminist groups for defending the convention, it also claimed that the convention was a Trojan Horse sneaking LGBTQI rights and that it actually increased violence against women. It also marked a moment of intra-conservative competition in which an Islamic women's GONGO, established by the President's daughter, was targeted intensely (Kütük-Kuriş, 2022; Tabak et al., 2022). This GONGO, KADEM, was known for its rhetoric emphasizing gender equity instead of gender equality, its conservative stance with respect to women's roles in the family, and its influence on and cooperation with state bodies dislocating profeminist women's organizations from the process of policy making (Çelebi, 2022; Diner, 2018). KADEM defended the Istanbul Convention, albeit ambivalently. The fact that the ultra-conservative forces could attack KADEM in this particular instance is seen as a clear signal of who is winning out in the struggle inside the conservative block between the moderates and the radicals (Kütük-Kuriş, 2022; Tabak et al., 2022; Ünal, 2021). In these studies, the president's announcement of a decree withdrawing from the Istanbul Convention in March 2021 appears as the sharpest peak the anti-gender mobilization achieved in this period between 2010 and 2021.

3. Actors

Majority of the scholarship is in broad agreement on the role that the 20 year rule of the AKP government played in the rise of conservatism, anti-feminist and anti-gender discourses and policies in Turkey. For many authors, it is the gradual transformation of the state, the regime that paved the way for the budding anti-gender mobilizations, with the participation of new NGOs established for the purpose of challenging gender equality legislation, right-wing intellectuals, and Islamic cults. These organizations ally with one another on specific campaigns, creating a de facto network. While there is some debate over where to position prominent women's GONGOs spearheaded by actors-originating from AKP circles (whether they are anti-gender, anti-feminist and so on), there is broad agreement that they also played an active role in the challenging of the gender equality frame.

3.1. AKP government

Many authors agree that until 2019, AKP was the sole subject of anti-gender mobilization in the country (Eslen-Ziya & Bjørnholt, 2022; Kourou, 2021; Özkazanç, 2020). Some authors position this governmental stance in the political party's historical trajectory of a familialist discourse. This discourse has positioned women's rights advocacy in terms of women's familial roles, women's empowerment as firmly located in the family (Arat, 2021; Güneş-Ayata & Doğangün, 2017). Yet, there has also been a regression in the last decade because of the partial suspension of EU accession process (and hence the external pressure to democratize); growing centralization of power, patrimonialism institutionalized in the presidential system have been effective in the intensification of a conservative gender climate. These factors explain the regressing situation in gender equality despite earlier legal reforms (Güneş-Ayata & Doğangün, 2017; Ugur-Çınar, 2017).

In this literature, some authors focus on AKP's institutionalizing and magnifying of anti-gender discourse with the state and non-state organizations. The AKP transformed state institutions and bureaucracy to the extent that a number of them became the locus of anti-gender mobilization, exponentially increasing the mobilization's influence (Adak, 2021; Çavdar & Yaşar, 2019; Coşar, 2021;

Günaydın, 2021; Hülagü, 2021; Ugur-Çınar, 2017). Second, the government interfered with the organized domain of women's movement by establishing new GONGOs, most prominently KADEM, and aligning several conservative women's organizations with its cause (Çelebi, 2022; Diner, 2018). The government provided enormous resources as well as visibility and power to these NGOs, claiming them to be true representatives of Turkish women, while banishing profeminist advocacy organizations as deceitful and unauthentic (Güneş-Ayata & Doğangün, 2017; Keysan, 2019; Koyuncu & Özman, 2019; Yabancı, 2019).

Other researchers focus on internal party dynamics. Tabak et al. (2022) identifies two shifts in AKP's gender politics, the first one being from gender equality to gender justice (challenging "secular normative status quo" with a kind of moderate conservatism), the second shift from moderate conservatism (gender justice) to radical conservatism (rejectionism). The authors argue that with the last shift taking place from the mid 2010s onwards, the government emboldened its anti-genderist or rejectionist stance. During the process of withdrawal from the Istanbul Convention, the moderate wing of the party with its satellite institutions positioned in the NGO field turned out to be more hesitant in their agenda and chose not to risk being isolated within the party (Kütük-Kuriş, 2022). Drawing on her fieldwork on AKP's women's branches during the 2019 local elections, Kourou (2021) adds that women cadres of AKP have been active in using and disseminating anti-gender rhetoric. Underlining clientelistic logic in women's branches' interactions with their constituents, Çavdar (2022) doubts the "optimistic" forecast that the latter would reject the last turn in AKP's gender politics. Further research is needed to understand if these efforts have massified the resolutely anti-gender position, once observed as marginal within the party.

3.2. State Bureaucracy

As AKP won elections throughout the 2000s, there has also been a growing convergence between state policies and party doctrines. Scholars emphasize the growing influence of religious-conservative climate to the aftermath of 2007 and point to the intensification of discourses on biological destiny, demands for three-children families, attempts to ban abortion and C-section as well as policies that have outlawed co-ed dorms and gave religious clerics the right to perform civil marriage ceremonies (Acar & Altunok, 2013; Cindoğlu & Ünal 2017; Coşar, 2021; Gülel, 2021).

This is also the period in which what used to be the Ministry of Women and Family has passed through several rounds of institutional (re/de)structuring, ultimately dropping the word women and becoming the Ministry of Family and Social Services. Çavdar and Yaşar (2019) delineate that the first decree issued after the renaming of the ministry listed the ministry's primary objective as making social policies at the national level and the second as protecting the family against social and cultural erosion. Prevention of gender based discrimination and protection of women's rights was listed as the fourth objective. A more recent report adds that the protection of women's rights also dropped from the agenda of the Ministry and the only notion reminiscent of equality is the concept "equal opportunities for women and men" invoked occasionally and in a limited manner in some issue areas (Sancar et al., 2021).

Focusing on the state bureaucracy, some studies refer to The Presidency of Religious Affairs as another influential anti-gender and anti-feminist actor, which has intensified collaborations with the Ministry promoting religiously sanctioned heterosexual family (Adak, 2021; Coşar, 2021; Günaydın, 2021; Mutluer, 2019). The Presidency of Religious Affairs itself has been expanding its sphere of influence

since the establishment of Family Spiritual Guidance and Counseling Desks in 2003 (Adak, 2021; Coşar, 2021; Kocamaner, 2019). These units expanded the reach of the Presidency beyond the mosques into the private sphere of households in an effort to religiously sanction AKP's anti-feminist politics (Adak, 2021; Çavdar & Yaşar, 2019). The Presidency's counseling activities along this line which often involve breaches of women's and children's legally recognized rights attract attention of pro-feminist publics who could still successfully hold the institution accountable for its activities (Çavdar & Yaşar, 2019).

Günaydın (2021) also points to international conferences on families organized or promoted by state institutions such as Human Rights and Equality Institution of Turkey (TİHEK), under AKP rule. She argues that these conferences are the venues where anti-gender politics amplified throughout the 2010s. Hülagü (2021) further points to TİHEK's role in transplanting men's rights groups' discourses (such as "the plight of men is underrated") within state bureaucracy: the institution's support gives these groups a political legitimacy which they, otherwise, would not have had.

3.3. KADEM (Kadın ve Demokrasi Derneği - Woman and Democracy Association)

Established in 2013, KADEM is one of the women's organizations, located within the Islamist movement and with organic ties to the AKP government. Positioned as a GONGO with enormous visibility, resources and power, KADEM has attracted several researchers' interest. This is the organization that has successfully promoted the notion of gender equity/justice as a more "culturally apt" alternative to gender equality. Ayhan (2019) sees KADEM as born out of the institutionalization efforts of a conservative gender agenda, one that was tasked with hosting the Women20 Summit in 2015, one of the NGOs that wrote a shadow report for the CEDAW 2015 constructive dialogue and worked with the government on the workshop on Istanbul Convention in 2019. These examples indicate the organization's expanding influence, replacing independent feminist organizations which had previously worked closely with the government in international agreements, meetings and so on.

There is some debate over where to place KADEM on the spectrum of political actors. Some scholars call it anti-feminist but not necessarily anti-gender. For example, Tabak et al. (2022) position KADEM and anti-genderists at the opposite sides of conservative political spectrum. The authors describe KADEM's construction of the gender justice frame as an attempt to localize global gender equality norms. They state that KADEM supports the government's pro-family policies, but also perceives women as individuals with rights, particularly recognizing women's right to employment. In a similar vein, Kütük-Kuriş (2022) sees KADEM as not feminist, but not anti-gender either. She discusses how they have always campaigned against violence against women and early & forced marriages, pushed for equality before the law while also framing their stance as gender justice/equity and not equality. She explains KADEM's contradictory and changing stance on a number of issues in terms of Molyneux's argument that when mobilizing actors have an opportunity window they push it, when it is in their interests to be co-opted to retain their place in the larger mobilization, they refrain from acting. These studies substantiate their nuanced location of KADEM vis-a-vis anti gender mobilization with its becoming a scapegoat in the anti-Istanbul Convention campaign, its labeling as a partner to an "international conspiracy, a.k.a. the Soros Project that operates worldwide to allegedly eradicate the institution of family," or as "green feminists' who are betraying the Islamic values and becoming slaves to the feminist ideology" (Kütük-Kuriş, 2022; Tabak et al., 2022).

On the other hand, Çelebi (2022) locates KADEM in anti-gender/anti feminist polity together with other Islamist women's organizations. Çelebi (2022) identifies three characteristics of the concept of

gender equity/justice: prioritizing patriarchal norms in the family, attributing essentialist characteristics to sexes, and assuming binary heteronormative norms. Ayhan (2019) agrees that KADEM is an anti-gender actor because it promotes an essentialist notion of gender and hinders feminists' efforts for change. In Ayhan's terms, KADEM's gender justice frame is "simply anti-genderism under a different name" which is "sneaky, hence dangerous" because the organization pursues this agenda while publicizing itself as a women's rights advocate. For Eslen-Ziya (2020), as well, KADEM is unquestioningly an anti-gender actor as it pursues two goals: one is the protection of the societal values against those who blame the society for injustices against women and second is the reproduction of an essentialist gender ideology.

3.4. Extremist anti-gender groups and men's rights activists

Çelebi (2022) notes the differences between KADEM and "extremist" anti-gender groups such as, Divorced People and Family Platform (Boşanmış İnsanlar ve Aile Platformu), Turkey Family Council (Türkiye Aile Meclisi), and Thought Platform (Düşünce Platformu). These organizations have been established in the last decade and they have become increasingly vocal in the past few years with campaigns against alimony legislation, the Istanbul Convention, the domestic violence legislation, and advocating for under-age marriage. Hülagü (2021) adds the National Will Platform (Milli İrade Platformu) as an umbrella organization which has gathered together anti-feminist groups to lobby and campaign against pro-gender equality policies. There is also the International Family Institute (Uluslararası Aile Enstitüsü), established in 2015, which announces its objective as developing a family policy agenda based on Islamic rules and lobbies against international conventions, particularly CEDAW and Istanbul Convention (Günaydın, 2021).

Nevertheless, many authors note the lack of a grass-roots anti-gender mobilization in Turkey until recently (Eslen-Ziya & Bjørnholt, 2022; Kourou, 2021; Özkazaç, 2020). Ünal (2021) argues that men's rights discourses are fairly new, emerging onto the political scene in recent years, following on the heels of increasing authoritarianism. Now emboldened by the radicalization of the right in general, they can attack not just feminists but also organizations like KADEM, which is close to the government, and has put intensive effort to differentiate itself from feminist-minded organizations. For Özkazaç (2020), time will show whether a popular grassroots movement comparable to mobilizations in European countries will take shape in Turkey, for now, only seeds of such a movement are thrown. Eslen-Ziya and Bjørnholt (2022) agrees that "an unformulated mobilization and anti-genderism" with state backup characterizes Turkish scene.

3.5. Intellectuals of the anti-gender politics

Anti-gender mobilization is also fueled by right wing newspapers such as *Milli Gazete*, *Yeni Akit*, and *Yeni Şafak* and writers such as Abdurrahman Dilipak, İhsan Şenocak, Yusuf Kaplan, and Sema Maraşlı (Eslen-Ziya & Bjørnholt, 2022; Kütük-Kuriş, 2022). They produce content that gets reposted by men's rights activists' Facebook and Twitter accounts. Özkazaç (2019) focuses specifically on two intellectuals of anti-gender mobilization: Mücahit Gültekin and Sema Maraşlı. Sema Maraşlı focuses on "problems of domestic and married life" and opposes the notion of gender equality and the related legislation on domestic violence, child custody, and alimony. One of her essays directly vilifies women; another is an open letter to Erdoğan to revoke related legislation. Mücahit Gültekin, a university professor and researcher at Afyon Kocatepe University Kadın ve Aile Araştırmaları Uygulama ve

Araştırma Merkezi, cites actors of anti-gender mobilization across the world and translates their ideas into Turkish context. What roles the recently established women and family studies centers at universities play with regards to emergence and proliferation of anti-gender politics in Turkey remains to be further investigated, given the importance of counter-knowledge production for the mobilization.

3.6. Religious communities or cults

One thorny issue in the case of Turkey that is not elaborately studied in the literature is the role Islamist cults play in pushing anti-gender and anti-feminist agendas forward. Except for Kütük Kuriş (2022) there is no hint of the extent to which they are central to anti-gender movements. Her study indicates that several such organizations have been at the forefront of advocacy against the Istanbul Convention. Their ideology is both anti-gender and anti-feminist. Perhaps because of the closed nature of these groups and the reluctance of feminist scholars to study them, the current literature does not cover the extent to which there has been a historically resilient anti-feminism and anti-genderism in Turkey around these cults. In that sense, the connections between organized religion and anti-gender mobilization needs to be further investigated.

4. Allies

Studies on anti-gender and anti-feminist politics in Turkey make a widespread case that this mobilization has emerged from the government and state bureaucracy in the past twenty years (Çavdar & Yaşar, 2019; Coşar, 2021; Eslen-Ziya & Bjørnholt, 2022; Günaydın, 2021; Güneş-Ayata & Doğangün, 2017; Kourou, 2021; Özkazanç, 2020). Therefore, the taxonomy that emerges from this literature runs against a frame which might separate the state and non-state actors and explore the possibility of the state institutions and political parties being allies, rather than actors, of the anti-gender and anti-feminist movement. Similarly, the sphere of organized religion involving both the Presidency of Religious Affairs and religious cults appears very much invested in the spread of anti-gender and anti-feminist politics. As Kandiyoti's (Kandiyoti, 1989, 2016) works indicate, religiously motivated political actors have long placed gender issues at the center of their discursive politics to mark their difference from rival political movements. Increasing polarization might have left little if no room for actors embedded in this network to calibrate their position vis-a-vis anti-gender and anti-feminist agenda in order not to become actors, but stay as allies to the mobilization.

5. Themes and agendas

Issues related to health & reproductive rights, LGBTQI+ rights and gender based violence are especially prominent in the advocacy conducted by anti-gender and anti-feminist mobilization, encompassing NGOs, men's rights groups and also state actors. In terms of the labor market, it is mainly the government and GONGOs that have been putting in place state policies that start with the assumption that women's primary role is care-giving in families. The situation regarding migration in Turkey is complex: Turkey currently hosts the largest number of refugees in the world and there is a general anti-immigrant sentiment on the rise (Ozduzen et al., 2021; Sert & Daniş, 2021). However, anti-gender and anti-feminist movements have not picked up on this as an issue as forcefully as the others. There are two other issues that have become especially important in Turkey: education and alimony rights.

These actors mobilize for what they call the natural order of things and Islamic way of life and blame many actors for the existing state of affairs. Feminists, LGBTQIs and women, whose aspirations are claimed to contradict with their “god-given” gendered natures and responsibilities are placed uppermost on anti-genderist’s list of foes. “Western forces” are seen as a major threat, including the EU and UN which are said to enforce legislations incompatible with the so called values of the country and to fund feminist and LGBTQI+ organizations. Furthermore, the increasingly radical voices distance themselves from even the AKP government and state institutions such as the Ministry of Family and Social Services claimed to be co-opted by feminists and GONGO’s like KADEM. Specific to the recent political events and the current polarization in the country the groups blamed also include the “traitors” who were part of the Gezi movement or the coup attempt of 2016.

The demands and solutions proposed include withdrawal from all international conventions including CEDAW, UN Beijing Declaration, and Istanbul Convention and repeal of all national legislation inspired by these. The codes specifically targeted include the Civil Code, Penal Code, and the domestic violence law no. 6284. They demand for bringing back the notion of head of household, encouraging housewifery for women, and allowing and encouraging underage marriages, removing alimony or adding time limit to alimony as well as joint custody. There are also demands for further familialization and Islamization of public policies; changing the education curriculum at all levels to remove gender equality related content and promoting gender segregation at universities. In fact, many of these actors broadly demand for rewriting all laws based on Islamic principles. These demands and solutions for the most part are justified with reference to arguments such as “human nature” and “Turkish culture” as well as the belief that “we should live in harmony with Islam.”

Authors note that these demands have started winning concessions in recent years. The president withdrew unilaterally from the Istanbul Convention (Altan-Olcay & Oder, 2021). The budget for the Presidency of Religious Affairs has exponentially increased in the last two decades and religious clerics have been authorized to perform civil marriage ceremonies (Adak, 2021). Feminist organizations are no longer part of deliberations for policy and law making (Coşar, 2021; Gülel, 2021). There are moves to institute gender segregation in higher education along with moves to change curricula to marginalize women and gender studies programs (Bilim Akademisi, 2019, 2020, 2021).

There is not much scholarship on the purchase of this advocacy at the general societal level. However, limited survey data show that the supporters of the withdrawal from the Istanbul Convention constituted a minority both before and after the President’s decision (KONDA, 2020; O’Neil & Çarkoğlu, 2022).

5.1. Labor market

While there is not much direct debate on the labor market among men’s rights groups and other radical actors, there is an extensive scholarship on the relevant policies of AKP in the past 20 years, which reveals certain striking features. One important piece of information to note in the Turkish case is that while the educational attainments are roughly equal among men and women, in the realm of labor force participation, women participate at half the rate of men, respectively 35,5% and 71,8% (Turkstat, 2022).

A variety of explanations are offered to explain how and why women’s labor force participation and employment remain consistently much lower than men and much lower than in countries with similar economic structures and sizes (Buğra & Özkan, 2012). One predominant explanation is the resolution

of the care crisis engendered by the neoliberal social contract through neoconservative discourses and policies, which normalize women's roles at home as caregivers and incentivize them to not join the labor force (Dedeoğlu, 2022; Ekiz Gökmen, 2022; Hülügü, 2021; Ilkkaracan et al., 2021a; İzdeş Terkoğlu & Memiş, 2022). Various policies enacted at the state level such as conditional cash transfer programs, payments to extended family members ("grandmother project") for taking care of children, promoting entrepreneurial activities to be conducted from home so as not to "disrupt" care giving "duties," training in areas where the job market is narrow to begin with and the creation of temporary jobs are analyzed as constituting the hegemonic assumption that women's place is at home (Çavdar & Yaşar, 2019; Gökşen et al., 2015; Telsereen, 2020).

In terms of advocacy to this end, we were able to find only discussions of KADEM as supportive of such policies. Çelebi (2022) points to KADEM's vision of promoting women's labor force participation while keeping intact the primacy of familial roles for women. Accordingly, in line with the essentialist notion of gender justice, KADEM advocates commodification and flexibilization of women's labor and supports state policies reinforcing women's primary role as caregiver and the family as the principal social policy institution.

5.2. Health & reproductive rights

Health & reproductive rights have been increasingly an issue for anti-gender mobilization in Turkey. This includes at its core the escalating attempts by the government to revise existing laws or change how laws are interpreted so that access to contraception and abortion is limited (Unal, 2019). The justification for these changes are to be found in discourses uttered frequently by the government elite emphasizing motherhood as the god-given role of women, how it is necessary to have three children per family in order to avoid demographic dangers facing the country, how family is the backbone of the country and the societal dangers posed by those who threaten the structure and sanctity of the family, i.e. feminists and LGBTQI actors (Akkan, 2018; Diner, 2018; Günaydın, 2021; Güneş-Ayata & Doğangün, 2017; Yazici, 2012).

Scholars note that it is important to see that these discourses are not isolated, individual speech acts and that they have actually been incrementally connected to various policy initiatives over the years, posing as solutions to these "dangers" (Korkut & Eslen-Ziya, 2016). For example, Telsereen (2020) describes the 2003 Turkey Reproductive Health Program, financed by the EU, launched in the first phase of AKP government, remarkable in its inclusion of married and single women and its addressing of not just safe motherhood and family planning but also sexually transmitted diseases. However, she also draws attention to the inclusion of an article through which family court judges can encourage couples to solve their problems amicably by seeking help from experts. Çavdar and Yaşar (2019) discuss the transformation of Mother-Child Health and Family Planning Clinics into Family Health Clinics in 2009 which resulted in the reduction of accessible contraception. Çavdar and Yaşar (2019) also discuss the history of anti-abortion policy making. Shortly after AKP came to power, they note the issuing of the 2002 communique that women will have to pay for their own abortions in public hospitals. Then, in 2007 a communique announced that the social security system will no longer reimburse for abortion related procedures. In addition, they discuss the 2014 regulation lowering the coefficient / score for abortion procedures and its intention to discourage doctors from performing the procedure. Finally, while abortion, technically, is still legal, the majority of the public hospitals, in practice, do not perform it (O'Neil et al., 2020).

5.3. Migration

So far, the literature on anti-gender and anti-feminist mobilization in Turkey has not identified migration as an issue area. This might be explained by the hegemonic position of the AKP government in anti-gender mobilization and its difference from European nationalist and conservative parties in terms of Sunni Muslim migrant-welcoming attitude mostly qualified with neo-colonialist aspirations and anti-Western and anti-EU discourses (Ozduzen et al., 2021; Sert & Daniş, 2021). Sert and Daniş (2021) show that the government purposefully avoided the crisis framing widely resonant in European contexts, and instead used the control frame, claiming the state has been powerful in migration management. Özdüzen et al. (2021) note recent securitization of Syrian migrants and increasing mob attacks against settled Syrians, though these are also not related to anti-gender mobilization.

5.4. LGBTQI+ rights

The withdrawal from the Istanbul Convention, one of the main objectives for anti-genderists in Turkey, is tied both to the issues of LGBTQI+ rights and of gendered violence (Eslen-Ziya, 2020, 2022; Kütük-Kuriş, 2022; Tabak et al., 2022). Scholars show how the anti-gender movement has been calling LGBTQI+ groups “abnormalities,” “perverts and constantly reproducing the frame “homosexuality as sin.” In fact, there have even been calls to expel gay individuals from the country (Özdüzen and Korkut 2020; Özkazanç 2019).

Scholars note that one result of this insistent advocacy has been the presidential withdrawal from the Istanbul Convention. Another result has been the banning of trans and LGBTQI Pride Parades (Savcı 2020 and Mutluer 2019). Mutluer (2019) delineates the increase in the popularity of and participation in the LGBTQI Pride Parade, which had been first organized with 30 participants in 2003, but witnessed numbers around 100,000 participants after Gezi in 2013. This is the moment that the members of the government party started becoming openly homophobic and the pride marches have been banned from 2015 onwards (Özbay 2022). When LGBTQI groups try to organize it, they are attacked by security forces (Mutluer 2019). Savcı 2020 adds that there is increasing violence against trans people by civilians who feel increasingly authorized to perform violence against marginalized groups purportedly on behalf of the state.

5.5. Gender-based violence

Legislation on gender-based violence is, yet again, a major issue area that was at the heart of the anti-feminist and anti-gender campaign for the Istanbul Convention, designed to provide a variety of measures to prevent domestic violence and protect the victims, and the repeal of 6284, instituted in the aftermath of joining the convention (Kütük-Kuriş, 2022; Özkazanç, 2019b). The arguments used in this campaign included the discourse of family dissolution, rising divorce rates, and men being victimized when they are restrained from the residence and so on. Hülagu (2021) and Eslen-Ziya (2022) shows that the campaign against the Istanbul Convention and the law 6284, argued not just that the convention and the law actually breaks up the family, but that it leads to more violence when men who are driven away from their homes, feel “frustrated” and kill their wives. To that end, the slogan Istanbul Sözleşmesi Öldürür (The Istanbul Sözleşmesi Kills) appropriated and reversed the feminist slogan İstanbul Sözleşmesi Yaşatır (The Istanbul Convention Saves Lives) (Eslen-Ziya 2022). As a result

of this campaign and the radical wing of AKP succeeding, the president withdrew from the Istanbul Convention in 2021.

Issues of gender based violence are not limited to temporally or thematically to the Convention. The literature notes the Presidency of Religious Affairs's increasing involvement in state-sanctioned activities related to domestic violence (Çavdar & Yaşar, 2019). Focusing on KADEM's campaign in this issue area, Akyüz and Sayan-Cengiz (2016) observe that the organization approaches violence as an individual problem of "anger management" and paradoxically glorifies men and masculine values while removing women's agency. There has been a set of larger slow-cooking anti-feminist demands on allowing underage marriage, including the 2016 legislative proposal to bring back the law that absolved a rapist of his crime if he married the victim and there was the consent of the child (Gülel, 2021). The government has justified this proposal with discourses of protecting the family and not victimizing children, who remain fatherless when the rapists go to jail (Unal, 2022). The bill was withdrawn when there was massive protest against it (Altan-Olcay & Oder, 2021; Ertan, 2020; Gülel, 2021).

5.6. Education

Education has long been a "battleground" between secular and Islamic actors in Turkey (Kandiyoti and Emanet 2017). Islamic actors have always demanded to shape the existing schooling system and curriculum along what they see as national and Islamic values, though only recently anti-gender elements came to fore in their agenda. Kandiyoti and Emanet (2017) and Tesleren (2020) explains how the AKP governments incorporated many demands of these actors in the education system leading to drastic changes in the national organization and rationale of education. Özkazanç (2019b) focuses on the Gender Equality Project, adopted by the Higher Education Council, with funding from the EU: when anti-feminists began vehemently attacking the project, several state institutions and KADEM chose to disavow their own years of activity under this banner. As a result, this project was removed from the Higher Education Council website and the president of the council explained the decision with the argument that the project went against social values and did not find widespread acceptance in society. Özkazanç (2020) mentions that there is not a comparable attack on women and gender studies centers at universities, though like Çağatay (2019), she notes that AKP's overall strategy of dismissing dissident academics and filling their posts with pro-government cadres has an effect on these research centers. Göker and Polatdemir (2022) draws attention to several recent developments at universities such as "familialisation of gender studies, politically charged appointments of people without expertise to gender studies centres, and sexual harassment units or the dismissal of existing experts" as threatening the achievements of pro-gender equality change actors. Göker and Polatdemir (2022) argue, however, that these achievements were context-specific and less than fully institutionalized. Insofar as the scholarship describes, reactions to such anti-gender developments are limited and lack sufficient planning for the future.

5.7. Divorce, child custody, and alimony

Yet another important area of contention for anti-feminist activists has been the legal stipulations that enforce in situations of divorce that marital property is equally divided and the ex-spouse with more economic capital pay alimony to the other. This legislation has been built on feminist advocacy that paid attention to the widespread economic vulnerability of women, most outside of the labor force

and even when they are in employment, their earning capacity is severely limited because of the largely temporary and low-quality job positions they hold (Anil et al., 2005; Marshall-Aldıkaçtı, 2013).

Men's rights activists and religious leaning newspapers and intellectuals have been attacking this legislation, especially since 2018 (Telseren 2020). The attackers argue that alimony payments make divorce more likely and therefore break up the sanctity of marriage (Hülagü, 2021; Ünal, 2021). The more radical discourses blame "evil" women of abusing alimony to divorce husbands, who are the "real victims" (Özcan, 2020; Özkazanç, 2020). Some right-wing writers also argue that the current legislation burdens the poor to take care of the poor and demand that the welfare state steps in (Özcan, 2020).

Several scholars observe policy shifts in line with these justifications. The Presidency of Religious Affairs has been intensely advising women to keep the family together by carrying out their "duties" as efficiently as possible while also discussing the "perils of divorce." (Çavdar & Yaşar, 2019). Telseren (2020) and Özar and Yakut Çakar (2013) discuss how women's marital status has been used as criteria for exclusion from social assistance schemes. Several authors refer to the report of the Divorce Commission which included a number of men's rights groups in its proceedings and finally proposed a series of reversals from previous profeminist changes in the Civil Code and Penal Code (Ayata & Candaş, 2018; Coşar, 2021; Kandiyoti, 2019). These proposals include limiting the restraining period in cases of domestic violence to 15 days, enforcing of negotiation and arbitration before divorce proceedings can start, a 5-year surveillance period for child abusers if the marriage is "unproblematic" and the introduction of theologians in family counseling services (Coşar, 2021). Özcan (2020) adds that the President's Executive Program published in August 2018 already recognized some of anti-alimony campaigners' demands.

6. Repertoires of action (strategies)

The writing on strategies used by anti-gender and anti-feminist groups can be categorized in three phases, all corresponding to the temporal centrality of one group of actors. In the first decade of AKP's rule, the government is seen as the central anti-feminist and anti-gender actor, utilizing a variety of policy making and cooptation strategies to normalize conservative gender norms. The widening of this maneuvering space is also due to women's GONGOs, which become an effective tool in sidelining actual, independent feminist mobilization while also enabling the government to charade as being inclusive of civil society organizations. These GONGOs specifically utilize strategies such as producing pseudoscientific knowledge and lobbying, attempting to displace and discredit knowledge production by and lobbying efforts of feminist activists and scholars. Finally, in the more recent years, as ultra-conservative groups gain a foothold, they have been more audacious in their uses of social media, especially in the form of campaigns and defamation campaigns against profeminist forces. They have also begun taking direct actions in the form of marches and street protests.

6.1. Government-led strategies: Hegemonic discourse production, policy making and cooptation

There is a hefty group of writing on discursive strategies used by the political leadership, especially the current president Erdoğan (Cindoglu & Unal, 2017; Gülel, 2021; Korkut & Eslen-Ziya, 2016). Feminist scholarship has emphasized the need to pay attention to these speech acts as constitutive of AKP's political regime rather than relegating them to being strategic maneuvers for drawing away attention from other pressing issues (Kandiyoti, 2016; Korkman, 2016). Erdoğan's speech acts on reproductive rights have found room in policy recommendations for incentivizing birthing three children, designing of financial incentives for early marriages and childbirth, practical inaccessibility of abortion in the public health system even though it is still legal, and the designing of social policies encouraging women to be stay-at-home caregivers (Korkman, 2016; Korkut & Eslen-Ziya, 2016).

A different kind of discussion on government strategies focuses on the realm of policy making. Coşar (2021) argues that the government has been utilizing a strategic move that gives the semblance of democratic and inclusive consultation in the preparation of new policies and laws, without actually going through with it. Accordingly, during the initial stages of law making, civil society organizations are invited for meetings and consultations. However, when the process moves forward, the progressive organizations are denied a voice in the final stages (Gülel, 2021). This way the policy makers can claim to have conducted democratic deliberation without actually listening to what feminist groups have to say. There is also the tactical move to sideline, from the beginning, the more vociferous, experienced organizations during these invitations.

A different take comes from Arat (2021) who argues that at different stages, AKP utilized varying strategies to ensure that the gender agenda served their own consolidation of power. Using Thelen's conceptualization of how existing institutions can be transformed, she has argued that in the initial stages, AKP did what she calls a purposeful neglect of laws. In this phase, the government did pass a number of progressive laws to appease secular segments of the society and international audiences. However, these laws were very much neglected in implementation, rendering them toothless. In the second phase, old laws were reinterpreted to new, more conservative ends. A third strategy Arat (2021) discusses is the establishment of pro-government organizations, which operate like NGOs but actually have organic connections with the government as exemplified in the case of KADEM.

6.2. Positioning as the "true" women's rights advocate

Both the government and its satellite organizations in the NGO field such as KADEM, position themselves as the true representatives of women in the country, arguing that what they advocate for is the real interests of women whereas feminist groups, alienated from the so-called authentic fabric of society, are framed as being clueless. For KADEM, this is to be found in a rights framework that is based on gender equity and justice in the family (Kütük-Kuriş, 2022; Tabak et al., 2022). For AKP, this is represented in the distribution of roles for the women's cadres of the party and Erdoğan's assumed protectiveness of women in AKP (Kourou, 2021).. For some men's rights groups, which actually, today, critique KADEM and AKP for being too lenient on feminist demands, it is again an argument that is based on protecting the family, ergo the women in the family (Özcan, 2020).

6.3. Lobbying

Literature especially studies KADEM's lobbying efforts. Çelebi (2022), for instance, identifies KADEM's four interlinked strategies. These are direct engagement in domestic policy making processes, the construction and utilization of solid institutional and personal links with the government, expertise and advocacy work, and international agenda setting and representation. All of these point to organic links between the government and KADEM but they also show the organization's positioning as an "insider" which could continue claiming to lobby on behalf of women of the country (Ehrhart, 2022; Ertan, 2020).

Other lobbying strategies include organizing hybrid conferences merging state and non-state actors, bringing together likeminded people to have influence policy making and producing policy documents in which organizational aims are framed as solutions to existing issues. Günaydın (2021) gives the examples of International Family Institute and Human Rights and Equality Institution of Turkey (TİHEK), and discusses how the former drafted a Family Convention as an alternative to international conventions as early as 2016 and the latter appropriated men's rights groups' discourses while positioning itself as a supposedly autonomous human rights body (Günaydın, 2021).

6.4. Production of knowledge

The anti-gender groups have been participating in and organizing a number of conferences with frequent support from and under the sponsorship of state institutions (Günaydın, 2021). Packaged as "scientific gatherings," these international conferences are clearly motivated to impact knowledge production on gender. The scholarship proposes that the outcome of this knowledge production is disseminated in three different ways. These include a bombardment of newspaper columns by op-ed writers linked with these groups, publication of journals where "scientific arguments" are served to a wider academic community, and state strategies to transform existing gender centers in higher institutions of education (Kütük-Kuriş, 2022).

In the area of knowledge production, KADEM has been a leading force for the most part of the 2000s. Eslen-Ziya (2020), for instance, offers the concept of troll science to characterize anti-genderists' production of knowledge through the case of KADEM's journal. She defines troll science as something "based on (distorted) scientific arguments molded into populist discourse, creating an alternative narrative on the conceptions of gender equality." In her view, the concept of pseudoscience does not exactly equate with troll science since speedy distribution, echoing and intensification of emotions are also important attributes of troll science.

State strategies on this front might have a drastic impact on the organization of knowledge production. Some scholars argue that the Turkish case is different from its counterparts in places such as Hungary, where gender studies as an academic discipline is being targeted directly. This argument is based on the observation that gender departments and programs have been for the most part left alone in Turkey (Çağatay, 2019). However, there are still important signals to be taken into consideration pertaining especially to public institutions of higher education. In 2019, after right-wing newspapers began a campaign, the Higher Education Council removed its Gender Equality Position Paper from its website. The president of the Council used the justification that the paper citing "gender equality" went against social values and did not find widespread acceptance in society (Bilim Akademisi, 2019; Göker & Polatdemir, 2022; Hülügü, 2021). He went on to proclaim that women's studies classes would be now organized through the principle of gender equity/justice instead of

gender equality (Özkazanç 2019). Feminist scholars, who advocated openly against the government, have been targeted, some removed from their positions in public universities. In fact, in one case because of this targeted firing of faculty, one of the oldest graduate programs in the country had to stop recruiting new students (Özüğurlu & Dayan, 2020). There are also reports of women and gender studies centers renamed as women and family studies (Özüğurlu & Dayan, 2020).

6.5. Defamation campaigns in social media

Starting mid-2010's with the establishment of more radical anti-feminist, anti-gender organizations, scholars note the more intense use of social media (especially Twitter) to lobby against feminist achievements in the policy realm, including those against the signing of international conventions, to organize defamation campaigns targeting specific individuals and organizations, and to produce discourses that attempt to normalize gender based violence. Özcan (2020) quantifies this intensified use with the examples of The Platform for Divorced People and the Family, which launched its Twitter page in April 2018, and the Platform for the Victims of Unlimited Alimony which launched its page in October 2018. She shows how both platforms aggressively tweeted since their inception, with the Platform for Divorced People tweeting on average 472 times per month and the Platform for the Victims of Unlimited Alimony tweeting on average 637 times per month (both figures until February 2020). This means, together, 36 tweets from two sites (including retweets) per day (Özcan, 2020). Eslen-Ziya (2022) offers the concept of "networked misogyny" whose effects/power exceed the boundaries of the digital space, negatively impacting not just mainstream gender politics but women's lives in the everyday.

Some scholars study the discursive frames used in social media campaigns and identify two distinct strategies on this front. Ünal (2021) identifies a performative rhetoric, which relies on polarization and stereotypes, building on and perpetuating existing antagonisms across the political spectrum. Özdüzen and Korkut (2020) show how, in this manner, social media can effectively catapult mundane, everyday, private, ordinary events to the realm of the political confrontation between anti-feminist/anti-gender actors and their adversaries. In this polarized language, issues are framed in terms of an antagonistic confrontation between the so called "Turkish-Islamic way of life" versus "the Westernized," "perverted," "foreign" life styles, "domestic, culturally authentic and national" citizens versus "Geziciler, çapulcular," "traitors and the coup-supporters" (Ozdüzen & Korkut, 2020; Ünal, 2021). Defamation campaigns against organizations working against gender based violence, for instance, called one prominent feminist organization, Mor Çatı, an enemy of the family (Hülagü, 2021). A second, integral strategy is the inflammatory language used in the attacks and lynch campaigns. Özdüzen and Korkut (2020) also show that anti-genderists use strong words - e.g. "disgusting" "imbecile" - and express their ideas in an emotional tone imbued with hatred, especially in campaigns against LGBTQI groups, whereas pro-genderists mostly express their advocacy with words signifying feelings of solidarity.

One campaign that stands out in the studies is the campaign initiated in 2019 against the Istanbul Convention to pressure the government to withdraw Turkey's signature. Kütük-Kuriş (2022) delineates this campaign and discusses the use of a combination newspaper columns, petitions, Youtube videos, street protests, and social media. She discusses how the coalition expanded with the visible support of radical Islamist groups. The polarized language aforementioned was taken to a new level with a right-wing writer calling supporters of the convention "prostitutes." Kütük-Kuriş (2022) also delineates

the ways in which these actors began a concerted attack against KADEM, a pro-government women's GONGO, for supporting the Convention and how this attack against an unlikely, intra-group opponent both signified their growing strength and increased it.

6.6. Direct action

Anti genderists recently embraced a more traditional social movement repertoire that is direct action, gathering its supporters in city centers or in front of mosques following Friday prayers on and around specific days such as March 8th and Pride weeks (Çağatay et al., 2022; Özkazanç, 2019b). Çağatay et al. (2022) point to the use of fundamentalist hymns and sometimes small arms in these actions. Since this is a relatively new repertoire adopted by anti-genderist mobilization, the literature lacks detailed analysis.

7. Frames of arguments

Several discourses, frames of reference utilized by anti-feminist and anti-gender groups, are discussed in the existing scholarship. A significant portion of the literature examines the ways in which various issues (abortion, divorce & alimony payments, Istanbul convention, demands for gender equality) are framed as threats to the "traditional family," how they victimize various categories of people (men, children, women and men who got married underage), how the term gender and LGBTQI is against nature, how these identity categories, gender equality demands as well as the rights based language are "Western" concepts that threaten "our national culture." Studies also focus on enmity produced on particular actors: feminists, human rights activists, and also moderate Islamist actors.

7.1. Threatening the family

A prominent frame used against gender equality agendas is the argument that they threaten the family. Hülagu (2021) and Eslen-Ziya (2022) show that in the campaign against the Istanbul Convention and the national domestic violence act no. 6284, anti-genderists/anti-feminists argued that both break up the family and lead to more violence against women, rather than vice versa. Hülagü (2021) also shows that a similar discourse appears when challenging the articles of the Penal Code regulating sexual abuse of children and advocating for "marriage exemption" to commute the sentences of sexual perpetrators: the so-called reason being "thousands of families" suffer because "the fathers are in jail" and "the mothers have to raise their children alone."

Anti-alimony campaigners also use a similar framing. The legal requirement of alimony, according to these discourses, threatens the family because men, who are "unjustly condemned to pay alimonies in perpetuity" are frustrated and end up killing ex-wives and committing suicides or cannot marry a second time because of the financial burden they are under (Hülagü, 2021, p. 36).

7.2. "It's not natural"

Frames of biology and nature prominently figure out in homophobic discourses emerging from anti-gender politics. Özkazanç (2019b) points to the writings of Mücahit Gültekin who claims that "gender ideology seeks to artificially alter the God-given sex differences." According to Özkazanç (2019b),

Gültekin regards women who advocate for gender equality and LGBTQI as “hedonistic and bodily creatures,” and likens them to robots because they are “as much alien and a threat to humanity.” This is not an isolated frame, several authors discuss how anti-gender and anti-feminist mobilizations makes constant references to the religious term “fitrat” depicting biological and divine destiny to refute the conception of gender as an insidious political construct and to depict LGBTQI as an “abnormality” and “sin” (Eslen-Ziya & Bjørnholt, 2022; Ozduzen & Korkut, 2020; Savcı, 2020; Tabak et al., 2022).

7.3. “The West” threatening the “Turkish & Islamic culture”

Yet another frame pits the so-called West, Western norms and Westernized human rights advocacy against the so-called Turkish culture and Islamic way of life. This narrative draws from both Ottomanist and nationalist rhetoric, a discursive frame that is widely recognized.

According to this frame, Istanbul Convention can be depicted as un-Islamic, a “Western-import,” a “Soros project to erase the differences between sexes” (Kütük-Kuriş, 2022). Other relevant frames include those that resemble the Istanbul Convention and CEDAW to Crusades and the Istanbul Convention to a Trojan Horse, both intending to destroy the Turkish Muslim society and introducing LGBTQI rights through the backdoor (Eslen-Ziya, 2020; Ünal, 2021). It is argued that such conventions are promoted as universal rights but are actually based on Western women’s experiences, and operate as global impositions on local cultures.

There is abundant evidence that similar frames are used not just for these conventions but for concepts such as gender and gender equality, as well. In many, these concepts are seen as incompatible with the so-called Turkish culture and norms (Eslen-Ziya, 2022) and not being culturally and nationally authentic enough (Kandiyoti, 2022). Özkazanç (2019b) discusses how right wing authors such as Gültekin describes concepts such as “gender equality, human rights, women’s rights, children’s rights and even animal rights” seemingly innocent but are, in reality, treacherous because they signify “the West’s intentions” to “reformat” or “hack” Turkish society.

Interestingly, this discussion of cultural authenticity turns into a confrontational debate within right wing groups, as well. On the one hand is KADEM, whose entire existence is based on promoting the concept of gender equity/justice as more culturally appropriate for Turkey than gender equality (Çağatay, 2019; Kütük-Kuriş, 2022; Tabak et al., 2022). For example, as Eslen-Ziya (2020) shows, there are discussions in KADEM’s journal defining feminism as belonging to the West and, therefore, not compatible with “the Turkish culture.” On the other hand are the radical voices, who also argue that gender equity/justice framing is a smokescreen for gender equality. Radical right wing writers, such as Abdurrahman Dilipak go as far as to accuse KADEM members as becoming “slaves to the feminist ideology” (Tabak et al., 2022).

7.4. The “real victims,” their “human rights” and “the real villains”

Scholars note that there is an escalating use of the language of victimhood, the rights of men and children as opposed to women in anti-gender/anti-feminist campaigns targeting laws pertaining to domestic violence, sexual violence against children, marriage and alimony. In these discourses, the real villains are varied, but the victims are men, children, the family and so on.

Özkazanç (2019a) show how anti-Pride Parade campaign actors blamed not only CHP, the secular opposition party, for their support of the parades but also the AKP government, specifically the related ministry, and KADEM for paving the way for tolerance to “gay perversity.” Anti-gender actors have been especially vehemently attacking KADEM for “worshiping women” and “doing cruelty to men” through the laws on alimony, child custody, and domestic violence (Özkazanç, 2019a). Women’s organizations such as Mor Çatı, who advocate for the rights of domestic violence survivors, are seen as “enemies of the family” along with foreigners from “Brussels” who fund them. These actors construct a “we” who is not going to “let the enemies of the family win.” One writer goes as far as to say that feminists “are worse than terrorists” (Ünal, 2021).

Many studies note how anti-feminists frame men as victims of feminist policies and position themselves as the protector of the rights of these “real victims” (Eslen-Ziya & Bjørnholt, 2022; Hülägü, 2021; Özcan, 2020; Özkazanç, 2019b; Ünal, 2021). Feminists are also the enemies because they “teach women how to lie” and how to abuse the principle of “women’s testimony is fundamental.” This discourse builds on discourses of the 1990s and 2000s, in which more fringe voices were already growing hostile against feminists, always denigrated as women who don’t know motherhood, considered dangerous, creating conflict between women and men, demanding unconditional freedom and damaging the fabric of the family (Coşar & Yeğenoğlu, 2011). The anti-feminist groups then give themselves the role of acting on behalf of the “male victims who cannot make their voices heard as much as the voice of the rich feminist organizations is heard” (Hülägü, 2021, p. 34). In these discourses, for instance those deployed by some of the radical right wing newspapers such as Yeni Şafak, poor men and their second wives are pitted against “privileged” feminists, who, because of their class origins, cannot claim to represent the category of women in Turkey (Özcan, 2020). Feminists are also seen as guilty of hypocrisy because they purportedly advocate flirting among thirteen-year olds but oppose underage marriage, thereby victimizing “youngsters whose only fault is to ask for an official marriage instead of flirting” (Hülägü, 2021, p. 36).

Anti-alimony campaigners also frame “widows who receive alimony payments ... as unjustly enriched women whose class status unfairly augments” as a result of these payments. Özkazanç (2019a) shows how the same authors accuse women for being guilty of the dissolution of the family. Women are depicted, for instance in the writings of one op-ed writer Sema Maraşlı, as “abusive, heartless, money grubbers, greedy, insatiable, demanding, shameless, impudent, unscrupulous and as liars” and men as “frightened, manipulated, abused, dominated and punished as well as their money and sources are sponged off.” Men are not the only victims, either: the second wives, the mothers and sisters of husbands who have to help with alimony payments so that their sons / brothers do not end up in jail are also framed as unjustly victimized groups. Özcan (2020) argues that these discourses also increasingly draw on a rights based language, reinterpreting human rights as the “rights of divorced humans,” claiming their advocacy benefits everyone.

8. Transnational connections

The literature on transnational connections of anti-gender and anti-feminist activists in Turkey is more or less confined to the discussion of some examples in articles on other aspects of the movement. These examples and the claims made around them can be grouped into two. First, there is a discussion of broad ideological agreements even though there are no explicit institutional or actor based links and the argument is that beyond the shared world view of conservatism, Islamist rejectionists in

Turkey are developing an independent advocacy (Tabak et al., 2022). Yet this shared world view, scholars also show, has resulted in the borrowing of multiple ideas, frames and examples, over the years, from anti-gender and anti-feminist movements elsewhere. Second, there is some reference to the organization of and participation in international family conferences as venues in which connections are established.

Özkazañç (2019b) observes that from February 2019 onwards, anti-gender intellectuals started to adopt some ideas from Western anti-gender movements. This new anti-gender narrative in Turkey is anti-Western, and yet, ironically it borrows from and translates the discourses of its Western counterparts, directly (Çağatay, 2019; Özkazañç, 2019b). At the core of these ideas is the attack on the concept of gender with the argument that not only is it un-scientific but it is also dangerous because it intends to erase divine and biologically-proven differences between sexes and that if adopted, there will come a post-human age in which the family no longer exists and societies are hacked with genetic engineering and surveillance technologies (Özkazañç, 2019b). The slogans the Turkish Family Assembly put into circulation to protest March 08, 2019 included “stop the global war on the family,” “the terrorism of gender equality,” and “homosexuality is a crime against humanity,” previously used by anti-genderists in several European countries (Eslen-Ziya, 2020). Eslen and Bjornholt (2022) also notes how Turkish anti-genderist adopted a video, originally made for Vladimir Putin’s political campaign, and circulated it with Turkish subtitles: The video depicts the adoption of a young boy in a Russian orphanage by a gay family to his and the orphanage employees’ disappointment. This video was shared widely on Twitter with Turkish subtitles and the text and hashtag: “is this the family you want to be? #Istanbulconventionistreachery.”

Another clear strategy adopted not just by the anti-gender and anti-feminist mobilizers but also the government, in the aftermath of the presidential withdrawal from the Istanbul Convention, was to give examples from EU countries which had not ratified the Istanbul Convention. Frequently, the government officers explained that Turkey was not the only country who was concerned and that Poland was also likely to leave the Convention, with the argument that the LGBTQI community was imposing their ideas about gender on the entire society (Eslen-Ziya, 2022).

One final discussion is about the role conferences on families play in transnationalizing anti-gender mobilization. Günaydın (2021) suggests that these conferences constitute the largest gatherings of anti-genderists passing beyond national borders. As a result, she suggests, frames such as “natural family” as composed of one man and one woman, constructed by The World Congress of Families, are shared and travel through these conferences, and end up translated into the Turkish context.

9. Explanation

Explanations for the rise of anti-gender and anti-feminist backlash in Turkey can be summarized in terms of which actors are the focus of the analysis and the positioning of the causes with respect to domestic or international factors. Most authors agree that it is a combination of domestic and international political and economic factors that explain the rise of radical conservative factions with anti-feminist and anti-gender agendas. Most also agree that understanding the very recent development of men’s rights groups requires an analysis of political shifts that happened in the last two decades during AKP’s governmental rule. Thus it is apt to start the categorization of the existing analyses with the AKP and study how the political field changed under its rule in the last 20 years, paving the way to more vocal anti-gender and anti-feminist alliances in the last few years.

Actors	Causal factors	Causal factors
AKP, the government and state bureaucracy	Domestic politics	International politics
men's rights groups, religious cults, radical Islamic intellectuals	Domestic politics	International politics

9.1. Government Ideology

Many scholars argue that while AKP was moderate in its early period, as it consolidated its power, it has become more radical and conservative. During the first decade of the 2000s, AKP was in power when a number of important feminist achievements marked legal changes in Turkey, including the signing of the Istanbul Convention. However, even during this period, scholars argue that various policy and discursive moves showed the limitations of the legal changes. Arat (2021), for instance, argues that there have been three stages in AKP's rule, roughly corresponding to the different ways in which women's rights issues have been utilized to consolidate power. These stages, she argues, have gone hand in hand with democratic backsliding. Accordingly, in the first stage, even though a number of progressive laws were passed, these laws were purposefully neglected in implementation. In the second stage, existing laws were reinterpreted in ways that not only emptied out their progressive content but actually coopted them in service of normalizing conservative gender norms. Finally, the civil society realm was transformed by the active displacement of existing women's and feminist NGOs through newly established GONGOs (Arat, 2021).

Similarly, other authors show how existing seemingly progressive policies as well as rights-based discourses have been strategically used to cement a conservative understanding of women's places and roles in society (Gökşen et al., 2015; Alniacik et al. 2017; Özkazanç, 2020). Several scholars point to how a neoconservative, familial understanding of women, their so-called biological destiny as mothers, wives and primary caregivers fit well with a neoliberal state, whose welfare policies leave much to be desired in terms of public care provisioning and is unable to produce sufficient and decent jobs (Acar & Altunok, 2013; Bugra, 2014; Candas & Silier, 2014; Coşar & Yeğenoğlu, 2011; Dedeoğlu & Elveren, 2015; Ilkcaracan et al., 2021b). In other words, these explanations of growing gender conservatism in the country focus on the ideological roots of the political leadership in AKP as well as the "marriage of convenience" between neoconservatism and neoliberalism in Turkey (Kandiyoti, 2016).

9.2. Intra-conservative bloc power competitions

Other scholars argue that AKP has never been a monolithic bloc and that its history is shaped by a continuous competition between more moderate and more radical Islamist groups inside. Tabak et al. (2022a), for instance, argue that during the first decade of AKP, the more moderate wing of the party that coalesced in and around KADEM acted as a norm localizer. Accordingly the conservative norm localizers have appropriated the concept of gender and the norm of gender equality, reconstructed these in line with the conservative Islamic norms through the concept of gender equity/justice (Tabak

et al., 2022). Within the confines of gender equity advocacy, KADEM and others in the party promoted policies to prevent violence against women, advocated for the signing of the Istanbul Convention, designed policy and program tools to support women's entrepreneurship and flexible labor force participation (so as to not prevent their work as housewives), while discursively positioning themselves against feminists (Çelebi, 2022). KADEM's authoritative say on gender discussions within the conservative bloc was short lived, coming to end in the mid 2010s (Tabak et al., 2022, Kütük-Kuriş 2022). Accordingly, the studies looking at intra conservative group debate indicate that anti-feminism and anti-genderism has always existed within this bloc. Through a combination of domestic and international factors, they have begun to ascend to power and have become more vocal, more recently.

9.3. Domestic electoral calculations

Domestically, one factor that is important in explaining AKP's growing hegemony is the successive electoral victories (Gumuscu, 2013). However, when Turkey shifted to a presidential system through a narrowly won plebiscite in 2018, scholars have also pointed to a new role electoral calculations played in the radicalization of the party. Kütük-Kuriş (2022) argues that as the party became more authoritarian over time, it began losing its support among liberal and Muslim democrat voters, who also did not support the shift to a presidential system. Since, in this new system, a party needs more than 50% to maintain power, AKP had to seek new supporters and partners. This has resulted in its current alliance with the Nationalist Action Party, the ultranationalist party, as well as attempts to keep the Muslim conservative political base together. This is the political backdrop against which the radical wing of the party, which Tabak et al. (2022) call norm rejectionists, began increasing their voice and power. In fact, the definitive shift from the norm localizers to norm rejectionists happened when the latter found it possible to attack KADEM despite its apparent power in the political system (Kütük-Kuriş 2022).

9.4. Economic crisis

There is also the crisis-imbued political economic backdrop: Hülügü (2021) explains the state-led intensification of anti-feminist campaigns in terms of the government attempts to resolve the escalating economic crisis, threatening both the neoliberal social contract and the patriarchal gender contract. The author says, this is an attempt to buy time in the face of a state and economic crisis in the country.

9.5. EU accession process (and its lack thereof)

On the international front, the European Union accession process was sidelined after 2013. The scholarship emphasizes that this meant progressive forces lost an important anchor through which they pressured the government for change. With the accession process hitting the breaks, the idea of the EU as a role model for democracy and gender equality has become less credible (Aybars et al., 2019). As a result, Scotti and Roma (2021) argue that the will for harmonization has slowed down after 2013 and the rift between existing laws and implementation has widened. In this sense, Cindoğlu and Ünal (2017) and Uğur-Çınar (2017) argue that as undemocratic elements of the regime gained power,

neopatrimonialism and/or unprecedented proliferation of discourses of sexuality and women's bodies has become more widespread.

9.6. The rise of ultra-conservative voices outside of AKP, but connected to it

In this context of electoral calculations, de-democratization, socio-economic crisis and the radicalization of government discourse, orthodox Islamist groups have found an expanded power to voice anti-feminist and anti-gender agendas. In this process, newspapers such as *Yeni Akit*, *Milli Gazete*, *Yeni Şafak* rallied the campaign against the so-called vulnerabilities created by "feminist" state policies (Hülagü, 2021). As the government moved toward authoritarianism and the anti-democratic public space widened, demands for a naturalist gender order, a roll back in national progressive legislations and withdrawing from international treaties have become normalized (Kandiyoti, 2022; Ünal, 2021). Thus as Eslen-Ziya and Bjørnholt (2022) argue, the state's anti-feminist politics has galvanized anti-gender mobilization rather than vice versa.

This is a new phase in which anti-gender and anti-feminist actors demand a "masculinist restoration" (Ünal, 2021). These actors problematize "the crisis" of hegemonic masculinity, demand the restoration of the traditional gender order all in the meanwhile also normalizing violence in the everyday (Kandiyoti 2016). This normalization of violence also fits with the agenda of a government that might need it for continuing its grip on power (Alniacik, 2021).

9.7. International connections

How the recent rise of anti-gender/anti-feminist mobilization in the world impacted the Turkish scene and emboldened grassroots organizing in this line is yet to be studied in this literature. Available research implies an ironic influence. Turkish anti-gender movement brings together elements from Islamic and ultranationalist discourses, utilizes an anticolonial rhetoric and a condemnation of human rights discourses (Özkazanç 2020). The ironical international connection here is the discursive affinity of this idea with a critical knowledge production in the West on imperialism and on the hegemony of Western institutions of governance, which produce tremendous conundrums and dangers for rights activists in countries like Turkey precisely because they can more easily be accused of being "foreign compradors." (Altan-Olcay, 2015, 2022; Altan-Olcay & Oder, 2021; Kandiyoti, 2016).

10. Counter-movements

Feminist activism, along with human rights groups, a variety of progressive NGOs, advocates of secularism have been long positioned as counter-movements to the government and these rising anti-gender and anti-feminist mobilizations. These are discussed in detail in the WP2 literature review. For purposes of summary, it can be said that as these radical voices began to be heard more in the government, this is also the period feminist advocacy has been less able to participate in policy making deliberations. Feminist groups have disengaged from the state, as the state became the main anti-gender and anti-feminist actor. Most feminists are now organizing at the grassroots level, trying to establish sustainable alliances across different organizations and groups, building coalitions and platforms to resist on an issue based manner. In the meanwhile, they engage in extensive knowledge production to monitor - state institutions, document and publicize abuse of women's and LGBTQI

rights. As they try to find ways to resist, they have to also find ways of not risking state wrath and repression. At this stage, for feminist movements the goal is to sustain movement achievements rather than advocating for new state reforms, to establish alliances with parallel social movements and other oppositional groups.

11. Other important issues

There is much discussion about the peculiarity of the Turkish case. Most important discussion in this respect is on the question whether gender acts as a symbolic glue in Turkey. On the one hand, authors like Özkazanç (2020) argue that this is not the case. In her view, the symbolic glue that brings together ultra-nationalists and Islamists is a discourse that draws on a combination of Islamo-Turkist ideology and borrows from anti-colonial discourses to propagate the idea that human rights is a Western colonial project (Özkazanç, 2020). She goes on to argue that gender can be the very Achilles' heel for the government and its right wing ideology. This is the case because there is widespread societal reaction to domestic violence and child victims in violent homes and/or public institutions. On the other hand, scholars like Kandiyoti (2016) do find that the AKP rule has very much centralized politics of gender in its polarizing strategy, developed to stay in power and to keep a variety of blocs in right wing mobilization together.

12. Conclusion

The scholarship on anti-gender movements in Turkey is a relatively new field, extending from the feminist scholarship documenting, critiquing and theorizing the growing conservatism of the government in the last two decades. In this sense, one important finding emerging from the Turkish case is that the government has been the "original" anti-feminist and anti-gender actor, encouraging and legitimizing other radical conservative groups that have joined in the scene more recently.

Another important finding pertains to the intra-conservative bloc competitions and the ways in which the scholarship is at odds with one another on how to locate especially some GONGOs. These GONGOs have historically worked to discredit gender and gender equality and to replace it with concepts such as gender equity / justice, based on the idea of divine and biological destinies of sexes while advocating against violence against women. In recent years, ironically they, themselves, are targets of more radical factions, who argue that gender equity is a smokescreen for gender equality and that their work against violence against women threatens the family. The literature's chronological discussion reveals that we are at a moment in time when radical factions are emboldened and these groups have begun winning concessions, which would have been unimaginable ten years ago. There is not much written on some of the driving forces among these groups such as religious cults because they are harder to access and others, precisely because of their apparent will to defame anyone.

The main issues that stand out in the Turkish case include the following. First, there is the mobilization against Turkey's participation in international conventions. Anti-gender actors oppose these conventions because they frame them as Western imports, threats to the "Turkish and Islamic culture," Trojan horses through which LGBTQI rights and non-heterosexual families will be normalized and elite projects with little purchase at the level of society will become the law. Ironically, as they do that, they repeat, in some cases verbatim, discourses produced by their counterparts in the West. There is a need for studying these transnational connections and their extent.

This advocacy is integral to the main focus of the movement: health & reproductive rights, LGBTQI+ rights and gender based violence. A discourse of familialism and tradition disparages not only non-heterosexual families and LGBTQI rights in general, but also propagates against policies that take measures against domestic violence and enable access to abortion.

Additional issue areas, specific to Turkey include attacks against legislation that protects alimony rights in cases of divorce and bans underage marriages. In the past couple of years, child sexual abuse especially in religious cults has been repeatedly making the news, with right wing state actors reluctant to take action against perpetrators (often high rank members of such groups) unless there is tremendous social pressure. This is a relatively new phenomenon which requires research. We can also add to this list emboldened demands for further familialization and Islamization of public policies; rewriting laws based on Islamic principles; changing the education curriculum at all levels to remove gender equality related content and promoting gender segregation at universities. These demands and solutions always connect to discourses of “the natural order of things,” “Turkish culture,” “Islamic culture,” and so on.

Broadly these actors, depending on their positionality, use a combination of repertoire of action. If in the government, they are engaged in hegemonic discourse production and ultra-conservative law and policy making. If they are officially outside of the government, they use a combination of lobbying, knowledge production, social media defamation campaigns and more recently direct action. In terms of framing, there are various frames used, some try to position themselves as the true representatives of the society (or women or men). Most home in on discourses of threat (to the family, to “Turkish - Islamic” culture and so on), the threat coming from “the West,” “Western compradors,” “Turkish liberals,” etc.

More recent developments such as direct action by these groups, the organization of simultaneous street protests across Turkey “to protect the family,” the recent move by the government to change the constitution to define the family explicitly in heterosexual terms and introduce new wording on veiling, which risks protecting the rights of veiled women but not others, rising cases of child sexual abuse have not made their way into scholarship yet.

There is also little writing that indicates labor market and migration as issue areas taken up by these groups. In terms of the labor market, the government and GONGOs have been relentlessly producing discourses and policies that lock women in unpaid care-giving roles in families. In terms of migration, there is an anti-immigrant sentiment on the rise but there is little indication that anti-gender and anti-feminist movements see this as an issue area.

All in all, more research is needed into the ways in which this radicalization is happening, how much purchase they have at the societal level, how they engage with feminist actors and how they impact them, and what intra-conservative bloc competitions are. As the movement is gaining momentum as we write this, we will need to follow its trajectory carefully.

13. Timeline

- 20.07.2010 Then the Prime Minister Erdoğan's voicing of his disbelief in equality between men and women.
- 11.05.2011 Istanbul Convention's opening for signature in Turkey, the country becoming the first signatory.
- 03.06.2011 Dropping the word women from the related state ministry and its restructuring as the Ministry of Family and Social Policies.
- 08.03.2012 Enactment of national domestic violence and violence against women legislation no. 6284.
- 25.05.2012 Then the Prime Minister Erdoğan's likening of abortion to massacre, the takeoff moment of the governments' anti-abortion and C-sections birth campaign.
- 08.06.2012 The start of the profeminist campaign against the proposed abortion ban.
- 04.07.2012 Enactment of law no 6354 that restricts cesarean delivery to medical reasons.
- January 2013 Attempts to criminalize abortion are withdrawn.
- 08.03.2013 KADEM was established.
- 28.05.2013-16.06.2013 Gezi protests gathering people belonging to different democratic struggles; feminists' and LGBTQI activists' solidifying of relations with parallel social movements and oppositional actors.
- 07.06.2015 National elections which disqualified AKP to form government on its own and electoral victory of HDP, pro-Kurdish party, bringing expressly feminist M.P.s to the parliament.
- 28.06.2015 Banning of annual Pride Parade using the religious sensitivities frame and police intervention against activists consisting of a number of M.P.s from oppositional political parties.
- 01.11.2015 Repeat national elections in which AKP won 49.5% of votes, enabling the party to form its own government.
- 20.07.2016 The beginning of a two-years long state of emergency regime, escalating state pressure on feminist activists and organizations.
- 16.11.2016 "Marry your rapist bill" presented to the parliament and withdrawn due to tremendous feminist mobilization.
- 18.10.2017- The enactment of the "Mufti bill" which authorized religious clerics to perform civil marriage ceremonies.
- January 2019 Anti-gender campaign against the Gender Equality Project (2014-2016) implemented by the Ministry of Education succeeds; the content is removed from the Ministry's website.
- February 2019 Anti-gender campaign against the Gender Equality Position Paper of the Higher Education Council succeeds; the Council annuals the paper.

- 08.03.2019 Turkish Family Assembly calls for demonstration against March 8th, International Women's Day in Friday prayers.
- 08.03.2019 Open letter of the head of Turkish Family Assembly to the Minister of Family, attacking KADEM.
- 08.03.2019 Banning of the Feminist Night March and police intervention against thousands of women gathered in the city center.
- 09.03.2019 News accusing feminist activists of booing ezan in the night march circulates; the President backs up this news in election rallies.
- 31.03.2019 Opposition's victory in local elections in major cities, followed by Istanbul results canceled.
- 01.06.2019 The president says that the Istanbul Convention is not nass, equivalent to divine decree, in the iftar organized by National Will Platform.
- 23.06.2019 CHP-led opposition wins Istanbul mayorship in repeated local elections.
- 29.06.2019 More than 30 CHP-run local municipalities show solidarity with Pride Parade on Twitter using #Pride2019.
- 05.07.2019 Diyanet's hutbe announced at the friday sermon damns homosexuality.
- July 2019 Anti-gender/anti-feminist campaign against the Istanbul Convention, targeting KADEM as well.
- 24.04.2020 Diyanet's hutbe announced at the friday sermon damns homosexuality; connects HIV and Coronavirus.
- Summer 2020 Anti-gender/anti-feminist campaign against the Istanbul Convention finds support among many leading AKP figures.
- 19.03.2021 President Erdoğan issues a decree stating Turkey's withdrawal from the Istanbul Convention and on 1 July 2021, pulled out of Istanbul Convention.

14. List of the anti-gender and anti-feminist organizations and initiatives

Name of the organization (original)	Name of the organization (English)	Anti-gender or anti-feminist?	Logo of the organization	Head of the organization (in the period 2010-2021)	Web-page (social media)	Size of the organization (if available)	Comment (brief description)
Türkiye Aile Meclisi	Turkey Family Council	Anti-gender/Anti-feminist		Adem Çevik	Twitter: https://twitter.com/ailemeclisiorg	n/a	An anti-gender/anti-feminist organization that became visible during 2019 campaigns against the Feminist Night March and the Istanbul Convention.
Boşanmış Babalar Platformu	Divorced Fathers Platform	Anti-feminist		Necil Beykont	FB: https://www.facebook.com/people/Bo%C5%9Fanm%C4%B1%C5%9F-Babalar-Platformu/100032095041629/	n/a	A men's rights organization campaigning against gender-based violence and alimony legislation.

Boşanmış İnsanlar ve Aile Platformu	Divorced People and Family Platform	Anti-gender/anti-feminist		İlknur Birsel	Twitter: https://twitter.com/trbiaplatformu Facebook: https://tr-tr.facebook.com/groups/biaplatformu/	n/a	A men's rights organization targeting gender-based violence and alimony legislation.
Süresiz Nafaka Mağdurları Platformu	Victims of Unlimited Alimony Platform	Anti-feminist		Mesut Arabul	Twitter: https://twitter.com/snmplatformu	n/a	A men's rights organization targeting gender-based violence and alimony legislation.
Milli İrade Platformu	National Will Platform	Anti-gender/anti-feminist		n/a	Webpage: https://www.milliradeplatformu.com/ Twitter: https://twitter.com/milliradeplatf	n/a	An umbrella organization, founded in 2013 to side with the government against an oppositional religious community, later joined in lobbying and campaigning against pro-gender equality policies.

Türkiye Düşünce Platformu	Turkey Thought Platform	Anti-gender/anti-feminist	n/a	Hayrettin Karaman	Webpage: https://www.tudp.org/	n/a	An anti-gender/anti-feminist platform that came to front in the 2020 campaign against the Istanbul Convention
İslam Dünyası Sivil Toplum Kuruluşları Birliği - Uluslararası Aile Enstitüsü	The Unions of NGOs of the Islamic World - International Family Institute	Anti-gender/anti-feminist		Rabiye Yılmaz	Webpage: https://idsb.org/tr/uluslar-arasi-aile-enstitusu/	n/a	Established in 2015 under the auspices of the Unions of NGOs of the Islamic World, this organization presents its objective as developing a family policy agenda based on Islamic rules and has been lobbying against international conventions, including CEDAW.
STK Türkiye Aile Platformu	NGO Turkey Family Platform	Anti-gender/anti-feminist		Funda Akyol (recent coordinator)	Webpage: https://turkiyeaileplatformu.com/	n/a	The organization presents itself as working with the ideal of a strong natural family in which healthy generations will grow.
Kadın ve Demokrasi Derneği	Women and Democracy Association	Anti-feminist		Saliha Okur Gümrukçüoğlu	Webpage: https://kadem.org.tr/ Twitter: https://twitter.com/kademorgtr	n/a	A GONGO, known for its rhetoric emphasizing gender equity instead of gender equality, and its influence on and cooperation with state bodies dislocating profeminist organizations from the process of policy making until mid-2015; targeted by radical anti-

							genderists in 2019 and 2020 anti-Istanbul Convention campaigns.
Aile Akademisi Derneği	Family Academy Association	Anti-feminist/Anti-gender		Yasin Kuruçay	Webpage: https://aileakademisi.org/	n/a	Established in 2012, the organization is active in terms of anti-genderist knowledge production, positions itself as an academic NGO providing trainings on family life.
Fikirde Birlik ve Mücadele Platformu	Unity in Idea and Struggle Platform	Anti-feminist/Anti-gender		Kürşad Mican	Webpage: https://fikirdebirlikvemucadeleplatformu.org/ Twitter: https://twitter.com/fikird ebirlik	n/a	Positions itself as an umbrella organization including more than 150 NGOs; organized public demonstrations against LGBTQI with the following slogan “Oppose LGBT imposition!” in several cities in 2022; the organization’s call for these demonstrations broadcasted on TV as public service announcement.

Notes on the list:

Except for the last organization, Unity in Idea and Struggle Platform, this list is embrative of non-state anti-gender/anti-feminist organizations, discussed in the literature so far. It does not include the government and specific state institutions found to be active in mobilizing anti-gender/anti-feminist ideas and/or enacting policies along this line.

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FIERCE

Feminist Movements Revitalizing
Democracy in Europe

Step by step guide for WP1 (T1.1)

**WP1- Anti-gender rhetoric/movements and their
influence on democracies**

Version: 1.0

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Contents

1. Relevant parts from the FIERCE application
2. Working definitions
3. Step by step guide for work package 1

1 Relevant parts from the FIERCE application

1.1 Objectives (WP1)

- To understand the structural and contextual conditions at national and transnational levels explaining the rise and in particular the developments and transformations of the anti-feminist and the anti-gender mobilizations in the eight countries and over the period 2010-21.
- To identify how gender and gender categories are framed, used, disseminated and widely communicated.
- To disclose the complex and expanding web of interactions and connections both within anti-feminist/anti-gender groups, communities and milieus as well as among these and external actors at local, national and transnational level, covering both institutional and civil society actors (individuals, groups, organizations and communities).

Work package 1 has three parts:

Part	Tasks	Time frame
T1.1	a. Literature review (state of the arts) b. Preparation of documents for later analysis	M1 – M6
T1.2	a. Interviews with anti-gender actors b. Social network analysis	M6 – M26
T1.3	a. Interviews with representatives of political parties and policy decision makers b. Content/frame analysis of documents about and by anti-gender and anti-feminist movements	M6 – M26

These guidelines refer to part 1 of the work package 1 (T1.1) colored in gray.

1.2 Description of work

T 1. 1: Setting up the research framework and mapping actors, debates and policy outcomes (Leader: University of Ljubljana, duration: M1 – M6)

Task 1: Review of academic and expert literature (covering the period from 2010 to 2021):

- Identify the main actors on the scene and their main strategies.
- Map the anti-feminist and anti-gender interconnections and alliances on local, national and transnational levels.
- List the main core themes referring to the five thematic areas (labor market, health & reproduction rights, LGBTQ+ and migration) and specify if there are any other important themes (e.g., academic freedom) and add eventual controversies.

Task 2: Preparation of documents for later analysis:

- a. Collect documents and relevant campaign material by anti-gender and anti-feminist movements to help identify most salient anti-gender and anti-feminist debates, both at national and the EU level.
- b. List the documents according to the five main thematic fields (if relevant, add another field).

2 Working definitions

Gender ideology/gender theory

Gender ideology is an empty signifier that can stand for anything from marriage equality and sex education in schools to reproductive and adoption rights and abortion. In everyday usage "gender ideology" (or "gender theory" or even "genderism," as it is called in some languages) has become synonymous with a kind of conspiracy theory of "radical feminists and LGBT activists" and other "leftist elites" who supposedly seek a cultural revolution. The alleged goal of this revolution is the denial of biological facts about men and women and the "promotion" of gender fluidity. "Gender theory" is thus constructed as a project of social engineering.

"Gender ideology" is a common framework that combines different discourses into one big threat that different actors can refer to and connect with.

Anti-gender actors/movement

In our project, we will use anti-gender actors to mean all actors who use "gender ideology" or "gender theory" or "genderism" as a key term/concept in their rhetoric and actions.

There is a broad network of actors that are considered part of the current anti-gender movement. These includes citizens' initiatives or organizations of "concerned citizens," family associations, pro-life groups, radical nationalist parties, right-wing populists, etc. In some countries, these groups function as satellite organizations of the church. In some countries, these actors have transformed into political parties, and in some countries, anti-gender ideology has become part of official state politics, e.g., in Poland. In addition, anti-gender actors are increasingly forming international coalitions and organizations, such as *Agenda Europe* or the *European Center for Law and Justice*. Some national actors, such as the Polish think tank *Ordo Iuris*, are establishing branches in other countries (e.g., *Ordo Iuris Croatia*), and in some countries initiatives are copied from other countries (e.g., Italy copied the French *Manif pour tous* in *Manif pour tous Italy*).

Anti-feminist actors/movement

Anti-feminist actors reject some or all forms of feminism, its political struggles for equality, and its principles. There are various forms of antifeminism, but generally they are based on the belief that the traditional gender division of labor is natural, or that women's rights and equality negatively affect men's rights and position in society without necessarily making use of conceptual devices such as "gender ideology" or "genderism" and without assuming the features of conspiracy theories.

Anti-feminist actors typically include various men's and fathers' organizations, but also religious groups, pro-life initiatives, and the like. Many of these actors now overlap with the anti-gender movement or have used the success of the anti-gender movement and its platform to spread their ideas. These actors are usually older initiatives/organizations that existed before the anti-gender movement and their target was an attack on feminism as such.

3 Step by step guidelines for Work package 1 (T 1.1)

3.1 Literature review (state of the arts)

The documents analyzed in the first step of our project include existing literature that presents, analyzes, and discusses (on a national level) anti-gender and anti-feminism movements, their campaigns, and the issues that the actors in these movements address.

This includes:

- a. scholarly articles, book chapters, monographs, conference papers, etc.
- b. Expert reports and other "gray literature" (any type of text (report, pamphlet, book, article, etc.) that cannot be classified as scientific but contains "expert knowledge" on the topic. These reports are usually produced by non-governmental organizations, movements, journalists, and other members of the "critical public".

Use the following keywords (and others as appropriate, depending on the national context) when searching for these texts: Anti-gender movement, anti-gender campaigns, anti-gender politics, anti-feminist movement, anti-feminist campaigns, anti-feminist politics, anti-feminism, LGBT ideology, gender ideology, gender theory.

Collect all documents listed above that cover the period from 2010 to 2021 in your country (including transnational and EU-related texts if they relate to your country). Do not include primary sources (such as statements or documents from anti-gender actors, media articles, parliamentary debates, etc.) in the analysis of the state of the arts. These documents will be analyzed in the next phases of the project.

Please upload any collected documents that will be used for this analysis to our "Cloud library" on Teams [HERE](#) (Teams → Documents → General → O2_WPs → WP1 – Anti-gender influence → 01 – Cloud Library – State of the Arts). This will allow us to refer and go back to the original sources when writing reports, articles, etc.

Picture 1 – Print screen of Cloud Library for Slovenia

The result of the literature review is a national state of the arts report that should be organized according to these guidelines and the template below.

The template provides the basic structure of the report (i.e., chapter titles) and includes numerous research questions for each chapter. You do not need to answer every single question! Use these questions to help

structure the report and identify blind spots in the currently available literature in your country and add EU-related issues in all sections of the report when they are relevant to depict the national situation.

3.1.1 Structure of the report

1. Introduction

In the introduction provide the basic information on the available literature and studies on anti-gender and anti-feminist movement in your country. Also provide a brief overview of key gender/LGBT policies that were discussed in your country in the period 2010-2021.

- To what extent is the anti-gender and anti-feminist movement in academic and activist circles in your country a topic of analysis?
- Who is writing about it?
- Are there specific years the literature on this topic increased?
- What and how are the main issues addressed by recent studies?
- What were the key gender/LGBT policies in the period 2010-2021 in your country?

2. The history of the anti-gender/anti-feminist movement and its context

Based on the available literature try to briefly describe the roots of the movement and its development.

- What was the trigger/political opportunity for the emergence of anti-gender actors?
- What are the key events from which the movement emerged and developed?
- How did the movement grow and expand?

3. Actors

This part is a description (and possibly classification) of the actors in the anti-gender and anti-feminist network in your country.

- Who (i.e., what types of actors) are the proponents of the anti-gender/anti-feminist movement in your country?
- Who are the main actors (names and background)?
- What types of organizations do they represent (is there a network of anti-gender organizations? Do the same actors appear in different anti-gender organizations?)
- What are the names of the anti-gender organizations - what message do these names convey?
- What is the role of women/youth in the movement?

4. Allies

This part explains how the anti-gender and anti-feminist actors are supported by other actors that do not necessarily consider themselves as part of the anti-gender/anti-feminist movement.

- Who are the allies of the anti-gender/anti-feminist movement? How do they cooperate?
- What are the links of the anti-gender/anti-feminist actors to state institutions and political parties (to what extent are anti-gender/anti-feminist actors independent ... or just a satellite organization of the state or political parties)?
- What is their relationship with the church/church groups/Vatican/non-Christian religious organizations? Are these actors satellite organizations of the church?
- What is the role of clergy/laity in the movement?

5. Themes and agendas

Our research project focuses on five thematic policy areas: (1) labor market, (2) health & reproductive rights, (3) migration, (4) LGBTQ+ rights and (5) gender-based violence. Describe how these topics figure in the anti-gender and anti-feminist movement in your country and whether these policy issues are/were a trigger for anti-gender movement to be established. Define any other topics that are also important and do not fit into these five policy areas, if found in the literature. Please, organize this part of the report in five (or more) subparagraphs according to the thematic policy areas, but address only those areas that are covered in the literature.

- What main issues are addressed by the anti-gender/anti-feminist movement? Why? (Try to explain the national political/economic/institutional situation).
- Why are these topics/issues problematic for the actors in anti-gender/anti-feminist movement?
- Who is to be blamed or who do the movements attribute responsibility for the problems?
- What kind of solutions do these actors offer?
- How are these solutions justified?
- To what extent have they succeeded in influencing the decision-making process?
- How does the general public respond to their claims?

6. Repertoires of action (strategies)

In this part describe the main strategies and types of actions used by the anti-gender/anti-feminist movement and explain how the movement uses the term “gender” as part of their strategies.

- Do they use citizens' initiatives, referendums, lobbying, demonstrations, requests for auditions to the Parliamentary Commissions, etc.? How effective are these strategies? What other strategies they use?
- The role of new media (social media)?
- What kind of visual materials do they use for their campaigns? Is visual material playing on the emotions of general public?
- Do they present themselves as feminists and claim to defend a true version of feminism?

7. Frames of arguments

In this part describe the main frames of arguments that anti-gender/anti-feminist actors use in their rhetoric and explain how the movement uses the term "gender" as part of their strategies.

- What are their key arguments (i.e. protection of innocent children, demographic winter, protection of life, protection of traditional family, free speech etc.)
- Do they (re)construct the past (what is presented as wrong in the past and the cause of current "problems": sexual revolution, emancipation of women, etc.?)
- The role of the term "gender" - how is it translated into national language? How do they use other terms, such as queer, trans ...?
- Who and what are their references (not only academically, but broader)?
- What role does the "human rights discussion" play in their discourse?
- Is there evidence of femonationalism, homonationalism (i.e. a favorable association between nationalist ideology and feminism/LGBT in order to exclude other groups, most often immigrants) ...?

8. Transnational connections

In this part describe how the local/national actors are connected with EU and transnational anti-gender and anti-feminist actors/organizations and what role the national actors play in transnational anti-gender networks.

- Do your local actors play a role in the transnational anti-gender scene? What role? How?
- What are the connections to other actors (national, EU, transnational) with similar agendas? How do they cooperate?
- Is there a transloading of agendas/strategies from your national context into another national context of transnational context?

9. Explanations of the anti-gender/anti-feminist backlash

If the available literature provides any explanation of the emergence and successes of the anti-gender movement in your country, summarize it in this part of the report.

- How is the anti-gender backlash explained in your national context?
- What explanation do the authors of the available studies offer?

10. Counter-movements

In this part briefly explain if any countermovement emerged as a reaction to the activities of anti-gender and anti-feminist movement. Describe what kind of actions the counter-movements took and what have they achieved.

11. Other important issues

If there are any other important issues discussed in the literature that cannot be put into any other subchapter of this report, summarize it here.

12. Conclusion

Outline the main findings in your local context (based on the state of the art) and point out the blind spots.

13. Timeline

Create a graphic timeline of key moments in the development of the anti-gender movement in your country, including its major successes and failures, as well as key oppositional events/actions on the part of feminists, LGBTQ+, and similar actors (including political parties, governments, etc.).

Key moments should be defined based on the existing analysis and studies. The most basic definition of a key moment is a moment that was important for future actions of the movement (in terms of its visibility, influence on political deliberation, etc.). The “successes” and “failures” refer to the question whether these movements succeeded or not in what they wanted (for example change of the definition of family in the constitution - as in Croatia or Slovakia and Romania etc.)

Example of the timeline:

Tailor the presentation of the timeline to your needs.

14. List of anti-gender/anti-feminist organizations

Provide a list of anti-gender/anti-feminist organizations in your country and links to their websites/FB pages and other information according to the table below (see next page).

List of the anti-gender and anti-feminist organizations and initiatives

Name of the organization (original)	Name of the organization (English)	Anti-gender or anti-feminist?	Logo of the organization	Head of the organization (in the period 2010-2021)	Web-page (social media)	Size of the organization (if available)	Comment (brief description)
Za otroke gre	Children are at stake	Anti-gender		Aleš Primc	Web: http://24kul.si/koalicija-za-otroke-gre FB: https://www.facebook.com/Za-otroke-gre-646841078755940	n/a	Leading Slovenian anti-gender organization that presents itself as a coalition of concerned citizens (parents and grandparents)
Družinska pobuda	Family initiative	Anti-gender		Tomaž Merše	Web: https://www.druzinskapobuda.si/	n/a	NGO active in protecting "natural traditional family" of a father, a mother and children.
Etc.							

Please use the APA referencing system¹ and provide the bibliography at the end of the report.

The length of the report should be up to (+/-) 10,000 words, not including bibliography, timeline, and list of anti-gender/anti-feminist organizations. 10,000 words is the length of a typical scholarly article. Try to think of this report as a draft version of a review article that you can later publish (with some modifications) in scientific journal.

This report should be finished by month 4,5 (mid-January 2023) to allow for comments, review and editing.

3.2 Preparation of documents for later analysis

Collect documents (in electronically searchable formats, such as .doc, .docx, or searchable .pdf) from anti-gender/anti-feminist actors or about anti-gender/anti-feminist actors and issues relevant to anti-gender/anti-feminist mobilization. The time frame for collecting documents is 2010 - 2021.

Catalogue according to main five thematic policy areas: (1) labor market, (2) health and reproductive rights, (3) migration, (4) LGBTQ+ rights, and (5) gender-based violence. If there are other important areas that have sparked an anti-gender or anti-feminist movement in your country, specify this. If there are no policy debates and consequently available documents on some of the five areas, note this in your report. These documents will help us identify the most important debates at both the national and EU levels.

Upload these documents to our "Cloud Library" on Teams [HERE](#) (Teams → Documents → General → 02_WPs → WP1 – Anti-gender influence → 02 – Cloud Library – Anti-gender documents) and make a list of all collected documents (an excel template will be prepared for this).

¹ In the APA reference list, the writer should provide the author, year, title, and source of the cited work in an alphabetical list of references. The reference format varies depending on the document type but broadly speaking always follows the same pattern of author, date, title, source. If the source is undated, the abbreviation **n.d.** (no date) is used.

Reference type	Template	Example
Journal article with a DOI	Author, A., & Author, B. (year). Title of article. <i>Journal Title</i> , Volume (Issue), page range. DOI	Schmidt, F. L., & Oh, I.-S. (2016). The crisis of confidence in research findings in psychology: Is lack of replication the real problem? Or is it something else? <i>Archives of Scientific Psychology</i> , 4(1), 32–37. https://doi.org/10.1037/arc0000029
Whole book	Author, A., & Author, B. (year). <i>Title of book</i> . Publisher.	Brown, B. (2010). <i>The gifts of imperfection: Let go of who you think you're supposed to be and embrace who you are</i> . Hazelden.
Edited book chapter with a DOI	Author, A., & Author, B. (year). Title of chapter. In E. Editor & A. Editor (Eds.), <i>Title of book</i> (pp. xx–xxi). Publisher. DOI	Singh, A. A., Hwahng, S. J., Chang, S. C., & White, B. (2017). Affirmative counseling with trans/gender-variant people of color. In A. Singh & L. M. Dickey (Eds.), <i>Affirmative counseling and psychological practice with transgender and gender nonconforming clients</i> (pp. 41–68). American Psychological Association. https://doi.org/10.1037/14957-003
Webpage on a website	Author, A., & Author, B. (year). <i>Title of page</i> . Site Name. URL Group Author. (year). <i>Title of page</i> . URL	American Psychological Association. (n.d.). <i>APA divisions</i> . https://www.apa.org/about/division/

Each partner should collect documents that cover all five thematic policy areas (and possibly other relevant areas). The selection criteria should be the relevance of the document for the anti-gender or anti-feminist movement. The focus is on those issues that anti-gender/anti-feminist movement reacted to or initiated a public/political debate about.

Each partner should collect at least (but possibly more):

1. **10 parliamentary debates** that include:

- Transcripts of parliamentary sessions and/or specific parliamentary committees (e.g., discussions on proposed new law),
- Parliamentary or political party statements on specific policy areas where anti-feminist or anti-gender actors responded to or attempted to influence the policy debate (including media reports), etc.
- Any other type of documents relevant to anti-gender or anti-feminist actors produced by policy makers.

If possible, please, select 2 debates by each thematic field. If possible, select those debated that were important also from the feminist movement point of view as these debates will be analyzed in work package 2.

2. **20 documents from anti-gender and anti-feminist actors** that include the following.

- Public statements
- Any type of text from the anti-gender or anti-feminist actors' website
- Publicity materials (e.g., for referendum campaigns)
- Policy proposals drafted by anti-gender or anti-feminist actors
- Etc.

If possible, please, select 4 documents by each thematic field.

Note that these documents will be analyzed using a content/frame analysis, which means that very short texts, such as short Facebook posts or one- or two-sentence media statements, are not suitable for such analysis.

These documents (with corresponding list of documents in excel) should be finished by month 5 (end of January 2023) to allow for comments, review and editing.